

9
(200)
5a3
Puerto Rico
1986

Water Resources Data Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands Water Year 1986

U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY WATER-DATA REPORT PR-86-1

Prepared in cooperation with the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico,
the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands, and other agencies

CALENDAR FOR WATER YEAR 1986

1985

OCTOBER							NOVEMBER							DECEMBER						
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S
		1	2	3	4	5						1	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6	7	8	9	10	11	12	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
20	21	22	23	24	25	26	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
27	28	29	30	31			24	25	26	27	28	29	30	29	30	31				

1986

JANUARY							FEBRUARY							MARCH							
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	
			1	2	3	4							1								1
5	6	7	8	9	10	11	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
12	13	14	15	16	17	18	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
26	27	28	29	30	31		23	24	25	26	27	28	23	24	25	26	27	28	29		
													30	31							

APRIL							MAY							JUNE							
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	
			1	2	3	4						1	2	3	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6	7	8	9	10	11	12	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	
20	21	22	23	24	25	26	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	
27	28	29	30				25	26	27	28	29	30	31	29	30						

JULY							AUGUST							SEPTEMBER								
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S		
			1	2	3	4						1	2				1	2	3	4	5	6
6	7	8	9	10	11	12	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	7	8	9	10	11	12	13		
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	14	15	16	17	18	19	20		
20	21	22	23	24	25	26	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	21	22	23	24	25	26	27		
27	28	29	30	31			24	25	26	27	28	29	30	28	29	30						
							31															

Water Resources Data Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands

Water Year 1986

by Russell E. Curtis, Jr., Zaida Aquino, Pedro L. Díaz, and René García

U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY WATER-DATA REPORT PR-86-1
Prepared in cooperation with the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico,
the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands, and other agencies

UNITED STATES DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR

DONALD PAUL HODEL, Secretary

GEOLOGICAL SURVEY

Dallas L. Peck, Director

For additional information on the water resources investigation programs

in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands write to:

Chief, Caribbean District, Water Resources Division

U.S. Geological Survey

GPO Box 4424

San Juan, PR 00936

(Telephone: (809) 753-4414)

ERRATA SHEET

REPORT: WATER RESOURCES DATA - PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS - WATER YEAR 1986

PAGE 87.--

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	41	20	2.2	41	25	2.8	68	155	80
2	41	19	2.1	36	13	1.3	43	30	3.5
3	40	19	2.1	35	14	1.3	35	15	1.4
4	39	16	1.7	44	37	8.9	33	12	1.1
5	40	15	1.6	46	50	8.5	30	10	.81
6	43	13	1.5	35	10	.95	28	10	.76
7	41	15	1.7	126	952	3990	27	9	.66
8	40	18	1.9	57	61	10	27	9	.66
9	38	20	2.1	48	58	10	27	9	.66
10	36	20	1.9	51	90	36	26	9	.63
11	45	44	8.1	52	83	22	25	8	.54
12	39	18	1.9	36	12	1.2	25	8	.54
13	35	15	1.4	41	26	3.6	25	8	.54
14	55	91	26	36	18	1.7	24	8	.52
15	60	87	21	33	15	1.3	22	8	.48
16	56	87	21	30	13	1.1	22	8	.48
17	98	432	680	30	13	1.1	25	10	.84
18	59	93	17	30	12	.97	26	10	.70
19	43	50	5.8	30	12	.97	23	10	.62
20	61	105	27	30	12	.97	22	10	.59
21	59	65	14	28	12	.91	22	10	.59
22	44	25	3.0	29	12	.94	28	14	1.2
23	42	25	2.8	34	18	2.0	25	10	.68
24	47	37	5.4	33	15	1.6	24	9	.58
25	43	15	1.7	40	51	19	26	13	1.2
26	41	12	1.3	40	28	3.6	23	10	.62
27	43	14	1.6	29	10	.78	21	10	.57
28	42	12	1.4	36	19	2.2	30	20	2.0
29	40	12	1.3	60	93	39	25	10	.68
30	42	24	3.0	57	103	32	22	10	.59
31	44	27	3.7	39	28	2.9	---	---	---
TOTAL	1437	---	867.2	1292	---	4209.59	829	---	104.74
YEAR	25021		227330.80						

PAGE 213.-- "Figure 23.-- Rio Guanajibo basin" should read "Figure 20.-- Southeastern river basins-- Rio Humacao to Rio Seco basins."

PAGE 249.-- "Figure 20.--Southeastern river basins--Rio Humacao to Rio Seco basins." should read "Figure 23.-- Rio Guanajibo basin."

PREFACE

This annual hydrologic data report of Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands is one of a series of annual reports that document hydrologic data gathered from the U.S. Geological Survey's surface- and ground-water data-collection networks in each state, Puerto Rico, the U.S. Virgin Islands, and the other Trust Territories. These records of streamflow, ground-water levels, and quality of water provide the hydrologic information needed by state, local and Federal agencies, and the private sector for developing and managing our Nation's land and water resources.

The report is the culmination of a concerted effort by dedicated personnel of the U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Division who collected, compiled, analyzed, verified, and organized the data, and who typed, edited, and assembled the report. In addition to the authors, who had primary responsibility for assuring that the information contained herein is accurate, complete and adheres to Geological Survey policy and established guidelines, the following personnel contributed significantly to the collection, processing and tabulations of the data:

José M. Agis	Karl Johnson
George Arroyo	Rafael Peña-Cortés
Angel Class Cacho	Ana V. Sánchez
Eloy Colón-Dieppa	Luis Santiago-Rivera
Iris M. Concepción	Luis Soler
Carlos Figueroa	José A. Torres
Javier García	Heriberto Torres-Sierra
Ralph González	Ricardo J. Vachier
Felipe Hernández	

This report was prepared in cooperation with agencies of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico, the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands, and with other federal agencies under the general supervision of Allen L. Zack, District Chief, Caribbean District, San Juan, Puerto Rico.

ILLUSTRATIONS

	Page
Figure 1. Graph showing monthly-mean discharge of selected streams in Puerto Rico.....	4
2. Graph showing ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	6
3. Map showing location of maximum concentration of fecal coliform bacteria at sampled sites.....	10
4. Map showing location of maximum concentration of fecal streptococci bacteria at sampled sites.....	11
5. Map showing location of continuous surface-water and crest-stage gage stations in Puerto Rico.....	13
6. Map showing location of water-quality stations in Puerto Rico.....	14
7. Map showing location of ground-water stations in Puerto Rico.....	15
8. Map showing location of surface-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	16
9. Map showing location of ground-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	17
10. Grid showing system for numbering wells and miscellaneous sites (latitude and longitude).....	18
11. Map showing the Río Guajataca basin.....	51
12. Map showing the Río Camuy basin.....	63
13. Map showing the Río Grande de Arecibo basin.....	69
14. Map showing the Río Grande de Manatí basin.....	93
15. Map showing the Río Cibuco basin.....	111
16. Map showing the Río de la Plata basin.....	125
17. Map showing the Río Hondo to the Río Puerto Nuevo basins.	137
18. Map showing the Río Grande de Loíza basin.....	153
19. Map showing northeastern river basins--the Río Herrera to the Río Antón Ruíz basins.....	189
20. Map showing southeastern river basins--the Río Humacao to the Río Seco basins.....	213
21. Map showing south coast river basins--the Río Salinas to the Río Jacaguas basins.....	227
22. Map showing south coast river basins--the Río Inabón to the Río Loco basins.....	233
23. Map showing the Río Guanajibo basin.....	249
24. Map showing the Río Yagüez and the Río Grande de Añasco basins.....	269
25. Map showing the Río Culebrinas basin.....	279

CONTENTS

v

	Page
Preface.....	iii
List of surface-water and water-quality stations, in downstream order, for which records are published.....	viii
List of ground-water wells, by basin, for which records are published.....	xii
Introduction.....	1
Cooperation.....	2
Summary of hydrologic conditions.....	2
Surface water.....	3
Ground water.....	5
Water quality.....	7
Special networks and programs.....	9
Explanation of records.....	9
Station identification numbers.....	12
Downstream order system.....	12
Latitude-longitude system.....	12
Records of stage and water discharge.....	18
Data collection and computation.....	18
Data presentation.....	20
Identifying estimated daily discharge.....	23
Accuracy of the records.....	23
Records of surface-water quality.....	23
Classification of records.....	24
Arrangement of records.....	24
On-site measurements and sample collection.....	24
Water temperature.....	25
Sediment.....	26
Laboratory measurements.....	26
Data presentation.....	26
Remark codes.....	28
Records of ground-water levels.....	28
Data collection and computation.....	28
Data presentation.....	29
Records of ground-water quality.....	30
Data collection and computation.....	30
Data presentation.....	31
Access to WATSTORE data.....	31
Definition of terms.....	32
Publications on Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations.....	46
Surface- and quality-of-water records for Puerto Rico.....	49
Discharge at partial-record stations in Puerto Rico.....	287
Water-quality at partial-record stations in Puerto Rico.....	291
Ground-water records for Puerto Rico.....	300
Surface-water records for the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	335
Ground-Water records for the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	341
Index.....	359

REPORT DOCUMENTATION PAGE		1. REPORT NO. USGS/WRD/HD-88/220	2.	3. Recipient's Accession No.
4. Title and Subtitle Water Resources Data for Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands, Water Year 1986				5. Report Date April 1988
7. Author(s) Russell E. Curtis, Jr., Zaida Aquino, René García, Pedro Díaz				6.
9. Performing Organization Name and Address U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Division G.P.O. Box 4424 San Juan, Puerto Rico 00936				8. Performing Organization Rept. No. USGS-WDR-PR-86-1
12. Sponsoring Organization Name and Address U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Division G.P.O. Box 4424 San Juan, Puerto Rico 00936				10. Project/Task/Work Unit No.
15. Supplementary Notes Prepared in cooperation with the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico, the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands and other agencies.				11. Contract(C) or Grant(G) No. (C) (G)
16. Abstract (Limit: 200 words) Water-resources data for surface-water, quality-of-water, and ground-water records for the 1986 water year for Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands, consists of records of discharge, water quality of streams, and water levels of wells. This report contains discharge records for 50 streamflow-gaging stations, and 2 crest-stage, partial-record streamflow stations; stage records for 1 lagoon; water quality records for 16 streamflow-gaging stations, 45 ungaged streamsites, 11 lake sites, 1 lagoon, and 1 bay; and water-level records for 57 observation wells. These data represent that part of the National Water Data System collected by the U.S. Geological Survey and cooperating local and federal agencies in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.				13. Type of Report & Period Covered Annual-Oct. 1, 1985 to Sept. 30, 1986
17. Document Analysis a. Descriptors *Surface water, *Water quality, *Ground water, Aquifers, Chemical analysis, Gaging Stations, Hydrologic data, Sediments, Streamflow, Water analysis, Water levels, Lakes.				14.
b. Identifiers/Open-Ended Terms Puerto Rico, U.S. Virgin Islands, Sampling sites.				
c. COSATI Field/Group				
18. Availability Statement: NO RESTRICTION ON DISTRIBUTION		19. Security Class (This Report) UNCLASSIFIED	21. No. of Pages 376	
		20. Security Class (This Page) UNCLASSIFIED	22. Price	

TABLES

	Page
Table 1. Island-wide monthly precipitation averages for 1986 water year.....	3
2. Peak discharges during Oct. 6-7, 1985 at selected U.S. Geological Survey streamflow stations through- out Puerto Rico.....	5
3. Highest water level (in feet below land-surface datum) recorded during 1985 water year at selected ground- water wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	7
4. Sites with maximum concentration of selected parameters..	8
5. Factors for conversion of chemical constituents in milli- grams per liter to milliequivalents per liter.....	37

**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED**

(Letter after station name designates type of data:
(d) discharge, (c) water-quality, (e) elevation)

	Page
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN	
Río Guajataca at Lares (c).....	52
Río Guajataca above Lago Guajataca (d).....	54
Canal Principal de Diversiones at Lago Guajataca (c).....	56
Río Guajataca below Lago Guajataca (d).....	58
Río Guajataca above mouth near Quebradillas (dc).....	60
RIO CAMUY BASIN	
Río Camuy near Bayaney (d).....	64
Río Camuy near Hatillo (d).....	66
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN	
Río Grande de Arecibo near Adjuntas (c).....	70
Río Grande de Arecibo near Utuado (c).....	72
Río Caonillas above Lago Caonillas near Jayuya (c).....	74
Río Grande de Arecibo below Lago Dos Bocas near Florida (c).....	76
Río Grande de Arecibo above Arecibo (d).....	78
Río Tanamá near Utuado (dc).....	80
Río Tanamá at Charco Hondo (d).....	88
Río Grande de Arecibo at Central Cambalache (c).....	90
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN	
Río Orocovis near Orocovis (c).....	94
Río Grande de Manatí near Morovis (dc).....	96
Río Grande de Manatí at Ciales (d).....	99
Río Grande de Manatí at Highway 149 at Ciales (c).....	101
Río Cialitos at Highway 649 at Ciales (c).....	103
Río Grande de Manatí at Highway 2 near Manatí (dc).....	105
LAGUNA TORTUGUERO BASIN	
Laguna Tortuguero Outlet near Vega Baja (c).....	110
RIO CIBUCO BASIN	
Río Cibuco below Corozal (dc).....	112
Río Cibuco at Vega Baja (dc).....	115
Drainage Ditch below Warner Lambert Laboratory near Sabana (c).....	118
Drainage Ditch at Río Cibuco below Central San Vicente (c).....	120
Río Cibuco below Central San Vicente (c).....	122
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN	
Río de La Plata at Proyecto La Plata (dc).....	126
Río de La Plata near Comerio (c).....	129
Río Guadiana near Naranjito (c).....	131
Río de La Plata at Toa Alta (c).....	133
Río de La Plata at Highway 2 near Toa Alta (d).....	136
RIO HONDO BASIN	
Río Hondo at Flood Channel near Cataño (c).....	138

**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED--Continued**

	Page
RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN	
Río de Bayamón near Aguas Buenas (c).....	140
Río Guaynabo near Bayamón (c).....	142
Río de Bayamón at Flood Channel at Bayamón (c).....	144
RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN	
Río Piedras:	
Río Piedras near Río Piedras (c).....	146
Río Piedras at Hato Rey (c).....	148
Laguna San José:	
Laguna San José No.2 at San Juan (c).....	150
Bahía de San Juan:	
Bahía de San Juan No.5 at San Juan (c).....	151
QUEBRADA BLASINA BASIN	
Quebrada Blasina near Carolina (c).....	154
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN	
Río Grande de Loíza at Quebrada Arenas (d).....	156
Quebrada Blanca at El Jagual (d).....	158
Quebrada Salvatierra near San Lorenzo (d).....	160
Río Cayaguas at Cerro Gordo (d).....	162
Río Turabo at Borinquen (d).....	164
Río Grande de Loíza at Caguas (dc).....	166
Río Caguitas at Highway 30 at Caguas (c).....	169
Río Bairoa near Caguas (c).....	171
Río Gurabo:	
Quebrada Caimito near Juncos (d).....	173
Río Valenciano near Juncos (d).....	175
Quebrada Mamey near Gurabo (d).....	177
Río Gurabo at Gurabo (d).....	179
Río Gurabo near Gurabo (c).....	181
Lago Loíza at Damsite (c).....	183
Río Grande de Loíza below Trujillo Alto (c).....	184
Río Canóvanas near Campo Rico (d).....	186
RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN	
Quebrada Sonadora near El Verde (d).....	190
Quebrada Toronja at El Verde (d).....	192
Río Espiritu Santo near Río Grande (dc).....	194
RIO MAMEYES BASIN	
Río Mameyes near Sabana (d).....	197
RIO SABANA BASIN	
Río Sabana at Sabana (d).....	199
RIO FAJARDO BASIN	
Río Fajardo near Fajardo (dc).....	203
Río Fajardo below Fajardo (c).....	209

**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED--Continued**

	Page
RIO BLANCO BASIN	
Río Icacos near Naguabo (d).....	211
RIO HUMACAO BASIN	
Río Humacao at Highway 3 at Humacao (c).....	214
RIO GUAYANES BASIN	
Río Guayanés at Yabucoa (c).....	216
Río Guayanés above mouth at Playa de Guayanés (c).....	218
RIO MAUNABO BASIN	
Río Maunabo at Maunabo (c).....	220
RIO CHICO BASIN	
Río Chico at Providencia (c).....	222
RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN	
Río Grande de Patillas near Patillas (dc).....	224
RIO COAMO BASIN	
Río Coamo near Coamo (c).....	228
RIO DESCALABRADO BASIN	
Río Descalabrado near Los Llanos (d).....	230
RIO JACAGUAS BASIN	
Río Jacaguas at Juana Diaz (d).....	231
RIO INABON BASIN	
Río Inabón at Real Abajo (d).....	234
RIO BUCANA BASIN	
Río Bucaná:	
Río Cerrillos near Ponce (c).....	236
RIO PORTUGUES BASIN	
Río Portugués near Ponce (dc).....	238
Río Portugués at Ponce (c).....	241
RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN	
Río Guayanilla near Guayanilla (d).....	243
Río Guayanilla at Central Rufina (c).....	244
RIO LOCO BASIN	
Río Loco at Guánica (c).....	246
LAGUNA CARTAGENA BASIN	
Laguna Cartagena near Boquerón (e).....	250
Laguna Cartagena Outflow near Boquerón (d).....	251

**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED--Continued**

	Page
LAGUNA JOYUDA BASIN	
Quebrada Mamey at Joyuda (d).....	253
RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN	
Río Guanajibo near San Germán (c).....	254
Río Rosario at Rosario (d).....	256
Río Rosario near Hormigueros (dc).....	257
Río Guanajibo near Hormigueros (dc).....	265
RIO YAGUEZ BASIN	
Río Yagüez near Mayagüez (c).....	270
RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN	
Río Grande de Añasco near Lares (c).....	272
Río Grande de Añasco near San Sebastián (dc).....	274
Río Grande de Añasco near Añasco (c).....	277
RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN	
Río Culebrinas near San Sebastián (c).....	280
Río Culebrinas at Highway 404 near Moca (d).....	282
Río Culebrinas near Aguada (c).....	284
ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS	
Bonne Resolution Gut at Bonne Resolution (d).....	337
Turpentine Run at Mariendal (d).....	338
ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS	
Guinea Gut at Bethany (d).....	339
ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS	
Jolly Hill Gut at Jolly Hill (d).....	340

GROUND-WATER WELLS, BY BASIN, FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED

	Page
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN	
Well 182422067015100 Local number 165.....	303
Well 182647066552400 Local number 202.....	304
RIO CAMUY BASIN	
Well 182856066510700 Local number 203.....	305
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN	
Well 182737066370900 Local number 204.....	306
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN	
Well 182621066343300 Local number 135.....	307
Well 182757066325600 Local number 206.....	308
Well 182710066303700 Local number 207.....	309
Well 182534066283000 Local number 208.....	310
Well 182634066262500 Local number 209.....	311
Well 182308066260400 Local number 210.....	312
RIO CIBUCO BASIN	
Well 182647066201700 Local number 70.....	313
Well 182615066235300 Local number 211.....	314
Well 182515066194000 Local number 212.....	315
Well 182330066185700 Local number 213.....	316
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN	
Well 182746066170800 Local number 214.....	317
Well 182548066171200 Local number 215.....	318
Well 182530066135400 Local number 216.....	319
Well 182655066142400 Local number 217.....	320
RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS	
Well 182623066111000 Local number 218.....	321
Well 182441066082600 Local number 219.....	322
Well 182413066044000 Local number 220.....	323
Well 182436066031200 Local number 221.....	324
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN	
Well 182515065594100 Local number 222.....	325
RIO HUMACAO TO RIO SECO BASINS	
Well 175858066100200 Local number 6.....	326
Well 180415065513900 Local number 96.....	327
RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS	
Well 175829066232100 Local number 87.....	328
RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS	
Well 180133066503300 Local number 132.....	329
Well 175950066354200 Local number 141.....	330

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

Well 180132067033800 Local number 143..... 331

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

Well 182018066593200 Local number 83..... 332

Well 182442067091700 Local number 200..... 333

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

Well 174225064471900 Local number 1..... 343

Well 174225064472000 Local number 2..... 344

Well 174243064475100 Local number 3..... 345

Well 174245064475800 Local number 4..... 346

Well 174336064523200 Local number 5..... 346

Well 174308064484400 Local number 6..... 347

Well 174525064460600 Local number 7..... 348

Well 174527064460100 Local number 8..... 348

Well 174532064460300 Local number 9..... 349

Well 174329064454700 Local number 10..... 349

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

Well 182050064580400 Local number 1..... 350

Well 182138064543100 Local number 2..... 350

Well 182138064542500 Local number 3..... 350

Well 182136064541900 Local number 4..... 351

Well 182029064535200 Local number 5..... 351

Well 182038064550300 Local number 6..... 352

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

Well 182010064472600 Local number 1..... 353

Well 182109064460300 Local number 2..... 353

Well 182116064451000 Local number 3..... 354

Well 182042064454500 Local number 5..... 355

Well 182044064454600 Local number 6..... 356

Well 182044064454800 Local number 7..... 356

Well 182044064454900 Local number 8..... 356

Well 182044064455000 Local number 9..... 357

Well 182044064455200 Local number 10..... 357

Well 181956064464500 Local number 11..... 358

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

1

INTRODUCTION

The Water Resources Division of the U.S. Geological Survey, in cooperation with local and federal agencies obtains a large amount of data pertaining to the water resources of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico and the Territory of the U.S. Virgin Islands each water year. These data, accumulated during many water years, constitute a valuable data base for developing an improved understanding of the water resources of the area. To make these data readily available to interested parties outside the Geological Survey, the data are published annually in this report series entitled "Water Resources Data for Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands, 1986."

This report includes records on both surface and ground water. Specifically, it contains: (1) Discharge records for 50 streamflow-gaging stations, and 2 crest-stage, partial-record streamflow station; (2) stage records for 1 lagoon; (3) water-quality records for 16 streamflow-gaging stations, and for 45 ungaged streamsites, 11 lake sites, 1 lagoon, and 1 bay; and (4) water-level records for 57 observation wells.

Water-resources data for Puerto Rico for calendar years 1958-67 were released in a series of reports entitled "Water Records of Puerto Rico". Water-resources data for the U.S. Virgin Islands for the calendar years 1962-69 were released in a report entitled "Water Records of U.S. Virgin Islands." Included were records of streamflow, ground-water levels, and water-quality data for both surface and ground water.

Beginning with the 1968 calendar year, surface-water records for Puerto Rico were released separately on an annual basis. Ground-water level records and water-quality data for surface and ground water were released in companion reports covering periods of several years. Data for the 1973-74 reports were published under separate covers. Water-resources data reports for 1975-76, 1977, 1978, 1979-80, 1981-82, 1983, 1984, and 1985 water years consist of one volume each and contain data for streamflow, water quality and ground water.

Publications similar to this report are published annually by the Geological Survey for all States. These official Survey reports have an identification number consisting of the two-letter State abbreviation, the last two digits of the water year, and the volume number. For example, this volume is identified as "U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-86-1". These water-data reports are for sale in paper copy or in microfiche by the National Technical Information Service, U.S. Department of Commerce, Springfield, Virginia, 22161.

Additional information, including current prices, for ordering specific reports may be obtained from the District Chief at the address given on back of title page or by telephone (809) 783-4660.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

COOPERATION

The U.S. Geological Survey has had cooperative agreements with organizations of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico and the Territory of the U.S. Virgin Islands for the systematic collections of water resources data since 1958. Organizations that supplied data are acknowledged in the station descriptions. Organizations that assisted in collecting data through cooperative agreements with the Survey are:

Puerto Rico Environmental Quality Board
 Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority
 Puerto Rico Department of Agriculture
 Puerto Rico Industrial Development Company
 Puerto Rico Department of Public Works
 Puerto Rico Highway Authority
 Puerto Rico Department of Natural Resources
 Puerto Rico Department of Health
 Puerto Rico Electric and Power Authority
 Puerto Rico Rice Corporation
 Puerto Rico Administration for Agricultural Development
 Puerto Rico Land Administration
 Center for Energy and Environment Research, University
 of Puerto Rico
 Water Resources Research Institute, University of
 Puerto Rico
 Water Resources Research Institute, College of the
 Virgin Islands
 Department of Public Works of the U.S. Virgin Islands

Funds were also provided by the Corps of Engineers, U.S. Army, for the collection of records at five gaging stations published in this report. Ground-water quality data at selected sites was collected with support from the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.

SUMMARY OF HYDROLOGIC CONDITIONS

Precipitation was slightly higher than usual in the 1986 water year. The average was about 118 percent of normal, islandwide, with variations of 116 percent normal in the north; 123 percent normal in the south; 120 percent normal in the east; and 112 percent normal in the west. Monthly average precipitation islandwide for water year 1986 and the 30-year normal as reported by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration are listed in table 1.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Table 1. Island-wide monthly precipitation averages for 1986 water year

	<u>Water year 1986</u> (inches)	<u>30-year</u> <u>normal</u> (inches)
Oct.	20.60	7.74
Nov.	6.58	5.95
Dec.	1.64	4.32
Jan.	2.56	3.08
Feb.	1.76	2.29
Mar.	2.67	2.62
Apr.	7.41	4.63
May	15.14	6.48
June	2.97	5.58
July	4.11	4.48
Aug.	6.00	7.28
Sept.	<u>3.17</u>	<u>7.78</u>
TOTAL	74.61	62.23

Surface Water

Streamflow in Puerto Rico was generally within normal range during the 1986 water year (fig. 1). During October it was well above normal due to increased precipitation caused by a tropical wave. This event produced monthly-mean discharges that were 162 to 522 percent of the long-term median at all index stations. Historical maximum peak flows were recorded for some sites and are shown in table 2. An estimated 180 people died, and millions of dollars in losses occurred as a result of severe floods and landslides in the southern and central areas. Streamflow began to decrease to the normal range during November, but was still excessive in the northern and eastern areas.

From December to March, streamflow decreased seasonally to normal levels, although some stations were slightly below or above average. After this moderate drought season, above normal precipitation during April increased streamflow above the long-term median with normal to excessive flows. They continued increasing during May when the highest and second highest monthly-mean flows were exceeded at Río Grande de Añasco near San Sebastián on the west coast, and Río Grande de Manatí on the north coast. However, the northern and eastern areas were the most affected, where some gaging stations recorded maximum peak discharges for the water year. Similar high-flow conditions persisted for the west and north coasts during June and July, but flow began to decline to normal limits in the eastern and southern areas by June, and was lower than usual by July.

Unshaded area indicates range between highest and lowest record for the month

Figure 1.--Monthly mean discharge of selected streams in Puerto Rico.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

In August increased flows occurred islandwide and averaged 109 percent above the long-term median, compared with an average of 38 percent of the median during September. Streamflow ranged from about 28 percent of the median in Río Inabón at Real Abajo to 137 percent of the median in Río Fajardo near Fajardo. Record low flows for August occurred at two index stations. Monthly-mean discharges at Río Inabón at Real Abajo and Río Grande de Añasco near San Sebastián sites were an all-time low for the entire period of record (23 years) at those sites.

In the U.S. Virgin Islands, conditions were generally the same as in Puerto Rico. The passing of the tropical wave during October 1985, produced precipitation 224 percent above the 30-year norm for this month. For the rest of the year it was below normal except for April and May when it was 260 and 226 percent above normal respectively.

Table 2. Peak discharges during October 6-7, 1985 at selected U.S. Geological Survey streamflow gaging stations throughout Puerto Rico

Station number	Station name	1986 peak (Cubic feet per second)	Previous maximum of record (Cubic feet per second)	Water Year	Period of Record
50011200	Río Guajataca below Lago de Guajataca	1,350	624	1985	8-69 to 12-70, 4-84 to 9-86
50014800	Río Camuy near Bayaney	6,450	3,510	1985	5-84 to 9-86
50015700	Río Camuy near Hatillo	10,500	6,250	1985	6-84 to 9-86
50038100	Río Grande de Manatí Highway 2 near Manatí	97,200	90,000(revised)	1985	10-63 to 9-68, 2-70 to 9-86
50055650	Quebrada Caimito near Juncos	992	700	1985	1-84 to 9-86
50108000	Río Descalabrado near Los Llanos	30,000	7,000	1969	1-66 to 12-69, 2-84 to 9-86
50111500	Río Jacaguas at Juana Díaz	40,000	12,700	1985	3-84 to 9-86
50112500	Río Inabón at Real Abajo	19,000	5,720	1970	7-64 to 7-70, 4-71 to 9-86
50115000	Río Portugués near Ponce	21,000	13,100	1975	7-64 to 9-86

Ground Water

In general, ground-water levels in selected wells rose during October and May in response to above-normal rainfall. New record-high water levels were recorded at several wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands (Table 3).

Figure 2.--Ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Ground-water levels along the north coast limestone aquifers of Puerto Rico remained practically unchanged during the first half of the water year (fig. 2). Above normal rainfall during mid-May caused a significant rise in the water levels. At the Lederle recording well, an increase of 2.5 ft was registered. The water levels declined during the rest of the period, reaching nearly steady conditions by September 1986.

Ground-water levels in the south coast alluvial aquifers of Puerto Rico followed a cyclic pattern associated with rainfall and ground-water withdrawals for public supply, industrial, and irrigation uses. Above-normal rainfall produced by a tropical depression that affected south-central Puerto Rico during October 6-7, 1985, caused a significant rise in the water levels (fig. 2). At the Alomar well, an increase of 4.5 ft in the water levels was recorded, while at nearby recording wells a maximum increase of 22.0 ft was recorded. The water levels decreased during the rest of the year in response to water demand for irrigation and diminished precipitation.

Table 3. Highest water level and previous extreme (in feet below land-surface datum) recorded during 1986 water year at selected ground-water wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands

Well Name	Local no.	Location	1986 extreme	Date	Previous extreme	Date	Period of Record
Yabucoa #7	96	PR	13.39	11-18-85	15.38	12-09-84	4-78 to 9-86
Restaurada 8A	141	PR	11.19	10-09-85	15.65	08-20-83	10-81 to 9-86
Vivoni well	143	PR	37.86	11-20-85	38.00	09-19-82	12-81 to 9-86
Guinea Gut	11	St. John	3.05	06-13-86	3.34	05-25-82	3-82 to 9-86
Fairplains #2	2	St. Croix	20.91	11-27-85	21.80	01-03-84	6-83 to 9-86
Grade School 3	6	St. Thomas	3.72	05-22-86	5.19	11-27-84	3-82 to 9-86

Ground-water levels in the U.S. Virgin Islands (St. Thomas, St. Croix, and St. John) responded to the same climatological conditions that affected Puerto Rico. Above-normal rainfall during October and May resulted in an increase in water levels of 17.8 ft. and 20.5 ft respectively at the Guinea Gut recording well (fig. 2).

Water Quality

As part of the ongoing interagency agreement, the U.S. Geological Survey completed the second year of sampling for selected parameters which were added to the regular schedule in 1985. These parameters are part of a wider set of constituents studied to detect the effects of pollution on the streams and lakes in Puerto Rico.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Table 4. Sites with maximum concentration of selected parameters

	Boron B	Copper Cu	Manganese Mn
Site number	50047530	50055250	50146000
Site name	Río Hondo at flood channel near Cataño	Río Caguitas at Highway 30 at Caguas	Río Grande de Añasco near Añasco
Maximum concentrations	0.97 mg/L	0.22 mg/L	1.7 mg/L
	Iron Fe	Zinc Zn	Cyanide
Site number	50146000	50063800	50055250
Site name	Río Grande de Añasco near Añasco	Río Espíritu Santo near El Verde Río Grande	Río Caguitas at Highway 30 at Caguas
Maximum concentrations	50 mg/L	0.24 mg/L	0.220 mg/L
	Phenols	Sulfide	MBAS *
Site number	50091800	50048800	50091800
Site name	Río Chico at Providencia	Río Piedras near Río Piedras	Río Chico at Providencia
Maximum concentrations	42 mg/L	14 mg/L	5.1 mg/L

* MBAS - Methylene blue active substances.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

The presence of high concentrations of fecal coliform (FC) and fecal streptococci (FS) bacteria continue being the principal water quality problem of Puerto Rico. Bacteria concentrations exceeding one million colonies per hundred milliliters of raw water were found at several stations including Río Hondo at flood channel near Cataño (50047530), Río Piedras at Hato Rey (50049100), Río Caguaitas at Highway 30 at Caguas (50055250), Río Bairoa near Caguas (50055400), and Río Chico at Central Providencia (50091800) (fig. 3 and 4). These sites are located close to urban zones, industrial parks, and suburban zones and receive the direct discharge from sewage treatment plants.

Three suspended sediment stations were operated during the year at Río Tanamá near Utuado (50028000), located in the north central part of the island; Río Fajardo near Fajardo (50071000) in the east, close to El Yunque Rain Forest; and Río Rosario near Hormigueros (50136400) in the west, close to the Maricao Forest Reserve. Maximum sediment concentrations recorded were 9,340 mg/L at 50028000, 2,210 mg/L at 50071000, and 8,150 mg/L at 50136400. Maximum sediment loads were 79,900 tons per day (ton/d) at 50028000, 22,100 ton/d at 50071000, and 74,700 ton/d at 50136400.

SPECIAL NETWORKS AND PROGRAMS

National Stream Quality Accounting Network (NASQAN) is a nationwide data-collection network designed by the U.S. Geological Survey to meet many of the information needs of government agencies and other groups involved in natural or regional water-quality planning and management. The 500 or so sites on NASQAN are generally located at the downstream ends of hydrologic accounting units designated by the U.S. Geological Survey Office of Water Data Coordination in consultation with the Water Resources Council. The objectives of NASQAN are (1) to obtain information on the quality and quantity of water moving within and from the United States through a systematic and uniform process of data collection, summarization, analysis, and reporting such that the data may be used for, (2) description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of data from this and other programs, (3) detection of changes or trends with time in the pattern of occurrence of water-quality characteristics, and (4) providing a nationally consistent data base useful for water-quality assessment and hydrologic research.

EXPLANATION OF THE RECORDS

The surface-water and ground-water records published in this report are for the 1986 water year that began October 1, 1985 and ended September 30, 1986. A calendar of the water year is provided on the inside of the front cover. The records contain streamflow data, stage and content data for lakes and reservoirs, water-quality data for surface and ground water, and ground-water-level data. The locations of the stations and wells where the data were collected are shown in figures 3 to 9. The following sections of the introductory text are presented to provide users with a more detailed explanation of how the hydrologic data published in this report were collected, analyzed, computed, and arranged for presentation.

Figure 3.--Location of maximum concentration of fecal coliform bacteria at sampled sites.

Figure 4.--Location of maximum concentration of fecal streptococci bacteria at sampled sites.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Station Identification Numbers

Each data station, whether streamsite or well, in this report is assigned a unique identification number. This number is unique in that it applies specifically to a given station and to no other. The number usually is assigned when a station is first established and is retained for that station indefinitely. The systems used by the U.S. Geological Survey to assign identification numbers for surface-water stations and for ground-water well sites differ, but both are based on geographic location. The "downstream order" system is used for regular surface-water stations and the "latitude-longitude" system is used for wells.

Downstream order system

Since October 1, 1950, the order of listing hydrologic-station records in Survey reports is in a downstream direction along the main stream. All stations on a tributary entering upstream from a main-stream station are listed before that station. A station on a tributary that enters between two main-stream stations is listed between them. A similar order is followed in listing stations in first rank, second rank, and other ranks of tributaries.

As an added means of identification, each hydrologic station and partial-record station has been assigned a station number. These are in the same downstream order used in this report. In assigning station numbers, no distinction is made between partial-record stations and other stations; therefore, the station number for a partial-record station indicates downstream order position in a list made up of both types of stations that may be established; hence, the numbers are not consecutive. The complete 8-digit number for each station such as 50028000, which appears just to the left of the station name, includes the 2-digit part number "50" plus the 6-digit downstream order number "028000."

Latitude-Longitude System

The 8-digit downstream order station numbers are not assigned to wells and miscellaneous sites where only random water-quality samples or discharge measurements are taken.

The well and miscellaneous site numbering system of the U.S. Geological Survey is based on the grid system of latitude and longitude. The system provides the geographic location of the well or miscellaneous site and a unique number for each site. The number consists of 15 digits. The first 6 digits denote the degrees, minutes, and seconds of latitude, the next 7 digits denote degrees, minutes, and seconds longitude, and the last 2 digits (assigned sequentially) identify the wells or other sites within a 1-second grid. The numbers shown in the grid correspond to the local numbers assigned to each well as visited in the field. An example is well 16 (fig. 10).

Figure 5.--Location of continuous surface-water and crest-stage gage stations in Puerto Rico.

Figure 6.--Location of water-quality stations in Puerto Rico.

Figure 7.--Location of ground-water stations in Puerto Rico.

16.

Figure 8.--Location of surface-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.

Figure 9.--Location of ground-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Figure 10.--Grid showing system for numbering wells and miscellaneous sites (latitude and longitude).

Records of Stage and Water Discharge

Records of stage and water discharge may be complete or partial. Complete records of discharge are those obtained using a continuous stage-recording device through which either instantaneous or mean daily discharges may be computed for any time, or any period of time, during the period of record. Complete records of lake or reservoir content, similarly, are those for which stage or content may be computed or estimated with reasonable accuracy for any time, or period of time. They may be obtained using a continuous stage-recording device, but need not be. Because daily mean discharges and end-of-day contents commonly are published for such stations, they are referred to as "daily stations."

By contrast, partial records are obtained through discrete measurements without using a continuous stage-recording device and pertain only to a few flow characteristics, or perhaps only one. The nature of the partial record is indicated by table titles such as "Crest-stage partial records," or "Low-flow partial records." Records of miscellaneous discharge measurements or of measurements from special studies, such as low-flow seepage studies, may be considered as partial records, but they are presented separately in this type of report. Location of all complete-record and crest-stage partial-record stations for which data are given in this report are shown in figures 5 and 8.

Data Collection and Computation

The data obtained at a complete-record gaging station on a stream or canal consists of a continuous record of stage, individual measurements of discharge throughout a range of stages, and notations regarding factors that may affect the relationships between stage and discharge. These data, together with supplemental information, such as weather records, are used to compute daily discharges. The data obtained at a complete-record gaging station on a lake or reservoir consist of a record of stage and of notations regarding factors that may affect the relationship between stage and lake content. These data are used with stage-area and stage-capacity curves or tables to compute water-surface areas and lake storage.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Continuous records of stage are obtained with analog recorders that trace continuous graphs of stage or with digital recorders that punch stage values on paper tapes at selected time intervals. Measurements of discharge are made with current meters using methods adapted by the Geological Survey as a result of experience accumulated since 1880. These methods are described in standard textbooks, in Water-Supply Paper 2175, and in U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations, Book 3, Chapter A6.

In computing discharge records, results of individual measurements are plotted against the corresponding stages, and stage-discharge relation curves are then constructed. From these curves, rating tables indicating the approximate discharge for any stage within the range of the measurements are prepared. If it is necessary to define extremes of discharge outside the range of the current-meter measurements, the curves are extended using: (1) logarithmic plotting; (2) velocity-area studies; (3) results of indirect measurements of peak discharge, such as slope-area or contracted-opening measurements, and computations of flow-over-dams or weirs; or (4) step-backwater techniques.

Daily mean discharges are computed by applying the daily mean stages (gage heights) to the stage-discharge curves or tables. If the stage-discharge relation is subject to change because of frequent or continual change in the physical features that form the control, the daily mean discharge is determined by the shifting-control method, in which correction factors based on the individual discharge measurements and notes of the personnel making the measurements are applied to the gage heights before the discharges are determined from the curves or tables. This shifting-control method also is used if the stage-discharge relation is changed temporarily because of aquatic growth or debris on the control.

At some stream-gaging stations the stage-discharge relation is affected by the backwater from reservoirs, tributary streams, or other sources. This necessitates the use of the slope method in which the slope or fall in a reach of the stream is a factor in computing discharge. The slope or fall is obtained by means of an auxiliary gage set at some distance from the base gage. At some stations the stage-discharge relation is affected by changing stage; at these stations the rate of change in stage is used as a factor in computing discharge.

In computing records of lake or reservoir contents, it is necessary to have available from surveys, curves or tables defining the relationship of stage and contents. The application of stage to the stage-content curves or tables gives the contents from which daily, monthly or yearly changes then are determined. If the stage-content relationship changes because of deposition of sediment in a lake or reservoir, periodic surveys may be necessary to redefine it. Even when this is done, as time between the last survey increases, the contents computed may increase in error. Discharges over lake or reservoir spillways are computed from stage-discharge relationships much as other stream discharges are computed.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

For some gaging stations there are periods when no gage-height record is obtained, or the recorded gage height is so faulty that it cannot be used to compute daily discharge or contents. This happens when the recorder stops or otherwise fails to operate properly, intakes are plugged, the float is loose in the well, or for various other reasons. For such periods, the daily discharges are estimated from the recorded range in stage, previous or following record, discharge measurements, weather records, and comparison with other station records from the same or nearby basins. Likewise, daily contents may be estimated from operator's logs, previous or following record, inflow-outflow studies, and other information. Information explaining how estimated daily-discharge values are identified in station records is included in the next two sections, "Data Presentation" (REMARKS paragraph) and "Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge."

Data Presentation

The records published for each gaging station consist of two parts, the manuscript or station description and the data table for the current water year. The manuscript provides, under various headings, descriptive information, such as station location; period of record; average discharge; historical extremes; record accuracy; and other remarks pertinent to station operation and regulation. The following information, as appropriate, is provided with each continuous record of discharge or lake content. Comments to follow clarify information presented under the various headings of the station description.

LOCATION.--Information on locations is obtained from the most accurate maps available. The location of the gage with respect to the cultural and physical features in the vicinity and with respect to the reference place mentioned in the station name is given.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Drainage areas are measured using the most accurate maps available. Drainage areas are updated as better maps become available.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This indicates the period for which there are published records for the station or for an equivalent station. An equivalent station is one that was in operation at a time that the present station was not, and whose location was such that records from it can reasonable be considered equivalent with records from the present station.

REVISED RECORDS.--Published records, because of new information, occasionally are found to be incorrect, and revisions are printed in later reports. Listed under this heading are all the reports in which revisions have been published for the station and the water years to which the revisions apply. If a revision did not include daily, monthly, or annual figures of discharge, that fact is noted after the year dates as follows: "(M)" means that only the instantaneous maximum discharge was revised; "(m)" that only the instantaneous minimum was revised; and "(P)" that only peak discharges were revised. If the drainage area has been revised, the report in which the most recently revised figure was first published is given.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

GAGE.--The type of gage in current use, the datum of the current gage, and a condensed history of the types, locations, and datums of previous gages are given under this heading.

REMARKS.--All periods of estimated daily-discharge record will either be identified by date in this paragraph of the station description for water-discharge stations or flagged in the daily-discharge table. (See next section, "Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge.") If a remarks statement is used to identify estimated record, the paragraph will begin with this information presented as the first entry. The paragraph is also used to present information relative to the accuracy of the records, to special methods of computations, to conditions that affect natural flow at the station and, possibly, to other pertinent items. For reservoir stations, information is given on the dam forming the reservoir, the capacity, outlet works and spillway, and purpose and use of the reservoir.

COOPERATION.--Records provided by a cooperating organization or obtained for the Geological Survey by a cooperating organization are identified here.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--The discharge value given is the arithmetic mean of the water-year mean discharges. It is computed only for stations having at least 5 water years of complete record, and only water years of complete record are included in the computation. It is not computed for stations where diversions, storage, or other water-use practices cause the value to be meaningless. If water developments significantly altering flow at a station are put into use after the station has been in operation for a period of years, a new average is computed as soon as 5 water years of record have accumulated following the development. The median of yearly mean discharges also is given under this heading for stations having 10 or more water years of record, if the median differs from the average given by more than 10 percent.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Extremes may include maximum and minimum stages and maximum and minimum discharges or content. Unless otherwise qualified, the maximum discharge or content is the instantaneous maximum corresponding to the highest stage that occurred. The highest stage may have been obtained from a graphic or digital recorder, a crest-stage gage, or by direct observation of a nonrecording gage. If the maximum stage did not occur on the same day as the maximum discharge or content, it is given separately. Similarly, the minimum is the instantaneous minimum discharge, unless otherwise qualified, and was determined and is reported in the same manner as the maximum.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Included here is information concerning major floods or unusually low flows that occurred outside the stated period of record. The information may or may not have been obtained by the U.S. Geological Survey.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Extremes given here are similar to those for the period of record, except the peak discharge listing may include secondary peaks. For stations meeting certain criteria, all peak discharges and stages occurring during the water year and greater than a selected base discharge are presented under this heading. The peaks greater than the base discharge, excluding the highest one, are referred to as secondary peaks. Peak discharges are not published for canals, ditches, drains, or streams for which the peaks are subject to substantial control by man. The time of occurrence for peaks is expressed in 24-hour local standard time. For example, 12:30 a.m. is 0030, and 1:30 p.m. is 1330. The minimum for the current water year appears below the table of peak data.

REVISIONS.--If a critical error in published records is discovered, a revision is included in the first report published following discovery of the error.

Although rare, occasionally the records of a discontinued gaging station may need revision. Because, for these stations, there would be no current or, possibly, future station manuscript published to document the revision in a "Revised Records" entry, users of data for these stations who obtained the record from previously published data reports may wish to contact the District office to determine if the published records were ever revised after the station was discontinued. Of course, if the data were obtained by computer retrieval, the data would be current and there would be no need to check because any published revision of data is always accompanied by revision of the corresponding data in computer storage.

Manuscript information for lake or reservoir stations differs from that for stream stations in the nature of the "Remarks" and in the inclusion of a skeleton stage-capacity table when daily contents are given.

The daily table for stream-gaging stations gives mean discharge for each day and is followed by monthly and yearly summaries. In the monthly summary below the daily table, the line headed "TOTAL" gives the sum of the daily figures. The line headed "MEAN" gives the average flow in cubic feet per second during the month. The lines headed "MAX" and "MIN" give the maximum and minimum daily discharges, respectively, for the month. Discharge for the month also is usually expressed in cubic feet per second per square mile (line headed "CFSM"), or in inches (line headed "IN."), or in acre-feet (line headed "AC-FT"). Figures for cubic feet per second per square mile and runoff in inches are omitted if there is extensive regulations or diversion or if the drainage area includes large noncontributing areas. In the yearly summary below the monthly summary, the figures shown are the appropriate discharges for the calendar and water years.

Data collected at partial-record stations follow the information for continuous-record sites. Data for partial-record discharge stations are presented in two tables. The first is a table of annual maximum stage and discharge at crest-stage stations, and the second is a table of discharge measurements at low-flow partial-record stations.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge

Estimated daily-discharge values published in the water-discharge tables of annual State data reports are identified either by flagging individual daily values with the letter symbol "e" and printing a table footnote, "e Estimated," or by listing the dates of the estimated record in the REMARKS paragraph of the station description.

Accuracy of the Records

The accuracy of streamflow records depends primarily on: (1) The stability of the stage-discharge relation or, if the control is unstable, the frequency of discharge measurements; and (2) the accuracy of measurements of stage, measurements of discharge, and interpretation of records.

The accuracy attributed to the records is indicated under "REMARKS." "Excellent" means that about 95 percent of the daily discharges are within 5 percent of the true; "good," within 10 percent; and "fair," within 15 percent. Records that do not meet the criteria mentioned, are rated "poor." Different accuracies may be attributed to different parts of a given record.

Daily mean discharges in this report are given to the nearest hundredth of a cubic foot per second for values less than 1 ft³/s; to the nearest tenth between 1.0 and 10 ft³/s; to whole numbers between 10 and 1,000 ft³/s; and to 3 significant figures for more than 1,000 ft³/s. The number of significant figures used is based solely on the magnitude of the discharge value. The same rounding rules apply to discharges listed for partial-record stations and miscellaneous sites.

Information used in the preparation of the records in this publication, such as discharge-measurement notes, gage-height records, temperature measurements, and rating tables are on file in the Caribbean District office. Also, most of the daily mean discharges are in computer-readable form and have been analyzed statistically. Information on the availability of the unpublished information or on the results of statistical analyses of the published records may be obtained from the District office.

Records of Surface-Water Quality

Records of surface-water quality ordinarily are obtained at or near stream-gaging stations because interpretation of records of surface-water quality nearly always requires corresponding discharge data. Records of surface-water quality in this report may involve a variety of types of data and measurement frequencies.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Classification of Records

Water-quality data for surface-water sites are grouped into one of three classifications. A continuing-record station is a site where data are collected on a regularly scheduled basis. Frequency may be once or more times daily, weekly, monthly, or quarterly. A partial-record station is a site where limited water-quality data are collected systematically over a period of years. Frequency of sampling is usually less than quarterly. A miscellaneous sampling site is a location other than a continuing or partial-record station, where random samples are collected to give better areal coverage to define water-quality conditions in the river basin.

A careful distinction needs to be made between "continuing records" as used in this report and "continuous recordings," which refers to a continuous graph or a series of discrete values punched at short intervals on a paper tape. Some records of water quality, such as temperature and specific conductance, may be obtained through continuous recordings; however, because of costs, most data are obtained only monthly or less frequently. Locations of stations for which records on the quality of surface water appear in this report are shown in figure 6.

Arrangement of Records

Water-quality records collected at a surface-water daily record station are published immediately following that record, regardless of the frequency of sample collection. Station number and name are the same for both records. Where a surface-water daily record station is not available or where the water quality differs significantly from that at the nearby surface-water station, the continuing water-quality record is published with its own station number and name in the regular downstream-order sequence. Water-quality data for partial-record stations and for miscellaneous sampling sites appear in separate tables following the table of discharge measurement at miscellaneous sites.

On-site Measurements and Sample Collection

In obtaining water-quality data, a major concern needs to be assuring that the data obtained represent the in situ quality of the water. To assure this, certain measurements, such as water temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen, need to be made onsite when the samples are taken. To assure that measurements made in the laboratory also represent the in situ water, carefully prescribed procedures need to be followed in collecting the samples, in treating the samples to prevent changes in quality pending analysis, and in shipping the samples to the laboratory. Procedures for onsite measurements and for collecting, treating, and shipping samples are given in publications on "Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations," Book 1, Chap. D2; Book 3, Chap. C2; Book 5, Chap. A1, A3, and A4. Detailed information on collecting, treating, and shipping samples may be obtained from the Geological Survey District office.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

One sample can define adequately the water quality at a given time if the mixture of solutes throughout the stream cross section is homogeneous. However, the concentration of solutes at different locations in the cross section may vary widely with different rates of water discharge, depending on the source of material and the turbulence and mixing of the stream. Some streams must be sampled through several vertical sections to obtain a representative sample needed for an accurate mean concentration and for use in calculating load. All samples obtained for the National Stream Quality Accounting Network (see definitions) are obtained from at least several verticals. Whether samples are obtained from the centroid of flow or from several verticals, depends on flow conditions and other factors which must be evaluated by the collector.

Chemical-quality data published in this report are considered to be the most representative values available for the stations listed. The values reported represent water-quality conditions at the time of sampling as much as possible, consistent with available sampling techniques and methods of analysis. In the rare case where an apparent inconsistency exists between a reported pH value and the relative abundance of carbon dioxide species (carbonate and bicarbonate), the inconsistency is the result of a slight uptake of carbon dioxide from the air by the sample between measurement of pH in the field and determination of carbonate and bicarbonate in the laboratory.

For chemical-quality stations equipped with digital monitors, the records consist of daily maximum, minimum, and mean values for each constituent measured and are based upon hourly punches beginning at 0100 hours and ending at 2400 hours for the day of record. More detailed records, when available, (hourly values) may be obtained from the U.S.G.S. District office whose address is given on the back of the title page of this report.

Water Temperature

Water temperatures are measured at most of the water-quality stations. In addition, water temperatures are taken at time of discharge measurements for water-discharge stations. For stations where water temperatures are taken manually once or twice daily, the water temperatures are taken at about the same time each day. Large streams have a small diurnal temperature change; shallow streams may have a daily range of several degrees and may follow closely the changes in air temperature. Some streams may be affected by waste-heat discharges.

At stations where recording instruments are used, either mean temperatures or maximum and minimum temperatures for each day are published. Water temperatures measured at the time of water-discharge measurements are on file in the District office.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Sediment

Suspended-sediment concentrations are determined from samples collected by using depth-integrating samplers. Samples usually are obtained at several verticals in the cross section, or a single sample may be obtained at a fixed point and a coefficient applied to determine the mean concentration in the cross sections.

During periods of rapidly changing flow or rapidly changing concentration, samples may have been collected more frequently (twice daily or, in some instances, hourly). The published sediment discharges for days of rapidly changing flow or concentration were computed by the subdivided-day method (time-discharge weighted average). Therefore, for those days when the published sediment discharge value differs from the value computed as the product of discharge times mean concentration times 0.0027, the reader can assume that the sediment discharge for that day was computed by the subdivided-day method. For periods when no samples were collected, daily discharges of suspended sediment were estimated on the basis of water discharge, sediment concentrations observed immediately before and after the periods, and suspended-sediment loads for other periods of similar discharge.

At other stations, suspended-sediment samples were collected periodically at many verticals in the stream cross section. Although data collected periodically may represent conditions only at the time of observations, such data are useful in establishing seasonal relations between quality and stream-flow and in predicting long-term sediment-discharge characteristics of the stream.

In addition to the records of suspended-sediment discharge, records of the periodic measurements of the particle-size distribution of the suspended sediment and bed material are included for some stations.

Laboratory Measurements

Sediment samples, samples for biochemical-oxygen demand (BOD), samples for indicator bacteria, and daily samples for specific conductance are analyzed locally. All other samples are analyzed in the Geological Survey laboratories in Denver, Co. or Ocala, Fla. Methods used in analyzing sediment samples and computing sediment records are given in TWRI, Book 5, Chap. C1. Methods used by the Geological Survey laboratories are given in TWRI, Book 1, Chap. D2; Book 3, Chap. C2; Book 5, Chap. A1, A3, and A4.

Data Presentation

For continuing-record stations, information pertinent to the history of station operation is provided in descriptive headings preceding the tabular data. These descriptive headings give details regarding location, drainage area, period of record, type of data available, instrumentation, general remarks, cooperation, and extremes for parameters currently measured daily. Tables of chemical, physical, biological, radiochemical data, and so forth, obtained at a frequency less than daily are presented first, and tables of "daily values" of specific conductance, pH, water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and suspended sediment then follow in sequence, when these parameters are studied.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

In the descriptive headings, if the location is identical to that of the discharge gaging station, neither the LOCATION nor the DRAINAGE AREA statements are repeated. The following information, as appropriate, is provided with each continuous-record station. Comments that follow clarify information presented under the various headings of the station description.

LOCATION.--See Data Presentation under "Records of Stage and Water Discharge;" same comments apply.

DRAINAGE AREA.--See Data Presentation under "Records of Stage and Water Discharge;" same comments apply.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This indicates the periods for which there are published water-quality records for the station. The periods are shown separately for records of parameters measured daily or continuously and those measured less than daily. For those measured daily or continuously, periods of record are given for the parameters individually.

INSTRUMENTATION.--Information on instrumentation is given only if a water-quality monitor temperature record, sediment pumping sampler, or other sampling device is in operation at a station.

REMARKS.--Remarks provide added information pertinent to the collection, analysis, or computation of the records.

COOPERATION.--Records provided by a cooperating organization or obtained for the Geological Survey by a cooperating organization are identified here.

EXTREMES.--Maximums and minimums are given only for parameters measured daily or more frequently. None are given for parameters measured weekly or less frequently, because the true maximums or minimums may not have been sampled. Extremes, when given, are provided for both the period of record and for the current water year.

REVISIONS.--If errors in published water-quality records are discovered after publication, appropriate updates are made to the Water-Quality File in the U.S. Geological Survey's computerized data system, WATSTORE, and subsequently by monthly transfer of update transactions to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's STORET system. Because the usual volume of updates makes it impractical to document individual changes in the State data-report series or elsewhere, potential users of U.S. Geological Survey water-quality data are encouraged to obtain all required data from the appropriate computer file to insure the most recent updates.

The surface-water-quality records for partial-record stations and miscellaneous sampling sites are published in separate tables following the table of discharge measurements at miscellaneous sites. No descriptive statements are given for these records. Each station is published with its own station number and name in the regular downstream-order sequence.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Remark Codes

The following remark codes may appear with the water-quality data in this report:

<u>PRINTED OUTPUT</u>	<u>REMARK</u>
E	Estimated value
>	Actual value is known to be greater than the value shown
<	Actual value is known to be less than the value shown
K	Results based on colony count outside the acceptance range (non-ideal colony count)
L	Biological organism count less than 0.5 percent (organism may be observed rather than counted)
D	Biological organism count equal to or greater than 15 percent (dominant)
&	Biological organism estimated as dominant

Records of Ground-Water Levels

Only ground-water level data from a basic network of observation wells are published herein. This basic network contains observation wells so located that the most significant data are obtained from the fewest wells in the most important aquifers.

Data Collection and Computation

Measurements of water levels are made in many types of wells under varying conditions, but the methods of measurement are standardized to the extent possible. The equipment and measuring techniques used at each observation well ensure that measurements at each well are of consistent accuracy and reliability.

Each well is identified by means of (1) a 15-digit number that is based on latitude and longitude and (2) a local number that is provided for local needs. See figure 10.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Water-level records are obtained from direct measurements with a steel tape or from the graph or punched tape of a water-stage recorder. The water-level measurements in this report are given in feet with reference to land-surface datum (lsd). Land-surface datum is a datum plane that is approximately at land surface at each well. If known, the elevation of the land-surface datum is given in the well description. The height of the measuring point (MP) above or below land-surface datum is given in each well description. Water levels in wells equipped with recording gages are reported for every day and as an instantaneous observation at noon.

Water levels are reported to as many significant figures as can be justified by the local conditions. For example, in a measurement of a depth to water of several hundred feet, the error of determining the absolute value of the total depth to water may be a few tenths of a foot, whereas the error in determining the net change of water level between successive measurements may be only a hundredth of a few hundredths of a foot. For lesser depths to water, the accuracy is greater. Accordingly, most measurements reported to a hundredth of a foot, but some are given to a tenth of a foot or a larger unit.

Data Presentation

Each well record consists of two parts, the station description and the data table of water levels observed during the water year. The description of the well is presented first through use of descriptive headings preceding the tabular data. The comments to follow clarify information presented under the various headings.

LOCATION.--This paragraph follows the well-identification number and reports the latitude and longitude (given in degrees, minutes, and seconds); a landline location designation; the hydrologic-unit number; the distance and direction from a geographic point of reference; and the owner's name.

AQUIFER.--This entry designates by name (if a name exists) and geologic age the aquifer(s) open to the well.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--This entry describes the well in terms of depth, diameter, casing depth and/or screened interval, method of construction, use, and additional information such as casing breaks, collapsed screen, and other changes since construction.

DATUM.--This entry describes both the measuring point and the land-surface elevation at the well. The measuring point is described physically (such as top of collar, notch in top of casing, plug in pump base and so on), and in relation to land surface (such as 1.3 ft above land-surface datum). The elevation of the land-surface datum is described in feet above mean sea level datum, if available. It is reported with precision depending on the method of determination.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

REMARKS.--This entry describes factors that may influence the water level in a well or the measurement of the water level. It should identify wells that also are water-quality observation wells, and may be used to acknowledge the assistance of local (non-survey) observers.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This entry indicates the period for which there are published records for the well. It reports the month and year of the start of publication of water-level records by the U.S. Geological Survey and the words "to current year" if the records are to be continued into the following year. Periods for which water-level records are available, but are not published by the Geological Survey, may be noted.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--This entry contains the highest and lowest water levels of the period of published record, with respect to land-surface datum, and the dates of their occurrence.

A table of water levels follows the station description for each well. Water levels are reported in feet below land-surface datum and all taped measurements of water level are listed. For wells equipped with recorders, daily values tables are published for the instantaneous water-level observation at noon. The highest and lowest water levels of the water year are shown on a line below the table. Because all values are not published for wells with recorders, the extremes may be values that are not listed in the table. Missing records are indicated by dashes in place of the water level.

Records of Ground-Water Quality

Records of ground-water quality in this type of report differ from other types of records in that for most sampling sites they consist of only one set of measurements for the water year. The quality of ground water ordinarily changes only slowly; therefore, for most general purposes one annual sampling, or only a few samples taken at infrequent intervals during the year, is sufficient. Frequent measurement of the same constituents is not necessary unless one is concerned with a particular problem, such as monitoring for trends in nitrate concentration. In the special cases where the quality of ground water may change more rapidly, more frequent measurements are made to identify the nature of the changes.

Data Collection and Computation

The records of ground-water quality in this report were obtained mostly as a part of special studies in specific areas. Consequently, a number of chemical analyses are presented for some counties but none are presented for others. As a result, the records for this year, by themselves, do not provide a balanced view of ground-water quality Statewide. Such a view can be attained only by considering records for this year in context with similar records obtained for these and other counties in earlier years.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Most methods for collecting and analyzing water samples are described in the "U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations" manuals listed on a following page. The values reported in this type of report represent water-quality conditions at the time of sampling as much as possible, consistent with available sampling techniques and methods of analysis. All samples are obtained by trained personnel. The wells sampled are pumped long enough to assure that the water collected comes directly from the aquifer and has not stood for a long time in the well casing where it would have been exposed to the atmosphere and to the material, possibly metal, comprising the casings.

Data Presentation

The records of ground-water quality, when available, are published in a section titled QUALITY OF GROUND WATER immediately following the ground-water level records. Data for quality of ground water are listed alphabetically by County, and are identified by well number. The prime identification number for wells sampled is the 15-digit number derived from the latitude-longitude locations. No descriptive statements are given for ground-water-quality records; however, the well number, depth of well, date of sampling, and other pertinent data are given in the table containing the chemical analyses of the ground water. The REMARK codes listed for surface-water-quality records are also applicable to ground-water-quality records.

ACCESS TO WATSTORE DATA

The National WATER Data STORAGE and RETRIEVAL System (WATSTORE) was established for handling water data collected through the activities of the U.S. Geological Survey and to provide for more effective and efficient means of releasing the data to the public. The system is operated and maintained on the central computer facilities of the Survey at its National Center in Reston, Virginia.

WATSTORE can provide a variety of useful products ranging from simple data tables to complex statistical analyses. A minimal fee, plus the actual computer cost incurred in producing a desired product, is charged to the requester. Information about the availability of specific types of data, the acquisition of data or products, and user charges can be obtained locally from each of the Water Resources Division's District offices (see address given on the back of the title page).

General inquiries about WATSTORE may be directed to:

Chief Hydrologist
U.S. Geological Survey
437 National Center
Reston, Virginia 22092

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

DEFINITION OF TERMS

Terms related to streamflow, water-quality, and other hydrologic data as used in this report, are defined below. See also the table for converting inch-pound units to the International System of units (SI) on the inside of the back cover.

Acre-foot (AC-FT, acre-ft) is the quantity of water required to cover 1 acre to a depth of 1 foot and is equal to about 326,000 gallons or 1,233 cubic meters.

Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) is an organic, phosphate-rich, compound important in the transfer of energy in organisms. Its central role in living cells makes it an excellent indicator of the presence of living material in water. A measure of ATP therefore provides a sensitive and rapid estimate of biomass. ATP is reported in micrograms per liter of the original water sample.

Algae growth potential (AGP) is the maximum algal dry weight biomass that can be produced in a natural water sample under standardized laboratory conditions. The growth potential is the algal biomass present a stationary phase and is expressed as milligrams dry weight of algae produced per liter of sample.

Aquifer is a geologic formation, group of formations, or part of a formation that contains sufficient saturated permeable material to yield significant quantities of water to wells and springs.

Artesian means confined and is used to describe a well in which the water level stands above the top of the aquifer, tapped by the well. A flowing artesian well is one in which the water level is above the land surface.

Bacteria are microscopic unicellular organisms, typically spherical, rodlike, or spiral and threadlike in shape, often clumped into colonies. Some bacteria cause disease, while others perform an essential role in nature in the recycling of materials; for example, by decomposing organic matter into a form available for reuse by plants.

Total coliform bacteria are a particular group of bacteria that are used as indicators of possible sewage pollution. They are characterized as aerobic or facultative anaerobic, gram-negative, nonspore-forming, rod-shaped bacteria which ferment lactose with gas formation within 48 hours at 35°C. In the laboratory these bacteria are defined as all the organisms which produce colonies with a golden-green metallic sheen within 24 hours when incubated at 35°C \pm 1.0°C on M-Endo medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Fecal coliform bacteria are bacteria that are present in the intestines or feces of warm-blooded animals. They are often used as indicators of the sanitary quality of the water. In the laboratory they are defined as all organisms which produce blue colonies within 24 hours when incubated at $44.5^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ on M-FC medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

Fecal streptococcal bacteria are bacteria found also in intestines of warm-blooded animals. Their presence in water is considered to verify fecal pollution. They are characterized as Gram-positive, cocci bacteria which are capable of growth in brain-heart infusion broth. In the laboratory they are defined as all the organisms which produce red or pink colonies within 48 hours at $35^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ on KF-streptococcus medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

Bed material is the unconsolidated material of which a streambed, lake, pond, reservoir, or estuary bottom is composed.

Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is a measure of the quantity of dissolved oxygen, in milligrams per liter, necessary for the decomposition of organic matter by microorganisms, such as bacteria.

Biomass is the amount of living matter present at any given time, expressed as the mass per unit area or volume of habitat.

Ash mass is the mass or amount of residue present after the residue from the dry mass determination has been ashed in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 500°C for 1 hour. The ash mass values of zooplankton and phytoplankton are expressed in grams per cubic meter (g/m^3), and periphyton and benthic organisms in grams per square meter (g/m^2).

Dry mass refers to the mass of residue present after drying in an oven at 105°C for zooplankton and periphyton, until the mass remains unchanged. This mass represents the total organic matter, ash and sediment, in the sample. Dry-mass values are expressed in the same units as ash mass.

Organic mass or volatile mass of the living substance is the difference between the dry mass and the ash mass and represents the actual matter. The organic mass is expressed in the same units as for ash and dry mass.

Wet mass is the mass of living matter plus contained water.

Bottom material: See Bed material.

Cells/volume refers to the number of cells of any organism which is counted by using a microscope and grid or counting cell. Many planktonic organisms are multicelled and are counted according to the number of contained cells per sample, usually milliliters (mL) or liters (L).

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Chemical oxygen demand (COD) is a measure of the chemically oxidizable material in the water, and furnishes an approximation of the amount of organic and reducing material present. The determined value may correlate with natural water color or with carbonaceous organic pollution from sewage or industrial wastes.

Chlorophyll refers to the green pigments of plants. Chlorophyll a and b are the two most common green pigments in plants.

Color unit is produced by one milligram per liter of platinum in the form of the chloroplatinate ion. Color is expressed in units of the platinum-cobalt scale.

Contents is the volume of water in a reservoir or lake. Unless otherwise indicated, volume is computed on the basis of a level pool and does not include bank storage.

Control designates a feature downstream from the gage that determines the stage-discharge relation at the gage. This feature may be a natural constriction of the channel, an artificial structure, or a uniform cross section over a long reach of the channel.

Control structure as used in this report is a structure on a stream or canal that is used to regulate the flow or stage of the stream or to prevent the intrusion of salt water.

Crest-stage station is a special form of partial-record station that records the highest stage of the stream that occurred between periodic visits to the station. A stage-discharge relation for each gage may be developed from discharge measurements made by indirect methods or by current meter.

Cubic foot per second (cfs) is the rate of discharge representing a volume of 1 cubic foot passing a given point during 1 second and is equivalent to 7.48 gallons per second or 448.8 gallons per minute or 0.02832 cubic meters per second.

Cubic foot per second-day (cfs-day) is the volume of water represented by a flow of 1 cubic foot per second for 24 hours. It is equivalent to 86,400 cubic feet, approximately 1.9835 acre-feet, about 646,000 gallons, or 2,445 cubic meters.

Cubic feet per second per square mile (CFSM) is the average number of cubic feet of water flowing per second from each square mile of area drained, assuming that the runoff is distributed uniformly in time and area.

Discharge is the volume of water (or more broadly, volume of fluid plus suspended sediment), that passes a given point within a given period of time.

Instantaneous discharge is the discharge at a particular instant of time.

Mean discharge (MEAN) is the arithmetic mean of individual daily mean discharges during a specific period.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Dissolved refers to that material in a representative water sample which passes through a 0.45 um membrane filter. This is a convenient operational definition used by Federal agencies that collect water data. Determinations of "dissolved" constituents are made on subsamples of the filtrate.

Dissolved-solids concentration of water is determined either analytically by the "residue-on-evaporation" method, or mathematically by totaling the concentrations of individual constituents reported in a comprehensive chemical analysis. During the analytical determination of dissolved solids, the bicarbonate (generally a major dissolved component of water) is converted to carbonate. Therefore, in the mathematical calculations of dissolved-solids concentration, the bicarbonate value, in milligrams per liter, is multiplied by 0.492 to reflect the change.

Diversity index is a numerical expression of evenness of distribution of aquatic organisms. The formula for diversity index is:

$$\bar{d} = - \sum_{i=1}^s \frac{n_i}{n} \log_2 \frac{n_i}{n}$$

Where n_i is the number of individuals per taxon, n is the total number of individuals, and s is the total number of taxa in the sample of the community. Diversity index values range from zero, when all the organisms in the sample are the same, to some positive number, when some or all of the organisms in the sample are different.

Drainage area of a stream at a specified location is that area, measured in a horizontal plane, enclosed by a topographic divide from which direct surface runoff from precipitation normally drains by gravity into the stream above the specified point. Figures of drainage area given herein include all closed basins, or noncontribution areas, within the area unless otherwise noted.

Drainage basin is a part of the surface of the earth that is occupied by a drainage system, which consists of a surface stream or a body of impounded surface water together with all tributary surface streams and bodies of impounded surface water.

Gage height (G.H.) is the water-surface elevation referred to some arbitrary gage datum. Gage height is often used interchangeably with the more general term "stage," although gage height is more appropriate when used with a reading on a gage.

Gaging station is a particular site on a stream, canal, lake, or reservoir where systematic observations of hydrologic data are obtained.

Ground-water station is a well at which observations of ground-water level are made, either continuously by recorder, or periodically by hand. In addition, various chemical or physical parameters may be obtained, usually on a periodic basis.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Hardness of water is a physical-chemical characteristic that is commonly recognized by the increased quantity of soap required to produce lather. It is attributable to the presence of alkaline earths (principally calcium and magnesium) and is expressed as equivalent calcium carbonate (CaCO_3).

Hydrologic Bench-Mark Network is a network in small drainage basins around the country whose purpose is to provide consistent data on the hydrology, including water quality, and related factors in representative undeveloped watersheds nationwide, and to provide analyses on a continuing basis to compare and contrast conditions observed in basins more obviously affected by the activities of man.

Hydrologic unit is a geographic area representing part or all of a surface drainage basin or distinct hydrologic feature as delineated by the Office of Water Data Coordination on the State Hydrologic Unit Maps; each hydrologic unit is identified by an eight-digit number.

Land-surface datum (lsd) is a datum plane that is approximately at land surface at each ground-water observation well.

Measuring point (MP) is an arbitrary permanent reference point from which the distance to the water surface in a well is measured to obtain the water level.

Metamorphic stage refers to the stage of development that an organism exhibits during its transformation from an immature form to an adult form. This developmental process exists for most insects, and the degree of difference from the immature stage to the adult form varies from relatively slight to pronounced, with many intermediates. Examples of metamorphic stages of insects are egg-larva-adult or egg-nymph-adult.

Methylene blue active substances (MBAS) are apparent detergents. The determination depends on the formation of a blue color when methylene blue dye reacts with synthetic anionic detergent compounds.

Micrograms per gram (ug/g) is a unit expressing the concentration of a chemical element as the mass (micrograms) of the element per unit mass (gram) of material analyzed.

Micrograms per liter (UG/L, ug/L) is a unit expressing the concentration of chemical constituents in solution as mass (micrograms) of solute per unit volume (liter) of water. One thousand micrograms per liter is equivalent to one milligram per liter.

Milligrams per liter (MG/L, mg/L) is a unit for expressing the concentration of chemical constituents in solution. Milligrams per liter represent the mass of solute per unit volume (liter) of water. Concentration of suspended sediment also is expressed in mg/L, and is based on the mass of sediment per liter of water-sediment mixture. Conversion of chemical concentrations in Mg/L to milliequivalents per liter can be done by using the factors in table 5.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

TABLE 5.--Factors for conversion of chemical constituents in milligrams per liter to milliequivalents per liter.

<u>Ion</u>	<u>Multiply by</u>	<u>Ion</u>	<u>Multiply by</u>
Aluminum (Al+3)*.....	0.11119	Iodide (I-1).....	0.00788
Ammonia as NH ₄ +1.....	.05544	Iron (Fe+3).....	.05372
Barium (Ba+2).....	.01456	Lead (Pb+2).....	.00965
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃ -1)....	.01639	Lithium (Li+1).....	.14411
Bromide (Br-1).....	.01251	Magnesium (Mg+2)....	.08226
Calcium (Ca+2).....	.04990	Manganese (Mn+2)*...	.03640
Carbonate (CO ₃ -2).....	.03333	Nickel (Ni+2).....	.03406
Chloride (Cl-1).....	.02821	Nitrate (NO ₃ -1).....	.01613
Chromium (Cr+6)*.....	.11539	Nitrite (NO ₂ -1).....	.02174
Cobalt (Co+2)*.....	.03394	Phosphate (PO ₄ -3)...	.03159
Copper (Cu+2)*.....	.03148	Potassium (K+1).....	.02557
Cyanide (CN-1).....	.03844	Sodium (NA+1).....	.04350
Fluoride (F-1).....	.05264	Strontium (Sr+2)....	.02283
Hydrogen (H+1).....	.99209	Sulfate (SO ₄ -2).....	.02082
Hydroxide (OH-1).....	.05880	Zinc (Zn+2)*.....	.03060

*Constituent reported in micrograms per liter; multiply by factor and divide results by 1,000.

National Stream Quality Accounting Network (NASQAN) is a nationwide data-collection network designed by the U.S. Geological Survey to meet many of the information needs of government agencies and other groups involved in natural or regional water-quality planning and management. The 500 or so sites in NASQAN are generally located at the downstream ends of hydrologic accounting units designated by the U.S. Geological Survey office of Water Data Coordination in consultation with the Water Resources Council. The objectives of NASQAN are (1) to obtain information on the quality and quantity of water moving within and from the United States through a systematic and uniform process of data collection, summarization, analysis, and reporting such that the data may be used for, (2) description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of data from this and other programs, (3) detection of changes or trends with time in the pattern of occurrence of water-quality characteristics, and (4) providing a nationally consistent data base useful for water-quality assessment and hydrologic research.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

National Trends Network (NTN) is a network for sampling atmospheric deposition in the United States. The purpose of the network is to determine the variability, both in location and in time, of the composition of atmospheric deposition, which includes snow, rain, dust particles, aerosols, and gases. The core from which the NTN was built was the already-existing deposition-monitoring network of the National Atmospheric Deposition Program (NADP).

Organism is any living entity.

Organism count/area refers to the number of organisms collected and enumerated in a sample and adjusted to the number per unit area habitat, usually square meters (m²), acres, or hectare. Periphyton, benthic organisms, and macrophytes are expressed in these terms.

Organism count/volume refers to the number of organisms collected and enumerated in a sample and adjusted to the number per sample volume, usually milliliters (mL) or liters (L). Numbers of planktonic organisms can be expressed in these terms.

Total organism count is the total number of organisms collected and enumerated in any particular sample.

Parameter Code is a 5-digit number used in the U.S. Geological Survey computerized data system, WATSTORE, to uniquely identify a specific constituent. The codes used in WATSTORE are the same as those used in the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency data system, STORET. The Environmental Protection Agency assigns and approves all requests for new codes.

Partial-record station is a particular site where limited streamflow and/or water-quality data are collected systematically over a period of years for use in hydrologic analyses.

Particle-size is the diameter, in millimeters (mm), of a particle determined by either sieve or sedimentation methods. Sedimentation methods (pipet, bottom-withdrawal tube, visual-accumulation tube) determine fall diameter of particles in either distilled water (chemically dispersed) or in native water (the river water at the time and point of sampling).

Particle-size classification used in this report agrees with recommendations made by the American Geophysical Union Subcommittee on Sediment Terminology. The classification is as follows:

<u>Classification</u>	<u>Size (mm)</u>	<u>Method of analysis</u>
Clay.....	0.00024 - 0.004	Sedimentation
Silt.....	.004 - .062	Sedimentation
Sand.....	.062 - 2.0	Sedimentation or sieve
Gravel....	2.0 - 64.0	Sieve

The particle-size distributions given in this report are not necessarily representative of all particles in transport in the stream. Most of the organic matter is removed and the sample is subjected to mechanical and chemical dispersion before analysis in distilled water. Chemical dispersion is not used for native water analysis.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Percent composition is a unit for expressing the ratio of a particular part of a sample or population to the total sample or population, in terms of types, numbers, mass or volume.

Periphyton is the assemblage of microorganisms attached to and living upon submerged solid surfaces. While primarily consisting of algae, they also include bacteria, fungi, protozoa, rotifers, and other small organisms.

Pesticides are chemical compounds used to control undesirable organisms. Major categories of pesticides include insecticides, miticides, fungicides, herbicides, and rodenticides.

Picocurie (PC, pCi) is one trillionth (1×10^{-12}) of the amount of radioactivity represented by a curie (Ci). A curie is the amount of radioactivity that yields 3.7×10^{10} radioactive disintegrations per second. A picocurie yields 2.22 dpm (disintegrations per minute).

Plankton is the community of suspended, floating, or weakly swimming organisms that live in the open water of lakes and rivers.

Phytoplankton is the plant part of the plankton. They are usually microscopic and their movement is subject to the water currents. Phytoplankton growth is dependent upon solar radiation and nutrient substances. Because they are able to incorporate as well as release materials to the surrounding water, the phytoplankton have a profound effect upon the quality of the water. They are the primary food producers in the aquatic environment, and are commonly known as algae.

Blue-green algae are a group of phytoplankton organisms having a blue pigment, in addition to the green pigment called chlorophyll. Blue-green algae often cause nuisance conditions in water.

Diatoms are the unicellular or colonial algae having a siliceous shell. Their concentrations are expressed as number of cells per milliliter (cells/mL) of sample.

Green algae have chlorophyll pigments similar in color to those of higher green plants. Some forms produce algae mats or floating "moss" in lakes. Their concentrations are expressed as number of cells per milliliter (cells/mL) of sample.

Zooplankton is the animal part of the plankton. Zooplankton are capable of extensive movements within the water column and are often large enough to be seen with the unaided eye. Zooplankton are secondary consumers feeding upon bacteria, phytoplankton, and detritus. Because they are the grazers in the aquatic environment, the zooplankton are a vital part of the aquatic food web. The zooplankton community is dominated by small crustaceans and rotifers.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Primary productivity is a measure of the rate at which new organic matter is formed and accumulated through photosynthetic and chemosynthetic activity of producer organisms (chiefly, green plants). The rate of primary production is estimated by measuring the amount of oxygen released (oxygen method) or the amount of carbon assimilated by the plants (carbon method).

Milligrams of carbon per area or volume per unit time [mg C/(m².time) for periphyton and macrophytes and [mg C/(m³.time)] for phytoplankton are units for expressing primary productivity. They define the amount of carbon dioxide consumed as measured by radioactive carbon (carbon 14). The carbon 14 method is of greater sensitivity than the oxygen light and dark bottle method, and is preferred for use in unenriched waters. Unit time may be either hour or day, depending on the incubation period.

Milligrams of oxygen per area or volume per unit time [mgO / (m².time)] for periphyton and macrophytes and [mgO / (m³.time)] for phytoplankton are the units for expressing primary productivity. They define production and respiration rates as estimated from changes in the measured dissolved-oxygen concentration. The oxygen light and dark bottle method is preferred if the rate of primary production is sufficient for accurate measurements to be made within 24 hours. Unit time may be either the hour or day, depending on the incubation period.

Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) are industrial chemicals that are mixtures of chlorinated biphenyl compounds having various percentages of chlorine. They are similar in structure to organochlorine insecticides.

Radiochemical program is a network of regularly sampled water-quality stations where samples are collected to be analyzed for radioisotopes. The streams that are sampled represent major drainage basins in the conterminous United States.

Recoverable from bottom material is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after a representative sample of bottom material has been digested by a method (usually using an acid or mixture of acids) that results in dissolution of readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all bottom material is not achieved by the digestion treatment and thus the determination represents less than the total amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent in the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures would be required of all laboratories performing such analyses because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Return period is the average time interval between occurrences of a hydrological event of a given or greater magnitude, usually expressed in years. May also be called recurrence interval.

Runoff in inches (IN, in) shows the depth to which the drainage area would be covered if all the runoff for a given time period were uniformly distributed on it.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Sediment is solid material that originates mostly from disintegrated rocks and is transported by, suspended in, or deposited from water; it includes chemical and biochemical precipitates and decomposed organic material, such as humus. The quantity, characteristics, and cause of the occurrence of sediment in streams are influenced by environmental factors. Some major factors are degree of slope, length of slope, soil characteristics, land usage, and quantity and intensity of precipitation.

Bed load is the sediment that is transported in a stream by rolling, sliding, or skipping along the bed and very close to it. In this report, bed load is considered to consist of particles in transit within 0.25 ft of the streambed.

Bed load discharge (tons per day) is the quantity of bed load measured by dry weight that moves past a section as bed load in a given time.

Suspended sediment is the sediment that at any given time is maintained in suspension by the upward components of turbulent currents or that exists in suspension as a colloid.

Suspended-sediment concentration is the velocity-weighted concentration of suspended sediment in the sampled zone (from the water surface to a point approximately 0.3 ft above the bed) expressed as milligrams of dry sediment per liter of water-sediment mixture (mg/L).

Mean concentration is the time-weighted concentration of suspended sediment passing a stream section during a 24-hour day.

Suspended-sediment discharge (tons/day) is the rate at which dry mass of sediment passes a section of a stream or is the quantity of sediment, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes a section in a given time. It is calculated in units of tons per day as follows: concentrations (mg/L) x discharge ft^3/s x 0.0027.

Suspended-sediment load is a general term that refers to material in suspension. It is not synonymous with either discharge or concentration.

Total sediment discharge (tons/day) is the sum of the suspended-sediment discharge and the bed-load discharge. It is the total quantity of sediment, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes a section during a given time.

Total-sediment load or total load is a term which refers to the total sediment (bed load plus suspended-sediment load) that is in transport. It is not synonymous with total-sediment discharge.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Sodium-adsorption-ratio (SAR) is the expression of relative activity of sodium ions in exchange reactions within soil and is an index of sodium or alkali hazard to the soil. Waters range in respect to sodium hazard from those which can be used for irrigation on almost all soils to those which are generally unsatisfactory for irrigation.

Solute is any substance that is dissolved in water.

Specific conductance is a measure of the ability of a water to conduct an electric current. It is expressed in microsiemens per centimeter at 25°C. Specific conductance is related to the type and concentration of ions in solution and can be used for approximating the dissolved-solids content of the water. Commonly, the concentration of dissolved solids (in milligrams per liter) is about 65 percent of the specific conductance (in micromhos). This relation is not constant from stream to stream, and it may vary in the same source with changes in the composition of the water.

Stage-discharge relation is the relation between gage height (stage) and volume of water per unit of time, flowing in a channel.

Streamflow is the discharge that occurs in a natural channel. Although the term "discharge" can be applied to the flow of a canal, the word "streamflow" uniquely describes the discharge in a surface stream course. The term "streamflow" is more general than "runoff" as streamflow may be applied to discharge whether or not it is affected by diversion or regulation.

Substrate is the physical surface upon which an organism lives.

Natural substrate refers to any naturally occurring emerged or submersed solid surface, such as a rock or tree, upon which an organism lives.

Artificial substrate is a device which is purposely placed in a stream or lake for colonization of organisms. The artificial substrate simplifies the community structure by standardizing the substrate from which each sample is taken. Examples of artificial substrates are basket samplers (made of wire cages filled with clean streamside rocks) and multiplate samplers (made of hardboard) for benthic organism collection, and plexiglass strips for periphyton.

Surface area of a lake is that area outlined on the latest U.S.G.S. topographic map as the boundary of the lake and measured by a planimeter in acres. In localities not covered by topographic maps, the areas are computed from the best maps available at the time planimetered. All areas shown are those for the stage when the planimetered map was made.

Surficial bed material is that part (0.1 to 0.2 ft) of the bed material that is sampled using U.S. Series Bed-Material Samplers.

Suspended (as used in tables of chemical analyses) refers to the amount (concentration) of the total concentration in a water-sediment mixture. It is associated with the material retained on a 0.45-micrometer filter.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Suspended, recoverable is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after the part of a representative water-suspended sediment sample that is retained on a 0.45 um membrane filter has been digested by a method (usually using a dilute acid solution) that results in dissolution of only readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all the particulate matter is not achieved by the digestion treatment and thus the determination represents something less than the "total" amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent present in the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures are required of all laboratories performing such analyses because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Determinations of "suspended, recoverable" constituents are made either by analyzing portions of the material collected on the filter or, more commonly, by difference, based on determinations of (1) dissolved and (2) total recoverable concentrations of the constituent.

Suspended, total is the total amount of a given constituent in the part of representative water-suspended sediment sample that is retained on a 0.45 um membrane filter. This term is used only when the analytical procedure assures measurement of at least 95 percent of the constituent determined. A knowledge of the expected form of the constituent in the sample, as well as the analytical methodology used, is required to determine when the results should be reported as "suspended, total."

Determinations of "suspended, total" constituents are made either by analyzing portions of the material collected on the filter or, more commonly, by difference, based on determinations of (1) dissolved and (2) total concentrations of the constituent.

Taxonomy is the division of biology concerned with the classification and naming of organisms. The classification of organisms is based upon a hierarchical scheme beginning with Kingdom and ending with Species at the base. The higher the classification level, the fewer features the organisms have in common. For example, the taxonomy of a particular mayfly, Hexagenia limbata, is the following:

Kingdom.....	Animal
Phylum.....	Arthropoda
Class.....	Insecta
Order.....	Ephemeroptera
Family.....	Ephemeridae
<u>Genus</u>	<u>Hexagenia</u>
<u>Species</u>	<u>Hexagenia limbata</u>

Thermograph is an instrument that continuously records variations of temperature on a chart. The more general term "temperature recorder" is used in the table heading and refers to any instrument that records temperature whether on a chart, a tape, or any other medium.

Time-weighted average is computed by multiplying the number of days in the sampling period by the concentrations of individual constituents for the corresponding period and dividing the sum of the products by the total number of days. A time-weighted average represents the composition of water that would be contained in a vessel or reservoir that had received equal quantities of water from the stream each day for the year.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Tons per acre-foot indicates the dry mass of dissolved solids in 1 acre-foot of water. It is computed by multiplying the concentration of the constituent, in milligrams per liter by 0.00136.

Tons per day (T/DAY) is the quantity of a substance in solution or suspension that passes a stream section during a 24-hour period.

Total is the total amount of a given constituent in a representative water-suspended sediment sample, regardless of the constituent's physical or chemical form. This term is used only when the analytical procedure assures measurement of at least 95 percent of the constituent present in both the dissolved and suspended phases of the sample. A knowledge of the expected form of the constituent in the sample, as well as the analytical methodology used, is required to judge when the results should be reported as "total." (Note that the word "total" does double duty here, indicating both that the sample consists of a water-suspended sediment mixture and that the analytical method determined all of the constituent in the sample.)

Total discharge is the total quantity of any individual constituent, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes through a stream cross-section per unit of time. This term needs to be qualified, such as "total sediment discharge," "total chloride discharge," and so on.

Total, recoverable is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after a representative water-suspended sediment sample has been digested by a method (usually using a dilute acid solution) that results in dissolution of only readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all particulate matter is not achieved by the digestion treatment, and thus the determination represents something less than the "total" amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent present in the dissolved and suspended phases of the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures are required of all laboratories performing such analyses, because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Tritium Network is a network of stations which has been established to provide baseline information on the occurrence of tritium in the Nation's surface waters. In addition to the surface-water stations in the network, tritium data are also obtained at a number of precipitation stations. The purpose of the precipitation stations is to provide an estimate sufficient for hydrologic studies of the tritium input to the United States.

Water year in Geological Survey reports dealing with surface water supply is the 12-month period, October 1 through September 30. The water year is designated by the calendar year in which it ends and which includes 9 of the 12 months. Thus, the year ending September 30, 1980, is called the "1980 water year."

WDR is used as an abbreviation for "Water-Data Report" in the REVISED RECORDS paragraph to refer to State annual hydrologic-data reports (WRD was used as an abbreviation for "Water-Resources Data" in reports published prior to 1976).

WATER RESOURCES FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1986

Weighted average is used in this report to indicate discharge-weighted average. It is computed by multiplying the discharge for a sampling period by the concentrations of individual constituents for the corresponding period and dividing the sum of the products by the sum of the discharges. A discharge-weighted average approximates the composition of water that would be found in a reservoir containing all the water passing a given location during the water year after thorough mixing in the reservoir.

WSP is used as an abbreviation for "Water-Supply Paper" in references to previously published reports.

PUBLICATIONS ON TECHNIQUES OF WATER-RESOURCES INVESTIGATIONS

The U.S. Geological Survey publishes a series of manuals describing procedures for planning and conducting specialized work in water-resources investigations. The material is grouped under major subject headings called books and is further divided into sections and chapters. For example, Section A of Book 3 (Applications of Hydraulics) pertains to surface water. The chapter, the unit of publication, is limited to a narrow field of subject matter. This format permits flexibility in revision and publication as the need arises.

The reports listed below are for sale by the U.S. Geological Survey, Books and Open-File Reports Section, Federal Center, Box 25425, Denver, Colorado 80225 (authorized agent of the Superintendent of Documents, Government Printing Office). Prepayment is required. Remittance should be sent by check or money order payable to the U.S. Geological Survey. Prices are not included because they are subject to change. Current prices can be obtained by writing to the above address. When ordering or inquiring about prices for any of these publications, please give the title, book number, chapter number, and "U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations."

- 1-D1. *Water temperature--influential factors, field measurement, and data presentation*, by H. H. Stevens, Jr., J. F. Ficke, and G. F. Smoot: USGS--TWRI Book 1, Chapter D1. 1975. 65 pages.
- 1-D2. *Guidelines for collection and field analysis of ground-water samples for selected unstable constituents*, by W. W. Wood: USGS--TWRI Book 1, Chapter D2. 1976. 24 pages.
- 2-D1. *Application of surface geophysics to ground-water investigations*, by A. A. R. Zohdy, G. P. Eaton, and D. R. Mabey: USGS--TWRI Book 2, Chapter D1. 1974. 116 pages.
- 2-E1. *Application of borehole geophysics to water-resources investigations*, by W. S. Keys and L. M. MacCary: USGS--TWRI Book 2, Chapter E1. 1971. 126 pages.
- 3-A1. *General field and office procedures for indirect discharge measurements*, by M. A. Benson and Tate Dalrymple: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A1. 1967. 30 pages.
- 3-A2. *Measurement of peak discharge by the slope-area method*, by Tate Dalrymple and M. A. Benson: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A2. 1967. 12 pages.
- 3-A3. *Measurement of peak discharge at culverts by indirect methods*, by G. L. Bodhaine: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A3. 1968. 60 pages.
- 3-A4. *Measurement of peak discharge at width contractions by indirect methods*, by H. F. Matthai: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A4. 1967. 44 pages.
- 3-A5. *Measurement of peak discharge at dams by indirect methods*, by Harry Hulsing: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A5. 1967. 29 pages.
- 3-A6. *General procedure for gaging streams*, by R. W. Carter and Jacob Davidian: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A6. 1968. 13 pages.
- 3-A7. *Stage measurements at gaging stations*, by T. J. Buchanan and W. P. Somers: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A7. 1968. 28 pages.
- 3-A8. *Discharge measurements at gaging stations*, by T. J. Buchanan and W. P. Somers: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A8. 1969. 65 pages.
- 3-A9. *Measurement of time of travel and dispersion in streams by dye tracing*, by E. F. Hubbard, F. A. Kilpatrick, L. A. Martens, and J. F. Wilson, Jr.: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A9. 1982. 44 pages.
- 3-A10. *Discharge ratings at gaging stations*, by E. J. Kennedy: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A10. 1984. 59 pages.
- 3-A11. *Measurement of discharge by moving-boat method*, by G. F. Smoot and C. E. Novak: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A11. 1969. 22 pages.
- 3-A13. *Computation of continuous records of streamflow*, by E. J. Kennedy: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A13. 1983. 53 pages.
- 3-A14. *Use of flumes in measuring discharge*, by F. A. Kilpatrick and V. R. Schneider: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A14. 1983. 46 pages.
- 3-A15. *Computation of water-surface profiles in open channels*, by Jacob Davidian: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A15. 1984. 48 pages.
- 3-B1. *Aquifer-test design, observation, and data analysis*, by R. W. Stallman: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter B1. 1971. 26 pages.
- 3-B2. *Introduction to ground-water hydraulics, a programed text for self-instruction*, by G. D. Bennett: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter B2. 1976. 172 pages.
- 3-B3. *Type curves for selected problems of flow to wells in confined aquifers*, by J. E. Reed: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter B3. 1980. 106 pages.

- 3-C1. *Fluvial sediment concepts* by H. P. Guy: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter C1. 1970. 55 pages.
- 3-C2. *Field methods for measurement of fluvial sediment* by H. P. Guy and V. W. Norman: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter C2. 1970. 59 pages.
- 3-C3. *Computation of fluvial-sediment discharge*, by George Porterfield: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter C3. 1972. 66 pages.
- 4-A1. *Some statistical tools in hydrology*, by H. C. Riggs: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter A1. 1968. 39 pages.
- 4-A2. *Frequency curves* by H. C. Riggs: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter A2. 1968. 15 pages.
- 4-B1. *Low-flow investigations* by H. C. Riggs: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter B1. 1972. 18 pages.
- 4-B2. *Storage analyses for water supply* by H. C. Riggs and C. H. Hardison: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter B2. 1973. 20 pages.
- 4-B3. *Regional analyses of streamflow characteristics* by H. C. Riggs: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter B3. 1973. 15 pages.
- 4-D1. *Computation of rate and volume of stream depletion by wells* by C. T. Jenkins: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter D1. 1970. 17 pages.
- 5-A1. *Methods for determination of inorganic substances in water and fluvial sediments* by M. W. Skougstad and others, editors: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A1. 1979. 626 pages.
- 5-A2. *Determination of minor elements in water by emission spectroscopy* by P. R. Barnett and E. C. Mallory, Jr.: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A2. 1971. 31 pages.
- 5-A3. *Methods for analysis of organic substances in water* by D. F. Goerlitz and Eugene Brown: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A3. 1972. 40 pages.
- 5-A4. *Methods for collection and analysis of aquatic biological and microbiological samples* edited by P. E. Greeson, T. A. Ehlke, G. A. Irwin, B. W. Lium, and K. V. Slack: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A4. 1977. 332 pages.
- 5-A5. *Methods for determination of radioactive substances in water and fluvial sediments* by L. L. Thatcher, V. J. Janzer, and K. W. Edwards: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A5. 1977. 95 pages.
- 5-A6. *Quality assurance practices for the chemical and biological analyses of water and fluvial sediments*, by L. C. Friedman and D. E. Erdmann: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A6. 1982. 181 pages.
- 5-C1. *Laboratory theory and methods for sediment analysis* by H. P. Guy: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter C1. 1969. 58 pages.
- 7-C1. *Finite difference model for aquifer simulation in two dimensions with results of numerical experiments*, by P. C. Trescott, G. F. Pinder, and S. P. Larson: USGS--TWRI Book 7, Chapter C1. 1976. 116 pages.
- 7-C2. *Computer model of two-dimensional solute transport and dispersion in ground water*, by L. F. Konikow and J. D. Bredehoeft: USGS--TWRI Book 7, Chapter C2. 1978. 90 pages.
- 7-C3. *A model for simulation of flow in singular and interconnected channels* by R. W. Schaffranek, R. A. Baltzer, and D. E. Goldberg: USGS--TWRI Book 7, Chapter C3. 1981. 110 pages.
- 8-A1. *Methods of measuring water levels in deep wells* by M. S. Garber and F. C. Koopman: USGS--TWRI Book 8, Chapter A1. 1968. 23 pages.
- 8-A2. *Installation and service manual for U.S. Geological Survey manometers* by J. D. Craig: USGS--TWRI Book 8, Chapter A2. 1983. 57 pages.
- 8-B2. *Calibration and maintenance of vertical-axis type current meters* by G. F. Smoot and C. E. Novak: USGS--TWRI Book 8, Chapter B2. 1968. 15 pages.

**Surface
and
Quality-of-Water Records
for
Puerto Rico**

Figure 11.--Río Guajataca basin.

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN
50010500 RIO GUAJATACA AT LARES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'01", long 66°52'24", at bridge on Highway 111 (km 32.9), 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Quebrada Anon, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of Lares plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.16 sq mi (8.18 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (PERCENT SATURATION) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECCAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECCAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985										
31...	1445	15	260	7.60	23.0	9.0	--	--	<10	480 520
DEC										
13...	0925	6.8	205	7.80	20.0	1.4	9.1	99	<10	K660 2300
FEB 1986										
13...	0710	2.2	218	7.85	19.0	2.6	6.4	72	12	K630 5900
MAY										
02...	1115	15	258	7.75	23.0	21	7.9	94	18	5000 K9100
JUL										
07...	1550	--	348	7.53	23.5	260	7.9	95	110	45000 71000
SEP										
08...	1310	3.1	233	7.35	25.5	840	7.7	97	35	K1400 720

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
31...	76	2	22	5.0	10	0.5	2.2	74	<0.5	8.1	9.7
DEC											
13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	79	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	82	--	--	--
MAY											
02...	91	10	29	4.6	8.6	0.4	2.6	81	<0.5	12	9.5
JUL											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52	--	--	--
SEP											
08...	70	3	17	6.8	14	0.7	3.4	67	--	17	12

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
31...	<0.10	28	130	5.2	19	2.09	0.010	2.10	0.050	0.35
DEC										
13...	--	--	--	--	3	1.79	0.010	1.80	0.020	0.28
FEB 1986										
13...	--	--	--	--	7	--	<0.010	0.900	0.020	0.18
MAY										
02...	<0.10	21	140	5.6	22	1.88	0.020	1.90	0.110	0.39
JUL										
07...	--	--	--	--	--	1.14	0.060	1.20	0.250	1.7
SEP										
08...	0.30	22	130	1.1	--	1.29	0.010	1.30	0.290	0.11

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010500 RIO GUAJATACA AT LARES, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985 31...	0.40	2.5	11	0.060	<1	<100	20	1	8	<10
DEC 13...	0.30	2.1	9.3	0.060	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 13...	0.20	1.1	4.9	0.030	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 02...	0.50	2.4	11	0.060	1	<100	20	<1	8	10
JUL 07...	1.9	3.1	14	0.210	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 08...	0.40	1.7	7.5	0.220	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1985 31...	650	3	50	<0.10	<1	<1	50	<0.010	2	0.06
DEC 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 02...	1200	2	80	0.10	<1	<1	10	<0.010	<1	0.05
JUL 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 18...	1110	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.12	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 18...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUL 1986 18...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010600 RIO GUAJATACA ABOVE LAGO GUAJATACA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'57", long 66°55'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) off road 451, 3 mi (5 km) south of Lago Guajataka, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) east of Eneas and 2.0 mi (3.2 km) west of Piletas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 565 ft (172 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Apr. 25 to May 6, May 13-20, May 26 to June 9, June 26-30, July 13, 14 and Aug. 3-5. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 2,600 ft³/s (73.6 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 12.03 ft (3.667 m), from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on the basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 1.9 ft³/s (0.054 m³/s), Feb. 11, 17, 1986.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1800	1,540	43.6	10.08	3.072	Nov. 5	1700	1,790	50.7	10.60	3.231
Oct. 26	1730	2,400	68.0	11.69	3.563	May 13	0630	2,280	64.6	11.50	3.505
Oct. 27	1545	*2,550	72.2	*11.95	3.642	May 13	2100	2,420	68.5	11.72	3.572
Oct. 28	1630	1,620	45.9	10.24	3.121	June 10	1600	1,740	49.3	10.50	3.200
Nov. 3	1700	2,130	60.3	11.23	3.423	Sept. 3	1600	1,660	47.0	10.33	3.149

Minimum discharge, 1.9 ft³/s (0.054 m³/s), Feb. 11, 17.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	114	43	17	7.0	3.7	3.0	11	101	39	12	38	13
2	55	36	17	6.8	3.7	2.7	9.2	120	35	12	74	195
3	26	338	16	8.7	20	78	42	165	32	13	47	226
4	17	219	15	6.9	35	45	52	82	30	11	23	70
5	14	311	15	6.0	6.8	15	80	203	29	10	20	26
6	228	207	15	5.7	3.6	12	31	521	27	13	19	18
7	688	98	14	5.7	3.1	8.9	24	277	60	35	17	13
8	158	62	13	5.7	2.6	7.9	43	156	54	15	84	11
9	75	48	14	10	2.3	6.8	83	136	27	12	118	9.4
10	52	42	13	11	2.4	5.5	63	240	204	10	77	8.4
11	55	35	13	6.2	2.2	9.2	27	139	79	18	56	7.8
12	113	32	12	5.9	3.0	9.5	19	139	46	12	30	8.1
13	61	30	13	5.8	3.3	6.1	15	650	36	10	28	7.2
14	37	33	11	5.5	3.3	5.4	12	190	28	52	24	7.1
15	31	139	11	5.0	2.9	5.4	11	100	43	48	19	6.6
16	26	152	11	5.0	2.5	6.9	10	80	28	25	18	6.5
17	21	165	10	4.9	3.3	224	101	62	22	23	19	8.2
18	20	88	9.5	4.5	3.4	95	82	52	53	19	18	9.1
19	17	54	9.5	4.2	17	25	42	45	34	12	14	6.1
20	16	45	9.2	3.9	49	15	68	40	23	77	13	5.9
21	15	48	9.0	3.8	19	11	118	34	27	33	12	6.4
22	14	36	8.6	4.2	5.9	8.9	157	26	22	16	12	10
23	62	32	8.7	3.4	4.2	7.7	165	35	19	14	9.7	7.5
24	48	28	7.8	3.2	3.9	7.3	172	42	17	16	8.9	5.9
25	44	26	7.7	4.0	3.8	7.4	83	43	16	66	8.5	15
26	320	23	7.4	3.3	3.4	7.0	57	170	18	200	13	10
27	461	22	7.4	4.4	4.2	15	49	100	14	85	16	5.0
28	266	20	7.8	3.7	3.2	18	36	68	13	38	25	22
29	102	19	7.4	6.2	---	65	57	78	13	25	18	11
30	71	18	7.3	6.3	---	34	76	66	13	27	20	6.3
31	54	---	6.9	6.5	---	15	---	45	---	51	15	---
TOTAL	3281	2449	344.2	173.4	220.7	782.6	1795.2	4205	1101	1010	914.1	761.5
MEAN	106	81.6	11.1	5.59	7.88	25.2	59.8	136	36.7	32.6	29.5	25.4
MAX	688	338	17	11	49	224	172	650	204	200	118	226
MIN	14	18	6.9	3.2	2.2	2.7	9.2	26	13	10	8.5	5.0
CFSM	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
IN.	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
AC-FT	6510	4860	683	344	438	1550	3560	8340	2180	2000	1810	1510
CAL YR 1985 TOTAL	13641.9			MEAN 37.4	MAX 792	MIN 3.2	CFSM .00	IN. .00	AC-FT 27060			
WTR YR 1986 TOTAL	17037.7			MEAN 46.7	MAX 688	MIN 2.2	CFSM .00	IN. .00	AC-FT 33790			

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010600 RIO GUAJATACA ABOVE LAGO GUAJATACA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
NOV, 19	1306	54	366	24.0	JUL, 07	1045	13	287	24.0
DEC, 09	1444	14	305	22.5	AUG, 05	1255	19	370	24.5
JUN, 09	1048	31	254	22.5	SEP, 03	1213	32	310	23.0

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011000 CANAL PRINCIPAL DE DIVERSIONES AT LAGO DE GUAJATACA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'02", long 66°55'27", off Highway 476 at Lago Guajataca outlet, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) southwest of Segunda Unidad Baldorioty de Castro, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) south of Quebradillas Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-64, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECA, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
04...	0800	50	309	7.40	25.5	6.0	1.2	15	10	350	K160
DEC											
12...	1345	E55	389	7.40	24.5	1.2	1.6	19	<10	<1	K6
FEB 1986											
12...	1322	65	302	7.65	24.5	1.0	3.0	37	13	K3	K5
MAY											
02...	0740	55	429	7.50	24.5	10	1.3	--	19	K140	54
JUL											
08...	0805	70	287	7.12	25.5	2.5	1.8	22	<10	K8	21
SEP											
08...	1540	70	335	6.95	26.5	2.4	1.7	22	22	200	270

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)
OCT 1985										
04...	140	5	52	3.4	5.3	0.2	2.7	139	<0.5	9.4
DEC										
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	131	--	--
FEB 1986										
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	128	--	--
MAY										
02...	140	4	50	3.6	5.3	0.2	1.8	136	<0.5	10
JUL										
08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--
SEP										
08...	140	10	51	4.2	6.2	0.2	1.8	135	--	9.3

DATE	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
04...	8.1	0.10	5.1	170	23	4	<0.010	<0.100	0.160	0.44
DEC										
12...	--	--	--	--	--	2	<0.010	0.200	0.020	0.38
FEB 1986										
12...	--	--	--	--	--	2	<0.010	0.100	0.030	0.37
MAY										
02...	7.7	<0.10	6.6	170	25	1	<0.010	0.300	0.040	0.36
JUL										
08...	--	--	--	--	--	5	<0.010	<0.100	0.080	0.42
SEP										
08...	6.8	0.10	7.9	170	32	9	<0.010	0.100	0.180	0.42

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011200 RIO GUAJATACA BELOW LAGO GUAJATACA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'01", long 66°55'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on left bank, 250 ft (76 m) downstream from bridge on Highway 476, 1,000 ft (305 m) downstream from outlet tunnel, and 5.2 mi (8.4 km) southeast of Quebradillas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1969 to December 1970, April 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 535 ft (163 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--No estimated daily discharges during water year. Records fair except those for June 4-30, Aug. 1 to Sept. 3 and Sept. 5-19, which are poor. Flow regulated by Lago Guajataca Dam. Low flows are from seepage through and under dam and nearby springs.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 1,350 ft³/s (38.2 m³/s), May 13, 1986, gage height, 11.97 ft (3.648 m), from rating curve extended above 400 ft³/s (11.3 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 0.53 ft³/s (0.015 m³/s), May 31, June 1, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum discharge, 1,350 ft³/s (38.2 m³/s), May 13, gage height, 11.97 ft (3.648 m); minimum discharge, 0.68 ft³/s (0.019 m³/s), Jan. 27, Mar. 16.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	4.2	431	2.5	1.0	.79	1.2	1.2	386	495	1.5	1.7	1.7		
2	162	379	2.6	1.1	.76	1.2	1.6	485	494	1.5	1.6	2.3		
3	354	379	3.7	1.5	.90	1.3	1.7	481	492	1.6	1.5	1.8		
4	353	401	3.2	1.2	1.3	.95	1.3	481	282	1.5	1.5	1.6		
5	310	437	2.4	1.3	.86	.88	2.7	483	119	1.6	1.8	95		
6	288	461	2.0	1.2	.90	.86	1.3	606	55	1.5	1.8	214		
7	467	489	1.6	1.3	.87	.85	1.3	703	1.5	1.4	1.8	213		
8	537	494	1.5	1.4	.86	.82	3.5	444	1.4	1.6	75	191		
9	523	492	1.4	1.6	.82	.78	1.8	561	1.4	1.8	145	159		
10	520	490	1.5	1.3	.83	.78	1.4	560	1.7	1.8	146	159		
11	518	488	1.5	1.0	1.0	.79	1.3	583	1.5	1.8	132	60		
12	515	385	1.5	.98	.97	.76	1.3	540	1.4	1.8	178	1.6		
13	512	112	1.4	.99	.94	.71	1.3	835	1.4	1.8	192	1.9		
14	466	3.0	1.3	1.2	.88	.71	1.3	1110	1.3	1.8	365	2.0		
15	377	101	1.4	1.2	.73	.71	1.4	711	1.4	2.0	395	1.9		
16	184	271	1.4	1.1	.75	.71	1.5	590	1.4	1.9	341	1.9		
17	2.5	272	1.8	1.1	.75	.77	1.6	521	1.5	1.9	340	1.7		
18	2.3	335	1.3	1.0	.78	.98	1.7	500	1.4	1.8	240	1.6		
19	2.2	367	1.3	.95	.94	1.0	1.9	505	1.4	1.8	194	1.6		
20	2.0	363	1.3	.94	1.1	1.0	2.4	503	1.4	1.8	104	1.6		
21	2.0	396	1.5	.88	.94	.88	151	502	1.3	1.8	1.8	1.7		
22	2.2	172	1.4	.88	.82	.82	349	500	1.4	2.0	2.9	1.9		
23	2.4	3.2	1.3	.86	.78	.83	368	498	1.3	2.2	2.6	2.2		
24	1.8	2.0	1.3	.85	.78	.87	396	495	1.3	2.2	2.2	2.0		
25	59	2.1	1.3	.95	.83	1.3	457	494	1.3	2.0	2.2	1.9		
26	155	2.4	1.4	.89	1.1	1.3	480	496	1.3	1.9	2.2	1.8		
27	306	2.3	1.3	.78	1.1	1.2	477	495	1.3	2.0	1.8	1.4		
28	455	2.3	1.3	.77	1.1	1.4	386	496	1.2	1.7	1.9	1.4		
29	455	2.3	1.1	.80	---	1.3	313	495	1.3	1.5	1.7	1.4		
30	454	2.6	1.0	.84	---	1.2	314	495	1.4	1.6	1.7	1.4		
31	454	---	1.0	.84	---	1.2	---	496	---	2.9	1.7	---		
TOTAL	8445.6	7737.2	50.5	32.70	25.18	30.06	3724.5	17050	1970.2	56.0	2881.4	1131.3		
MEAN	272	258	1.63	1.05	.90	.97	124	550	65.7	1.81	92.9	37.7		
MAX	537	494	3.7	1.6	1.3	1.4	480	1110	495	2.9	395	214		
MIN	1.8	2.0	1.0	.77	.73	.71	1.2	386	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.4		
CFSM	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00		
IN.	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00		
AC-FT	16750	15350	100	65	50	60	7390	33820	3910	111	5720	2240		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	20616.28	MEAN	56.5	MAX	537	MIN	.79	CFSM	.00	IN.	.00	AC-FT	40890
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	43134.64	MEAN	118	MAX	1110	MIN	.71	CFSM	.00	IN.	.00	AC-FT	85560

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011200 RIO GUAJATACA BELOW LAGO DE GUAJATACA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS APRIL 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
NOV, 20	1428	326	287	24.5	JUL, 07	1303	1.4	344	27.0
MAY, 20	1339	411	275	24.0	AUG, 06	1219	1.7	352	27.0
JUN, 10	1105	1.6	410	26.0	SEP, 03	1428	1.8	380	26.5

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011400 RIO GUAJATACA ABOVE MOUTH NEAR QUEBRADILLAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°28'31", long 66°57'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on left bank at ford 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from bridge on Highway 2, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) west of Quebradillas plaza, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) upstream from the Atlantic Ocean, and 6.6 mi (10.6 km) downstream from Lago Guajataka.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February to May 1969 (monthly measurements only), July 1969 to December 1970, April 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 0.0 ft (0.0 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 3-8, Dec. 4-7, 9-19, 24-31, Jan. 1, 6-9, 11-21, 27-31, Feb. 1, 15-18, 22-28, Mar. 1-6, 23-26, 28-31, Apr. 21, Nov. 20-22, May 14 to June 10 and Aug. 24 to Sept. 12. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Flow regulated by Lago Guajataka 6.6 mi (10.6 km).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 6,200 ft³/s (176 m³/s), May 13, 1986, estimated based on a mean daily discharge correlation with station 50011200, 6.5 miles upstream; minimum discharge, 6.2 ft³/s (0.176 m³/s), Sept. 4, 9-12, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum discharge, 6,200 ft³/s (176 m³/s), May 13, 1986; minimum discharge, 8.6 ft³/s (0.24 m³/s), Dec. 24, Jan. 2.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	55	845	12	9.5	9.3	11	15	548	1100	19	12	12		
2	187	370	12	8.8	9.0	11	14	1250	1100	19	11	25		
3	820	391	11	8.8	9.2	16	14	1190	1100	19	11	35		
4	820	663	12	9.0	10	12	16	1450	390	19	12	60		
5	720	885	12	9.2	11	12	20	1320	80	19	11	100		
6	680	922	12	10	9.7	12	18	1960	45	19	12	190		
7	1100	1150	11	9.5	9.6	11	16	2650	37	19	12	180		
8	1200	1080	9.3	9.5	9.6	11	27	1440	31	19	17	170		
9	1390	1020	10	18	9.7	11	41	1390	28	19	44	160		
10	1240	962	11	9.9	9.7	12	21	1360	32	19	45	150		
11	1190	945	11	10	9.7	12	17	1410	40	20	38	22		
12	1240	725	11	10	9.6	12	16	1430	30	19	77	18		
13	1220	78	10	9.5	9.5	13	16	3000	29	19	81	24		
14	1040	14	10	9.0	9.6	13	16	4300	27	18	214	19		
15	708	118	10	9.3	10	14	16	2000	26	19	284	19		
16	429	659	10	9.3	10	14	16	1250	25	19	196	19		
17	17	492	10	8.8	10	14	16	1100	25	17	187	19		
18	11	349	10	9.8	10	14	17	1100	25	18	124	18		
19	9.9	468	9.8	9.8	10	15	17	1100	25	17	67	19		
20	9.3	389	9.1	9.8	9.7	14	18	1100	25	16	56	17		
21	9.0	539	9.2	9.5	9.9	14	82	1100	35	15	13	18		
22	9.2	317	9.5	9.1	11	14	813	1100	25	14	13	18		
23	9.3	14	9.3	9.0	10	14	726	1100	31	14	22	17		
24	11	11	9.4	9.0	11	14	878	1100	23	16	30	17		
25	10	11	9.3	9.1	11	14	953	1100	22	18	20	17		
26	46	11	9.3	9.4	11	14	933	1100	21	27	19	17		
27	347	12	9.3	9.5	11	14	1040	1100	21	14	18	16		
28	991	14	9.5	9.5	11	15	1100	1100	20	13	15	16		
29	876	14	9.5	9.5	---	65	890	1100	20	12	17	16		
30	860	12	9.3	9.5	---	29	596	1100	19	12	14	15		
31	818	---	9.5	9.5	---	23	---	1100	---	11	13	---		
TOTAL	18072.7	13480	316.3	300.1	280.8	484	8378	44448	4457	538	1705	1443		
MEAN	583	449	10.2	9.68	10.0	15.6	279	1434	149	17.4	55.0	48.1		
MAX	1390	1150	12	18	11	65	1100	4300	1100	27	284	190		
MIN	9.0	11	9.1	8.8	9.0	11	14	548	19	11	11	12		
CFSM	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00		
IN.	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00		
AC-FT	35850	26740	627	595	557	960	16620	88160	8840	1070	3380	2860		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	45559.3	MEAN	125	MAX	1460	MIN	7.7	CFSM	.00	IN.	.00	AC-FT	90370
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	93902.9	MEAN	257	MAX	4300	MIN	8.8	CFSM	.00	IN.	.00	AC-FT	186300

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011400 RIO GUAJATACA ABOVE MOUTH NEAR QUEBRADILLAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
10...	0900	E1050	310	8.00	25.0	5.3	8.5	100	12	220	620
DEC											
12...	0945	E406	473	7.40	24.0	1.6	7.2	82	<10	66	600
FEB 1986											
12...	0940	9.5	581	7.85	24.0	1.1	6.0	72	<10	74	64
APR											
29...	1315	E650	348	8.21	25.0	25	8.4	101	16	2800	4100
JUL											
11...	0905	19	510	7.41	25.0	2.0	5.9	71	14	260	300
SEP											
12...	0905	18	525	7.31	25.0	1.6	6.4	78	17	K60	K210

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
10...	160	8	57	3.1	5.0	0.2	1.6	147	<0.5	9.2	7.4
DEC											
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	205	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	216	--	--	--
APR											
29...	150	8	54	3.2	5.5	0.2	1.8	140	<0.5	11	8.1
JUL											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	207	--	--	--
SEP											
12...	210	19	72	7.1	15	0.5	1.3	190	--	8.8	25

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SI02)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2-NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
10...	0.10	5.4	180	0.0	10	0.280	0.020	0.300	0.140	0.36
DEC										
12...	--	--	--	--	6	1.99	0.010	2.00	0.040	0.36
FEB 1986										
12...	--	--	--	--	3	2.48	0.020	2.50	0.040	0.56
APR										
29...	<0.10	5.9	170	0.0	31	0.680	0.020	0.700	0.050	0.45
JUL										
11...	--	--	--	--	9	--	<0.010	2.00	0.060	0.14
SEP										
12...	0.10	7.2	250	12	4	--	<0.010	1.60	0.060	0.44

E = estimate

K = non-ideal count

Figure 12.--Rio Camuy basin.

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50014800 RIO CAMUY NEAR BAYANEY, PR

LOCATION ---Lat 18°23'48", long 66°49'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on left bank at Highway 488, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) southeast of school at Santiago, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) northwest from Escuela Manuel A. Rivera at Bayaney and 9.1 mi (14.6 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 341 ft (104 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: May 2-5 and Aug. 10 to Sept. 2. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 6,450 ft³/s (183 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 17.66 ft (5.383 m), from rating curve extended above 300 ft³/s (8.50 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 28 ft³/s (0.79 m³/s), Mar. 15-17, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,000 ft³/s (56.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	0930	*6,450	183	*17.66	5.383	May 5	2015	3,130	88.6	13.89	4.234
Oct. 27	2030	2,400	68.0	12.38	3.773	May 6	1900	2,640	74.8	12.93	3.941
Nov. 5	2030	2,160	61.2	11.82	3.603	May 13	1015	2,830	80.1	13.34	4.066
May 1	2015	2,670	75.6	12.99	3.959	May 14	0115	3,420	96.8	14.30	4.359
May 2	1645	3,250	92.0	14.06	4.285						

Minimum discharge, 28 ft³/s (0.79 m³/s), Mar. 15-17.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	182	174	95	55	44	32	34	776	160	63	121	150		
2	151	153	92	55	39	31	34	1360	140	61	77	600		
3	90	323	90	54	57	38	61	1700	128	60	73	435		
4	79	434	88	53	104	98	169	1300	118	59	68	388		
5	73	671	87	52	61	48	356	1160	111	58	111	157		
6	783	452	87	51	50	34	130	1490	104	60	115	110		
7	3820	321	85	51	40	32	152	1200	104	69	75	93		
8	1320	226	83	50	38	34	266	665	164	95	82	83		
9	470	179	83	53	37	32	420	739	121	61	230	77		
10	339	159	81	59	37	32	358	634	203	56	700	73		
11	261	143	81	54	36	31	125	470	233	60	500	68		
12	495	158	79	51	34	31	77	470	140	63	120	66		
13	391	143	77	50	34	30	63	1610	117	53	87	64		
14	220	151	74	49	34	29	57	1550	101	92	84	63		
15	188	473	73	48	33	29	54	579	105	103	74	61		
16	157	734	70	48	34	29	50	409	102	109	70	59		
17	138	514	71	47	32	179	354	304	88	75	72	58		
18	133	294	68	47	34	261	588	248	141	91	68	70		
19	123	213	67	46	34	96	220	210	123	65	68	61		
20	112	183	67	45	70	56	113	184	103	74	66	55		
21	107	179	66	44	80	42	342	161	90	88	62	54		
22	103	148	63	44	48	39	295	145	85	63	62	58		
23	177	137	63	43	35	37	222	132	80	60	60	60		
24	237	126	61	43	33	37	187	132	77	60	62	55		
25	202	119	60	43	33	37	186	125	74	65	64	54		
26	498	113	60	45	33	36	94	147	76	80	60	63		
27	874	107	58	40	33	46	87	214	77	123	60	55		
28	674	103	57	40	32	40	233	273	74	80	80	53		
29	385	99	57	44	---	38	359	410	68	67	70	73		
30	262	98	57	41	---	47	384	330	65	98	78	58		
31	208	---	55	66	---	37	---	215	---	113	84	---		
TOTAL	13252	7327	2255	1511	1209	1618	6070	19342	3372	2324	3603	3374		
MEAN	427	244	72.7	48.7	43.2	52.2	202	624	112	75.0	116	112		
MAX	3820	734	95	66	104	261	588	1700	233	123	700	600		
MIN	73	98	55	40	32	29	34	125	65	53	60	53		
CFSM	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00		
IN.	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00		
AC-FT	26290	14530	4470	3000	2400	3210	12040	38360	6690	4610	7150	6690		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	48669	MEAN	133	MAX	3820	MIN	31	CFSM	.00	IN.	.00	AC-FT	96530
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	65257	MEAN	179	MAX	3820	MIN	29	CFSM	.00	IN.	.00	AC-FT	129400

RIO CAMUY BASIN
50014800 RIO CAMUY NEAR BAYANEY, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS JUNE 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
MAY, 19	1312	211	264	24.0	AUG, 04	1345	69	289	25.0
JUN, 12	1217	124	266	23.3	SEP, 12	0959	66	332	24.0
JUL, 08	1139	100	263	24.0					

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50015700 RIO CAMUY NEAR HATILLO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'44", long 66°49'56", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) southwest of Hatillo plaza, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) southeast of Camuy plaza, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of Planta de Purificación, and 3.3 mi (5.5 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 13 ft (4 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: May 3-5, 8-19. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 10,500 ft³/s (297 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 24.75 ft (7.544 m), from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 36 ft³/s (1.02 m³/s), Mar. 19, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,800 ft³/s (51.0 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	1315	*10,500	297	*24.75	7.544	Apr. 28	2200	2,800	79.3	15.40	4.694
Oct. 12	2315	2,680	75.9	15.15	4.618	Apr. 29	2145	3,340	94.6	16.44	5.011
Oct. 26	2330	2,820	79.9	15.43	4.703	May 1	2245	5,680	161	20.00	6.096
Oct. 27	2345	3,940	112	17.49	5.331	May 2	1900	8,420	238	22.94	6.992
Oct. 28	2230	2,370	67.1	14.49	4.416	May 3	2015	6,840	194	21.33	6.501
Nov. 5	2300	3,480	98.6	16.69	5.087	May 5	2300	6,600	187	21.06	6.419
Nov. 6	2015	2,170	61.4	14.05	4.282	May 6	2145	6,510	184	20.96	6.389
Nov. 16	0030	3,430	97.1	16.60	5.060	May 13	1245	6,810	193	21.30	6.492
Mar. 17	2330	2,250	64.0	14.24	4.340	May 14	0145	7,750	214	22.08	6.730
Apr. 9	2330	3,620	102	16.94	5.163	Aug. 10	2215	3,240	91.8	16.24	4.950
Apr. 18	0115	3,100	87.8	15.99	4.874	Nov. 3	2215	2,250	63.7	14.23	4.337

Minimum discharge, 47 ft³/s (1.33 m³/s), Mar. 27.DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	
1	273	201	122	67	56	55	51	1570	201	90	133	186	
2	419	189	118	67	50	55	50	3900	176	87	92	438	
3	130	351	114	66	62	56	51	5280	162	85	87	550	
4	107	778	113	65	162	131	185	3000	151	83	83	688	
5	100	1100	110	64	95	81	702	2500	142	83	100	179	
6	928	1270	109	61	80	64	185	4120	134	84	124	124	
7	8150	709	105	61	69	60	284	4050	129	86	88	108	
8	2900	296	101	60	66	59	578	1700	176	114	89	98	
9	940	211	100	65	64	57	841	2000	167	85	244	91	
10	556	188	98	69	62	57	1220	1500	207	80	868	87	
11	324	174	97	63	62	56	206	1000	299	78	728	84	
12	514	184	96	59	59	56	121	900	164	88	143	81	
13	739	203	92	58	59	54	100	5060	148	77	107	80	
14	255	174	90	57	58	54	88	5460	129	95	103	79	
15	216	982	89	56	58	52	82	1500	125	123	93	76	
16	187	2220	87	56	59	52	78	700	133	130	86	74	
17	167	1210	86	57	57	233	241	450	116	90	89	73	
18	160	522	85	55	59	586	1200	350	129	107	82	81	
19	154	320	83	54	57	110	409	300	182	86	83	75	
20	143	252	82	53	89	70	277	292	121	83	79	70	
21	137	243	80	52	122	58	691	257	118	109	75	70	
22	134	202	79	52	78	53	562	231	109	84	73	72	
23	151	179	77	51	67	50	312	206	114	80	72	75	
24	388	165	76	51	61	48	247	186	106	79	74	71	
25	240	156	75	50	60	49	249	195	101	85	76	69	
26	575	148	73	52	59	50	138	187	98	87	71	75	
27	1300	141	73	49	58	60	129	310	103	127	70	71	
28	1320	136	71	49	57	90	571	441	101	97	99	66	
29	648	130	70	52	---	79	1340	678	95	86	86	82	
30	303	126	69	50	---	67	1130	556	92	108	97	73	
31	235	---	68	66	---	56	---	275	---	133	103	---	
TOTAL	22793	13160	2788	1787	1945	2658	12318	49154	4228	2909	4397	4046	
MEAN	735	439	89.9	57.6	69.5	85.7	411	1586	141	93.8	142	135	
MAX	8150	2220	122	69	162	586	1340	5460	299	133	868	688	
MIN	100	126	68	49	50	48	50	186	92	77	70	66	
CFSM	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	
IN.	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	
AC-FT	45210	26100	5530	3540	3860	5270	24430	97500	8390	5770	8720	8030	
CAL YR 1985 TOTAL	73305	MEAN	201	MAX	8150	MIN	39	CFSM	.00	IN.	.00	AC-FT	145400
WTR YR 1986 TOTAL	122183	MEAN	335	MAX	8150	MIN	48	CFSM	.00	IN.	.00	AC-FT	242300

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50015700 RIO CAMUY NEAR HATILLO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
NOV, 12	1118	160	299	23.5	JUL, 08	0852	130	303	23.5
DEC, 10	1047	98	307	23.0	AUG, 04	1029	83	324	24.0
JUN, 12	0853	159	295	23.0	SEP, 02	1044	145	295	24.0

Figure 13.--Río Grande de Arecibo basin.

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50020500 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO NEAR ADJUNTAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'54", long 66°44'12", at Highway 135 bridge, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream from Lago Adjuntas, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northwest of Adjuntas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.7 sq mi (32.9 sq km) this does not include 6.0 sq mi (15.6 sq km) above Lago Garzas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECA, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
30...	1540	--	90	7.20	21.5	230	9.0	105	49	--	--
DEC											
17...	0800	25	280	7.80	19.0	1.0	--	--	<10	<30	5800
FEB 1986											
19...	0830	12	337	8.05	18.5	1.0	9.1	103	32	26000	42000
MAY											
07...	0835	35	332	7.80	21.5	50	7.9	94	21	2400	K14000
JUL											
18...	0835	13	326	7.80	22.5	13	7.8	94	<10	K10000	K15000
SEP											
18...	0805	12	370	7.68	21.0	1.2	7.6	90	26	310	300

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CAC03	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
30...	35	2	9.0	3.0	5.3	0.4	1.4	33	<0.5	8.8	5.4
DEC											
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	101	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	106	--	--	--
MAY											
07...	85	6	21	7.8	16	0.8	2.3	79	<0.5	9.9	19
JUL											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	107	--	--	--
SEP											
18...	120	2	31	10	21	0.9	2.2	117	--	9.9	27

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
30...	<0.10	14	67	0.0	780	0.460	0.040	0.500	0.080	0.82
DEC										
17...	--	--	--	--	1	1.44	0.060	1.50	0.060	--
FEB 1986										
19...	--	--	--	--	7	0.900	0.100	1.00	0.070	0.43
MAY										
07...	<0.10	26	150	14	72	1.16	0.040	1.20	0.170	0.43
JUL										
18...	--	--	--	--	8	0.950	0.050	1.00	0.150	1.1
SEP										
18...	0.10	30	200	6.7	2	0.950	0.050	1.00	0.050	0.35

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50025000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO NEAR UTUADO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'11", long 66°41'59", at bridge near Highway 10 at km 56.4, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) downstream from Rio de Caguana, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) north of Utuado plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--66.0 sq mi (170.9 sq km) this excludes 6.0 sq mi (15.5 sq km) upstream from Lago Garzas, which is a diversion to Rio Guayanés in the Rio Tallaboa basin.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORMS, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
29...	1500	536	165	7.60	25.5	80	--	--	15	21000	7500
DEC 16...	1430	107	262	7.80	27.0	5.4	--	--	<10	52000	5600
FEB 1986											
18...	1610	39	265	8.10	26.5	6.2	7.2	91	22	K16000	4900
MAY 06...	1440	165	198	7.65	26.0	90	7.6	94	13	24000	1000
JUL 17...	1410	82	266	7.80	27.5	10	7.3	93	<10	24000	3200
SEP 17...	1425	35	290	7.88	33.0	7.0	7.2	102	34	3000	320

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
29...	53	0	13	5.0	8.5	0.5	2.4	55	<0.5	18	8.1
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	89	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--
MAY 06...	75	69	20	6.2	10	0.5	2.2	7	<0.5	22	8.7
JUL 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	75	--	--	--
SEP 17...	98	13	27	7.4	14	0.6	3.2	85	--	22	13

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
29...	<0.10	20	110	156	189	1.07	0.030	1.10	0.070	0.33
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	2	1.37	0.030	1.40	0.050	--
FEB 1986										
18...	--	--	--	--	15	1.25	0.050	1.30	0.030	0.57
MAY 06...	<0.10	24	97	43	176	1.18	0.020	1.20	0.100	0.60
JUL 17...	--	--	--	--	68	1.07	0.030	1.10	0.020	0.38
SEP 17...	0.20	29	170	16	11	1.05	0.050	1.10	0.030	0.37

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026050 RIO CAONILLAS ABOVE LAGO CAONILLAS NEAR JAYUYA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'26", long 66°38'22", 300 ft (91 m) off Highway 531, 700 ft (213 m) upstream from Lago Caonillas, 3.3 mi (5.3 km) northwest of Jayuya plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--40.4 sq mi (104.6 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
30...	1025	--	125	7.60	23.0	50	--	--	14	K7500	3400
DEC 17...	1200	66	208	8.10	23.0	9.0	--	--	<10	K640	K130
FEB 1986											
19...	1310	36	248	8.65	20.0	3.0	9.4	107	20	550	350
MAY 07...	1220	--	207	7.80	24.0	80	8.2	100	31	5600	5000
JUL 18...	1150	36	223	7.80	27.5	76	7.9	102	22	K7700	K2800
SEP 18...	1205	29	232	7.54	26.5	0.70	7.8	100	30	K7500	3400

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
30...	46	6	12	4.0	8.1	0.5	1.8	40	<0.5	11	6.4
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	71	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	79	--	--	--
MAY 07...	44	4	11	3.9	8.0	0.5	1.7	40	<0.5	11	7.8
JUL 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	72	--	--	--
SEP 18...	73	7	19	6.2	11	0.6	2.1	66	--	16	11

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
30...	0.10	22	89	0.0	125	--	0.020	<0.100	0.060	0.34
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	19	0.890	0.010	0.900	0.030	0.27
FEB 1986										
19...	--	--	--	--	9	--	<0.010	0.500	0.030	0.37
MAY 07...	0.10	21	88	0.0	104	1.08	0.020	1.10	0.040	0.66
JUL 18...	--	--	--	--	119	0.570	0.030	0.600	0.060	0.44
SEP 18...	0.10	21	130	10	152	0.580	0.020	0.600	0.060	0.24

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027250 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BELOW LAGO DOS BOCAS NEAR FLORIDA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'50", long 66°40'02", at pedestrian bridge, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) downstream from Lago Dos Bocas and 6.6 mi (10.6 km) west of Florida plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--169 sq mi (436 sq km) does not include 6.0 sq mi (15.6 sq km) above Lago Garzas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1970-71, 1974 to current year.

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
29...	1130	--	141	7.40	24.5	280	--	--	22	3500	28000
DEC											
16...	1220	--	199	7.40	24.0	4.5	--	--	<10	38	K20
FEB 1986											
18...	1345	113	198	7.75	25.0	2.4	5.5	67	39	K10	K16
MAY											
06...	1015	--	148	7.38	24.0	200	6.5	77	21	K1500	9300
JUL											
17...	1020	--	199	7.15	26.5	4.0	3.4	42	25	K45	K20
SEP											
17...	1115	--	247	7.15	27.5	3.0	3.7	47	84	K18	<10

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
29...	55	7	15	4.3	8.3	0.5	2.3	48	<0.5	17	8.0
DEC											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	69	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	67	--	--	--
MAY											
06...	48	5	13	3.7	7.1	0.5	2.2	43	<0.5	9.8	7.7
JUL											
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	71	--	--	--
SEP											
17...	82	2	22	6.5	11	0.5	2.2	80	--	15	10

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
29...	<0.10	19	100	0.0	298	0.740	0.060	0.800	0.100	0.70
DEC										
16...	--	--	--	--	2	--	<0.010	0.800	0.020	0.28
FEB 1986										
18...	--	--	--	--	5	0.490	0.010	0.500	0.040	0.36
MAY										
06...	0.10	17	86	0.0	200	0.760	0.040	0.800	0.100	0.60
JUL										
17...	--	--	--	--	5	0.180	0.020	0.200	0.180	0.42
SEP										
17...	0.10	23	140	0.0	2	--	<0.010	0.100	0.140	0.36

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'29", long 66°41'44", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) upstream from Rio Tanamá, 4.0 mi (6.4 km) south of Arecibo and 6.7 mi (10.8 km) above mouth, and 10.2 mi (16.4 km) downstream from Lago Dos Bocas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--200 mi² (520 km²), approximately, of which an undetermined amount does not contribute directly to surface runoff.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 30 ft (9 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 7 to Nov. 15. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Flow regulated by Lago Dos Bocas Dam 10.2 mi (16.4 km) upstream.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 45,800 ft³/s (1,300 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 18.22 ft (5.553 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 2,400 ft³/s (68.0 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 30 ft³/s (0.850 m³/s), Mar. 30, 1986.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 4,300 ft³/s (122 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	0900	*41,200	1,167	*17.85	5.441	May 13	1230	9,470	268	12.90	3.932
May 1	2215	5,520	156	10.67	3.252	May 14	0115	25,900	733	16.31	4.971
May 2	2030	4,320	122	9.51	2.899						

Minimum discharge, 30 ft³/s (0.850 m³/s), Mar. 30.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	209	1570	682	152	215	86	380	2410	1070	57	941	65		
2	695	2530	891	322	64	223	234	2930	946	53	218	796		
3	142	2400	305	818	639	370	309	2130	975	194	444	709		
4	467	630	530	416	301	166	559	1770	969	59	90	179		
5	122	1670	271	95	232	67	473	1850	828	125	186	259		
6	1630	2530	257	60	374	148	636	2060	852	73	558	92		
7	12900	2170	633	55	180	314	689	1960	305	610	377	723		
8	3500	2150	438	186	122	85	802	1960	574	108	368	741		
9	3000	800	936	86	49	47	789	1880	881	301	79	98		
10	2470	1130	530	47	169	261	862	1840	946	234	104	193		
11	2420	1900	637	108	436	404	568	1530	971	491	620	229		
12	2360	1900	275	70	510	427	431	436	950	99	930	598		
13	2230	1870	511	562	419	420	220	4670	927	59	618	109		
14	2180	1410	419	134	326	428	410	10700	571	443	322	58		
15	1480	1540	438	127	149	338	416	3050	229	338	190	720		
16	2530	2530	542	203	82	113	69	2010	698	514	73	624		
17	2270	2000	315	176	127	362	364	1790	663	500	53	453		
18	1670	1850	423	404	410	344	1120	1740	1160	661	90	526		
19	1630	1110	236	157	466	364	1370	1700	881	167	49	163		
20	1500	986	288	538	448	347	1220	1360	684	63	98	58		
21	755	1210	190	246	406	273	1260	1020	464	172	73	53		
22	1060	866	159	130	101	73	458	933	99	457	48	121		
23	430	557	370	60	124	63	447	1320	206	876	45	114		
24	1140	648	177	55	374	347	503	1250	561	758	46	240		
25	810	958	150	88	459	338	435	897	722	115	45	471		
26	1700	889	139	226	331	347	357	1100	739	109	195	483		
27	1800	750	153	378	325	202	179	1130	112	194	67	88		
28	1670	425	126	201	308	50	731	989	69	60	494	53		
29	2530	670	77	239	---	47	770	1240	241	530	553	78		
30	2530	739	87	337	---	42	1460	1360	62	889	463	56		
31	1670	---	620	408	---	323	---	981	---	966	119	---		
TOTAL	61500	42388	11805	7084	8146	7419	18521	61996	19355	10275	8556	9150		
MEAN	1984	1413	381	229	291	239	617	2000	645	331	276	305		
MAX	12900	2530	936	818	639	428	1460	10700	1160	966	941	796		
MIN	122	425	77	47	49	42	69	436	62	53	45	53		
CFSM	9.92	7.06	1.90	1.14	1.45	1.19	3.08	10.0	3.22	1.65	1.38	1.52		
IN.	11.44	7.88	2.20	1.32	1.52	1.38	3.44	11.53	3.60	1.91	1.59	1.70		
AC-FT	122000	84080	23420	14050	16160	14720	36740	123000	38390	20380	16970	18150		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	249008	MEAN	682	MAX	14800	MIN	40	CFSM	3.41	IN.	46.32	AC-FT	493900
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	266195	MEAN	729	MAX	12900	MIN	42	CFSM	3.64	IN.	49.51	AC-FT	528000

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS APRIL 1982 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 01	1100	114	231	25.5	JUL, 10	1000	78	254	27.0
NOV, 14	1204	222	225	25.0	AUG, 12	1045	120	254	27.0
DEC, 12	1109	122	246	23.5	SEP, 12	1022	130	251	26.5
JUN, 16	1009	126	225	25.5					

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'02", long 66°46'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on downstream side of left abutment of bridge on Highway 111, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from natural tunnel, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northeast of Angeles, and 5.8 mi (9.3 km) northwest of Utuado.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.4 mi² (47.7 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1944 to June 1958 (daily stage and two to four measurements per month by Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority), November 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 938.32 ft (286.00 m) above mean sea level. Datum of gage was lowered 3.00 ft (0.914 m) on Oct. 1978. Prior to Nov. 17, 1966, non-recording gage and Nov. 17, 1966 to Sept. 30, 1978 recording gage, both at present site.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 9, 10, Oct. 29 to Nov. 1, Nov. 8-14, Apr. 21-25, May 5-19. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--26 years (1961-86), 49.1 ft³/s (1.390 m³/s), 36.24 in/yr (920 mm/yr), 35,570 acre-ft/yr (43.8 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 48 ft³/s (1.36 m³/s), 34,800 acre-ft/yr (43 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 12,190 ft³/s (345 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 17.45 ft (5.319 m) new datum in use, from floodmark and recorder, from rating curve extended above 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 6.6 ft³/s (0.187 m³/s), June 12, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1730	4,580	130	13.64	4.157	Apr. 30	1745	4,410	125	13.45	4.100
Oct. 7	0645	*7,840	222	*15.69	4.782	May 1	1630	3,070	86.9	11.77	3.587

Minimum discharge, 14 ft³/s (0.396 m³/s), Mar. 14-16, 22-24, 27.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	54	115	64	33	24	19	17	352	87	41	41	68		
2	39	107	63	33	27	18	16	308	81	41	36	43		
3	34	128	62	32	77	19	83	256	78	40	35	35		
4	32	123	61	31	49	19	46	263	75	39	44	33		
5	34	199	60	30	33	18	141	210	72	40	46	30		
6	388	124	58	30	29	17	39	190	68	43	35	28		
7	1510	103	56	30	27	17	25	240	88	41	126	27		
8	381	90	54	29	25	17	58	200	92	40	57	27		
9	200	80	53	36	24	16	66	170	72	38	48	27		
10	140	75	52	34	24	15	34	150	92	36	51	26		
11	114	75	52	29	24	16	25	150	75	45	52	25		
12	193	80	51	27	23	16	22	140	82	39	36	25		
13	103	85	48	27	23	16	21	330	73	35	41	25		
14	119	115	46	26	23	15	20	440	64	55	36	24		
15	102	193	46	26	22	15	22	200	129	60	33	22		
16	81	224	45	26	21	15	65	150	72	56	30	22		
17	70	164	44	27	23	16	146	120	60	98	30	25		
18	69	135	43	26	22	22	185	110	80	59	30	26		
19	63	107	42	25	21	21	79	100	58	43	30	23		
20	60	100	41	25	24	16	92	88	52	61	30	22		
21	74	101	40	24	22	16	85	78	50	59	28	22		
22	61	88	40	27	20	14	35	73	48	44	29	28		
23	154	84	39	25	19	14	30	68	47	42	34	25		
24	101	80	38	25	19	15	30	92	47	47	33	24		
25	78	77	37	39	20	17	25	72	46	43	40	26		
26	167	74	36	34	19	16	27	68	47	41	40	23		
27	322	72	35	23	19	17	25	68	47	43	29	21		
28	292	69	35	25	19	16	30	96	44	42	36	30		
29	170	67	34	26	---	16	62	183	43	40	60	25		
30	155	65	34	56	---	16	445	114	42	42	57	22		
31	130	---	33	29	---	15	---	94	---	44	39	---		
TOTAL	5490	3199	1442	915	722	515	1996	5173	2011	1437	1292	829		
MEAN	177	107	46.5	29.5	25.8	16.6	66.5	167	67.0	46.4	41.7	27.6		
MAX	1510	224	64	56	77	22	445	440	129	58	126	68		
MIN	32	65	33	23	19	14	16	68	42	35	28	21		
CFSM	9.62	5.82	2.53	1.60	1.40	.90	3.61	9.08	3.64	2.52	2.27	1.50		
IN.	11.10	6.47	2.92	1.85	1.46	1.04	4.04	10.46	4.07	2.91	2.61	1.68		
AC-FT	10890	6350	2860	1810	1430	1020	3960	10260	3990	2850	2560	1640		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	22815	MEAN	62.5	MAX	1890	MIN	17	CFSM	3.40	IN.	46.13	AC-FT	45250
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	25021	MEAN	68.6	MAX	1510	MIN	14	CFSM	3.73	IN.	50.59	AC-FT	49630

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: January 1968 to current year.

REMARKS.--Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis and during high flow events. Estimates for period of missing daily record were made from a sediment transport curve developed from a period of record over 5 years.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 20,400 mg/L November 27, 1968; minimum daily mean, 0 mg/L during water year 1985.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 167,000 tons (152,000 tonnes) May 18, 1985, minimum daily, 0.0 ton (0.0 tonne) during many years.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 9,340 mg/L October 07, 1985; minimum daily mean, 5.0 mg/L JAN 23-24,1986.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 79,000 tons (72,000 tonnes) October 07, 1985; minimum daily, 0.34 ton (0.31 tonne) JAN 23-24,1986.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEARS OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
10...	1450	133	139	7.60	23.0	5.0	--	--	<10	240	730
DEC											
13...	1200	48	156	7.90	21.0	4.2	--	--	50	K73	360
FEB 1986											
13...	1020	25	162	8.15	19.0	5.3	9.3	104	11	K60	320
APR											
16...	1310	21	173	8.01	24.5	140	8.7	107	69	K1900	2800
JUL											
08...	1230	40	151	8.15	25.0	1.6	8.5	105	13	K40	K110
SEP											
09...	1435	25	183	8.20	28.0	2.9	8.2	109	16	K90	260

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
10...	46	5	11	4.5	6.4	0.4	1.5	41	<0.5	11	7.4
DEC											
13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	51	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	51	--	--	--
APR											
16...	55	7	14	4.9	9.5	0.6	2.7	48	<0.5	12	8.8
JUL											
08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	51	--	--	--
SEP											
09...	61	4	15	5.7	8.3	0.5	1.8	57	--	11	8.1

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued
WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEARS OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
OCT 1985							
07...	0720	3820	45000	464000	4	5	9
APR 1986							
30...	1740	4320	18100	211000	7	13	19
MAY							
01...	1620	2000	11700	63200	5	7	11
01...	1650	1620	13700	59900	6	10	15
02...	1600	1600	15300	66100	4	7	10
02...	1615	1310	6530	23100	10	16	24
04...	1755	810	2720	5950	14	22	35

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
OCT 1985							
07...	13	18	28	40	60	87	99
APR 1986							
30...	27	35	48	64	83	96	99
MAY							
01...	15	23	27	40	75	94	99
01...	23	30	41	57	81	97	100
02...	15	19	33	49	69	93	99
02...	34	43	53	70	88	98	100
04...	54	65	74	80	85	92	98

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued
SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	54	99	39	115	100	31	64	11	1.9
2	39	24	2.7	107	100	29	63	11	1.9
3	34	15	3.2	128	402	230	62	11	1.8
4	32	18	3.0	123	287	134	61	11	1.8
5	34	19	1.8	199	1010	2810	60	11	1.8
6	388	2870	24900	124	326	151	58	11	1.7
7	1510	9340	79900	103	185	53	56	11	1.7
8	381	1980	2980	90	125	30	54	11	1.6
9	200	550	297	80	110	24	53	12	1.7
10	140	325	123	75	100	20	52	12	1.7
11	114	238	73	75	100	20	52	12	1.7
12	193	948	2050	80	110	24	51	12	1.7
13	103	234	76	85	152	48	48	15	1.9
14	119	495	513	115	340	157	46	16	2.0
15	102	261	106	193	761	772	46	15	1.9
16	81	130	28	224	809	517	45	15	1.8
17	70	120	23	164	520	259	44	12	1.4
18	69	95	19	135	358	147	43	10	1.2
19	63	60	10	107	218	63	42	10	1.1
20	60	50	8.1	100	207	58	41	10	1.1
21	74	179	90	101	172	50	40	10	1.1
22	61	70	12	88	54	13	40	10	1.1
23	154	988	1880	84	18	4.1	39	8	.71
24	101	231	93	80	18	3.9	38	8	.82
25	78	116	27	77	17	3.5	37	8	.80
26	167	824	1520	74	16	3.2	36	9	.87
27	322	2190	11500	72	15	2.9	35	10	.95
28	292	1460	3420	69	12	2.2	35	10	.95
29	170	575	293	67	12	2.2	34	10	.92
30	155	230	96	65	11	1.9	34	10	.92
31	130	120	42	---	---	---	33	10	.89
TOTAL	5490	---	130128.8	3199	---	5663.9	1442	---	43.43

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	33	10	.89	24	7	.45	19	22	1.1
2	33	10	.89	27	9	.66	18	20	.97
3	32	10	.86	77	138	44	19	20	1.0
4	31	10	.84	49	54	8.0	19	20	1.0
5	30	10	.81	33	30	2.7	18	16	.78
6	30	10	.81	29	20	1.6	17	15	.69
7	30	10	.81	27	20	1.5	17	18	.83
8	29	10	.78	25	21	1.4	17	18	.83
9	36	23	2.9	24	20	1.3	16	17	.73
10	34	21	2.1	24	20	1.3	15	16	.65
11	29	8	.63	24	20	1.3	16	16	.69
12	27	8	.58	23	20	1.2	16	16	.69
13	27	8	.58	23	20	1.2	16	17	.73
14	26	7	.49	23	20	1.2	15	22	.89
15	26	7	.49	22	20	1.2	15	20	.81
16	26	7	.49	21	20	1.1	15	20	.81
17	27	6	.44	23	20	1.2	16	15	.65
18	26	6	.42	22	20	1.2	22	23	2.6
19	25	6	.41	21	20	1.1	21	14	.91
20	25	6	.41	24	23	1.7	16	12	.52
21	24	6	.44	22	17	1.0	16	12	.52
22	27	8	.66	20	15	.81	14	12	.45
23	25	5	.34	19	13	.67	14	12	.45
24	25	5	.34	19	18	.92	15	13	.53
25	39	49	12	20	20	1.1	17	12	.55
26	34	26	3.6	19	20	1.0	16	11	.48
27	23	7	.43	19	22	1.1	17	12	.55
28	25	11	.85	19	22	1.1	16	12	.52
29	26	10	.70	---	---	---	16	11	.48
30	56	150	82	---	---	---	16	10	.43
31	29	13	1.2	---	---	---	15	10	.41
TOTAL	915	---	119.19	722	---	83.01	515	---	23.25

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued
SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	17	10	.46	352	2570	13300	87	40	9.4
2	16	10	.43	308	1780	5560	81	40	8.7
3	83	274	164	256	1280	2800	78	35	7.4
4	46	174	30	263	1390	3040	75	35	7.1
5	141	514	436	210	1430	2930	72	30	5.8
6	39	53	5.8	190	1350	2650	68	25	4.6
7	25	49	3.3	240	1680	2800	88	152	59
8	58	420	723	200	1020	1120	92	182	54
9	66	276	265	170	754	549	72	80	16
10	34	54	5.2	150	1070	1270	92	168	74
11	25	50	3.4	150	910	973	75	110	22
12	22	55	3.3	140	1490	3470	82	123	35
13	21	55	3.1	330	2020	6080	73	69	16
14	20	50	2.7	440	900	614	64	30	5.2
15	22	54	3.4	200	775	481	129	774	1910
16	65	230	154	150	455	268	72	104	23
17	146	770	1580	120	155	84	60	60	9.7
18	185	1010	3120	110	125	63	80	194	98
19	79	125	31	100	100	48	58	34	5.8
20	92	181	72	88	45	11	52	25	3.5
21	85	282	226	78	45	9.5	50	23	3.1
22	35	70	6.6	73	40	7.9	48	21	2.7
23	30	60	4.9	68	40	7.3	47	20	2.5
24	30	60	4.9	92	218	135	47	20	2.5
25	25	50	3.4	72	97	21	46	19	2.4
26	27	46	9.3	68	94	20	47	17	2.2
27	25	20	1.4	68	104	24	47	17	2.2
28	30	26	2.0	96	241	180	44	18	2.1
29	62	180	105	183	834	1440	43	19	2.2
30	445	3190	26700	114	156	54	42	20	2.3
31	---	---	---	94	40	10	---	---	---
TOTAL	1996	---	33669.59	5173	---	50019.7	2011	---	2398.4

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued
SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	41	20	2.2	41	25	2.8	68	155	80
2	41	19	2.1	36	13	1.3	43	30	3.5
3	40	19	2.1	35	14	1.3	35	15	1.4
4	39	16	1.7	44	37	8.9	33	12	1.1
5	40	15	1.6	46	50	8.5	30	10	.81
6	43	13	1.5	35	10	.95	28	10	.76
7	41	15	1.7	126	952	3990	27	9	.66
8	40	18	1.9	57	61	10	27	9	.66
9	38	20	2.1	48	58	10	27	9	.66
10	36	20	1.9	51	90	36	26	9	.63
11	45	44	8.1	52	83	22	25	8	.54
12	39	18	1.9	36	12	1.2	25	8	.54
13	35	15	1.4	41	26	3.6	25	8	.54
14	55	91	26	36	18	1.7	24	8	.52
15	60	77	21	33	15	1.3	22	8	.48
16			21	30	13	1.1	22	8	.48
17			580	30	13	1.1	25	10	.84
18				30	12	.97	26	10	.70
19				30	12	.97	23	10	.62
2				30	12	.97	22	10	.59
21				28	12	.91	22	10	.59
22				29	12	.94	28	14	1.2
23				4	18	2.0	25	10	.68
24					15	1.6	24	9	.58
25	43				51	19	26	13	1.2
26	41				28	3.6	23	10	.62
27	43				0	.78	21	10	.57
28	42					2.2	30	20	2.0
29	40					39	25	10	.68
30	42	24				32	22	10	.59
31	44	27				2.9	---	---	---
TOTAL	1437	---					829	---	104.74
YEAR	25021		22735						

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028400 RIO TANAMA AT CHARCO HONDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'52", long 66°42'52", on right bank at abandoned power house at Charco Hondo, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) upstream from mouth, and 4 mi (6 km) south of Arecibo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--57.6 mi² (149.2 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1969 to June 1971, October 1981 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 60 ft (18 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 7-11, Dec. 3-11, Mar. 11-13, May 16-21, 24, 28-30 and June 7, 8, 10, 11, 15. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Diversion 0.8 mi (1.3 km) upstream for municipal supply of Arecibo.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--6 years (1970,1982-86), 102 ft³/s (2.889 m³/s), 24.05 in/yr (611 mm/yr), 73,900 acre-ft/yr (91.1 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 15,000 ft³/s (425 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 17.95 ft (5.471 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 21 ft³/s (0.595 m³/s), Apr. 27, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,000 ft³/s (56.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	unknown	*11,700	331	*17.11	5.215	May 1	2000	2,520	71.4	10.82	3.298
Oct. 27	1915	2,340	66.3	10.60	3.231	May 2	1900	2,250	63.7	10.48	3.194
Apr. 30	2115	4,310	122	12.78	3.895	May 14	0215	2,730	77.3	11.09	3.380

Minimum discharge, 22 ft³/s (0.623 m³/s), Apr.1.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	113	142	90	38	52	38	25	571	155	53	69	97
2	124	128	87	39	51	47	26	740	144	51	48	130
3	69	217	82	36	97	42	66	607	136	49	44	156
4	59	380	80	37	110	39	225	531	115	49	43	193
5	58	485	76	35	72	37	368	512	101	49	75	105
6	554	347	75	35	57	38	161	450	96	49	111	78
7	2500	248	74	35	52	38	101	598	140	48	129	58
8	900	183	71	36	50	35	151	463	160	47	99	52
9	400	149	69	39	48	36	197	371	107	46	70	49
10	250	138	67	51	46	36	204	332	130	46	83	46
11	190	129	66	39	44	35	107	331	125	45	127	44
12	330	128	63	39	43	34	81	289	104	52	64	41
13	332	135	60	36	43	33	65	707	97	44	56	44
14	219	162	57	36	41	34	47	982	85	52	73	41
15	206	362	56	36	40	33	41	467	180	69	55	38
16	173	527	55	38	40	34	42	310	105	72	50	38
17	144	391	54	38	45	33	174	240	89	92	52	38
18	122	273	52	37	43	62	485	225	91	93	49	42
19	117	216	50	36	45	64	227	205	107	56	50	37
20	103	182	48	35	45	46	110	190	82	54	49	36
21	101	177	48	36	41	32	183	180	87	77	45	38
22	111	151	47	38	41	27	127	172	76	52	45	44
23	128	140	45	38	40	27	79	162	71	49	45	47
24	212	131	43	38	39	27	74	190	66	48	52	40
25	158	121	43	38	38	30	81	165	64	53	44	40
26	246	113	42	58	38	28	57	161	64	52	63	42
27	439	108	43	43	36	29	54	183	63	56	45	35
28	379	102	40	40	37	39	72	280	59	54	59	44
29	250	98	40	46	---	28	109	420	55	51	68	60
30	187	94	40	55	---	26	498	300	54	68	97	39
31	167	---	37	73	---	24	---	174	---	78	71	---
TOTAL	9341	6157	1800	1254	1374	1111	4237	11508	3008	1754	2030	1792
MEAN	301	205	58.1	40.5	49.1	35.8	141	371	100	56.6	65.5	59.7
MAX	2500	527	90	73	110	64	498	982	180	93	129	193
MIN	58	94	37	35	36	24	25	161	54	44	43	35
CFSM	5.23	3.56	1.01	.70	.85	.62	2.45	6.44	1.74	.98	1.14	1.04
IN.	6.03	3.98	1.16	.81	.89	.72	2.74	7.43	1.94	1.13	1.31	1.16
AC-FT	18530	12210	3570	2490	2730	2200	8400	22830	5970	3480	4030	3550

CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	40582	MEAN	111	MAX	2500	MIN	34	CFSM	1.93	IN.	26.21	AC-FT	80490
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	45366	MEAN	124	MAX	2500	MIN	24	CFSM	2.15	IN.	29.30	AC-FT	89980

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028400 RIO TANAMA AT CHARCO HONDO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS MARCH 1983 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
NOV, 21	1308	64	256	23.0	JUL, 10	1333	47	257	26.0
DEC, 11	1306	176	267	23.5	AUG, 12	1356	586	257	26.0
JUN, 16	1302	106	185	24.5	SEP, 08	1245	51	273	25.0

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50029000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO AT CENTRAL CAMBALACHE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'20", long 66°42'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, at bridge on unimproved road, about 500 ft (152 m) upstream from Central Cambalache, near Highway 2, 8.3 mi (13.4 km) downstream from Dos Bocas Reservoir, 1.9 mi (3.1 km) downstream from Rio Tanamá, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) southeast of Arecibo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--200 sq mi (520 sq km), approximately.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1963-66, 1969 to current year.

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECA, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1985											
28...	1410	18	174	7.80	26.5	110	--	--	25	2000	3500
DEC											
04...	1040	224	260	7.80	23.0	6.1	--	--	<10	480	200
FEB 1986											
24...	1120	174	250	8.30	23.0	2.2	9.3	109	25	410	810
MAY											
08...	1425	2210	230	8.08	25.5	120	8.4	103	18	K1800	K8900
JUL											
07...	--	145	296	7.97	28.0	6.5	8.9	113	<10	--	--
07...	1310	145	296	7.97	28.0	6.5	8.9	113	<10	K110	K20
SEP											
09...	0940	182	310	8.15	26.5	2.2	7.9	98	13	K950	360

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	NONCARBONATE WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
28...	68	2	19	5.0	8.0	0.4	2.4	66	<0.5	11	8.1
DEC											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	105	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	94	--	--	--
MAY											
08...	73	1	23	3.8	6.7	0.4	1.9	72	<0.5	8.2	8.0
JUL											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	129	--	--	--
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	129	--	--	--
SEP											
09...	120	4	39	5.9	9.2	0.4	2.1	118	--	11	9.4

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
28...	<0.10	18	110	5.5	180	0.770	0.030	0.800	0.050	0.75
DEC										
04...	--	--	--	--	1	0.860	0.040	0.900	0.040	0.46
FEB 1986										
24...	--	--	--	--	2	--	<0.010	0.500	0.020	0.28
MAY										
08...	<0.10	16	110	660	130	0.870	0.030	0.900	0.060	0.54
JUL										
07...	--	--	--	--	6	--	--	--	--	--
07...	--	--	--	--	6	--	<0.010	0.600	0.040	0.16
SEP										
09...	0.10	17	160	81	6	--	<0.010	0.500	0.060	0.24

K = non-ideal count

Figure 14.--Río Grande de Manatí basin.

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50030700 RIO OROCOVIS NEAR OROCOVIS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'20", long 66°22'58", at flat low bridge about 300 ft (91 m) northwest of Highway 568, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) north of Orocovis plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--10.1 sq mi (26.2 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water year 1979 to current year.

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1985											
17...	1525	30	214	8.20	24.5	5.0	--	--	10	20000	6000
DEC 23...	1230	16	255	8.60	24.0	2.2	7.6	95	18	K1500	200
FEB 1986											
03...	1635	14	247	8.60	22.5	15	8.8	109	14	K9500	4100
APR 28...	1430	10	327	8.63	25.5	2.2	8.3	106	<10	K590	K1200
JUL 23...	1155	8.1	284	8.65	27.0	2.3	5.8	76	14	380	K100
SEP 03...	1550	6.1	320	8.30	27.5	2.4	7.3	98	<10	3000	860

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
17...	82	5	19	8.4	10	0.5	1.7	77	<0.5	9.1	12
DEC 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	92	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	96	--	--	--
APR 28...	120	0	30	11	13	0.5	1.8	120	<0.5	9.9	14
JUL 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	125	--	--	--
SEP 03...	130	13	32	12	14	0.6	2.2	116	--	11	14

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
17...	0.10	30	140	11	8	0.790	0.010	0.800	0.030	0.27
DEC 23...	--	--	--	--	1	--	<0.010	0.900	0.020	0.48
FEB 1986										
03...	--	--	--	--	13	0.780	0.020	0.800	0.030	0.47
APR 28...	0.10	30	180	5.2	1	0.890	0.010	0.900	0.040	0.36
JUL 23...	--	--	--	--	4	--	<0.010	0.600	<0.010	--
SEP 03...	0.10	34	190	3.1	1	--	<0.010	1.00	<0.010	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50031200 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI NEAR MOROVIS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'45", long 66°24'47", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on right bank, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) downstream from Quebrada Perchas, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) upstream from Rio Sana Muerto, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) south of Morovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--55.2 mi² (143.0 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1965 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete control. Elevation of gage is 440 ft (134 m), from topographic map. Feb. 2, 1966 to Apr. 27, 1967, staff gage read twice daily.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharge: Oct. 6, 7, June 3, 4 and Aug. 29-31. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Public water-supply pumpage, about 300 ft (91 m) above the station, influences low-flow discharges.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--21 years (1966-86), 107 ft³/s (3.030 m³/s), 26.32 in/yr (668 mm/yr), 77,520 acre-ft/yr (95.6 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 110 ft³/s (3.12 m³/s), 79,700 acre-ft/yr (98 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 48,000 ft³/s (1,359 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 17.89 ft (5.453 m), from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of computations of flow over broad-crested weir and step-backwater analysis; minimum discharges, 4.4 ft³/s (0.125 m³/s), Apr. 15, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,500 ft³/s (99.1 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	unknown	*28,500	807	*13.67	4.167	May 13	0745	15,900	450	10.38	3.164
May 1	1730	4,540	129	5.73	1.747	May 13	2330	18,100	513	11.01	3.356

Minimum discharge, 25 ft³/s (0.708 m³/s), Mar. 31.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	41	153	110	63	47	33	28	794	101	53	39	182		
2	48	131	107	61	53	32	26	387	92	51	38	161		
3	37	123	102	59	96	31	88	230	95	51	36	76		
4	37	120	102	61	81	31	111	278	100	48	42	52		
5	109	115	97	56	171	31	327	280	97	50	40	42		
6	6200	103	102	54	81	30	172	174	90	52	35	39		
7	3600	101	97	56	61	31	73	225	88	57	35	35		
8	554	92	92	56	54	29	339	513	91	49	35	33		
9	282	90	90	67	49	31	298	489	88	47	33	31		
10	198	91	90	71	46	31	112	403	82	42	33	30		
11	163	98	90	57	42	31	77	636	82	43	32	30		
12	145	157	88	53	42	29	58	324	81	48	34	29		
13	136	207	86	52	41	29	50	2740	85	42	60	29		
14	127	326	82	51	41	32	45	1090	80	80	57	29		
15	120	832	81	49	41	35	42	360	72	144	36	28		
16	111	614	82	52	40	32	61	259	74	94	32	27		
17	106	337	79	55	41	29	67	230	69	80	31	27		
18	115	328	76	53	41	30	87	212	67	54	29	27		
19	106	205	78	47	39	30	79	190	64	48	26	27		
20	102	203	76	46	49	31	110	167	63	44	26	26		
21	97	307	75	44	45	28	173	156	58	44	27	27		
22	93	194	76	43	39	27	130	153	56	42	27	28		
23	117	159	73	44	38	26	72	160	56	43	32	28		
24	304	147	73	49	36	30	59	137	53	42	129	30		
25	223	138	69	119	35	33	52	128	53	43	112	33		
26	210	123	70	160	33	29	47	131	52	41	43	33		
27	299	120	66	63	33	29	46	126	54	42	33	43		
28	317	115	68	51	32	28	48	216	52	42	147	63		
29	219	112	65	47	---	29	219	161	53	40	300	33		
30	166	112	63	46	---	32	653	118	53	40	150	30		
31	204	---	62	45	---	27	---	107	---	48	70	---		
TOTAL	14586	5953	2567	1830	1447	936	3749	11574	2201	1644	1799	1308		
MEAN	471	198	82.8	59.0	51.7	30.2	125	373	73.4	53.0	58.0	43.6		
MAX	6200	832	110	160	171	35	653	2740	101	144	300	182		
MIN	37	90	62	43	32	26	26	107	52	40	26	26		
CFSM	8.53	3.59	1.50	1.07	.94	.55	2.26	6.76	1.33	.96	1.05	.79		
IN.	9.83	4.01	1.73	1.23	.98	.63	2.53	7.80	1.48	1.11	1.21	.88		
AC-FT	28930	11810	5090	3630	2870	1860	7440	22960	4370	3260	3570	2590		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	64935	MEAN	178	MAX	17100	MIN	19	CFSM	3.22	IN.	43.76	AC-FT	128800
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	49594	MEAN	136	MAX	6200	MIN	26	CFSM	2.46	IN.	33.42	AC-FT	98370

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50031200 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI NEAR MOROVIS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1968 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI TOCOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1985											
17...	1210	101	238	8.00	26.5	5.0	--	--	<10	K170	56
DEC 12...	1415	87	275	7.30	24.0	1.1	7.6	91	<10	2900	96
FEB 1986											
03...	1315	109	251	8.50	21.5	22	8.8	103	20	K11000	2700
APR 15...	1355	43	286	8.22	30.0	3.5	7.3	98	18	K82	K180
JUL 14...	1430	47	244	8.20	28.0	2.5	8.2	106	21	460	82
SEP 03...	1215	77	237	8.06	28.0	43	7.7	100	<10	2800	K800

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
17...	90	4	21	9.2	11	0.5	2.3	86	<0.5	9.9	13
DEC 12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	82	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	96	--	--	--
APR 15...	99	3	23	10	11	0.5	2.3	96	<0.5	11	17
JUL 14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	99	--	--	--
SEP 03...	85	11	20	8.6	11	0.5	2.8	74	--	12	12

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
17...	0.10	26	140	39	13	0.890	0.010	0.900	0.030	0.27
DEC 12...	--	--	--	--	1	--	<0.010	0.900	0.020	0.28
FEB 1986										
03...	--	--	--	--	40	0.690	0.010	0.700	0.040	0.56
APR 15...	0.10	26	160	18	6	--	<0.010	0.700	0.020	0.38
JUL 14...	--	--	--	--	6	--	<0.010	0.200	0.010	0.29
SEP 03...	0.10	25	140	28	48	0.980	0.020	1.00	0.040	0.36

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50035000 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT CIALES, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'26", Long 66°27'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on left bank, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream from Hwy 145 bridge, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) downstream from Quebrada Saliente, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) upstream from Quebrada Cojo Vales, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southeast of Ciales.

DRAINAGE AREA.--128 mi² (332 km²), excludes 6.0 mi² (15.5 km²), the runoff from which is diverted through El Guineo and de Matrullas reservoirs.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1946 to September 1953, May 1956 to December 1957 (unpublished, available in files of Caribbean District Office and in the National Water Data Storage and Retrieval System, Washington, D.C.); February 1959 to September 1960 (monthly discharge measurements only); October 1960 to current year. Equivalent record from January 1971 to December 1972 published as 50035200 Rio Grande de Manati at Highway 145 at Ciales at site 1.6 mi (2.6 km) downstream, drainage area 132 mi² (342 km²).

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 140 ft (43 m), from topographic map. Prior to Apr. 1, 1962, staff gage, read twice daily, at site 100 ft (30 m) upstream at same datum. January 1971 to December 1972 at site 1.6 mi (2.6 km) downstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: May 1. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--26 years (1961-86), 268 ft³/s (7.590 m³/s), 28.43 in/yr (722 mm/yr), 194,200 acre-ft/yr (239 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 260 ft³/s (7.36 m³/s), 188,000 acre-ft/yr (230 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 125,000 ft³/s (3,540 m³/s), Oct. 9, 1970, gage height, 24.0 ft (7.32 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurements of peak flow at gage heights 13.2 ft (4.02 m), 15.0 ft (4.57 m), 19.0 ft (5.79 m), and 24.0 ft (7.32 m), datum then in use; minimum discharge, 20 ft³/s (0.566 m³/s), Apr. 20, 21, 1984.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate gage heights of major floods, pointed out by local residents are as follows: August 1899, 50 ft (15.2 m), September 1928, 36 ft (11.0 m), and September 1932, 34 ft (10.4 m) at site 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 7,000 ft³/s (198 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 7	0115	*75,400	2,135	*19.75	6.020	May 13	0830	45,400	1,286	15.64	4.767
Apr. 30	1700	10,400	294	7.93	2.417	May 13	2230	53,900	1,526	16.92	5.157
May 1	1800	8,390	238	7.18	2.188						

Minimum discharge, 47 ft³/s (1.33 m³/s), Mar. 28, 29, 31, Apr. 1-3.

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50035000 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT CIALES, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	141	375	261	134	100	72	47	2450	268	108	87	503		
2	173	335	253	131	114	70	47	1670	221	107	80	339		
3	121	315	241	125	280	69	196	637	208	106	76	168		
4	107	315	239	124	214	68	263	564	193	104	81	131		
5	204	286	234	122	359	69	1050	1180	178	107	83	97		
6	6590	388	245	120	185	68	501	550	171	122	74	87		
7	26500	353	233	120	136	67	165	568	183	139	72	79		
8	2670	271	221	117	120	66	1050	1390	203	113	73	75		
9	1020	244	218	130	108	65	958	1740	187	105	73	73		
10	616	231	210	148	102	65	241	1100	162	99	69	70		
11	485	233	206	120	95	66	165	2130	189	99	65	68		
12	421	364	205	114	95	66	124	746	165	103	63	68		
13	377	496	201	111	92	64	108	12500	158	96	79	67		
14	340	1220	194	106	90	65	97	4740	151	169	106	67		
15	329	3850	191	102	87	69	89	937	142	369	80	63		
16	295	3010	189	102	87	66	108	561	146	244	72	62		
17	282	1380	182	102	87	60	247	490	137	174	67	60		
18	290	1510	176	106	91	64	223	467	135	125	63	60		
19	275	684	174	98	86	65	198	371	133	102	60	58		
20	261	550	171	92	98	64	360	323	130	100	59	58		
21	248	784	166	91	104	58	360	301	127	97	58	60		
22	225	490	162	91	87	52	242	287	122	92	57	65		
23	325	400	159	92	83	50	144	264	121	88	58	65		
24	758	357	154	93	80	52	134	249	118	192	165	62		
25	535	340	150	220	77	58	127	242	115	159	190	75		
26	1480	311	149	343	76	55	106	265	114	113	81	68		
27	1230	295	145	126	73	51	95	237	116	89	68	69		
28	1020	282	141	104	72	49	97	428	110	92	308	92		
29	703	274	140	96	---	51	499	418	109	98	514	71		
30	472	267	136	93	---	61	2340	322	108	95	236	66		
31	488	---	134	119	---	51	---	300	---	99	165	---		
TOTAL	48981	20210	5880	3792	3278	1916	10381	38427	4620	3905	3382	2946		
MEAN	1580	674	190	122	117	61.8	346	1240	154	126	109	98.2		
MAX	26500	3850	261	343	359	72	2340	12500	268	369	514	503		
MIN	107	231	134	91	72	49	47	237	108	88	57	58		
CFSM	12.3	5.27	1.48	.95	.91	.48	2.70	9.69	1.20	.98	.85	.77		
IN.	14.24	5.87	1.71	1.10	.95	.56	3.02	11.17	1.34	1.13	.98	.86		
AC-FT	97150	40090	11660	7520	6500	3800	20590	76220	9160	7750	6710	5840		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	180518	MEAN	495	MAX	42700	MIN	45	CFSM	3.87	IN.	52.46	AC-FT	358100
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	147718	MEAN	405	MAX	26500	MIN	47	CFSM	3.16	IN.	42.93	AC-FT	293000

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS 1979 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
DEC, 13	1056	199	234	23.0	JUL, 11	1022	89	241	28.0
MAY, 27	0955	234	205	25.5	AUG, 13	1039	67	236	27.5
JUN, 13	1047	160	222	22.3	SEP, 05	1017	98	218	28.0

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50035500 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 149 AT CIALES, RP

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'46", long 66°28'06", at bridge on Highway 149, about 800 ft (244 m) upstream from confluence with Rio Cialitos, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) north of Ciales plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--136 sq mi (352 sq km) this excludes the 6 sq mi (15.5 sq km) upstream from Lago El Guineo and Lago de Matrullas, flow from which is diverted to Rio Jacaguas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FE CAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FE CAL, KF AGAR (COLS./PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
10...	1350	852	146	7.70	29.5	3.4	7.8	104	11	720	5500
DEC 24...	1000	164	239	8.30	23.0	2.4	8.6	100	<10	K180	K100
FEB 1986											
26...	1130	60	255	8.20	23.0	2.0	9.6	112	<10	--	--
APR 23...	1425	143	210	8.00	26.5	59	8.5	107	17	3400	K1400
JUL 17...	1010	203	207	7.75	27.0	15	8.3	105	10	2100	K12000
SEP 18...	1115	70	249	8.00	28.5	6.2	8.5	110	24	K20	K30

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
10...	53	5	13	5.0	8.0	0.5	2.2	48	<0.5	8.9	9.3
DEC 24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	82	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	93	--	--	--
APR 23...	77	7	19	7.2	10	0.5	2.0	70	<0.5	11	11
JUL 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	72	--	--	--
SEP 18...	96	0	23	9.4	13	0.6	2.1	98	--	10	14

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
10...	0.10	21	96	221	30	0.780	0.020	0.800	0.050	0.35
DEC 24...	--	--	--	--	2	0.700	0.010	0.710	0.030	0.37
FEB 1986										
26...	--	--	--	--	1	0.290	0.010	0.300	0.040	0.26
APR 23...	0.10	23	130	48	49	0.780	0.020	0.800	0.060	0.34
JUL 17...	--	--	--	--	21	0.690	0.010	0.700	0.040	0.26
SEP 18...	0.20	27	160	30	3	--	<0.010	0.200	0.040	0.36

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50035950 RIO CIALITOS AT HIGHWAY 649 AT CIALES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'18", long 66°28'28", 100 ft (30 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 649, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) upstream from mouth, and about 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Ciales plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.0 sq mi (44.0 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-71, 1974 to current year.

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
10...	1700	52	188	8.00	28.0	9.0	7.8	101	<10	1000	K1900
DEC 23...	1545	70	229	8.60	23.0	1.1	8.6	100	<10	470	270
FEB 1986											
26...	1315	14	229	8.70	23.0	1.4	9.2	107	12	--	--
APR 23...	1105	23	224	8.20	24.5	7.2	9.0	109	<10	K1000	650
JUL 17...	1220	37	212	8.05	27.0	12	8.5	108	<10	2000	K110000
SEP 18...	1315	11	244	8.25	28.0	3.0	8.8	114	22	240	360

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
10...	67	0	18	5.4	11	0.6	2.2	67	<0.5	9.5	12
DEC 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	79	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
APR 23...	88	6	26	5.7	9.9	0.5	1.7	82	<0.5	9.2	9.2
JUL 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	86	--	--	--
SEP 18...	100	0	30	6.9	11	0.5	1.6	105	--	6.6	13

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
10...	0.10	26	120	17	45	1.29	0.010	1.30	0.040	0.36
DEC 23...	--	--	--	--	4	--	<0.010	0.900	0.020	0.28
FEB 1986										
26...	--	--	--	--	1	--	<0.010	0.500	0.020	0.28
APR 23...	0.10	25	140	8.4	12	--	<0.010	0.700	0.030	0.37
JUL 17...	--	--	--	--	19	--	<0.010	0.900	0.040	0.46
SEP 18...	0.10	31	160	5.0	12	--	<0.010	0.500	0.030	0.27

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'52", long 66°31'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, at bridge on Highway 2, and 2.3 mi (3.7 km) west of Manati.

DRAINAGE AREA.--197 mi² (510 km²), approximately, of which about 38 mi² (98 km²) is partly or entirely noncontributing, excludes 6.0 mi² (15.5 km²) upstream from Lago El Guineo and Lago de Matrullas.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1963-68 (annual maximum discharge only), February 1970 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 14 ft (4 m), from topographic map. Prior to 1968 crest-stage gage at same site and datum 3.57 ft (1.088 m) lower.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Dec. 25-30. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--16 years (1971-86), 397 ft³/s (11.24 m³/s), 27.36 in/yr (695 mm/yr), 287,600 acre-ft/yr (355 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 370 ft³/s (10.5 m³/s), 269,000 acre-ft/yr (330 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 97,200 ft³/s (2,750 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 33.79 ft (10.299 m) from rating curve extended above 15,000 ft³/s (425 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurements of peak flow; minimum discharge, 33 ft³/s (0.935 m³/s), May 12, 1984.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate gage heights to gage datum of major floods, pointed out by local residents, are as follows: Sept. 13, 1928, 36.6 ft (11.16 m), Sept. 27, 1932, 36.3 ft (11.06 m), and Aug. 4, 1945, 34.3 ft (10.45 m).

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 9,000 ft³/s (255 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 7	0515	*97,200	2,750	*33.79	10.299	May 2	2115	16,100	456	29.02	8.845
Nov. 15	0400	9,260	262	27.68	8.437	May 13	1145	40,100	1,140	31.57	9.622
Nov. 16	0045	9,340	264	27.72	8.449	May 14	0115	71,500	2,020	32.97	10.049
Apr. 30	2245	11,500	326	28.30	8.626						

Minimum discharge, 88 ft³/s (2.492 m³/s), Mar. 23, 24.

REVISIONS.--The peak discharges and annual maximum (*) reported for some water years have been revised as shown in the following table. They supersede figures published in the reports for 1970, 1971, 1975-76, 1979-80, 1981-82, 1983, 1984 and 1985.

Water Year	Date	Discharge		Gage height		Water Year	Date	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
1970	Nov. 9, 1969	*68,100	1,930	32.85	10.013		Sept. 13, 1982	21,200	600	29.96	9.132
1971	Oct. 9, 1970	*81,800	2,360	33.30	10.150	1983	Apr. 21, 1983	*30,200	855	30.84	9.400
1975	Oct. 23, 1974	21,000	595	29.92	9.120		May 14, 1983	18,700	530	29.52	8.998
	Sept. 16, 1975	*21,400	606	29.99	9.141	1984	Sept. 11, 1984	8,600	244	27.36	8.339
1979	July 19, 1979	19,000	538	29.57	9.013	1985	Nov. 3, 1984	17,300	490	29.26	8.918
	Aug. 31, 1979	*34,500	977	31.18	9.504		May 17, 1985	37,300	1,060	31.38	9.565
1982	Dec. 13, 1981	*31,000	878	30.91	9.421		May 18, 1985	*90,000	2,550	33.54	10.223

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	201	585	393	181	165	111	99	3700	434	157	186	463		
2	286	515	372	178	165	110	99	4640	354	155	168	739		
3	201	529	347	175	358	108	151	2840	327	154	158	327		
4	169	675	335	177	339	109	547	1300	304	151	158	296		
5	259	616	324	173	476	107	1360	2310	290	147	163	193		
6	3040	576	340	171	283	105	1070	1610	276	160	152	164		
7	48600	675	314	170	197	103	387	1140	266	186	147	147		
8	7170	476	298	164	169	103	741	1760	382	220	145	138		
9	1950	417	291	181	154	102	2300	3070	350	158	148	138		
10	1190	396	284	210	144	104	482	2010	288	151	142	139		
11	928	399	285	172	139	105	325	2930	293	150	139	135		
12	795	504	281	160	133	103	233	1490	274	153	138	132		
13	653	854	274	157	130	101	186	13300	262	140	169	133		
14	557	1240	258	150	127	104	159	21100	254	134	203	130		
15	509	7140	254	145	126	110	143	2340	236	438	166	125		
16	447	6510	252	151	126	108	140	1340	235	466	152	120		
17	414	2530	247	167	123	99	287	1040	218	271	146	118		
18	414	2090	239	173	129	103	284	994	209	210	136	117		
19	407	1150	231	143	121	102	339	772	206	169	131	115		
20	370	894	229	144	122	103	248	652	201	154	130	112		
21	363	1090	222	153	150	99	711	583	194	146	128	111		
22	329	818	220	155	127	93	452	540	188	137	128	115		
23	314	676	215	152	115	90	333	494	185	133	130	121		
24	984	596	208	148	111	92	266	470	181	135	191	116		
25	850	549	204	165	114	106	228	448	175	362	313	119		
26	1540	512	200	562	115	102	176	449	171	206	186	123		
27	2560	473	195	233	113	99	155	477	173	179	149	114		
28	1190	445	191	178	111	96	155	575	169	179	464	129		
29	1220	425	185	162	---	107	433	807	162	201	720	124		
30	712	413	182	154	---	125	2610	582	157	279	519	112		
31	720	---	181	180	---	104	---	433	---	205	311	---		
TOTAL	79342	34768	8051	5584	4682	3213	15099	76196	7414	6086	6316	5165		
MEAN	2559	1159	260	180	167	104	503	2458	247	196	204	172		
MAX	48600	7140	393	562	476	125	2610	21100	434	466	720	739		
MIN	169	396	181	143	111	90	99	433	157	133	128	111		
CFSM	13.0	5.88	1.32	.91	.85	.53	2.55	12.5	1.25	.99	1.04	.87		
IN.	14.98	6.57	1.52	1.05	.88	.61	2.85	14.39	1.40	1.15	1.19	.98		
AC-FT	157400	68960	15970	11080	9290	6370	29950	151100	14710	12070	12530	10240		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	272646	MEAN	747	MAX	55900	MIN	80	CFSM	3.79	IN.	51.48	AC-FT	540800
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	251916	MEAN	690	MAX	48600	MIN	90	CFSM	3.50	IN.	47.57	AC-FT	499700

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
11...	1215	1020	205	8.10	26.5	100	8.3	103	--	--	70000
DEC 04...	1445	334	247	7.80	25.5	48	--	--	<10	3800	3700
FEB 1986											
06...	1135	279	247	7.85	22.5	35	8.1	94	22	K7400	3000
APR 02...	1350	97	320	7.80	27.0	1.7	9.5	88	28	2000	K730
JUN 05...	1055	293	312	7.69	27.0	6.5	7.2	90	13	K10000	600
AUG 29...	1030	520	219	7.67	27.0	89	6.4	80	14	K12000	K14000

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)	FLUORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)
OCT 1985											
11...	88	10	26	5.5	8.5	0.4	1.7	--	8.9	9.2	<0.10
DEC 04...	120	4	35	7.6	11	0.5	2.0	115	9.3	13	0.10
FEB 1986											
06...	100	6	28	7.3	9.0	0.4	1.9	94	9.5	11	0.20
APR 02...	130	17	41	7.9	11	0.4	2.3	118	10	13	0.20
JUN 05...	130	1	41	7.7	11	0.4	2.2	133	8.8	13	0.20
AUG 29...	91	6	27	5.7	10	0.5	2.7	88	9.1	9.3	0.10

DATE	SILICA, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 DISSOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA DISSOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA DISSOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS PO4)
OCT 1985											
11...	19	132	130	362	--	0.800	0.080	0.10	0.40	0.260	0.80
DEC 04...	22	162	170	146	19	0.780	0.070	0.09	0.50	0.080	0.25
FEB 1986											
06...	21	149	150	112	24	0.980	0.090	0.12	0.80	0.110	0.34
APR 02...	17	206	170	54	12	0.590	0.030	0.04	0.40	0.140	0.43
JUN 05...	20	184	180	146	28	0.650	0.060	0.08	0.30	0.110	0.34
AUG 29...	18	164	130	230	62	0.880	0.200	0.26	0.50	0.170	0.52

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	PHOS- PHORUS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHORUS, ORTHO, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHATE, ORTHO, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS PO4)	ALUM- INUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYL- LIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985 11...	0.040	0.030	0.09	40	<1	47	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	7
DEC 04...	0.050	0.050	0.15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 06...	0.090	0.090	0.28	70	1	44	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	3
APR 02...	0.090	0.090	0.28	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 05...	0.040	0.040	0.12	10	<1	51	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	3
AUG 29...	0.110	0.070	0.21	80	1	39	<0.5	2	<1	<3	11

DATE	IRON, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)	LITHIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)	MANGA- NESE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRON- TIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS V)
OCT 1985 11...	29	<1	<4	41	<0.1	<10	2	<1	<1	120	<6
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 06...	72	<1	<4	16	4.1	<10	7	<1	<1	150	<6
APR 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 05...	9	<1	<4	44	0.5	<10	<1	<1	<1	170	<6
AUG 29...	130	<5	8	26	2.5	<10	4	<1	<1	140	<6

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1986 05...	1055	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1986 05...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUN 1986 05...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
DEC 1985					
04...	1445	400	60	65	82
FEB 1986					
06...	1135	304	128	105	83
JUN					
05...	1055	329	100	89	89
AUG					
29...	1100	478	235	303	65

LAGUNA TORTUGUERO BASIN

50038200 LAGUNA TORTUGUERO OUTLET NEAR VEGA BAJA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°28'29", long 66°26'50", at bridge on Highway 686, 4.2 mi (6.8 km) northeast of Manati, and 4.4 mi (7.1 km) northwest of Vega Baja plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964-66, 1969-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS./100 ML)
NOV 1985										
01...	1145	37	1300	7.80	28.5	--	--	52	43	K27
DEC 18...	0950	33	1140	8.10	26.0	--	--	<10	K7	K20
FEB 1986										
06...	1645	25	1250	8.20	27.5	8.7	111	36	K31	K990
APR 22...	1005	24	1610	8.01	29.0	8.0	105	39	K15	K120
JUL 01...	1405	22	1110	8.20	30.5	7.3	97	25	K6	K10
SEP 02...	1515	27	1350	7.85	30.5	8.3	112	30	K8	68

DATE	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
NOV 1985										
01...	139	<0.5	14	0.880	0.020	0.900	0.420	0.68	1.1	2.0
DEC 18...	157	--	4	1.27	0.030	1.30	0.310	0.69	1.0	2.3
FEB 1986										
06...	142	--	9	0.880	0.020	0.900	0.210	0.69	0.90	1.8
APR 22...	115	<0.5	2	0.870	0.030	0.900	0.120	0.68	0.80	1.7
JUL 01...	119	--	4	0.680	0.020	0.700	0.130	0.77	0.90	1.6
SEP 02...	116	--	2	0.580	0.020	0.600	0.180	0.92	1.1	1.7

DATE	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	MANGANESE, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (UG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYLENE BLUE ACTIVE SUBSTANCE (MG/L)
NOV 1985										
01...	8.9	0.010	70	10	160	20	50	<0.010	8	0.11
DEC 18...	10	0.020	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986										
06...	8.0	0.010	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 22...	7.5	<0.010	90	<10	140	10	60	<0.010	2	0.13
JUL 01...	7.1	0.010	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 02...	7.5	<0.010	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

K = non-ideal count

Figure 15.--Río Cibuco basin.

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50038320 RIO CIBUCO BELOW COROZAL, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'13", long 66°20'07", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on right bank, 150 ft (46 m) downstream from Rio Corozal, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) northwest of Corozal.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.1 mi² (39.1 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1969 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 195 ft (59 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 8, 9 and May 12-15. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--17 years (1970-86), 29.6 ft³/s (0.838 m³/s), 26.62 in/yr (676 mm/yr), 21,440 acre-ft/yr (26.4 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 32 ft³/s (0.91 m³/s), 23,200 acre-ft/yr (29 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 13,600 ft³/s (385 m³/s), Nov. 7, 1979, gage height, 19.80 ft (6.035 m), from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of float and slope-area measurements of peak flow; minimum daily discharge, 1.3 ft³/s (0.037 m³/s), July 24-26, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,500 ft³/s (70.8 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1645	3,130	88.6	11.65	3.551	May 1	1730	4,330	123	13.09	3.990
Oct. 7	0045	4,310	122	13.07	3.984	May 9	1700	8,530	242	16.92	5.157
Nov. 15	1800	2,730	77.3	11.11	3.386	May 13	0700	9,680	274	17.78	5.419
Apr. 8	1445	3,560	101	12.19	3.716	May 13	2230	*11,000	312	*18.71	5.703
Apr. 30	1400	3,290	93.2	11.85	3.612						

Minimum discharge, 4.6 ft³/s (0.130 m³/s), Apr. 2.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	29	30	35	17	12	9.7	6.5	481	30	14	9.6	157
2	22	27	34	17	16	8.1	5.7	109	28	13	8.4	53
3	18	37	34	19	21	8.5	24	90	27	15	8.9	30
4	33	80	34	18	26	8.9	78	253	25	13	8.4	22
5	66	37	35	15	26	8.3	205	94	23	15	9.4	19
6	529	30	31	14	15	7.5	37	65	22	18	7.7	17
7	1210	27	30	14	13	7.2	20	111	21	13	8.3	14
8	110	25	29	13	12	7.4	250	122	20	13	7.7	13
9	60	24	29	34	11	7.5	60	544	20	11	6.7	12
10	44	24	28	19	11	7.8	29	102	20	11	6.1	12
11	38	31	28	14	12	7.8	23	83	19	17	7.8	12
12	33	118	28	12	11	7.1	14	49	28	13	6.8	12
13	30	93	26	13	11	7.5	12	1640	22	10	23	12
14	31	301	24	12	11	8.6	11	380	19	14	15	11
15	29	752	25	12	11	7.5	9.0	100	20	73	10	9.9
16	24	276	25	13	11	6.5	8.9	56	20	36	7.4	9.8
17	22	124	25	14	11	6.7	8.8	46	18	30	6.7	10
18	52	80	23	13	11	6.5	9.0	49	17	16	6.1	9.9
19	39	64	23	12	11	7.2	8.5	37	17	13	6.4	9.5
20	66	73	22	12	13	7.1	22	32	16	13	6.4	9.9
21	28	64	22	13	12	6.8	62	33	15	12	5.8	18
22	27	52	22	12	11	6.8	30	29	15	11	5.8	25
23	71	49	21	13	10	6.4	15	26	14	11	11	14
24	64	46	20	14	10	8.7	12	25	15	11	20	13
25	38	43	19	37	9.2	8.5	10	23	14	12	13	16
26	136	42	20	26	9.5	7.5	9.6	22	14	11	7.2	11
27	181	39	19	14	8.9	6.9	9.2	84	15	13	6.2	13
28	105	38	19	12	9.2	6.3	11	46	13	11	126	12
29	56	39	18	12	---	6.8	131	70	12	9.7	115	11
30	41	39	17	11	---	6.6	209	42	13	9.8	36	11
31	35	---	17	12	---	6.8	---	35	---	9.1	25	---
TOTAL	3267	2704	782	483	355.8	231.5	1340.2	4878	572	491.6	547.8	599.0
MEAN	105	90.1	25.2	15.6	12.7	7.47	44.7	157	19.1	15.9	17.7	20.0
MAX	1210	752	35	37	26	9.7	250	1640	30	73	126	157
MIN	18	24	17	11	8.9	6.3	5.7	22	12	9.1	5.8	9.5
CFSM	6.95	5.97	1.67	1.03	.84	.49	2.96	10.4	1.26	1.05	1.17	1.32
IN.	8.05	6.66	1.93	1.19	.88	.57	3.30	12.02	1.41	1.21	1.35	1.48
AC-FT	6480	5360	1550	958	706	459	2660	9680	1130	975	1090	1190

CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	16072.9	MEAN	44.0	MAX	2370	MIN	4.9	CFSM	2.91	IN.	39.60	AC-FT	31880
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	16251.9	MEAN	44.5	MAX	1640	MIN	5.7	CFSM	2.95	IN.	40.04	AC-FT	32240

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50038320 RIO CIBUCO BELOW COROZAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-76, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
16...	1110	24	344	7.80	24.5	3.0	--	--	12	K710	320
DEC 06...	1025	32	317	7.80	22.5	7.0	--	--	<10	4900	2600
FEB 1986											
04...	1100	15	316	8.20	22.0	25	8.4	98	36	5000	2000
APR 17...	1110	10	400	7.96	26.0	21	7.4	92	27	K1100	--
JUL 03...	0920	17	320	7.75	26.5	3.0	7.4	92	<10	K730	700
SEP 19...	0957	11	393	7.70	25.5	3.8	7.6	94	37	K750	370

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD MG/L AS CAC03	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WH WAT TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
16...	130	14	34	12	16	0.6	3.1	120	<0.5	18	22
DEC 06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	112	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	107	--	--	--
APR 17...	130	6	31	12	19	0.8	3.8	121	<0.5	15	27
JUL 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	117	--	--	--
SEP 19...	130	5	35	11	18	0.7	3.2	128	--	17	24

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
16...	0.10	31	210	13	4	1.34	0.160	1.50	0.660	0.14
DEC 06...	--	--	--	--	12	1.37	0.130	1.50	0.490	0.41
FEB 1986										
04...	--	--	--	--	22	1.51	0.390	1.90	0.450	0.95
APR 17...	0.10	30	210	6.0	4	0.780	0.320	1.10	1.20	0.50
JUL 03...	--	--	--	--	11	0.700	0.200	0.900	0.530	0.47
SEP 19...	0.10	32	220	6.2	7	0.760	0.140	0.900	0.810	1.1

K = non-ideal count

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039500 RIO CIBUCO AT VEGA BAJA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'53", long 66°22'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) downstream from Rio Indio, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) east of Vega Baja.

DRAINAGE AREA.--99.1 mi² (256.7 km²), of which 25.4 mi² (65.8 km²), does not contribute directly to surface runoff.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1973 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 7.79 ft (2.37 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Jan. 25 to Feb. 7. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--13 years (1974-86), 128 ft³/s (3.625 m³/s), 17.54 in/yr (446 mm/yr), 92,740 acre-ft/yr (114 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 120 ft³/s (3.40 m³/s), 86,900 acre-ft/yr (107 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 30,300 ft³/s (858 m³/s), Dec. 13, 1981, gage height, 18.84 ft (5.742 m), from rating curve extended above 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) on the basis of indirect measurements; minimum discharge, 6.1 ft³/s (0.173 m³/s), July 24, 25, 1977.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Flood of Dec. 11, 1965 reached a stage of 26.2 ft (7.99 m), datum unknown, discharge about 28,000 ft³/s (793 m³/s).

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,200 ft³/s (90.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 7	0615	*20,200	572	*17.98	5.480	May 13	1315	14,200	402	17.48	5.328
Nov. 15	2230	3,960	112	15.83	4.825						

Minimum discharge, 24 ft³/s (0.680 m³/s), Mar. 31 to Apr. 1-3.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	77	157	145	68	56	36	26	742	150	63	33	472		
2	76	131	139	70	64	35	27	1060	130	61	32	443		
3	59	129	132	65	90	34	33	913	123	65	31	216		
4	53	274	129	75	115	33	116	954	111	61	35	119		
5	255	342	127	65	115	34	572	498	104	59	37	92		
6	704	189	134	63	60	34	242	272	98	75	33	83		
7	9710	135	118	61	56	34	80	493	93	73	31	76		
8	998	118	111	61	54	33	451	612	93	71	32	68		
9	409	107	113	65	50	32	403	925	93	59	30	65		
10	298	105	111	127	49	35	124	872	88	55	30	52		
11	222	131	110	79	47	35	83	549	90	66	30	47		
12	170	306	109	67	45	32	54	403	93	85	40	46		
13	141	491	105	64	44	32	42	4650	116	59	73	48		
14	122	706	95	63	43	34	36	2510	90	56	142	45		
15	115	2490	92	61	42	35	33	538	118	163	69	43		
16	105	2200	91	60	41	31	31	380	118	154	51	42		
17	98	671	94	67	42	28	36	321	86	119	46	42		
18	148	462	89	74	42	34	53	306	81	60	42	41		
19	168	384	86	64	42	31	35	254	78	45	40	40		
20	229	352	83	57	43	30	82	218	74	41	40	40		
21	178	398	79	56	57	29	299	206	72	38	40	47		
22	105	315	80	55	41	28	260	192	68	35	40	69		
23	97	288	80	55	38	27	82	173	66	35	42	84		
24	333	246	76	55	37	30	51	160	65	35	119	55		
25	341	220	74	175	37	45	41	150	65	47	123	61		
26	424	199	73	115	37	36	35	143	63	46	50	55		
27	595	184	71	56	36	31	32	186	67	35	40	49		
28	399	167	74	54	35	29	39	254	66	42	302	50		
29	309	164	72	54	---	28	227	295	61	38	399	47		
30	204	160	69	53	---	28	488	215	59	34	191	48		
31	199	---	67	52	---	26	---	169	---	34	115	---		
TOTAL	17341	12221	3028	2156	1458	999	4113	19613	2679	1909	2358	2685		
MEAN	559	407	97.7	69.5	52.1	32.2	137	633	89.3	61.6	76.1	89.5		
MAX	9710	2490	145	175	115	45	572	4650	150	163	399	472		
MIN	53	105	67	52	35	26	26	143	59	34	30	40		
CFSM	5.64	4.11	.99	.70	.53	.32	1.38	6.39	.90	.62	.77	.90		
IN.	6.51	4.59	1.14	.81	.55	.38	1.54	7.36	1.01	.72	.89	1.01		
AC-FT	34400	24240	6010	4280	2890	1980	8160	38900	5310	3790	4680	5330		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	74652	MEAN	205	MAX	10800	MIN	32	CFSM	2.07	IN.	28.02	AC-FT	148100
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	70560	MEAN	193	MAX	9710	MIN	26	CFSM	1.95	IN.	26.49	AC-FT	140000

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039500 RIO CIBUCO AT VEGA BAJA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1985											
15...	1230	120	440	7.80	25.5	8.5	--	--	10	3900	820
DEC 02...	1330	138	406	7.80	24.5	8.5	7.8	94	<10	2900	320
FEB 1986											
07...	1145	58	390	7.90	23.0	11	4.9	58	14	K1100	520
APR 09...	1625	--	342	7.68	25.0	95	7.2	87	28	K7900	K12000
JUL 01...	1115	62	409	7.78	28.5	3.0	4.2	54	<10	K1700	290
SEP 02...	1115	550	342	7.75	24.5	170	6.8	82	18	25000	30000

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
15...	210	26	68	8.7	13	0.4	2.9	180	<0.5	18	22
DEC 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	167	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	151	--	--	--
APR 09...	130	26	41	7.2	12	0.5	3.9	106	<0.5	22	17
JUL 01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	167	--	--	--
SEP 02...	140	9	47	5.4	9.1	0.4	4.5	131	--	14	11

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
15...	0.20	20	260	84	9	1.26	0.040	1.30	0.120	0.48
DEC 02...	--	--	--	--	13	1.36	0.040	1.40	0.090	0.41
FEB 1986										
07...	--	--	--	--	24	1.44	0.060	1.50	0.150	0.45
APR 09...	0.10	15	180	0.0	134	1.64	0.060	1.70	0.250	0.75
JUL 01...	--	--	--	--	12	1.04	0.060	1.10	0.200	0.30
SEP 02...	0.10	12	180	270	34	0.950	0.050	1.00	0.120	2.4

K = non-ideal count

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039650 DRAINAGE DITCH BELOW WARNER LAMBERT LABORATORY NR SABANA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'17", long 66°21'09", 0.3 mile (0.5 km) northwest of Warner Lambert Laboratory, 0.6 mile (1.0 km) south of Sabana, and 1.1 miles (1.8 km) above confluence with Rio Cibuco.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1982 to April 1986 (discontinued).

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
NOV 1985										
08...	0905	E3.0	300	6.40	26.0	11	--	--	71	K1500 2000
DEC										
18...	1220	E3.0	718	6.90	25.5	15	--	--	35	360 K1200
FEB 1986										
05...	1510	E0.0	440	7.15	25.5	22	2.4	30	54	K1100 3000
APR										
22...	1235	E0.0	494	7.29	27.5	11	1.2	15	40	5300 300

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
NOV 1985											
08...	73	7	21	5.0	31	2	4.3	66	<0.5	13	53
DEC											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	105	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	101	--	--	--
APR											
22...	160	13	49	9.1	31	1	2.6	147	<0.5	16	42

DATE	FLUORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
NOV 1985										
08...	0.10	10	180	0.0	18	--	0.010	<0.100	0.090	0.91
DEC										
18...	--	--	--	--	8	--	0.010	<0.100	0.040	0.96
FEB 1986										
05...	--	--	--	--	26	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.040	1.2
APR										
22...	0.20	10	250	0.0	11	0.060	0.040	0.100	0.280	0.62

DATE	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
NOV 1985										
08...	1.0	--	--	0.100	4	<100	110	1	6	<10
DEC										
18...	1.0	--	--	0.050	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986										
05...	1.2	1.4	6.2	0.140	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
22...	0.90	1.0	4.4	0.120	1	100	100	<1	8	<10

K = non-ideal count

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039650 DRAINAGE DITCH BELOW WARNER LAMBERT LABORATORY NR SABANA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
NOV 1985 08...	5000	2	230	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	3	0.07
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 22...	1100	1	110	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	2	0.08

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039700 DRAINAGE DITCH AT RIO CIBUCO BELOW CENTRAL SAN VICENTE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'44", long 66°21'52", 60 ft (18 m), above confluence with Rio Cibuco, 984 ft (300 m) east of Central San Vicente, and 0.7 mi (1.2 km) west of Sabana.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1982 to April 1986 (discontinued).

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
25...	1055	30	368	7.00	26.0	21	0.8	--	10	K1100	20000
DEC											
05...	0945	23	606	7.20	24.5	15	--	--	30	570	6000
FEB 1986											
07...	1450	14	418	7.70	25.0	14	4.6	56	43	330	770
APR											
21...	1455	--	480	7.48	27.0	17	4.7	59	39	--	--
21...	1455	3.9	480	7.48	27.0	17	4.7	59	39	K1000	3300

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CAC03	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL MG/L AS CAC03	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
25...	110	0	24	12	14	0.6	2.2	109	<0.5	16	20
DEC											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	143	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	136	--	--	--
APR											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
21...	170	1	54	8.7	18	0.6	2.8	170	<0.5	15	32

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
25...	<0.10	24	180	14	28	1.17	0.030	1.20	0.070	0.33
DEC										
05...	--	--	--	--	26	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.050	0.65
FEB 1986										
07...	--	--	--	--	30	0.230	0.070	0.300	0.510	0.69
APR										
21...	--	--	--	--	31	--	--	--	--	--
21...	0.20	15	250	2.6	31	0.080	0.020	0.100	0.070	0.83

DATE	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985										
25...	0.40	1.6	7.1	2.20	<1	<100	70	1	5	10
DEC										
05...	0.70	0.90	4.0	0.080	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986										
07...	1.2	1.5	6.6	0.090	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
21...	0.90	1.0	4.4	0.120	2	<100	<10	<1	15	10

K = non-ideal count

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039700 DRAINAGE DITCH AT RIO CIBUCO BELOW CENTRAL SAN VICENTE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1985 25...	1400	3	80	<0.10	<1	1	30	<0.010	<1	0.06
DEC 05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
21...	770	4	290	0.50	<1	<1	20	<0.010	2	0.05

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039750 RIO CIBUCO BELOW CENTRAL SAN VICENTE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'47", long 66°21'53", at bridge on Highway 688, 1,000 ft (305 m) northeast of Central San Vicente, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) west of Sabana, and 1.3 mi (2.1 km) northwest of Warner Lambert Laboratory.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--water years 1982 to April 1986 (discontinued).

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
NOV 1985											
01...	1445	211	389	7.80	26.0	36	--	--	27	2300	500
DEC											
06...	1415	124	475	7.70	24.5	13	--	--	52	K1500	500
FEB 1986											
04...	1450	68	406	7.80	22.5	35	7.0	82	20	2400	4100
APR											
21...	1150	144	366	7.72	26.0	41	6.6	81	39	28000	27000

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
NOV 1985											
01...	170	20	54	8.0	15	0.5	2.8	148	<0.5	19	24
DEC											
06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	157	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	144	--	--	--
APR											
21...	140	13	44	6.4	12	0.5	5.0	123	<0.5	34	16

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SI02)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
NOV 1985										
01...	0.10	17	230	130	180	0.860	0.040	0.900	0.120	0.78
DEC										
06...	--	--	--	--	22	1.07	0.030	1.10	0.050	0.65
FEB 1986										
04...	--	--	--	--	43	0.850	0.050	0.900	0.110	0.69
APR										
21...	0.20	14	210	80	60	1.33	0.070	1.40	0.190	0.91

DATE	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N03)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
NOV 1985										
01...	0.90	1.8	8.0	0.140	2	<100	30	<1	20	20
DEC										
06...	0.70	1.8	8.0	0.100	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986										
04...	0.80	1.7	7.5	0.200	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
21...	1.1	2.5	11	0.290	1	100	10	<1	16	10

K = non-ideal count

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039750 RIO CIBUCO BELOW CENTRAL SAN VICENTE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
NOV 1985 01...	4200	5	170	<0.10	<1	<1	70	<0.010	<1	0.05
DEC 06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 21...	1900	6	120	<0.10	<1	<1	30	<0.010	<1	0.06

Figure 16.--Río de la Plata basin.

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT PROYECTO LA PLATA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'37", long 66°13'44", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at upstream side of bridge on Highway 173, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of Proyecto La Plata, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) upstream from Rio Usabón.

DRAINAGE AREA.--54.8 mi² (141.9 km²), excludes 8.2 mi² (21.1 km²) upstream from Carite Reservoir, the flow of which is diverted to Rio Guamaní.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1958 (occasional measurements only), February 1959 to March 1960 (monthly measurements only), April 1960 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 850 ft (259 m), from topographic map. Prior to Mar. 29, 1961, wire-weight gage read twice daily at same site and datum.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 6-17, Apr. 10-14, June 2-6, Aug. 19-22 and Aug. 29, 30. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. The Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority operates a pumping plant about 5 mi (8 km) upstream which can divert as much as 23 ft³/s (0.65 m³/s) into Cidra Reservoir.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--26 years (1961-86), 113 ft³/s (3.200 m³/s), 28.00 in/yr (711 mm/yr), 81,870 acre-ft/yr (101 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 91 ft³/s (2.58 m³/s), 65,900 acre-ft/yr (81 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 59,600 ft³/s (1,690 m³/s), Aug. 27, 1961, gage height, 32.21 ft (9.818 m), from rating curve extended above 7,000 ft³/s (198 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement; minimum daily discharge, 2.6 ft³/s (0.074 m³/s), July 25, 1974.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 4,000 ft³/s (113 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1330	*28,900	818	*22.00	6.706	May 13	2400	4,600	130	10.50	3.200

Minimum daily discharge, 6.2 ft³/s (0.176 m³/s), Aug. 27.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	28	248	98	44	27	15	14	186	47	22	18	159		
2	43	146	92	49	31	14	12	92	59	26	15	56		
3	30	498	86	50	37	13	44	50	56	21	13	33		
4	33	291	82	58	51	14	73	44	47	26	12	28		
5	84	272	86	54	75	16	47	41	45	25	14	26		
6	5000	246	91	46	37	17	36	40	42	26	13	27		
7	3000	191	84	42	29	16	18	146	41	34	11	25		
8	1000	156	75	39	28	13	219	146	48	23	15	22		
9	350	134	79	53	31	13	111	147	74	20	17	18		
10	250	120	77	86	29	13	24	599	75	19	13	18		
11	180	109	76	51	24	13	22	553	49	22	15	17		
12	150	149	84	43	24	17	21	199	41	53	24	16		
13	120	380	91	39	24	16	24	766	38	34	22	15		
14	110	401	73	37	23	19	50	611	47	31	44	17		
15	100	1110	70	35	22	23	44	175	37	34	15	17		
16	90	595	68	34	22	25	90	82	52	29	13	11		
17	83	389	62	34	22	18	57	52	35	22	12	11		
18	134	870	60	40	23	15	49	387	27	19	11	9.5		
19	157	339	61	34	24	16	46	178	23	21	9.0	8.5		
20	92	319	63	32	27	14	81	79	24	26	8.2	7.8		
21	77	697	59	32	23	14	58	54	22	26	7.8	12		
22	76	263	57	33	20	14	33	45	23	25	7.2	16		
23	482	207	55	25	20	14	29	36	23	21	17	13		
24	604	167	59	51	20	14	26	30	23	18	11	16		
25	506	146	63	48	20	15	25	27	23	18	12	21		
26	374	131	65	31	22	14	25	24	23	18	6.8	24		
27	544	122	55	29	19	14	26	24	22	18	6.2	18		
28	215	114	52	21	16	13	27	29	25	19	11	20		
29	752	106	50	23	---	33	417	32	26	20	631	23		
30	676	102	48	25	---	45	553	27	26	17	138	25		
31	729	---	45	21	---	21	---	71	---	18	66	---		
TOTAL	16069	9018	2166	1239	770	531	2301	4972	1143	751	1228.2	729.8		
MEAN	518	301	69.9	40.0	27.5	17.1	76.7	160	38.1	24.2	39.6	24.3		
MAX	5000	1110	98	86	75	45	553	766	75	53	631	159		
MIN	28	102	45	21	16	13	12	24	22	17	6.2	7.8		
CFSM	9.45	5.49	1.28	.73	.50	.31	1.40	2.92	.70	.44	.72	.44		
IN.	10.91	6.12	1.47	.84	.52	.36	1.56	3.38	.78	.51	.83	.50		
AC-FT	31870	17890	4300	2460	1530	1050	4560	9860	2270	1490	2440	1450		
CAL YR 1985 TOTAL	57179.9		MEAN	157	MAX	5000	MIN	8.0	CFSM	2.86	IN.	38.82	AC-FT	113400
WTR YR 1986 TOTAL	40918.0		MEAN	112	MAX	5000	MIN	6.2	CFSM	2.04	IN.	27.78	AC-FT	81160

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT PROYECTO LA PLATA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
18...	1030	122	327	8.20	25.5	1.0	--	--	11	2000	K170
DEC											
09...	1100	90	402	8.20	23.5	1.4	--	--	<10	290	160
FEB 1986											
14...	1110	24	480	8.45	24.0	1.8	9.9	122	20	K630	410
APR											
10...	1415	23	417	7.90	30.5	6.0	12.2	167	23	450	480
JUL											
15...	1325	32	362	8.70	29.5	3.0	10.0	134	<10	K70	K99
SEP											
24...	1435	27	356	8.17	30.5	15	7.2	99	<10	41	320

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
18...	120	7	31	11	21	0.9	1.5	116	<0.5	15	22
DEC											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	148	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	162	--	--	--
APR											
10...	140	13	37	12	25	0.9	2.6	129	<0.5	17	27
JUL											
15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	133	--	--	--
SEP											
24...	120	4	29	11	21	0.9	2.7	114	--	18	20

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
18...	0.10	23	190	64	2	0.730	0.070	0.800	0.040	0.36
DEC										
09...	--	--	--	--	5	1.02	0.080	1.10	0.050	0.45
FEB 1986										
14...	--	--	--	--	1	2.06	0.040	2.10	0.040	0.66
APR										
10...	0.20	23	220	14	16	1.74	0.060	1.80	0.060	0.64
JUL										
15...	--	--	--	--	7	0.880	0.020	0.900	0.020	0.88
SEP										
24...	0.10	20	190	14	9	1.24	0.060	1.30	0.030	0.57

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044000 RIO DE LA PLATA NEAR COMERIO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'33", long 66°12'28", at bridge on Highway 156, 0.56 mi (0.9 km) upstream from dam, about 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northeast of Comerio plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--139 sq mi (360 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
18...	1410	197	362	8.20	25.5	3.6	--	--	<10	25000	25000
DEC 20...	0850	143	397	8.30	23.5	1.5	--	--	14	K620	360
FEB 1986											
20...	1035	68	449	8.45	21.5	1.3	9.3	108	29	1000	730
APR 25...	1020	41	432	7.93	26.5	3.2	8.0	101	23	280	K100
JUL 16...	0900	86	362	8.00	26.5	1.8	8.5	107	<10	K1300	K800
SEP 05...	0855	58	365	7.61	27.0	4.6	7.6	98	<10	500	250

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NON-CARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
18...	140	9	33	13	20	0.8	2.3	127	<0.5	18	22
DEC 20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	152	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
APR 25...	150	12	35	15	25	0.9	2.7	137	<0.5	16	27
JUL 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	132	--	--	--
SEP 05...	130	11	31	13	21	0.8	2.9	120	--	18	19

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
18...	0.10	23	210	110	11	0.690	0.010	0.700	0.040	0.46
DEC 20...	--	--	--	--	5	0.980	0.020	1.00	0.050	0.35
FEB 1986										
20...	--	--	--	--	4	0.970	0.030	1.00	0.070	0.33
APR 25...	0.20	28	230	26	4	0.850	0.050	0.900	0.090	0.51
JUL 16...	--	--	--	--	9	0.580	0.020	0.600	0.030	0.37
SEP 05...	0.10	27	200	32	6	0.760	0.040	0.800	0.050	3.0

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN
50044850 RIO GUADIANA NEAR NARANJITO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'39", long 66°13'28", at steel-cross-bridge 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northwest of Highway 164, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from mouth and about 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northeast of Naranjito plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.0 sq mi (10.3 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water year 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
25...	1525	17	301	8.00	26.5	13	--	--	42	2100	2400
DEC											
20...	1045	12	304	8.30	23.5	3.0	--	--	<10	3100	600
FEB 1986											
20...	1315	6.2	302	8.65	24.5	1.3	10.2	124	24	K1000	930
APR											
25...	1335	6.4	355	8.25	30.5	1.5	8.5	113	<10	570	K130
JUL											
16...	1220	11	301	7.60	27.5	20	7.8	98	45	9300	2700
SEP											
05...	1200	7.9	355	7.80	29.5	4.4	7.7	102	<10	--	K100

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
25...	120	20	37	6.9	25	1	4.5	101	<0.5	19	42
DEC											
20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	105	--	--	--
APR											
25...	130	21	30	14	17	0.7	2.5	112	<0.5	15	24
JUL											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
SEP											
05...	140	28	31	14	17	0.7	2.6	107	--	19	21

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
25...	<0.10	14	210	9.6	16	--	0.010	<0.100	0.230	1.1
DEC										
20...	--	--	--	--	6	1.13	0.070	1.20	0.150	0.45
FEB 1986										
20...	--	--	--	--	3	1.19	0.010	1.20	0.040	0.56
APR										
25...	0.10	26	200	3.4	1	--	<0.010	1.40	0.030	0.47
JUL										
16...	--	--	--	--	39	1.99	0.010	2.00	0.050	0.75
SEP										
05...	0.10	27	200	4.2	2	1.29	0.010	1.30	<0.010	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT TOA ALTA, PR
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 66°15'39", at Highway 2, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) downstream from Rio Lajas, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest of Toa Alta, 11.3 mi (18.2 km) downstream from Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir.

DRAINAGE AREA.--208 sq mi (539 sq km), exclude 8.2 sq mi (21.2 sq km) upstream from Lago Carite, flow from which is diverted to Rio Guamani.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED SATUR- ATION	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)
OCT 1985											
16...	1630	231	296	7.60	28.0	0.60	--	--	K680	200	120
DEC											
05...	1140	224	319	7.80	25.5	17	--	--	2800	86	130
FEB 1986											
05...	1020	233	400	7.80	25.0	17	4.7	57	4300	6500	160
APR											
08...	1140	102	446	8.01	27.5	6.2	6.7	84	K2500	K160	160
JUN											
04...	1035	157	335	7.25	28.5	6.0	5.4	69	2600	K150	130
AUG											
26...	1120	15	491	7.85	30.0	3.1	9.4	125	350	82	210

DATE	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)
OCT 1985											
16...	32	34	8.3	13	0.5	2.1	87	17	18	0.10	20
DEC											
05...	9	34	10	16	0.6	2.1	117	15	22	0.10	21
FEB 1986											
05...	9	43	13	23	0.8	2.8	152	15	29	<0.10	19
APR											
08...	6	40	14	22	0.8	2.5	152	18	29	0.20	22
JUN											
04...	7	37	9.8	16	0.6	2.6	126	17	19	0.10	18
AUG											
26...	17	51	13	25	0.8	3.3	189	18	35	0.30	20

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHORUS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHORUS, ORTHO, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHATE, ORTHO, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS PO4)
OCT 1985											
16...	176	170	110	0.920	0.090	0.12	0.60	0.120	0.050	0.020	0.06
DEC											
05...	174	190	105	0.740	0.110	0.14	0.60	0.120	0.090	0.080	0.25
FEB 1986											
05...	231	240	145	0.510	0.360	0.46	0.80	0.210	0.140	0.130	0.40
APR											
08...	241	240	66	0.200	0.180	0.23	0.70	0.130	0.090	0.060	0.18
JUN											
04...	198	200	84	0.540	0.110	0.14	0.50	0.080	0.050	0.040	0.12
AUG											
26...	297	290	12	0.590	0.180	0.23	1.1	0.570	0.370	0.010	0.03

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT TOA ALTA, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	ALUM- INUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYL- LIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)
OCT 1985 16...	70	<1	42	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	4	55	2
DEC 05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 05...	20	1	50	<0.5	2	<1	<3	2	9	<1
APR 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 04...	80	1	41	<0.5	1	<1	<3	4	10	1
AUG 26...	30	2	56	<0.5	<1	2	<3	4	6	<5

DATE	LITHIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)	MANGA- NESE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRON- TIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
OCT 1985 16...	<4	53	<0.1	<10	6	<1	<1	130	6	15
DEC 05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 05...	5	240	0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1	220	8	5
APR 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 04...	4	46	0.2	<10	<1	<1	<1	160	7	8
AUG 26...	<4	140	<0.1	<10	1	<1	<1	340	7	5

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1986 04...	1035	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.09	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1986 04...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUN 1986 04...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046600 RIO DE LA PLATA AT TOA ALTA, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. e FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1985					
16...	1630	250	293	198	94
DEC					
05...	1230	251	52	35	95
APR 1986					
08...	1200	121	64	21	86
JUN					
04...	1035	152	52	21	97
AUG					
26...	1120	14	22	0.83	41

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046900 RIO DE LA PLATA AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR TOA ALTA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", Long 66°15'39", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at downstream side of bridge on Highway 2, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) downstream from Rio Lajas, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest of Toa Alta, 11.3 mi (18.2 km) downstream from Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir. Prior to September 25, 1984, at site about 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream.

DRAINAGE AREA.--208 mi² (539 km²), excludes 8.2 mi² (21.2 km²) upstream from Lago Carite, flow from which is diverted to Rio Guamani. Area at site used prior to September 25, 1984, 200 mi² (518 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1959 (measurement only), January 1960 to current year. Prior to September 1984, published as Rio de la Plata at Toa Alta, P.R.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 0.0 ft (0.0 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: May 1, 9-13. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Regulation at all stages by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir upstream from gage.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--26 years (1961-86), 281 ft³/s (7.958 m³/s), 19.08 in/yr (485 mm/yr), 203,600 acre-ft/yr (251 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 230 ft³/s (6.51 m³/s), 167,000 acre-ft/yr (210 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 95,500 ft³/s (2,700 m³/s), Sept. 6, 1960, gage height, 36.35 ft (11.079 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 12,000 ft³/s (340 m³/s) on basis of contracted-opening measurement of peak flow at site 1.0 mi upstream and different datum; minimum discharge, 2.2 ft³/s (0.062 m³/s), Apr. 25, 1984.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate discharges and elevations of major floods, as pointed out by local residents are as follows: Sept. 13, 1928, 120,000 ft³/s (3,400 m³/s), gage height, 37.4 ft (11.40 m); June 16, 1943, 82,000 ft³/s (2,320 m³/s), gage height, 34.4 ft (10.48 m), at site 1.0 mi upstream and different datum.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 6,000 ft³/s (170 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 7	0300	*74,400	2,110	*24.58	7.492	May 1	2245	6,280	178	12.85	3.917
Oct. 8	0930	9,280	263	14.94	4.554	May 13	1200	30,700	869	20.64	6.291
Oct. 26	1730	7,380	209	13.72	4.182	May 14	0615	23,900	666	19.53	5.953
Nov. 15	1915	7,720	219	13.98	4.261						

Minimum discharge, 2.6 ft³/s (0.074 m³/s), Apr. 1, 28.

DAY	DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986													
	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	119	989	268	104	27	5.9	11	3100	412	24	33	192		
2	98	617	259	115	27	6.2	9.7	1290	259	21	15	509		
3	83	677	242	110	39	6.5	10	342	194	19	15	187		
4	78	1310	244	125	71	6.3	20	197	158	18	18	89		
5	640	553	232	113	189	5.4	1100	179	142	17	23	59		
6	9880	395	264	102	114	5.7	778	110	116	28	15	55		
7	36100	347	230	97	82	6.8	191	337	103	33	17	51		
8	6210	304	203	96	74	6.3	259	392	107	17	19	45		
9	1920	271	207	170	66	6.3	1180	980	108	17	24	43		
10	854	256	211	192	59	8.5	309	1000	147	17	21	38		
11	544	282	194	120	43	8.4	120	2900	164	111	21	34		
12	418	485	192	103	28	6.9	82	800	178	61	41	26		
13	342	968	188	98	21	7.4	71	12000	181	21	126	21		
14	296	1140	188	88	13	11	57	10100	129	18	94	17		
15	264	5580	161	74	10	7.9	48	1450	221	147	35	15		
16	231	3260	156	68	11	8.2	36	705	268	174	25	13		
17	212	1220	161	76	11	7.7	20	479	145	147	20	13		
18	538	1500	142	84	9.4	10	15	526	106	79	17	12		
19	318	935	136	80	7.1	9.2	10	939	86	47	16	12		
20	392	677	134	68	7.3	9.5	15	482	78	33	20	11		
21	236	1600	129	59	10	9.3	87	339	68	26	26	15		
22	184	858	128	55	9.6	8.4	74	273	61	21	24	18		
23	244	567	128	56	13	7.8	55	223	54	18	21	22		
24	2470	468	126	57	10	9.9	42	189	47	20	24	17		
25	1340	396	109	60	8.1	13	20	169	40	21	19	26		
26	2220	354	113	68	6.6	13	11	155	34	17	16	23		
27	2250	325	114	72	5.8	13	5.6	142	34	17	16	17		
28	1260	304	110	64	5.9	9.2	3.0	451	36	21	43	20		
29	1590	295	107	51	---	8.0	391	416	32	22	2010	22		
30	1760	281	101	40	---	6.8	3210	323	27	20	704	17		
31	2140	---	98	29	---	9.2	---	347	---	44	257	---		
TOTAL	75231	27214	5275	2694	977.8	257.7	8240.3	41335	3735	1296	3775	1639		
MEAN	2427	907	170	86.9	34.9	8.31	275	1333	125	41.8	122	54.6		
MAX	36100	5580	268	192	189	13	3210	12000	412	174	2010	509		
MIN	78	256	98	29	5.8	5.4	3.0	110	27	17	15	11		
CFSM	12.1	4.53	.85	.43	.17	.04	1.37	6.66	.62	.21	.61	.27		
IN.	13.99	5.06	.98	.50	.18	.05	1.53	7.69	.69	.24	.70	.30		
AC-FT	149200	53980	10460	5340	1940	511	16340	81990	7410	2570	7490	3250		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	193796	MEAN	531	MAX	36100	MIN	10	CFSM	2.65	IN.	36.05	AC-FT	384400
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	171669.8	MEAN	470	MAX	36100	MIN	3.0	CFSM	2.35	IN.	31.93	AC-FT	340500

Figure 17.--Río Hondo to the Río Puerto Nuevo basins.

RIO HONDO BASIN

50047530 RIO HONDO AT FLOOD CHANNEL NEAR CATANO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'13", long 66°09'36", at Rio Hondo Channel, 800 ft (245 m) below junction with Rio Hondo, 0.9 mi (1.5 km) downstream from bridge on de Diego Expressway and 1.1 mi (1.8 km) above mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARDNESS AS CaCO3 (MG/L)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)
NOV 1985											
12...	1000	11000	7.40	27.0	11	--	290	>600000	33000	1300	1100
DEC 27...	1400	18000	7.60	28.5	11	--	320	2400000	58000	--	--
FEB 1986											
27...	1430	43400	7.60	31.0	7.2	0.2	3	1900	65000	<1000	--
MAY 16...	1015	13000	7.25	27.0	5.5	0.1	1	250	K9100000	77000	1000
JUL 28...	1240	14000	7.65	33.5	3.2	6.7	98	350	K120000	K17000	--
SEP 24...	1050	7200	7.45	30.0	10	0.3	4	130	K7600000	K160000	730

DATE	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS CL)	FLUORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)
NOV 1985												
12...	100	250	2000	25	73	133	<0.5	490	3700	0.40	7.6	6700
DEC 27...	--	--	--	--	--	189	--	--	6200	--	--	--
FEB 1986												
27...	--	--	--	--	--	165	--	--	19000	--	--	--
MAY 16...	110	180	1400	19	53	155	<0.5	480	2700	0.30	13	5000
JUL 28...	--	--	--	--	--	187	--	--	4800	--	--	--
SEP 24...	60	140	1200	20	54	132	--	380	2500	0.30	11	4400

DATE	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CD)
NOV 1985												
12...	0.0	30	0.010	<0.100	4.20	2.6	6.8	1.20	2	100	910	1
DEC 27...	--	30	0.010	<0.100	9.90	4.1	14	<0.010	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986												
27...	--	45	0.020	<0.100	4.70	--	--	1.60	--	--	--	--
MAY 16...	0.0	9	0.050	<0.100	4.20	2.7	6.9	1.30	2	100	630	1
JUL 28...	--	11	0.010	<0.100	7.10	3.9	11	2.10	--	--	--	--
SEP 24...	0.0	15	0.010	<0.100	4.40	2.6	7.0	1.70	--	--	--	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN
50047600 RIO DE BAYAMON NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'39", long 66°08'39", at bridge on Highway 156, and 2.9 mi (4.7 km) west of Aguas Buenas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.5 sq mi (47.9 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-65, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (PERCENT SATURATION) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1985											
24...	0950	137	151	7.60	23.5	52	--	--	19	4300	6700
DEC 09...	1445	30	243	8.00	23.5	14	--	--	<10	K7400	6000
FEB 1986											
14...	1440	30	219	8.40	21.5	5.0	9.0	106	23	430	K1400
MAY 05...	1500	14	336	8.04	27.0	3.2	7.7	99	25	450	3500
JUL 15...	0910	31	219	7.76	24.0	220	7.7	93	14	50000	23000
SEP 04...	0940	31	263	7.70	24.5	34	7.8	97	36	K800	1500

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE, TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
24...	53	4	12	5.6	9.4	0.6	2.7	49	<0.5	11	12
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	88	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	72	--	--	--
MAY 05...	120	6	28	11	13	0.5	2.1	109	<0.5	13	15
JUL 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	77	--	--	--
SEP 04...	89	2	21	8.9	14	0.7	2.7	87	--	8.5	14

DATE	FLUORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
24...	<0.10	16	98	36	51	0.360	0.040	0.400	0.080	0.52
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	7	--	<0.010	0.800	0.030	0.67
FEB 1986										
14...	--	--	--	--	3	--	<0.010	0.500	0.020	0.28
MAY 05...	<0.10	27	170	6.5	3	--	<0.010	0.700	0.010	0.39
JUL 15...	--	--	--	--	187	0.760	0.040	0.800	0.090	0.41
SEP 04...	<0.10	23	140	12	18	0.670	0.030	0.700	0.040	0.36

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047990 RIO GUAYNABO NEAR BAYAMON, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'32", long 66°07'59", at bridge on Highway 833, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Rio de Bayamón, and 2.3 mi (3.7 km) southeast of Bayamon plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--73.2 sq mi (189.6 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1964, 1971-73, 1976, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED SATUR- ATION	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
21...	1155	48	386	7.60	25.5	53	--	--	22	400000	4800
DEC											
23...	1150	26	434	7.70	24.0	1.1	--	--	18	K8900	3100
FEB 1986											
21...	1250	19	490	7.75	25.0	2.0	3.6	44	34	4000	400
APR											
23...	1250	20	506	7.08	29.0	3.2	3.3	43	37	3000	710
JUL											
22...	1230	20	460	7.40	29.0	4.5	4.1	53	35	20000	K700
SEP											
22...	1350	19	523	7.52	29.5	2.5	3.5	46	35	K15000	1400

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
21...	140	4	37	11	22	0.8	3.7	134	<0.5	12	29
DEC											
23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	156	--	--	--
APR											
23...	160	7	44	13	30	1	4.5	156	<0.5	21	43
JUL											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
SEP											
22...	150	0	41	12	32	1	5.0	163	--	16	39

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
21...	0.20	24	220	28	101	0.530	0.070	0.600	1.00	0.90
DEC										
23...	--	--	--	--	13	0.240	0.060	0.300	1.90	0.70
FEB 1986										
21...	--	--	--	--	1	0.170	0.030	0.200	2.60	1.1
APR										
23...	0.20	27	280	15	17	0.350	0.050	0.400	1.80	0.70
JUL										
22...	--	--	--	--	3	0.240	0.060	0.300	2.40	0.70
SEP										
22...	0.10	28	270	14	9	0.070	0.030	0.100	3.00	1.3

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50048510 RIO DE BAYAMON AT FLOOD CHANNEL AT BAYAMON, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'29", long 66°09'04", at bridge on Highway 890, 1.0 (1.6 km) downstream from bridge on Highway 2, and 3.2 mi (5.1 km) above mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--71.9 sq mi (186.2 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

REMARKS.--Prior to 1979 sampling site was 0.8 mile (1.3 km) downstream but was changed because of flood channel construction.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1985											
24...	1315	E450	222	7.40	24.5	4300	--	--	26	37000	36000
DEC 27...	1000	34	442	7.80	23.0	7.0	5.8	--	<10	50000	2100
FEB 1986											
21...	0955	35	458	7.60	23.0	2.1	4.6	54	50	48000	K1600
APR 23...	0940	42	485	7.24	26.0	20	4.4	54	17	K20000	40000
JUL 22...	0945	43	445	7.65	27.5	1.0	--	--	38	K85000	--
SEP 22...	1025	37	465	7.35	28.5	10	5.8	75	24	20000	--

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
24...	80	6	20	7.4	13	0.7	2.6	74	<0.5	16	15
DEC 27...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	136	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	151	--	--	--
APR 23...	150	7	39	13	24	0.9	3.6	144	<0.5	19	34
JUL 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	156	--	--	--
SEP 22...	150	0	40	13	28	1	4.1	158	--	20	31

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
24...	0.10	20	140	E170	528	0.610	0.090	0.700	0.320	0.98
DEC 27...	--	--	--	--	6	0.410	0.090	0.500	1.40	0.60
FEB 1986										
21...	--	--	--	--	9	0.290	0.110	0.400	2.00	0.80
APR 23...	0.20	24	240	27	48	0.470	0.130	0.600	1.20	0.70
JUL 22...	--	--	--	--	18	0.330	0.170	0.500	1.70	0.70
SEP 22...	0.10	27	260	26	19	0.110	0.090	0.200	2.20	0.70

E = estimate
K = non-ideal count

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50048510 RIO DE BAYAMON AT FLOOD CHANNEL AT BAYAMON, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985 24...	1.3	2.0	8.9	0.240	2	100	60	<1	15	40
DEC 27...	2.0	2.5	11	0.690	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 21...	2.8	3.2	14	0.830	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 23...	1.9	2.5	11	0.480	2	200	30	<1	20	10
JUL 22...	2.4	2.9	13	0.770	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 22...	2.9	3.1	14	0.910	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1985 24...	14000	5	450	<0.10	<1	<1	40	<0.010	<1	0.06
DEC 27...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 23...	2700	3	310	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	<1	0.11
JUL 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	ALDRIN DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DDD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DDE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DDT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DI- AZINON DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)
JUL 1986 22...	0945	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.14	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	ENDRIN, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	ETHION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	LINDANE DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	MALA- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)
JUL 1986 22...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	MIREX, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	PARA- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	PER- THANE DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	TRI- THION DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)
JUL 1986 22...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.10	<1	<0.01

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50048800 RIO PIEDRAS NEAR RIO PIEDRAS, PR
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'15", long 66°03'40", at bridge on Winston Churchill Avenue in the El Senorial Housing area, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) west of Highway 176, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) southwest of Rio Piedras plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.17 sq mi (20.9 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECALE, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
15...	1400	12	382	7.80	26.0	20	--	--	--	K8600	K83
DEC 26...	0915	9.5	364	7.90	22.0	4.0	7.8	88	<10	K21000	2500
FEB 1986											
14...	1030	6.2	377	7.60	24.0	15	--	--	13	4300	8000
APR 18...	1410	12	402	8.10	30.5	2.4	9.5	128	79	K95000	48000
JUL 18...	1110	5.5	386	7.55	29.0	--	5.7	75	--	K240000	K150000
SEP 12...	1115	6.7	417	7.65	26.0	2.0	6.4	80	51	>1000	K170000

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
15...	130	11	34	12	24	0.9	3.0	123	14	19	26
DEC 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	113	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	113	--	--	--
APR 18...	140	4	36	12	26	1	3.0	135	<0.5	15	29
JUL 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	143	--	--	--
SEP 12...	140	0	36	11	27	1	3.6	142	--	24	27

DATE	FLUORIDE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
15...	1.3	31	220	7.3	13	0.930	0.070	1.00	0.340	0.36
DEC 26...	--	--	--	--	--	1.15	0.050	1.20	0.290	0.31
FEB 1986										
14...	--	--	--	--	8	1.00	0.100	1.10	0.750	0.35
APR 18...	0.20	33	240	7.4	5	0.780	0.220	1.00	0.900	0.50
JUL 18...	--	--	--	--	--	0.600	0.100	0.700	1.40	0.90
SEP 12...	0.20	30	240	4.4	10	0.620	0.180	0.800	2.70	1.7

K = non-ideal count

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048800 RIO PIEDRAS NEAR RIO PIEDRAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985 15...	0.70	1.7	7.5	0.240	--	--	30	--	--	10
DEC 26...	0.60	1.8	8.0	0.140	--	--	--	--	--	--
26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 14...	1.1	2.2	9.7	0.280	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 18...	1.4	2.4	11	0.330	6	200	10	<1	18	<10
JUL 18...	2.3	3.0	13	0.500	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 12...	4.4	5.2	23	1.50	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1985 15...	2200	--	170	--	--	--	50	<0.010	<1	0.19
DEC 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 18...	270	3	190	<0.10	<1	<1	30	<0.010	2	0.27
JUL 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 18...	1110	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.12	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 18...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUL 1986 18...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50049100 RIO PIEDRAS AT HATO REY, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'34", long 66°04'10", at bridge on Avenida Piñero at Expreso Las Americas, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) southwest of Hato Rey.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.4 sq mi (39.9 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1971 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985										
15...	0945	17	422	7.60	26.5	2.7	--	--	17	K84000 4500
DEC 26...	1240	17	430	7.90	25.0	3.5	--	--	13	42000 20000
FEB 1986										
14...	1330	16	485	7.70	25.5	17	--	--	29	430000 33000
APR 18...	1115	4.3	464	7.80	27.5	25	6.8	87	27	K130000 K11000
JUL 18...	0915	14	396	7.65	28.0	15	6.2	80	16	31000 K1300000
SEP 12...	0835	14	422	7.80	27.0	1.8	5.7	72	10	28000 3200

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
15...	150	9	42	11	25	0.9	3.5	141	<0.5	22	27
DEC 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	131	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	156	--	--	--
APR 18...	160	8	44	12	32	1	3.7	151	<0.5	17	37
JUL 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	15	--	--	--
SEP 12...	150	5	44	10	26	1	3.5	146	--	25	29

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
15...	0.50	27	240	11	12	0.910	0.190	1.10	1.00	0.60
DEC 26...	--	--	--	--	4	1.10	0.100	1.20	0.610	0.49
FEB 1986										
14...	--	--	--	--	5	1.18	0.220	1.40	1.10	0.90
APR 18...	0.20	31	270	3.1	5	1.05	0.350	1.40	0.920	0.58
JUL 18...	--	--	--	--	12	0.770	0.130	0.900	0.190	0.51
SEP 12...	0.20	26	250	9.5	3	0.940	0.160	1.10	0.260	0.64

K = non-ideal count

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50049820 LAGUNA SAN JOSE NO. 2 AT SAN JUAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'46", long 66°02'10", 0.2 mi (0.3 km) east of Caño de Martín Peña, and 650 ft (200 m) south of Isla Guachinango.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985, TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	DEPTH AT SAMPLE LOCATION, TOTAL (FEET)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANSPARENCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, SATURATION (%)	COLIFORM, FECAL, (PERCENT) (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, (PERCENT) (COLS./100 ML)	ALKALINITY, TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO ₃)
NOV 1985											
07...	1310	1.00	10100	8.80	31.0	12.5	14.1	--	5200	<100	114
DEC 27...	0900	1.00	14600	8.80	25.5	10.5	4.4	57	K96000	4400	128
FEB 1986											
28...	0850	1.00	30700	8.24	23.0	15.0	2.2	29	K1100	<100	312
MAY 14...	1220	1.00	9500	8.80	27.5	7.20	8.2	108	45000	--	82
JUL 25...	0850	1.00	24400	8.45	30.0	14.8	0.7	10	200000	2400	136
SEP 25...	0915	1.00	26200	8.06	29.0	14.4	0.2	3	K13000	7500	147

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO ₂ +NO ₃ TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO ₃)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	CARBON, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS C)
NOV 1985											
07...	23	--	0.030	<0.100	0.290	2.2	2.5	--	--	0.550	19
DEC 27...	43	--	0.040	<0.100	1.10	4.7	5.8	--	--	0.680	16
FEB 1986											
28...	36	--	0.030	<0.100	1.10	3.3	4.4	--	--	0.950	22
MAY 14...	20	0.080	0.020	0.100	0.290	2.1	2.4	2.5	11	0.540	20
JUL 25...	34	--	0.020	<0.100	0.190	2.5	2.7	--	--	0.570	17
SEP 25...	32	--	0.010	<0.100	0.570	0.0	0.30	--	--	0.930	15

K = non-ideal count

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049920 BAHIA DE SAN JUAN NO. 5 AT SAN JUAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION--Lat 18°26'37", long 66°05'11", 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Puente de la Constitución, and 0.5 mi (0.8 km) south from U.S. Naval Reservation.

DRAINAGE--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD--Water years 1974 to present.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

WATER QUALITY DATA

DATE	TIME	DEPTH AT SAMPLE LOCATION, TOTAL (FEET)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANSPAR-ENCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, SATURATION (%)	COLIFORMS, (PER-CENT UM-MF) (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	ALKALINITY TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)
NOV 1985											
07...	1515	1.00	38200	8.00	31.0	26.3	3.8	--	K15000	K500	126
DEC											
27...	1035	1.00	41800	8.10	25.5	36.0	5.2	74	K28000	K400	127
FEB 1986											
28...	1135	1.00	44000	7.85	29.0	11.0	3.8	58	K15000	<100	107
MAY											
14...	1415	1.00	11100	7.60	26.5	7.20	4.2	54	57000	--	97
JUL											
25...	1040	1.00	12800	7.35	30.0	22.3	5.3	73	K98000	8000	108
SEP											
25...	1050	1.00	45000	7.59	29.5	34.8	2.1	32	K110000	K17000	133

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	CARBON, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS C)
NOV 1985											
07...	89	0.070	0.030	0.100	1.10	0.20	1.3	1.4	6.2	0.160	5.0
DEC											
27...	76	0.160	0.040	0.200	1.10	0.20	1.3	1.5	6.6	0.180	3.1
FEB 1986											
28...	77	0.070	0.030	0.100	0.770	0.43	1.2	1.3	5.8	0.190	4.7
MAY											
14...	70	0.260	0.040	0.300	0.680	0.82	1.5	1.8	8.0	0.280	11
JUL											
25...	16	0.310	0.090	0.400	0.880	0.62	1.5	1.9	8.4	0.290	7.5
SEP											
25...	39	--	0.030	<0.100	1.10	0.70	1.8	--	--	0.310	5.1

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50050300 QUEBRADA BLASINA NEAR CAROLINA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'27", long 65°58'28", at bridge on Highway 3, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) south of Valle Arriba Heights housing area, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) west-southwest of Carolina plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.96 sq mi (7.67 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1973 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985										
29...	1335	2370	111	6.70	28.0	850	7.8	99	69	K1100000 43000
DEC										
11...	1500	E250	250	7.90	26.0	40	7.8	<10	K150000	340
FEB 1986										
03...	1150	92	263	8.00	23.5	15	7.9	93	23	K9500 K1500
APR										
16...	1300	63	278	7.70	28.0	15	7.5	97	28	25000 K170
JUL										
15...	1055	113	211	7.65	28.5	27	7.6	99	18	K16000 440
SEP										
09...	1120	76	241	7.65	30.0	21	7.6	101	<10	20000 200

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
29...	29	0	6.5	3.0	8.0	0.7	1.0	29	<0.5	7.3	7.5
DEC											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	64	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	78	--	--	--
APR											
16...	77	0	18	7.8	23	1	2.4	80	<0.5	15	23
JUL											
15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	68	--	--	--
SEP											
09...	71	0	17	7.0	21	1	2.2	76	--	14	16

DATE	FLUORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
29...	<0.10	18	69	439	708	0.270	0.130	0.400	0.260	1.6
DEC										
11...	--	--	--	--	62	0.370	0.030	0.400	0.070	0.33
FEB 1986										
03...	--	--	--	--	34	0.450	0.050	0.500	0.140	0.46
APR										
16...	0.10	32	170	29	22	0.600	0.100	0.700	0.410	0.59
JUL										
15...	--	--	--	--	18	0.260	0.040	0.300	0.130	0.37
SEP										
09...	0.20	35	160	32	22	0.330	0.070	0.400	0.140	0.36

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50050900 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT QUEBRADA ARENAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'10", long 65°59'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at intersection of Highways 181 and 9990, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from confluence with Rio Emajagua and about 7.1 mi (11.4 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.00 mi² (15.54 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1977 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 175 ft (53 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--No estimated daily discharges during water year. Records fair.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--9 years (1978-86), 31.1 ft³/s (0.881 m³/s), 70.39 in/yr (1,788 mm/yr), 22,530 acre-ft/yr (27.78 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 11,700 ft³/s (331 m³/s), Nov. 5, 1983, gage height, 14.78 ft (4.505 m), from rating curve extended above 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 2.8 ft³/s (0.079 m³/s), May 5, 6, 1979.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,000 ft³/s (56.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1015	*3,850	109	*10.01	3.051	May 18	1115	2,950	83.5	9.21	2.807
Oct. 24	0815	2,040	57.8	8.25	2.515	May 31	0400	2,640	74.8	8.90	2.713
Apr. 29	1515	2,910	82.4	9.17	2.795	June 10	0130	2,150	60.9	8.37	2.551
May 13	0830	3,020	85.5	9.28	2.828						

Minimum discharge, 6.5 ft³/s (0.184 m³/s), Mar. 23, 24.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	76	58	16	13	11	8.5	22	20	28	16	9.9	15		
2	43	44	15	13	9.7	7.9	16	16	30	14	9.4	13		
3	63	38	15	15	13	7.8	15	19	26	14	9.0	11		
4	71	33	14	19	16	8.6	60	16	22	13	10	11		
5	80	32	18	13	16	9.6	40	13	22	13	9.3	22		
6	1250	30	17	12	11	8.6	23	41	22	23	8.5	12		
7	470	27	15	11	10	8.5	16	41	20	17	17	10		
8	151	25	14	11	9.8	7.7	20	50	20	13	16	9.6		
9	83	24	14	45	9.1	7.6	16	25	49	12	9.7	9.3		
10	64	23	15	20	8.9	7.4	12	205	214	11	9.2	8.7		
11	51	22	14	16	9.0	8.3	11	91	27	15	30	8.0		
12	43	43	23	14	9.0	8.1	11	31	23	17	12	8.0		
13	37	34	16	12	8.6	11	11	197	32	12	34	9.4		
14	34	26	14	12	8.3	14	11	138	27	12	19	8.5		
15	32	27	14	11	8.3	14	10	36	26	15	12	7.9		
16	30	26	14	11	8.3	9.2	9.9	28	25	13	11	7.6		
17	46	28	14	16	9.1	8.2	9.4	43	21	11	9.8	7.3		
18	60	83	13	15	9.1	7.7	8.7	245	18	11	9.2	7.0		
19	36	29	15	12	36	7.3	8.5	52	42	10	8.8	7.1		
20	29	29	16	12	18	7.4	8.7	37	21	9.8	8.5	7.0		
21	28	24	13	17	11	7.1	8.8	47	18	11	7.8	6.9		
22	27	21	13	12	9.8	7.0	9.6	62	17	9.7	7.9	9.9		
23	139	20	14	12	9.2	6.9	8.3	34	16	9.7	8.0	13		
24	236	19	17	26	9.0	7.0	8.5	29	16	9.1	9.5	55		
25	79	18	15	15	9.4	7.0	8.3	26	15	9.1	9.5	40		
26	160	17	14	12	8.8	10	8.7	25	15	9.2	7.9	24		
27	66	17	13	11	8.6	9.9	9.6	25	18	9.8	7.4	13		
28	45	17	13	11	8.7	11	33	24	16	9.0	89	11		
29	167	16	12	11	---	197	226	58	14	8.6	280	9.8		
30	54	17	12	11	---	26	37	25	13	18	22	9.0		
31	70	---	11	11	---	27	---	172	---	11	20	---		
TOTAL	3820	867	453	452	312.7	493.3	697.0	1871	873	386.0	731.3	391.0		
MEAN	123	28.9	14.6	14.6	11.2	15.9	23.2	60.4	29.1	12.5	23.6	13.0		
MAX	1250	83	23	45	36	197	226	245	214	23	280	55		
MIN	27	16	11	11	8.3	6.9	8.3	13	13	8.6	7.4	6.9		
CFSM	20.5	4.82	2.43	2.43	1.87	2.65	3.87	10.1	4.85	2.08	3.93	2.17		
IN.	23.68	5.38	2.81	2.80	1.94	3.06	4.32	11.60	5.41	2.39	4.53	2.42		
AC-FT	7580	1720	899	897	620	978	1380	3710	1730	766	1450	776		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	12865.5	MEAN	35.2	MAX	1250	MIN	7.5	CFSM	5.87	IN.	79.77	AC-FT	25520
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	11347.3	MEAN	31.1	MAX	1250	MIN	6.9	CFSM	5.18	IN.	70.35	AC-FT	22510

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50050900 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT QUEBRADA ARENAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
DEC, 03	1228	15	148	24.5	SEP, 16	1206	8.0	160	28.0
AUG, 20	1304	8.5	157	28.5					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'40", long 65°58'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from bridge on Highway 181, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.25 mi² (8.42 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 459 ft (140 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 8-11, Oct. 19 to Nov. 6, Nov. 25 to Dec. 2 and Sept. 15-29. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 7,400 ft³/s (210 m³/s), May 17, 1985, gage height, 14.58 ft (4.444 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 400 ft³/s (11.3 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 0.46 ft³/s (0.013 m³/s), May 8, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	2330	1,690	47.9	9.24	2.816	May 13	0815	*3,180	90.0	*11.10	3.383
May 8	1645	2,600	73.6	10.39	3.167	May 13	2400	2,610	73.9	10.41	3.173

Minimum discharge, 1.2 ft³/s (0.034 m³/s), Apr. 23-26.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	6.3	15	4.8	3.8	4.0	2.1	2.3	5.9	3.7	1.8	1.9	3.1
2	15	10	4.6	3.8	3.1	2.1	1.8	2.6	3.8	1.8	1.9	2.3
3	11	8.6	4.6	3.5	3.3	2.0	2.0	2.1	3.0	1.9	1.9	1.8
4	23	8.0	4.4	3.6	5.6	1.8	5.3	1.9	2.5	1.8	1.9	1.7
5	31	10	7.1	3.3	4.5	1.8	5.3	1.8	2.2	1.8	2.0	1.6
6	434	8.0	5.5	3.1	3.5	1.8	3.6	2.2	2.1	3.5	2.0	1.6
7	237	7.2	4.8	3.1	3.2	1.7	2.3	3.6	2.1	2.2	2.7	1.5
8	70	6.7	4.4	3.3	2.9	1.7	3.2	121	2.3	1.9	2.5	1.4
9	20	6.5	4.4	13	2.8	1.7	2.9	20	3.0	1.8	2.1	1.4
10	15	6.2	4.9	5.0	2.7	1.7	2.0	43	12	1.8	3.6	1.4
11	11	6.1	5.0	3.7	2.8	1.8	1.8	47	2.5	2.5	4.4	1.3
12	10	17	5.4	3.3	2.7	1.7	1.7	13	2.2	2.4	2.5	1.3
13	9.0	9.3	4.4	3.1	2.6	1.9	1.6	161	4.3	1.9	4.3	1.5
14	7.9	8.3	4.2	2.9	2.5	2.1	1.5	78	4.7	2.4	3.5	1.4
15	7.1	32	4.2	2.9	2.4	3.4	1.6	7.3	3.2	2.1	2.4	1.3
16	6.9	15	4.0	2.8	2.4	1.8	1.7	4.7	3.0	1.9	2.1	1.4
17	6.9	14	3.9	4.7	2.5	1.6	1.6	4.0	3.0	1.8	1.9	1.3
18	49	48	4.0	3.2	2.7	1.5	1.4	17	2.4	1.8	1.8	1.4
19	110	15	4.0	2.8	2.7	1.5	1.4	6.8	2.7	1.9	1.8	1.3
20	10	13	4.3	2.6	2.4	1.5	1.6	4.6	2.2	2.0	1.6	1.3
21	8.0	15	4.0	2.8	2.4	1.4	1.6	4.0	2.1	2.2	1.6	1.4
22	7.0	9.1	3.8	2.6	2.2	1.4	1.4	3.7	2.0	1.9	1.8	1.5
23	70	8.0	3.8	2.5	2.2	1.4	1.3	2.8	1.9	1.8	2.1	1.7
24	80	7.0	3.9	2.7	2.2	1.4	1.3	2.5	1.9	1.8	1.9	12
25	40	6.4	3.9	2.4	2.2	1.6	1.3	2.2	1.8	1.8	1.8	8.0
26	45	6.0	3.7	2.3	2.2	1.9	1.3	2.2	1.8	1.8	1.8	3.5
27	25	5.6	3.6	2.2	2.1	1.6	1.6	2.1	1.8	1.8	1.8	2.5
28	19	5.4	3.7	2.2	2.2	1.4	2.4	2.1	1.8	1.9	5.9	1.8
29	34	5.0	3.5	6.3	---	4.6	35	2.6	1.8	1.8	77	1.7
30	20	5.4	3.4	3.4	---	2.3	5.1	2.1	1.8	2.5	4.1	1.8
31	45	---	3.4	9.2	---	2.1	---	26	---	2.2	2.5	---
TOTAL	1483.1	336.8	133.6	116.1	79.0	58.3	98.9	599.8	85.6	62.5	151.1	67.2
MEAN	47.8	11.2	4.31	3.75	2.82	1.88	3.30	19.3	2.85	2.02	4.87	2.24
MAX	434	48	7.1	13	5.6	4.6	35	161	12	3.5	77	12
MIN	6.3	5.0	3.4	2.2	2.1	1.4	1.3	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.6	1.3
CFSM	14.7	3.45	1.33	1.15	.87	.58	1.02	5.94	.88	.62	1.50	.69
IN.	16.98	3.86	1.53	1.33	.90	.67	1.13	6.87	.98	.72	1.73	.77
AC-FT	2940	668	265	230	157	116	196	1190	170	124	300	133

CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	3895.48	MEAN	10.7	MAX	434	MIN	.51	CFSM	3.29	IN.	44.59	AC-FT	7730
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	3272.0	MEAN	8.96	MAX	434	MIN	1.3	CFSM	2.76	IN.	37.45	AC-FT	6490

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued
WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--JANUARY 1985 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
DEC, 03	1014	4.7	256	24.0					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'24", long 65°58'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left downstream side of bridge on Highway 181, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Rio Grande de Loiza, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.74 mi² (9.69 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 330 ft (100 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 8-22, Apr. 12-15 and Aug. 31 to Sept. 22. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 9,320 ft³/s (264 m³/s), May 17, 1985, gage height, 17.10 ft (5.212 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 0.69 ft³/s (0.020 m³/s), Apr. 9-13, 15, 16, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 6	1045	1,980	56.1	10.39	3.167	May 13	0815	*4,070	115	*13.17	4.014
May 8	1645	1,450	41.1	9.37	2.856	May 14	0015	1,480	41.9	9.43	2.874

Minimum discharge, 1.0 ft³/s (0.028 m³/s), July 23-26, Aug. 4-7, 22, 27, 28.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	5.1	15	2.9	3.0	3.4	1.3	1.8	2.9	6.2	1.7	1.4	3.5		
2	7.3	9.6	2.8	3.3	2.4	1.3	1.4	1.9	5.8	1.7	1.5	2.0		
3	9.2	7.6	3.4	2.7	2.7	1.1	2.7	1.7	5.2	2.2	1.2	1.8		
4	16	6.5	4.2	3.0	2.4	1.2	2.6	1.6	3.7	1.6	1.1	1.7		
5	28	8.4	6.8	2.6	2.4	1.4	6.2	1.5	3.2	1.5	1.0	3.0		
6	353	6.5	5.8	2.5	2.0	1.3	3.3	2.6	2.8	3.0	1.1	2.0		
7	143	5.3	4.9	2.4	2.0	1.3	1.7	6.3	2.8	1.9	1.8	1.7		
8	26	4.8	4.2	2.6	1.9	1.2	4.4	74	2.7	1.5	2.2	1.5		
9	20	4.4	4.1	10	1.8	1.2	2.4	15	13	1.4	1.5	1.3		
10	13	4.3	4.1	5.5	1.8	1.2	1.5	27	34	1.4	2.8	1.2		
11	10	4.2	4.4	3.6	1.9	1.3	1.4	32	4.1	1.7	7.5	1.3		
12	8.0	16	4.2	2.9	1.9	1.2	1.3	12	3.2	2.0	2.2	1.1		
13	6.6	7.9	3.7	2.8	1.7	1.4	1.5	146	9.2	1.4	8.6	1.5		
14	5.8	12	3.5	2.6	1.6	1.5	1.3	100	9.6	1.5	4.7	1.2		
15	5.4	72	3.6	2.5	1.6	5.8	1.2	15	4.1	1.7	2.3	1.1		
16	5.0	22	3.5	2.4	1.6	1.8	1.5	7.8	3.7	1.4	1.7	1.2		
17	5.2	14	3.3	7.2	1.7	1.5	1.6	5.5	3.1	1.4	1.4	1.2		
18	10	56	3.4	3.3	1.8	1.4	1.2	26	2.6	1.4	1.3	1.1		
19	5.6	13	3.4	2.6	1.7	1.4	1.2	12	3.2	1.2	1.3	1.1		
20	5.2	9.6	3.7	2.5	1.5	1.3	1.2	7.2	2.4	1.3	1.2	1.1		
21	5.0	22	3.2	2.6	1.5	1.3	1.3	5.6	1.9	1.5	1.1	1.2		
22	4.9	7.3	3.0	2.4	1.4	1.3	1.2	4.8	1.7	1.2	3.0	1.1		
23	86	5.6	3.2	2.0	1.4	1.3	1.2	4.0	1.8	1.1	1.7	1.7		
24	94	4.6	3.5	2.1	1.4	1.3	1.2	3.3	2.1	1.1	1.4	1.2		
25	40	4.1	3.3	2.0	1.4	1.6	1.2	3.1	1.8	1.2	2.1	9.7		
26	45	3.8	3.1	1.9	1.4	2.0	1.2	2.9	1.8	1.1	1.2	3.9		
27	30	3.5	2.8	1.8	1.3	1.5	1.7	2.7	1.8	1.3	1.1	3.0		
28	19	3.3	2.8	1.8	1.4	1.3	3.3	2.6	1.8	1.5	3.8	2.0		
29	34	3.1	2.6	2.9	---	5.2	36	4.5	1.6	1.4	73	1.7		
30	21	3.2	2.5	2.3	---	1.8	6.9	3.4	1.6	2.7	5.9	1.6		
31	57	---	2.5	11	---	1.7	---	26	---	1.9	2.5	---		
TOTAL	1123.3	359.6	112.4	102.8	51.0	51.4	96.6	560.9	142.5	48.9	144.6	69.5		
MEAN	36.2	12.0	3.63	3.32	1.82	1.66	3.22	18.1	4.75	1.58	4.66	2.32		
MAX	353	72	6.8	11	3.4	5.8	36	146	34	3.0	73	12		
MIN	4.9	3.1	2.5	1.8	1.3	1.1	1.2	1.5	1.6	1.1	1.0	1.1		
CFSM	9.68	3.21	.97	.89	.49	.44	.86	4.84	1.27	.42	1.25	.62		
IN.	11.17	3.58	1.12	1.02	.51	.51	.96	5.58	1.42	.49	1.44	.69		
AC-FT	2230	713	223	204	101	102	192	1110	283	97	287	138		
CAL YR 1985 TOTAL	3790.23			10.4	MAX	400	MIN	.89	CFSM	2.78	IN.	37.70	AC-FT	7520
WTR YR 1986 TOTAL	2863.5			7.85	MAX	353	MIN	1.0	CFSM	2.10	IN.	28.48	AC-FT	5680

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS FEBRUARY 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
DEC, 13	1446	4.4	378	25.0					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'13", long 65°57'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at downstream side on bridge on Highway 912, at Barrio Cerro Gordo, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) south of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--10.2 mi² (26.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1977 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 490 ft (150 m), from topographic map. Prior to Oct. 1, 1983, at site 2,000 ft (610 m) downstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Dec. 25 to Jan. 21, May 1-9, May 21-30, June 1-9, Aug. 17-29 and Sept. 24 to Oct. 2. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--9 years (1978-86), 49.5 ft³/s (1.402 m³/s), 65.90 in/yr (1,674 mm/yr), 35,860 acre-ft/yr (44.22 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 13,200 ft³/s (374 m³/s), Aug. 31, 1979, gage height, 9.44 ft (2.877 m), site and datum then in use, from rating curve extended above 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) on the basis of slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 7.1 ft³/s (0.201 m³/s), Feb. 4, May 3, 1981, Apr. 12, 13, 16, 17, 1983.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2.500 ft³/s (70.8 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1045	4,040	114	15.49	4.721	May 14	0145	2,510	71.1	13.24	4.036
Apr. 29	1545	4,110	116	15.59	4.752	May 18	1130	*4,190	119	*15.69	4.782

Minimum discharge, 11 ft³/s (0.312 m³/s), Apr. 25, 26.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	60	98	40	30	18	15	62	25	20	30	23	24		
2	67	87	41	35	17	14	26	20	28	22	20	16		
3	61	83	37	40	17	16	15	25	23	22	18	14		
4	70	75	31	50	28	17	19	17	21	19	18	16		
5	101	77	44	35	39	20	38	24	22	19	17	41		
6	1530	65	45	27	20	19	31	38	20	65	16	19		
7	664	61	39	25	18	17	16	40	18	35	33	17		
8	171	59	36	30	19	15	28	48	16	23	51	15		
9	76	56	37	74	18	16	58	22	28	20	20	16		
10	58	56	38	60	19	16	16	254	217	19	26	14		
11	45	59	35	30	21	18	13	208	21	46	61	13		
12	48	84	60	22	19	17	14	65	16	37	22	13		
13	49	88	42	21	16	25	16	346	29	24	42	19		
14	37	68	38	25	19	27	15	495	39	26	51	24		
15	30	84	40	23	18	37	15	62	52	37	25	15		
16	35	72	39	27	18	16	15	38	55	27	18	17		
17	55	67	33	41	21	14	15	28	40	25	17	17		
18	68	141	31	27	22	14	15	591	29	25	16	18		
19	51	66	34	20	63	15	15	88	35	21	15	19		
20	35	64	36	19	31	16	14	37	28	22	15	18		
21	38	59	33	30	20	16	15	30	23	27	14	17		
22	37	48	35	24	18	15	15	60	21	20	15	23		
23	360	44	46	19	17	15	14	30	19	19	16	45		
24	644	42	53	23	15	15	16	26	17	20	15	70		
25	173	40	35	18	15	14	13	24	16	18	14	50		
26	120	41	32	16	16	20	13	23	19	18	13	30		
27	117	41	30	15	19	16	18	24	25	21	12	17		
28	105	39	32	24	15	13	45	22	27	24	80	15		
29	277	39	31	20	---	174	693	60	20	21	200	14		
30	124	44	32	22	---	51	81	23	19	63	59	13		
31	150	---	28	20	---	27	---	273	---	38	36	---		
TOTAL	5456	1947	1163	892	596	740	1379	3066	963	853	998	659		
MEAN	176	64.9	37.5	28.8	21.3	23.9	46.0	98.9	32.1	27.5	32.2	22.0		
MAX	1530	141	60	74	63	174	693	591	217	65	200	70		
MIN	30	39	28	15	15	13	13	17	16	18	12	13		
CFSM	17.3	6.36	3.68	2.82	2.09	2.34	4.51	9.70	3.15	2.70	3.16	2.16		
IN.	19.90	7.10	4.24	3.25	2.17	2.70	5.03	11.18	3.51	3.11	3.64	2.40		
AC-FT	10820	3860	2310	1770	1180	1470	2740	6080	1910	1690	1980	1310		
CAL YR 1985 TOTAL	22203		MEAN	60.8	MAX	1890	MIN	15	CFSM	5.96	IN.	80.98	AC-FT	44040
WTR YR 1986 TOTAL	18712		MEAN	51.3	MAX	1530	MIN	12	CFSM	5.03	IN.	68.24	AC-FT	37120

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
DEC, 04	1301	34	128	24.0	SEP, 16	0955	17	141	26.0
AUG, 20	1010	15	140	27.0					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'10", long 66°02'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at right upstream end of bridge on Highway 765, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) south of Villa Borinquen, and 7.3 mi (11.7 km) upstream from Rio Grande de Loiza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.89 mi² (20.44 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 430 ft (131 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 6, 7, Feb. 16 to Mar. 11, Mar. 16-24, May 2-6, May 21 to June 9, July 13, 14 and Sept. 18-23. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 11,600 ft³/s (328 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 17.06 ft (5.200 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 4.0 ft³/s (0.113 m³/s), May 6, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 6	1600	*6,160	174	*13.27	4.045	May 13	2345	3,700	105	10.95	3.338
May 8	1630	2,920	82.7	10.11	3.082	Aug 29	0115	1,700	48.1	8.47	2.582

Minimum daily discharge, 6.0 ft³/s (0.170 m³/s), Mar. 22, 23.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	61	44	21	17	14	8.0	11	19	25	12	15	16
2	54	39	20	17	13	8.0	9.8	13	30	11	15	15
3	54	36	20	18	25	8.2	15	18	23	12	16	14
4	58	33	20	21	19	9.0	20	13	20	10	16	13
5	70	35	22	17	17	10	20	12	23	11	15	19
6	989	31	20	15	14	8.4	17	11	20	31	14	13
7	338	30	20	15	14	7.8	13	26	19	13	17	10
8	255	29	19	15	13	7.4	12	157	17	10	23	8.4
9	134	29	19	27	13	7.0	9.8	42	20	9.5	17	9.1
10	93	28	19	17	12	8.0	9.7	50	100	8.3	20	8.5
11	73	27	19	14	12	7.0	9.3	67	20	22	44	8.4
12	65	59	25	14	12	6.9	9.2	31	17	15	24	9.9
13	61	33	19	14	11	7.6	8.8	251	30	11	79	11
14	58	45	18	13	9.0	8.2	8.8	151	32	16	68	9.4
15	57	85	18	13	8.2	10	11	29	29	17	40	8.6
16	56	51	17	12	8.4	6.4	11	18	34	14	30	7.9
17	58	43	17	16	8.8	7.0	10	18	23	12	22	7.0
18	81	73	17	14	35	6.6	10	120	18	12	19	6.8
19	59	47	17	13	25	6.4	11	29	26	11	14	6.8
20	54	42	17	13	15	6.4	11	16	16	14	11	6.6
21	53	52	17	13	10	6.2	11	15	14	14	9.7	6.2
22	52	34	16	11	9.2	6.0	13	60	14	8.4	17	6.6
23	152	30	16	8.9	8.8	6.0	11	30	13	9.8	14	8.0
24	131	27	18	12	8.4	7.0	11	26	12	12	18	57
25	85	25	18	9.0	9.0	9.1	11	24	11	13	10	31
26	137	24	17	8.5	8.4	9.6	11	23	11	9.0	8.6	16
27	82	23	16	7.3	8.6	8.7	13	24	12	14	6.8	11
28	67	21	17	7.6	8.4	8.8	17	22	12	17	67	9.5
29	95	21	16	18	---	26	75	56	12	12	270	8.3
30	60	22	15	13	---	13	48	22	11	14	27	9.2
31	60	---	15	16	---	12	---	90	---	16	20	---
TOTAL	3702	1118	565	439.3	369.2	266.7	458.4	1483	664	411.0	987.1	371.2
MEAN	119	37.3	18.2	14.2	13.2	8.60	15.3	47.8	22.1	13.3	31.8	12.4
MAX	989	85	25	27	35	26	75	251	100	31	270	57
MIN	52	21	15	7.3	8.2	6.0	8.8	11	11	8.3	6.8	6.2
CFSM	15.1	4.73	2.31	1.80	1.67	1.09	1.94	6.06	2.80	1.69	4.03	1.57
IN.	17.45	5.27	2.66	2.07	1.74	1.26	2.16	6.99	3.13	1.94	4.65	1.75
AC-FT	7340	2220	1120	871	732	529	909	2940	1320	815	1960	736
CAL YR 1985 TOTAL	12044.8			MEAN 33.0	MAX 1300	MIN 4.8	CFSM 4.18	IN. 56.79	AC-FT 23890			
WTR YR 1986 TOTAL	10834.9			MEAN 29.7	MAX 989	MIN 6.0	CFSM 3.76	IN. 51.08	AC-FT 21490			

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS JANUARY 1985 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
DEC, 04	0955	20	153	22.5					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR

LOCATION ---Lat 18°14'33", long 66°00'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank 250 ft (76 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 189, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) downstream from Rio Turabo, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) east of Plaza de Caguas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--89.8 mi² (232.6 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1959 (low-flow measurement only), February to November 1959 (monthly measurements only), December 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 143.28 ft (43.672 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Jan. 7-12. Records fair except those for points of estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGES.--26 years (1961-86), 224 ft³/s (6.344 m³/s), 33.87 in/yr (860 mm/yr), 162,300 acre-ft/yr (200 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 215 ft³/s (6.09 m³/s), 156,000 acre-ft/yr (192 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 71,500 ft³/s (2,020 m³/s), Sept. 6, 1960, gage height, 31.17 ft (9.501 m), from rating curve extended above 6,000 ft³/s (170 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement; minimum daily discharge, 10 ft³/s (0.283 m³/s), Apr. 5, 10, 29, 1968.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 8,000 ft³/s (227 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	2400	*22,800	646	*19.80	6.035	May 13	0945	16,700	473	16.75	5.105
Apr. 29	1715	9,900	280	13.90	4.237	May 18	1330	8,480	240	13.17	4.014
May 8	1730	14,520	411	15.91	4.849						

Minimum discharge, 27 ft³/s (0.765 m³/s), Apr. 25, 26.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	329	456	185	117	101	61	142	278	222	103	76	165		
2	411	376	176	147	78	54	97	144	177	103	83	247		
3	379	334	172	128	98	51	110	102	203	103	67	117		
4	461	308	164	156	143	53	238	98	160	93	66	101		
5	749	314	202	140	182	65	226	95	132	88	65	143		
6	8560	285	198	115	100	64	198	160	118	179	54	109		
7	7600	258	180	105	83	57	98	545	115	129	61	99		
8	2190	244	161	200	79	48	162	1980	135	98	146	83		
9	908	238	164	450	80	51	193	630	363	85	68	78		
10	672	226	165	190	68	51	83	1060	946	80	62	75		
11	530	221	167	150	67	57	61	1310	203	118	218	65		
12	447	335	193	120	71	64	52	308	160	155	113	61		
13	396	447	180	110	72	69	48	2870	249	100	131	64		
14	363	457	157	100	61	84	44	1320	280	100	241	84		
15	338	1630	153	100	66	195	51	457	178	121	115	55		
16	323	581	146	96	60	100	87	292	245	121	82	46		
17	398	352	135	156	60	64	57	238	194	95	63	41		
18	675	1270	138	140	77	54	37	1940	168	89	55	34		
19	455	391	147	104	105	48	33	482	222	81	52	29		
20	319	358	153	87	113	46	93	296	174	77	46	29		
21	297	893	136	105	76	44	62	266	147	90	43	31		
22	289	310	133	102	65	39	39	289	132	75	46	37		
23	2020	273	130	89	70	36	42	206	126	67	115	61		
24	2760	253	140	109	58	37	33	180	126	65	94	549		
25	1060	234	130	122	58	35	32	160	103	69	81	350		
26	1450	223	132	88	58	61	28	150	103	66	58	211		
27	807	215	117	78	58	57	39	138	126	65	49	130		
28	512	204	118	76	59	40	124	132	121	76	136	89		
29	1260	197	113	94	---	480	1830	180	108	66	2940	63		
30	552	194	111	102	---	180	460	163	100	99	316	54		
31	944	---	105	95	---	108	---	1040	---	136	215	---		
TOTAL	38454	12077	4701	3971	2266	2453	4799	17509	5841	2992	5957	3300		
MEAN	1240	403	152	128	80.9	79.1	160	565	195	96.5	192	110		
MAX	8560	1630	202	450	182	480	1830	2870	946	179	2940	549		
MIN	289	194	105	76	58	35	28	95	100	65	43	29		
CFSM	13.8	4.49	1.69	1.43	.90	.88	1.78	6.29	2.17	1.07	2.14	1.22		
IN.	15.93	5.00	1.95	1.65	.94	1.02	1.99	7.25	2.42	1.24	2.47	1.37		
AC-FT	76270	23950	9320	7880	4490	4870	9520	34730	11590	5930	11820	6550		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	123626	MEAN	339	MAX	10400	MIN	23	CFSM	3.78	IN.	51.21	AC-FT	245200
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	104320	MEAN	286	MAX	8560	MIN	28	CFSM	3.18	IN.	43.21	AC-FT	206900

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATURATION (%)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
29...	1335	2370	111	6.70	28.0	850	7.8	99	69	54000	43000
DEC 11...	1500	E250	250	7.90	26.0	40	7.8	96	<10	K150000	340
FEB 1986											
03...	1150	92	263	8.00	23.5	15	7.9	93	23	K9500	K1500
APR 16...	1300	63	278	7.70	28.0	15	7.5	97	28	25000	K170
JUL 15...	1055	113	211	7.65	28.5	27	7.6	99	18	K16000	440
SEP 09...	1120	76	241	7.65	30.0	21	7.6	101	<10	20000	200

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WH WAT TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
29...	29	0	6.5	3.0	8.0	0.7	1.0	29	<0.5	7.3	7.5
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	64	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	78	--	--	--
APR 16...	77	0	18	7.8	23	1	2.4	80	<0.5	15	23
JUL 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	68	--	--	--
SEP 09...	71	0	17	7.0	21	1	2.2	76	--	14	16

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
29...	<0.10	18	69	439	708	0.270	0.130	0.400	0.260	1.6
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	62	0.370	0.030	0.400	0.070	0.33
FEB 1986										
03...	--	--	--	--	34	0.450	0.050	0.500	0.140	0.46
APR 16...	0.10	32	170	29	22	0.600	0.100	0.700	0.410	0.59
JUL 15...	--	--	--	--	18	0.260	0.040	0.300	0.130	0.37
SEP 09...	0.20	35	160	32	22	0.330	0.070	0.400	0.140	0.36

E = estimate
K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055250 RIO CAGUITAS AT HIGHWAY 30 AT CAGUAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'11", long 66°01'26", at Highway 30 bridge, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) east of Caguas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--14.1 sq mi (36.5 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
16...	1645	28	540	7.10	30.0	6.7	5.2	--	47	70000	5400
DEC											
16...	1355	38	750	7.70	25.0	3.5	5.2	--	120	23000	K1000
FEB 1986											
18...	1315	21	660	7.60	26.5	10	4.4	--	80	<1000	<1000
APR											
22...	1305	22	592	7.60	29.5	8.0	4.8	64	76	46000	<1000
JUL											
15...	1340	61	386	7.45	30.5	40	3.6	48	55	2000000	K110000
SEP											
15...	1325	24	616	7.65	31.0	9.0	4.3	58	75	K1330000	K110000

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WH WAT TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
16...	150	19	40	13	38	1	4.6	134	<0.5	45	40
DEC											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	164	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	156	--	--	--
APR											
22...	150	8	40	12	40	1	6.5	141	<0.5	52	43
JUL											
15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	121	--	--	--
SEP											
15...	150	0	39	12	51	2	6.9	164	--	59	55

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITU- ENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
16...	0.30	27	290	22	10	0.600	0.100	0.700	6.00	2.1
DEC										
16...	--	--	--	--	10	0.490	0.210	0.700	15.0	2.0
FEB 1986										
18...	--	--	--	--	20	0.590	0.310	0.900	10.0	3.0
APR										
22...	0.30	29	310	18	22	0.890	0.210	1.10	9.20	--
JUL										
15...	--	--	--	--	16	0.440	0.160	0.600	5.70	4.1
SEP										
15...	0.90	29	350	23	13	1.25	0.250	1.50	10.0	7.0

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50055400 RIO BAIROA NEAR CAGUAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'28", Long 66°02'13", at bridge on Highway 1, about 2.5 mi (4.0 km) upstream from Rio Grande de Loiza, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) north of Caguas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.4 sq mi (14.0 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1962-66, 1973-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
16...	1345	11	401	7.70	30.0	2.5	0.5	--	38	310000	68000
DEC 16...	1130	8.6	395	8.00	23.0	4.1	7.8	--	<10	28000	3000
FEB 1986											
18...	1115	7.2	458	7.40	23.5	10	0	--	99	K2000000	130000
APR 21...	1220	5.6	348	7.80	25.5	39	8.0	99	29	40000	450000
JUL 16...	0910	5.1	377	7.65	25.5	12	8.4	104	<10	K9700	K1800
SEP 10...	0900	4.5	412	7.90	26.0	1.5	8.2	102	15	2400	2700

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
16...	140	0	34	14	24	0.9	4.6	156	<0.5	23	34
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	121	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	141	--	--	--
APR 21...	120	16	28	12	18	0.7	4.3	103	<0.5	16	23
JUL 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	121	--	--	--
SEP 10...	150	13	35	14	24	0.9	4.2	132	--	19	37

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
16...	0.20	29	260	7.6	3	1.29	0.110	1.40	1.20	1.0
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	2	1.78	0.020	1.80	0.060	0.34
FEB 1986										
18...	--	--	--	--	12	1.25	0.050	1.30	3.80	3.4
APR 21...	0.20	23	190	2.8	52	1.33	0.070	1.40	0.150	0.45
JUL 16...	--	--	--	--	17	0.980	0.020	1.00	0.100	0.50
SEP 10...	0.20	27	240	2.9	6	1.19	0.010	1.20	0.080	0.32

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055650 QUEBRADA CAIMITO NEAR JUNCOS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'08", long 65°52'12", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at upstream side of bridge on Highway 31, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Rio Gurabo, and 3.5 mi (5.6 km) east of Juncos.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.82 mi² (2.12 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 310 ft (95 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 13-16, Apr. 15 to May 8 and June 29 to July 15. Records poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 992 ft³/s (28.1 m³/s), Oct. 6, 1985, gage height, 13.37 ft (4.075 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, no flow many days in each year.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 150 ft³/s (4.25 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1745	*992	28.1	*13.37	4.075	May 13	0815	339	9.60	10.53	3.210
Oct. 7	0300	254	7.19	10.13	3.088	Aug. 28	2400	331	9.37	10.49	3.197
Oct. 18	1445	170	4.81	9.69	2.954	Aug. 29	0200	240	6.80	10.06	3.066
May 9	1630	414	11.7	10.87	3.313						

No flow many days.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	3.6	3.3	.51	.37	.19	.13	.17	.09	2.4	.00	.15	2.9		
2	21	2.5	.46	.35	.24	.12	.13	.06	1.6	.01	.05	1.9		
3	4.3	1.9	.40	.31	.48	.12	.11	.05	1.1	.02	.04	1.1		
4	8.0	1.5	.37	.36	.70	.14	.17	.03	.55	.01	.02	.75		
5	7.3	1.3	.61	.30	.32	.12	1.6	.03	.45	.00	.00	.58		
6	136	1.1	.51	.27	.19	.14	.53	.04	.27	.50	.00	1.5		
7	71	.99	.36	.27	.18	.13	.17	.38	.25	.13	.01	.67		
8	14	.80	.30	.27	.19	.11	.15	.35	.20	.04	.01	.28		
9	5.8	.76	.28	1.4	.18	.12	.14	11	1.2	.02	.00	.15		
10	3.3	.68	.24	.43	.18	.12	.10	5.8	.25	.00	.00	.11		
11	2.3	.82	.22	.27	.21	.16	.09	6.7	.15	.01	.34	.09		
12	1.7	2.4	.22	.24	.20	.13	.09	2.4	.12	.04	.03	.07		
13	1.0	4.4	.22	.25	.18	.17	.08	32	.12	.01	.01	.71		
14	.70	1.6	.23	.24	.16	.32	.07	23	.14	.02	.03	.25		
15	.50	30	.29	.20	.12	.41	.06	4.6	.14	.11	.00	.07		
16	.35	11	.24	.24	.12	.09	.05	1.7	.19	.03	.30	.04		
17	.33	3.7	.26	.27	.14	.08	.05	.70	.15	.01	.02	.00		
18	11	3.7	.26	.25	.12	.08	.04	1.0	.12	.00	.01	.00		
19	3.5	2.1	.27	.24	.12	.08	.03	.51	.11	.00	.00	.00		
20	1.6	1.4	.23	.22	.13	.09	.04	.27	.09	.00	.00	.00		
21	.94	2.2	.22	.25	.10	.08	.04	.27	.07	.00	.00	.00		
22	.65	1.1	.24	.23	.12	.07	.03	.25	.06	.00	.00	.00		
23	8.3	.91	.22	.28	.13	.09	.03	.18	.05	.00	.00	.05		
24	23	1.0	.22	.39	.14	.09	.03	.14	.04	.00	.00	.02		
25	13	.75	.35	.30	.17	.12	.02	.11	.03	.00	.00	.03		
26	5.3	.64	.26	.26	.15	.14	.02	.11	.03	.00	.00	.01		
27	3.4	.60	.22	.24	.13	.13	.10	.10	.08	.00	.00	.00		
28	2.8	.51	.25	.22	.13	.10	.20	.09	.03	.00	7.4	.00		
29	7.0	.51	.30	.21	---	.59	3.0	.09	.02	.11	28	.00		
30	4.2	.52	.31	.25	---	.14	1.0	.09	.01	5.0	4.8	.00		
31	4.4	---	.31	.21	---	.21	---	6.1	---	1.1	5.0	---		
TOTAL	370.27	84.69	9.38	9.59	5.42	4.62	8.34	98.24	10.02	7.17	46.22	11.28		
MEAN	11.9	2.82	.30	.31	.19	.15	.28	3.17	.33	.23	1.49	.38		
MAX	136	30	.61	1.4	.70	.59	3.0	32	2.4	5.0	28	2.9		
MIN	.33	.51	.22	.20	.10	.07	.02	.03	.01	.00	.00	.00		
CFSM	14.5	3.44	.37	.38	.23	.18	.34	3.87	.40	.28	1.82	.46		
IN.	16.80	3.84	.43	.44	.25	.21	.38	4.46	.45	.33	2.10	.51		
AC-FT	734	168	19	19	11	9.2	17	195	20	14	92	22		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	809.00	MEAN	2.22	MAX	136	MIN	.00	CFSM	2.71	IN.	36.70	AC-FT	1600
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	665.24	MEAN	1.82	MAX	136	MIN	.00	CFSM	2.22	IN.	30.18	AC-FT	1320

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055650 QUEBRADA CAIMITO NR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS JUNE 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
DEC, 05	1232	1.5	342	25.5	SEP, 15	1235	0.07	351	32.0

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'58", long 65°55'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank at Highway 919, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Quebrada Don Victor, 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from Rio Gurabo and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) south of Juncos.

DRAINAGE AREA.--16.4 mi² (42.5 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1971 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 320 ft (98 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Mar. 7-12. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--15 years (1972-86), 51.3 ft³/s (1.453 m³/s), 42.48 in/yr (1,079 mm/yr), 37,170 acre-ft/yr (45.8 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 52 ft³/s (1.47 m³/s), 37,700 acre-ft/yr (46 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 25,700 ft³/s (728 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 21.30 ft (6.492 m), from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement and step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 2.0 ft³/s (0.057 m³/s), May 11, 1984.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate discharges (no stages were recorded) of major floods are as follows: Sept. 6, 1960, 37,100 ft³/s (1,050 m³/s); Oct. 9, 1970, 18,200 ft³/s (515 m³/s).

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,400 ft³/s (96.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 6	1130	*7,460	211	*11.32	3.450	May 13	0830	4,280	121	8.49	2.588
Oct. 7	2330	3,800	108	8.05	2.454	May 14	0100	5,490	155	9.65	2.941
Oct. 24	1745	5,690	161	9.84	2.999						

Minimum discharge, 6.3 ft³/s (0.178 m³/s), Apr. 25.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	46	90	29	24	13	8.8	64	22	42	25	20	22		
2	79	79	31	27	13	9.0	17	16	57	21	18	19		
3	79	63	29	22	12	9.1	13	14	53	22	13	16		
4	77	58	27	22	15	9.3	29	16	35	20	14	15		
5	180	64	41	20	15	11	28	12	32	19	12	15		
6	2920	55	38	18	12	11	23	20	27	40	12	16		
7	1420	50	30	18	11	9.0	14	88	54	30	18	15		
8	428	45	26	17	11	8.6	23	69	107	20	42	13		
9	136	42	25	35	11	9.0	46	49	141	19	19	12		
10	95	40	26	27	11	8.8	14	308	204	17	20	12		
11	76	44	25	20	12	9.4	11	215	51	19	33	11		
12	66	56	34	18	12	8.8	11	53	42	20	17	11		
13	59	51	25	17	11	11	10	851	79	17	50	12		
14	53	51	23	16	10	13	9.5	831	68	24	49	18		
15	50	385	24	16	10	38	9.3	89	46	24	25	12		
16	51	130	23	17	10	13	9.5	61	54	19	18	11		
17	72	74	22	61	12	11	9.1	54	34	18	16	11		
18	201	200	24	24	16	8.2	9.0	417	33	18	14	9.5		
19	80	63	23	19	12	8.2	8.6	127	49	16	14	9.7		
20	56	54	26	17	12	8.2	8.4	69	31	16	13	9.5		
21	55	50	22	18	11	8.3	8.3	66	28	16	12	9.0		
22	47	41	22	16	11	8.8	7.8	63	26	15	11	11		
23	453	40	22	15	9.9	8.5	7.4	42	25	20	11	12		
24	1050	37	25	17	9.7	7.4	7.9	36	24	18	11	33		
25	208	34	21	16	11	8.3	7.1	32	22	15	11	26		
26	150	31	23	16	11	17	7.1	29	23	14	9.8	16		
27	104	31	21	14	9.6	8.8	10	29	26	16	9.5	13		
28	77	30	21	14	9.0	9.8	21	26	23	17	27	15		
29	478	30	19	13	---	93	365	25	21	14	386	12		
30	112	30	18	14	---	18	60	23	21	23	29	11		
31	160	---	19	13	---	35	---	114	---	24	20	---		
TOTAL	9118	2048	784	621	323.2	445.3	868.0	3866	1478	616	974.3	427.7		
MEAN	294	68.3	25.3	20.0	11.5	14.4	28.9	125	49.3	19.9	31.4	14.3		
MAX	2920	385	41	61	16	93	365	851	204	40	386	33		
MIN	46	30	18	13	9.0	7.4	7.1	12	21	14	9.5	9.0		
CFSM	17.9	4.16	1.54	1.22	.70	.88	1.76	7.62	3.01	1.21	1.91	.87		
IN.	20.68	4.65	1.78	1.41	.73	1.01	1.97	8.77	3.35	1.40	2.21	.97		
AC-FT	18090	4060	1560	1230	641	883	1720	7670	2930	1220	1930	848		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	27815.2	MEAN	76.2	MAX	3910	MIN	9.1	CFSM	4.65	IN.	63.09	AC-FT	55170
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	21569.5	MEAN	59.1	MAX	2920	MIN	7.1	CFSM	3.60	IN.	48.93	AC-FT	42780

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued
WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
DEC, 05	1018	34	274	22.5	SEP, 15	1030	12	253	28.0
MAR, 12	0950	10	280	24.0					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'57", long 65°56'44", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at left downstream side of bridge on Highway 189, 1.9 mi (3.0 km) southeast of Gurabo plaza, and 2.1 mi (3.4 km) northwest of Juncos plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.30 mi² (5.96 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 180 ft (55 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Feb. 27 to Mar. 3. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 1,690 ft³/s (47.9 m³/s), May 15, 1985, gage height, 9.42 ft (2.871 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 400 ft³/s (11.3 m³/s) on basis of indirect measurement of peak flow and step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 0.24 ft³/s (0.007 m³/s), Aug. 30, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	0015	841	23.8	7.66	2.335	May 13	0830	*1,070	30.3	*8.16	2.487
Nov. 15	0945	528	15.0	6.84	2.085	May 14	0015	985	27.9	7.97	2.429
May 9	1600	506	14.3	6.77	2.063						

Minimum discharge, 0.46 ft³/s (0.013 m³/s), Sept. 20, 21, 30.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	2.8	4.3	2.3	1.4	1.1	.88	1.1	2.2	.96	.75	.67	1.6		
2	9.8	3.4	2.2	1.6	1.1	.85	.73	1.7	2.8	.75	.64	.91		
3	2.3	3.1	2.0	1.4	1.1	.77	.71	1.5	1.2	.72	.64	.79		
4	17	3.0	2.0	1.5	5.9	.79	1.0	1.4	.92	.69	.64	.69		
5	17	3.0	2.2	1.5	1.9	.80	2.1	1.4	3.5	.70	.59	.68		
6	251	2.8	2.2	1.5	1.2	.80	1.4	1.4	.99	1.1	.57	.74		
7	189	2.7	2.3	1.5	1.1	.79	.83	2.8	.91	.87	.62	.66		
8	54	2.5	2.3	1.5	1.1	.75	27	17	.87	.79	1.1	.62		
9	8.6	2.6	2.5	2.0	1.1	.72	3.5	41	4.3	.78	.75	.62		
10	5.2	2.5	2.5	1.8	1.1	.72	1.2	21	1.3	.76	.77	.60		
11	4.1	2.6	2.5	1.6	1.1	.76	1.1	18	.96	.79	2.0	.57		
12	3.6	3.2	2.4	1.5	1.1	.74	.89	2.9	.91	.82	.84	.56		
13	3.4	4.6	2.2	1.5	1.0	.74	.84	173	1.3	.80	.74	.56		
14	3.2	3.4	2.1	1.4	1.0	.82	.80	87	1.5	.72	.84	.56		
15	3.2	87	2.2	1.3	1.0	1.8	.84	2.4	.93	.75	1.1	.59		
16	3.2	12	1.9	1.4	1.0	.81	.89	1.4	.95	.77	.91	.55		
17	3.1	7.6	2.0	1.4	1.0	.75	.82	1.1	.87	.69	.75	.53		
18	14	31	1.9	1.3	1.0	.73	.76	2.8	.84	.64	.75	.51		
19	5.2	5.2	1.9	1.3	1.0	.73	.73	5.4	.81	.61	.73	.50		
20	3.4	4.7	1.8	1.2	.99	.73	7.4	1.3	.80	.59	.70	.49		
21	3.2	34	1.8	1.2	.95	.72	1.6	1.0	.79	.59	.70	.49		
22	3.1	4.5	1.7	1.3	.94	.70	.86	.99	.78	.60	.72	.52		
23	35	3.8	1.6	1.4	.90	.69	.73	.92	.79	.62	.72	.55		
24	34	3.4	1.6	1.4	.88	.72	.69	.88	.78	.59	.72	.74		
25	10	3.0	1.7	1.4	.85	.74	.66	.83	.76	.58	.71	.68		
26	6.2	2.8	1.6	1.3	.83	.75	.62	.84	.74	.57	.68	.63		
27	5.1	2.6	1.4	1.3	.82	.73	.69	.83	.83	.57	.69	.57		
28	3.6	2.5	1.4	1.3	.91	.69	1.3	.84	.78	.59	11	.54		
29	21	2.4	1.4	1.3	---	1.3	40	.82	.75	.59	55	.51		
30	6.3	2.4	1.4	1.2	---	.80	4.7	.79	.76	2.0	1.6	.49		
31	25	---	1.3	1.2	---	1.0	---	3.1	---	.92	1.0	---		
TOTAL	755.6	252.6	60.3	43.9	33.97	25.32	106.49	398.54	35.38	23.31	89.89	19.05		
MEAN	24.4	8.42	1.95	1.42	1.21	.82	3.55	12.9	1.18	.75	2.90	.63		
MAX	251	87	2.5	2.0	5.9	1.8	40	173	4.3	2.0	55	1.6		
MIN	2.3	2.4	1.3	1.2	.82	.69	.62	.79	.74	.57	.57	.49		
CFSM	10.6	3.66	.85	.62	.53	.36	1.54	5.61	.51	.33	1.26	.27		
IN.	12.22	4.09	.98	.71	.55	.41	1.72	6.45	.57	.38	1.45	.31		
AC-FT	1500	501	120	87	67	50	211	791	70	46	178	38		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	2099.59	MEAN	5.75	MAX	251	MIN	.28	CFSM	2.50	IN.	33.96	AC-FT	4160
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	1844.35	MEAN	5.05	MAX	251	MIN	.49	CFSM	2.20	IN.	29.83	AC-FT	3660

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS MARCH 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
DEC, 06	1201	2.1	612	24.0					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'30", long 65°58'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 181, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) east of Gurabo, and 4.5 mi (7.6 km) upstream from Rio Grande de Loiza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--60.2 mi² (155.9 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1958 (occasional low-flow measurements only), January to September 1959 (monthly measurements only), October 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 136.58 ft (41.63 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Nov. 21-27 and June 10-26. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--27 years (1960-86), 135 ft³/s (3.823 m³/s), 30.45 in/yr (773 mm/yr), 97,810 acre-ft/yr (120 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 130 ft³/s (3.68 m³/s), 94,200 acre-ft/yr (116 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 74,600 ft³/s (2,133 m³/s), Sept. 6, 1960, gage height, 27.7 ft (8.44m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 8,000 ft³/s (227 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement at gage height 21.6 ft (6.58 m), contracted opening, culvert and flow over road measurement at gage height 23.76 ft (7.242 m), and estimate of peak flow based on slope-area measurements of Rio Gurabo and Rio Valenciano, 7.0 mi (11.3 km) upstream, adjusted for channel storage and flow from intervening area; minimum discharge, 4.5 ft³/s (0.127 m³/s), Feb. 21, 25, 1968.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate elevation to gage datum of the Aug. 4, 1945 flood, as pointed out by local residents, 26.6 ft (8.11 m).

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 6	2045	*19,300	547	*19.37	5.904	Nov. 15	1330	5,370	152	11.63	3.545
Oct. 8	0315	5,330	151	11.58	3.530	Apr. 29	1800	5,810	164	12.16	3.706
Oct. 23	1730	4,160	118	10.08	3.072	May 13	1130	10,600	300	15.87	4.837
Oct. 24	2000	4,930	140	11.09	3.380	May 14	0245	12,370	350	16.72	5.096
Oct. 29	1015	3,790	107	9.56	2.914	Aug. 29	0515	6,680	189	13.15	4.008

Minimum discharge, 12 ft³/s (0.340 m³/s), Mar. 25, Apr. 26, 27, May 6.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN VALUES													
	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	210	235	65	44	32	21	138	55	182	51	55	99		
2	725	199	65	59	30	21	51	32	126	50	40	68		
3	205	177	65	47	31	21	40	21	126	49	32	48		
4	214	149	62	48	64	20	42	19	85	47	29	42		
5	833	177	89	48	70	27	129	15	140	45	27	41		
6	8800	164	97	40	39	25	132	21	85	126	26	69		
7	5470	139	82	37	32	23	45	205	71	122	29	57		
8	1900	114	70	35	30	21	85	192	164	48	67	39		
9	413	104	69	83	30	20	175	515	304	37	27	35		
10	261	98	70	94	29	20	44	678	269	34	31	33		
11	202	101	68	50	28	21	31	818	124	33	98	31		
12	168	173	74	41	27	25	28	158	89	40	50	29		
13	149	265	71	36	25	22	26	3090	106	34	39	29		
14	136	198	61	34	24	38	24	3050	145	34	152	41		
15	119	2060	60	33	24	173	23	260	94	73	38	32		
16	111	584	63	33	25	51	22	174	156	55	52	29		
17	128	233	59	76	25	32	21	136	96	37	33	27		
18	587	583	59	56	30	26	19	464	81	36	29	26		
19	282	231	59	41	31	20	17	249	102	31	28	25		
20	148	190	63	35	28	20	24	160	73	28	27	24		
21	126	410	55	37	28	19	21	136	60	28	23	23		
22	113	125	54	35	27	19	20	128	59	26	25	24		
23	1170	96	52	35	25	16	16	104	66	26	30	29		
24	1840	88	53	43	23	19	16	88	51	25	30	57		
25	860	83	50	46	23	16	15	72	50	25	31	49		
26	351	80	56	37	24	25	13	66	51	23	27	37		
27	317	78	49	31	21	24	16	71	55	24	26	31		
28	240	72	47	30	21	19	49	68	66	27	102	32		
29	973	69	47	30	---	179	1240	75	61	34	1970	28		
30	384	56	43	32	---	84	253	70	57	285	132	26		
31	406	---	43	34	---	71	---	476	---	146	87	---		
TOTAL	27841	7341	1920	1360	846	1138	2775	11666	3194	1679	3392	1160		
MEAN	898	245	61.9	43.9	30.2	36.7	92.5	376	106	54.2	109	38.7		
MAX	8800	2060	97	94	70	179	1240	3090	304	285	1970	99		
MIN	111	66	43	30	21	16	13	15	50	23	23	23		
CFSM	14.9	4.07	1.03	.73	.50	.61	1.54	6.25	1.76	.90	1.81	.64		
IN.	17.20	4.54	1.19	.84	.52	.70	1.71	7.21	1.97	1.04	2.10	.72		
AC-FT	55220	14560	3810	2700	1680	2260	5500	23140	6340	3330	6730	2300		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	80107	MEAN	219	MAX	10900	MIN	16	CFSM	3.64	IN.	49.50	AC-FT	158900
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	64312	MEAN	176	MAX	8800	MIN	13	CFSM	2.92	IN.	39.74	AC-FT	127600

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURAGO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
DEC, 06	0946	89	326	24.0	MAR, 11	1250	19	390	27.0

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50057025 RIO GURABO NEAR GURABO, PR
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'56", long 65°59'04", at bridge on Highway 941, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) west-northwest from gaging station 50057000, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) northwest of Gurabo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--62.8 sq mi (162.7 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATURATION (%)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECA, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
29...	1730	325	125	6.80	26.0	550	8.0	--	61	54000	55000
DEC 19...	1345	22	412	7.60	27.5	6.4	2.8	35	22	120000	K6000
FEB 1986											
26...	1225	18	436	7.75	26.5	5.6	5.2	66	21	K100	<10
APR 24...	1015	18	430	7.60	29.5	6.0	5.3	70	15	2000	K40
JUL 14...	1230	25	358	7.55	30.0	2.5	5.0	67	31	140000	2000
SEP 10...	1155	33	363	7.70	30.0	11	5.0	67	13	15000	2000

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
29...	37	0	8.3	4.0	8.2	0.6	3.3	37	<0.5	9.5	8.9
DEC 19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	115	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	131	--	--	--
APR 24...	130	8	29	15	36	1	4.6	126	<0.5	18	39
JUL 14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	117	--	--	--
SEP 10...	110	0	25	12	27	1	4.6	121	--	20	27

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
29...	<0.10	15	79	70	480	0.250	0.150	0.400	0.360	1.7
DEC 19...	--	--	--	--	17	1.30	0.100	1.40	0.540	0.26
FEB 1986										
26...	--	--	--	--	7	1.58	0.120	1.70	0.880	0.92
APR 24...	0.20	35	250	12	8	1.30	0.100	1.40	0.240	0.86
JUL 14...	--	--	--	--	14	0.750	0.050	0.800	0.610	0.69
SEP 10...	0.20	32	220	19	12	1.13	0.070	1.20	0.480	0.52

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059000 LAGO LOIZA AT DAMSITE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'49", long 66°01'00", at pumphouse at damsite, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) south of Trujillo Alto plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--208 sq mi (539 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECA, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
NOV 1985										
01...	1130	124	190	7.10	27.0	3.2	--	23	K890	750
DEC 20...	0845	124	312	7.50	25.0	5.8	--	63	54	42
FEB 1986										
25...	1020	--	305	7.35	25.0	1.6	20	26	K18	K35
APR 21...	1430	124	288	7.40	26.0	1.2	15	22	96	50
JUL 14...	1405	124	265	7.00	31.0	2.2	30	13	K2	76
SEP 09...	1335	170	162	7.40	30.0	3.4	45	<10	K250	87

DATE	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
NOV 1985										
01...	53	<0.5	114	0.610	0.090	0.700	0.150	0.45	0.60	1.3
DEC 20...	90	--	3	0.480	0.120	0.600	0.230	0.47	0.70	1.3
FEB 1986										
25...	92	--	3	0.380	0.020	0.400	0.130	0.47	0.60	1.0
APR 21...	84	<0.5	7	0.180	0.020	0.200	0.310	0.49	0.80	1.0
JUL 14...	90	--	10	0.050	0.050	0.100	0.200	0.60	0.80	0.90
SEP 09...	52	--	35	0.220	0.080	0.300	0.370	0.63	1.0	1.3

DATE	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	MANGANESE, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYLENE BLUE ACTIVE SUBSTANCE (MG/L)
NOV 1985										
01...	5.8	0.170	30	50	4400	110	20	<0.010	4	0.03
DEC 20...	5.8	0.150	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986										
25...	4.4	0.170	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 21...	4.4	0.180	40	30	370	320	40	<0.010	<1	0.07
JUL 14...	4.0	0.130	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 09...	5.8	0.220	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059100 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW TRUJILLO ALTO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'35", long 66°00'15", 100 ft (30 m) downstream of Highway 181 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northwest of Trujillo Alto plaza, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northeast of Lago Loiza Reservoir.

DRAINAGE AREA.--213 sq mi (552 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1981 to current year.

REMARKS: Flow controlled by Lago Loiza reservoir.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, (PERCENT SATURATION) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
NOV 1985										
01...	1435	30	209	7.70	29.5	64	7.6	--	22	3100 490
DEC										
20...	0945	--	421	8.00	26.0	1.5	7.0	--	52	2000 40
FEB 1986										
25...	1310	11	402	8.85	26.0	1.1	13.3	166	24	K860 200
APR										
24...	1410	6.8	369	8.20	29.5	4.5	8.0	106	30	2400 K35
JUL										
24...	1055	7.8	347	8.50	31.0	3.0	11.0	149	19	100 K10
SEP										
15...	1035	6.7	342	8.30	30.0	0.60	10.6	141	27	K18 K16

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
NOV 1985											
01...	63	0	15	6.1	13	0.7	2.6	64	<0.5	18	14
DEC											
20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	133	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	132	--	--	--
APR											
24...	120	5	30	12	27	1	2.8	119	<0.5	17	29
JUL											
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	119	--	--	--
SEP											
15...	120	3	29	11	25	1	2.8	115	--	24	24

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
NOV 1985										
01...	<0.10	<0.1	130	--	90	0.700	0.100	0.800	0.150	0.55
DEC										
20...	--	--	--	--	1	0.970	0.030	1.00	0.030	0.27
FEB 1986										
25...	--	--	--	--	2	0.480	0.020	0.500	0.060	0.44
APR										
24...	0.20	23	210	3.9	1	0.270	0.030	0.300	0.070	0.73
JUL										
24...	--	--	--	--	23	--	<0.010	0.100	0.030	0.27
SEP										
15...	0.20	24	210	3.8	1	--	<0.010	0.200	0.030	0.57

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50061800 RIO CANDVANAS NEAR CAMPO RICO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'08", long 65°53'21", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at center pier on downstream side of bridge, on paved secondary road, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of junction of Highways 185 and 186, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) south of Campo Rico, and 4.4 mi (7.1 km) south of Loiza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.84 mi² (25.48 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1967 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 225 ft (68 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Feb. 9-11. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--19 years (1968-86), 28.5 ft³/s (0.807 m³/s), 39.33 in/yr (999 mm/yr), 20,650 acre-ft/yr (25.5 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 27 ft³/s (0.76 m³/s), 19,600 acre-ft/yr (24 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 15,000 ft³/s (425 m³/s), Sept. 13, 1982, gage height, 13.1 ft (3.99 m), from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 350 ft³/s (9.91 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurements and step-backwater analysis made in 1981; minimum daily discharge, 0.80 ft³/s (0.023 m³/s), July 24, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,500 ft³/s (70.8 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s) (m ³ /s)		Gage height (ft) (m)		Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s) (m ³ /s)		Gage height (ft) (m)	
Oct. 6	1800	*6,960	197	*9.80	2.987	May 13	2315	5,710	162	8.98	2.737
Nov. 15	1800	2,740	77.6	6.59	2.009						

Minimum discharge, 3.5 ft³/s (0.099 m³/s), Apr. 26.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	29	46	36	15	8.4	5.6	19	16	41	9.0	10	24		
2	157	41	34	17	9.1	5.1	8.1	25	26	8.9	7.8	13		
3	47	38	33	17	17	5.0	23	9.1	23	8.5	7.1	10		
4	55	43	32	21	32	5.1	15	6.9	21	8.4	7.0	8.8		
5	180	44	35	17	27	7.6	116	5.7	19	8.0	6.1	8.3		
6	1050	40	34	15	14	5.6	35	5.8	17	10	5.7	10		
7	640	33	31	14	11	5.2	13	14	16	12	5.5	10		
8	202	29	29	14	9.4	4.7	9.8	30	15	7.9	6.6	7.7		
9	93	29	30	45	8.6	5.6	10	171	42	6.7	5.4	7.0		
10	69	26	29	21	8.4	5.6	7.9	82	22	6.7	4.9	6.9		
11	57	36	31	13	8.3	5.9	7.0	94	18	5.8	18	6.5		
12	49	138	32	11	7.8	5.6	6.4	25	16	6.6	19	6.7		
13	45	249	28	11	7.2	6.3	6.6	571	17	5.9	23	7.3		
14	41	132	25	10	7.0	7.8	6.2	355	17	6.5	21	8.7		
15	37	743	28	11	7.3	18	5.8	49	17	16	11	7.2		
16	35	215	25	11	6.9	8.6	6.1	33	17	11	9.8	6.7		
17	34	111	24	12	7.2	7.0	6.0	27	18	11	7.6	6.6		
18	166	127	22	11	6.9	5.3	5.8	45	15	8.2	6.2	6.3		
19	62	75	21	10	6.7	5.0	5.2	36	14	6.7	6.3	6.2		
20	42	142	21	8.8	7.0	5.1	5.1	26	15	5.9	6.2	5.7		
21	35	265	21	9.5	6.3	4.9	5.5	23	13	5.9	5.5	6.1		
22	33	80	21	10	6.2	4.3	5.3	21	12	6.0	5.8	6.7		
23	273	69	20	11	5.9	4.3	4.2	18	11	5.7	5.6	7.1		
24	304	62	20	14	5.5	5.3	4.8	17	12	5.6	6.9	6.7		
25	124	52	19	13	5.8	5.6	4.8	16	11	5.8	6.2	7.2		
26	69	48	20	9.8	6.1	5.5	4.0	15	11	5.3	5.6	8.1		
27	60	45	18	9.3	5.7	5.8	4.3	15	14	4.9	4.9	7.9		
28	65	42	18	8.7	5.7	6.3	7.7	73	11	5.5	96	6.7		
29	94	40	17	8.9	---	17	43	30	9.5	8.5	319	5.9		
30	56	39	16	8.9	---	15	25	21	9.3	67	20	6.1		
31	59	---	16	9.9	---	7.9	---	176	---	35	16	---		
TOTAL	4262	3079	786	417.8	264.4	211.6	425.6	2051.5	519.8	324.9	685.7	242.1		
MEAN	137	103	25.4	13.5	9.44	6.83	14.2	66.2	17.3	10.5	22.1	8.07		
MAX	1050	743	36	45	32	18	116	571	42	67	319	24		
MIN	29	26	16	8.7	5.5	4.3	4.0	5.7	9.3	4.9	4.9	5.7		
CFSM	13.9	10.5	2.58	1.37	.96	.69	1.44	6.73	1.76	1.07	2.25	.82		
IN.	16.11	11.64	2.97	1.58	.00	.80	1.61	7.76	1.97	1.23	2.59	.92		
AC-FT	8450	6110	1560	829	524	420	844	4070	1030	644	1360	480		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	15944.2	MEAN	43.7	MAX	1050	MIN	4.8	CFSM	4.44	IN.	60.28	AC-FT	31630
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	13270.4	MEAN	36.4	MAX	1050	MIN	4.0	CFSM	3.70	IN.	50.17	AC-FT	26320

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
 50061800 RIO CANOVANAS NEAR CAMPO RICO, PR--Continued
 WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
MAY, 16	0940	34	146	23.0	AUG, 18	1428	6.0	229	30.0
JUN, 19	1340	13	209	28.5	SEP, 10	1330	6.6	207	29.5
JUL, 16	1453	9	224	30.0					

Figure 19.--Northeastern river basins--Río Herrera to Río Antón Ruíz basins.

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063440 QUEBRADA SONADORA NEAR EL VERDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'24", long 65°49'03", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, in Caribbean National Forest, at El Yunque, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) upstream from Rio Espiritu Santo, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Highway 185, and about 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of El Verde.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.01 mi² (2.62 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 1,230 ft (375 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Feb. 8-11. Records poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 2,160 ft³/s (61.2 m³/s), May 14, 1985, gage height, 9.36 ft (2.853 m) from rating curve extended above 20 ft³/s (0.57 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 0.20 ft³/s (0.006 m³/s), July 14, 15, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s) (m ³ /s)		Gage height (ft) (m)		Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s) (m ³ /s)		Gage height (ft) (m)	
Oct. 24	1400	698	19.8	7.52	2.292	Aug. 13	1845	595	16.8	7.30	2.225
May 13	0830	569	16.1	7.24	2.207	Aug. 24	1845	*2,120	60.0	*9.32	2.841

Minimum discharge, 0.46 ft³/s (0.013 m³/s), Mar. 8.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	6.5	4.6	2.8	2.8	1.8	.80	6.2	28	3.7	2.6	3.0	7.7
2	14	6.1	2.9	4.1	2.7	.70	3.2	13	2.2	3.1	1.7	4.3
3	12	4.4	2.1	12	4.9	.62	7.9	3.3	1.9	6.0	1.4	3.3
4	6.3	3.8	2.5	9.9	22	.86	11	2.3	1.7	2.6	1.7	2.9
5	20	3.7	7.7	4.0	7.4	.88	28	1.8	1.7	6.4	.91	2.8
6	132	3.0	5.7	3.1	4.7	.59	11	2.2	1.5	11	.69	4.2
7	53	3.0	3.5	3.1	3.7	.57	5.0	9.5	1.5	8.9	5.1	2.8
8	13	2.4	2.3	3.5	2.2	.51	3.7	4.7	1.6	3.4	1.5	2.2
9	8.2	2.2	3.0	20	1.9	1.0	3.5	8.1	6.2	2.6	1.2	1.9
10	5.7	2.0	3.8	6.0	1.7	.91	2.9	8.5	13	2.2	1.4	1.7
11	4.3	11	4.8	4.8	1.4	1.9	2.7	9.2	3.5	2.1	9.1	1.5
12	3.6	37	12	3.8	1.2	1.2	2.5	3.0	4.2	4.2	5.1	1.3
13	3.1	46	4.0	3.3	.97	3.9	2.4	50	13	2.2	42	1.2
14	3.2	24	2.6	2.9	.99	7.5	2.2	27	10	2.4	10	1.1
15	2.2	99	5.1	2.9	.91	8.5	2.1	5.2	11	14	12	.96
16	1.9	17	3.4	3.4	.70	7.9	2.3	3.5	10	8.4	3.8	.86
17	1.5	11	3.3	5.4	1.7	1.8	2.3	3.2	6.2	10	2.8	.74
18	13	15	2.7	4.0	1.4	1.4	2.0	17	3.8	3.5	2.2	.65
19	13	7.6	4.4	2.8	18	1.1	1.8	5.6	6.6	2.7	1.9	.56
20	8.8	22	7.2	3.3	4.5	1.5	1.7	3.5	5.0	2.3	1.7	.49
21	4.3	24	7.1	3.9	1.9	1.2	3.5	3.3	4.2	2.4	1.5	.99
22	6.3	5.3	9.9	3.1	1.5	.81	1.9	3.5	3.3	2.0	1.7	1.9
23	53	5.9	4.6	5.4	1.3	.66	1.6	2.7	3.3	1.8	15	3.5
24	88	5.9	4.8	6.0	1.2	1.4	1.6	2.4	3.3	1.8	72	1.5
25	13	4.2	3.3	3.2	1.1	4.3	1.4	2.1	2.6	1.8	8.2	2.5
26	7.8	3.4	4.2	2.3	.95	1.6	1.3	1.9	3.3	1.5	3.9	2.3
27	7.2	3.0	2.7	2.0	.86	2.6	1.9	1.9	11	1.5	3.2	4.8
28	5.8	2.6	5.1	1.8	.86	7.1	8.5	2.8	3.6	1.5	43	2.6
29	8.6	2.6	2.9	1.7	---	23	19	4.1	2.7	34	27	4.6
30	5.5	5.0	2.3	2.9	---	6.8	8.7	3.0	2.3	22	5.5	2.3
31	5.9	---	2.1	2.2	---	9.4	---	12	---	5.4	4.4	---
TOTAL	530.7	386.7	134.8	139.6	94.44	103.01	153.8	248.3	147.9	176.3	294.60	70.15
MEAN	17.1	12.9	4.35	4.50	3.37	3.32	5.13	8.01	4.93	5.69	9.50	2.34
MAX	132	99	12	20	22	23	28	50	13	34	72	7.7
MIN	1.5	2.0	2.1	1.7	.70	.51	1.3	1.8	1.5	1.5	.69	.49
CFSM	16.9	12.8	4.31	4.46	3.34	3.29	5.08	7.93	4.88	5.63	9.41	2.32
IN.	19.55	14.24	4.96	5.14	3.48	3.79	5.66	9.15	5.45	6.49	10.85	2.58
AC-FT	1050	767	267	277	187	204	305	493	293	350	584	139

CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	2737.98	MEAN	7.50	MAX	132	MIN	.23	CFSM	7.43	IN.	100.84	AC-FT	5430
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	2480.30	MEAN	6.80	MAX	132	MIN	.49	CFSM	6.73	IN.	91.35	AC-FT	4920

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063440 QUEBRADA SONADORA NEAR EL VERDE, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS APRIL 1983 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
MAY, 15	1450	4.8	50	21.5	AUG, 19	0958	2.0	60	22.5
JUN, 20	0929	4.3	51	21.5	SEP, 11	0937	1.5	64	22.5
JUL, 15	1035	17	59	22.0					

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063500 QUEBRADA TORONJA AT EL VERDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'43", long 65°49'14", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, in Caribbean National Forest, at downstream side of culvert on Highway 186, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Rio Espiritu Santo, and about 0.9 mi (1.4 km) south of El Verde.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.064 mi² (0.166 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete broad-V-notch crested weir. Elevation of gage is 876 ft (267 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--No estimated daily discharges during water year. Records poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 18 ft³/s (0.51 m³/s), July 5, 1983, gage height, 1.71 ft (0.521 m), from rating curve extended above 1.0 ft³/s (0.03 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, no flow for part of each day Apr. 10, 17, 1983.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 13 ft³/s (0.37 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 24	1530	*17	0.48	*1.69	0.515	May 14	0030	14	0.40	1.64	0.500
May 1	2115	13	0.37	1.63	0.497	Aug. 24	1930	14	0.40	1.65	0.503

Minimum discharge, 0.04 ft³/s (0.001 m³/s), July 8-14, 18-24.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	.32	.50	.15	.11	.07	.08	.09	1.7	.24	.08	.13	.87		
2	.49	.45	.12	.13	.09	.08	.06	1.1	.21	.09	.09	.40		
3	.67	.35	.10	.21	.21	.07	.32	.45	.18	.07	.09	.30		
4	.44	.33	.09	.26	.98	.08	.25	.26	.18	.05	.09	.27		
5	.92	.42	.15	.13	.25	.07	.31	.22	.17	.09	.08	.24		
6	6.8	.31	.12	.12	.14	.07	.21	.25	.17	.11	.07	.18		
7	5.2	.27	.10	.11	.12	.07	.10	.66	.17	.07	.11	.15		
8	2.0	.25	.09	.13	.10	.07	.11	.34	.15	.05	.07	.14		
9	1.5	.27	.08	.59	.09	.08	.09	.57	.26	.05	.07	.14		
10	1.1	.24	.08	.18	.08	.08	.06	.67	.34	.05	.09	.13		
11	.93	.43	.08	.14	.08	.08	.06	.63	.16	.04	.22	.11		
12	.78	1.7	.19	.12	.07	.08	.05	.37	.17	.06	.17	.11		
13	.58	2.8	.12	.12	.07	.16	.06	2.9	.23	.04	1.6	.09		
14	.49	1.7	.11	.13	.07	.18	.05	2.9	.21	.06	.49	.09		
15	.45	5.3	.14	.15	.07	.19	.05	.80	.21	.26	.36	.09		
16	.42	1.9	.10	.14	.06	.17	.07	.48	.35	.07	.18	.08		
17	.40	1.2	.08	.16	.07	.08	.08	.45	.17	.08	.15	.08		
18	.56	1.2	.08	.14	.06	.07	.06	.96	.13	.05	.13	.07		
19	.82	.71	.09	.12	.13	.08	.06	.44	.13	.04	.11	.07		
20	.71	.83	.14	.13	.09	.07	.06	.35	.12	.04	.09	.07		
21	.42	1.1	.15	.12	.06	.07	.27	.30	.11	.04	.08	.09		
22	.44	.48	.26	.12	.05	.07	.07	.25	.09	.04	.09	.09		
23	3.3	.45	.13	.10	.05	.06	.06	.22	.09	.04	.16	.08		
24	4.5	.36	.13	.10	.05	.08	.06	.21	.08	.10	1.5	.07		
25	2.3	.36	.10	.08	.07	.12	.06	.20	.08	.08	.62	.09		
26	1.3	.27	.11	.07	.08	.06	.06	.18	.10	.07	.23	.09		
27	1.0	.22	.09	.07	.08	.06	.08	.19	.13	.07	.20	.12		
28	.80	.20	.10	.06	.08	.06	.22	.63	.09	.08	2.2	.14		
29	.80	.18	.13	.07	---	.59	.27	.58	.08	.89	1.9	.15		
30	.66	.20	.11	.07	---	.11	.71	.27	.08	.71	.54	.06		
31	.63	---	.12	.08	---	.11	---	.45	---	.19	.39	---		
TOTAL	41.73	24.98	3.64	4.26	3.42	3.30	4.06	19.98	4.88	3.76	12.30	4.66		
MEAN	1.35	.83	.12	.14	.12	.11	.14	.64	.16	.12	.40	.16		
MAX	6.8	5.3	.26	.59	.98	.59	.71	2.9	.35	.85	2.2	.87		
MIN	.32	.18	.08	.06	.05	.06	.05	.18	.08	.04	.07	.06		
CFSM	21.1	13.0	1.87	2.19	1.87	1.72	2.19	10.0	2.50	1.87	6.25	2.50		
IN.	24.26	14.52	2.12	2.48	1.99	1.92	2.36	11.61	2.84	2.19	7.15	2.71		
AC-FT	83	50	7.2	8.4	6.8	6.5	8.1	40	9.7	7.5	24	9.2		
CAL YR 1985 TOTAL	148.74		MEAN	.41	MAX	6.8	MIN	.03	CFSM	6.41	IN.	86.46	AC-FT	295
WTR YR 1986 TOTAL	130.97		MEAN	.36	MAX	6.8	MIN	.04	CFSM	5.62	IN.	76.13	AC-FT	260

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063500 QUEBRADA TORONJA AT EL VERDE, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS APRIL 1983 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
MAY, 15	1543	0.59	82	22.5	AUG, 19	1143	0.10	119	23.5
JUN, 20	1121	.10	117	23.0	SEP, 11	1122	.11	119	24.5
JUL, 15	1256	.20	111	23.0					

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063800 RIO ESPIRITU SANTO NEAR RIO GRANDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'37", long 65°48'49", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at left abutment, on downstream side of bridge on Highway 966, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Quebrada Jiménez, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) southeast of Río Grande.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.62 mi² (22.33 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to April 1963 (annual low-flow and occasional measurements only), August 1966 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 40 ft (12 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 2, 5-8, June 15, 16, 27 and Aug. 31 to Sept. 8. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--20 years (1967-86), 57.5 ft³/s (1.628 m³/s), 90.59 in/yr (2,301 mm/yr), 41,660 acre-ft/yr (51.4 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 52 ft³/s (1.47 m³/s), 37,700 acre-ft/yr (46 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 12,400 ft³/s (351 m³/s), Dec. 2, 1983, gage height, 12.07 ft (3.679 m), from rating curve extended above 600 ft³/s (17.0 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 4.0 ft³/s (0.113 m³/s), July 3-5, 1975, Apr. 14, 15, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 6	unknown	3,490	98.8	7.59	2.313	July 29	1645	3,240	91.8	7.40	2.256
Oct. 24	1430	*7,400	210	*9.94	3.030	Aug. 13	1845	5,190	147	8.74	2.664
Nov. 15	1345	3,150	89.2	7.32	2.231	Aug. 24	1845	6,480	184	9.47	2.886
May 13	0915	6,330	179	9.39	2.862						

Minimum discharge, 7.7 ft³/s (0.218 m³/s), July 26, 27.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	30	41	31	19	17	11	35	283	36	17	24	54		
2	130	48	33	31	35	11	23	227	22	18	17	36		
3	83	36	25	60	46	10	80	90	19	30	14	30		
4	45	40	26	106	207	11	51	23	18	18	15	27		
5	150	60	59	28	84	13	210	18	17	28	12	26		
6	850	38	42	22	40	10	77	24	16	63	11	30		
7	530	29	30	20	27	11	27	95	15	44	28	30		
8	170	25	22	22	21	9.7	49	36	18	20	14	23		
9	86	24	29	174	18	12	26	87	70	16	14	20		
10	62	23	31	52	16	12	16	74	72	15	13	19		
11	50	68	39	33	16	18	14	96	32	14	118	18		
12	41	332	88	25	15	14	13	27	26	25	53	17		
13	36	492	37	22	14	27	13	741	54	16	446	17		
14	35	213	22	20	14	38	12	386	73	14	105	19		
15	30	1170	38	20	15	77	11	51	85	91	67	17		
16	28	217	27	22	13	58	28	34	100	28	24	17		
17	29	120	25	33	15	17	14	28	39	67	19	16		
18	164	185	22	30	17	13	11	122	27	19	15	16		
19	135	81	26	20	75	11	11	44	36	14	14	15		
20	97	124	50	21	43	12	10	28	32	12	13	15		
21	42	310	48	26	17	12	101	25	27	11	13	16		
22	39	65	93	20	14	9.9	13	27	23	11	13	22		
23	630	60	40	31	14	9.3	11	22	21	9.9	75	25		
24	995	68	37	41	13	12	10	20	20	11	452	18		
25	167	55	24	25	12	21	9.5	18	18	11	78	22		
26	129	39	32	18	12	15	9.0	18	17	8.4	24	22		
27	86	34	22	17	11	17	12	20	70	8.5	19	34		
28	59	32	36	16	11	41	32	92	21	9.1	431	21		
29	89	31	22	16	---	188	140	89	17	360	325	34		
30	53	45	18	20	---	39	166	36	16	228	46	21		
31	56	---	17	18	---	37	---	125	---	52	41	---		
TOTAL	5126	4105	1091	1028	852	796.9	1234.5	3006	1057	1288.9	2553	697		
MEAN	165	137	35.2	33.2	30.4	25.7	41.1	97.0	35.2	41.6	82.4	23.2		
MAX	995	1170	93	174	207	188	210	741	100	360	452	54		
MIN	28	23	17	16	11	9.3	9.0	18	15	8.4	11	15		
CFSM	19.1	15.9	4.08	3.85	3.53	2.98	4.77	11.3	4.08	4.83	9.56	2.69		
IN.	22.12	17.72	4.71	4.44	3.68	3.44	5.33	12.97	4.56	5.56	11.02	3.01		
AC-FT	10170	8140	2160	2040	1690	1580	2450	5960	2100	2560	5060	1380		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	25171.2	MEAN	69.0	MAX	1170	MIN	5.9	CFSM	8.00	IN.	108.63	AC-FT	49930
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	22835.3	MEAN	62.6	MAX	1170	MIN	8.4	CFSM	7.26	IN.	98.55	AC-FT	45290

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063800 RIO ESPIRITU SANTO NEAR RIO GRANDE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1961-66, 1968 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
24...	1100	555	70	7.70	23.5	44	9.4	--	27	620	K4000
DEC 13...	1130	36	103	7.50	21.0	2.6	6.2	--	52	3500	2000
FEB 1986											
12...	1045	15	121	7.90	22.5	1.5	8.4	--	11	490	200
APR 17...	1025	15	106	7.80	24.0	44	9.0	108	15	K1800	820
JUL 03...	1000	41	92	7.45	26.0	5.2	8.6	106	40	3000	930
SEP 08...	1205	21	100	7.45	27.0	0.70	8.5	107	<10	K620	270

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
24...	9	0	1.9	1.1	3.5	0.5	0.30	13	<0.5	7.5	4.4
DEC 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	23	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	38	--	--	--
APR 17...	32	0	6.8	3.7	7.8	0.6	0.60	32	<0.5	4.9	10
JUL 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	28	--	--	--
SEP 08...	32	0	6.6	3.8	7.7	0.6	0.60	33	--	4.7	9.1

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
24...	<0.10	6.2	33	49	59	--	0.020	<0.100	0.040	0.36
DEC 13...	--	--	--	--	1	0.160	0.140	0.300	5.80	2.4
FEB 1986										
12...	--	--	--	--	1	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.010	0.19
APR 17...	<0.10	20	73	2.9	6	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.040	0.26
JUL 03...	--	--	--	--	10	--	<0.010	<0.100	<0.010	--
SEP 08...	<0.10	20	72	4.1	4	--	<0.010	<0.100	<0.010	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50065500 RIO MAMEYES NEAR SABANA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'46", long 65°45'04", on left bank, at bridge on Highway 988, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) west of Sabana, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) downstream from Rio de la Mina, and 3.2 mi (5.1 km) southeast of Mameyes.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.88 mi² (17.82 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1967 to December 1973. June 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 275 ft (84 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Nov. 2-14. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--3 years (1968-73, 1984-86), 58.0 ft³/s (1.642 m³/s), 114.48 in/yr (2,908 mm/yr), 42,000 acre-ft/yr (51.8 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 19,800 ft³/s (561 m³/s), Sept. 4, 1973, gage height, 13.02 ft (3.968 m), from rating curve extended above 1,800 ft³/s (51.0 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 5.1 ft³/s (0.144 m³/s), Apr. 8, 9, 1970.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 4,000 ft³/s (113 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1515	5,850	166	8.57	2.612	May 13	0915	8,160	231	9.56	2.914
Oct. 24	0515	6,660	139	8.94	2.725	Aug. 13	2030	*9,700	275	*10.12	3.084
Nov. 15	1515	4,230	120	7.70	2.347	Aug. 24	1930	4,620	131	7.93	2.417

Minimum daily discharge, 9.0 ft³/s (0.255 m³/s), Mar. 8.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	113	57	33	35	23	10	27	314	45	30	55	108		
2	115	82	34	43	37	9.9	17	103	28	34	32	47		
3	82	56	31	61	47	9.6	17	73	25	35	38	34		
4	59	50	33	77	141	11	43	50	23	27	29	30		
5	113	80	73	38	58	11	253	42	23	37	26	35		
6	1100	49	43	32	29	11	68	46	20	44	23	42		
7	340	42	35	30	28	14	35	200	19	63	28	26		
8	139	40	32	30	23	10	37	61	22	34	24	25		
9	92	38	46	156	21	15	29	73	50	34	22	23		
10	70	37	44	53	19	13	24	75	67	31	24	23		
11	58	37	46	39	19	16	22	86	27	28	66	21		
12	50	130	84	33	19	13	20	43	28	42	90	20		
13	48	100	43	30	18	28	19	324	59	32	675	20		
14	50	140	33	29	19	31	19	207	62	32	72	20		
15	41	572	56	28	18	42	19	67	74	48	80	19		
16	39	156	37	31	17	26	43	48	70	31	27	18		
17	35	106	36	34	18	15	23	42	47	51	26	17		
18	70	109	35	30	15	13	19	192	31	44	24	18		
19	94	74	45	26	84	12	19	68	61	34	22	17		
20	63	87	66	28	24	12	18	43	44	29	21	18		
21	48	172	58	31	14	11	82	42	39	28	20	20		
22	47	64	94	26	12	10	53	65	37	24	23	19		
23	342	66	60	43	12	9.9	43	35	33	23	66	20		
24	669	59	49	44	11	11	44	31	30	35	300	16		
25	157	51	38	30	11	16	37	28	28	28	73	20		
26	117	43	41	25	10	14	35	25	32	29	41	24		
27	95	39	32	24	10	14	60	30	69	24	34	30		
28	71	35	47	23	11	189	121	26	32	26	206	19		
29	98	34	33	22	---	158	160	97	30	135	175	25		
30	65	48	30	25	---	33	444	32	28	140	57	24		
31	82	---	28	26	---	47	---	179	---	45	44	---		
TOTAL	4562	2654	1395	1182	768	835.4	1850	2747	1183	1277	2443	798		
MEAN	147	88.5	45.0	38.1	27.4	26.9	61.7	88.6	39.4	41.2	78.8	26.6		
MAX	1100	572	94	156	141	189	444	324	74	140	675	108		
MIN	35	34	28	22	10	9.6	17	25	19	23	20	16		
CFSM	21.4	12.9	6.54	5.54	3.98	3.91	8.97	12.9	5.73	5.99	11.5	3.87		
IN.	24.67	14.35	7.54	6.39	4.15	4.52	10.00	14.85	6.40	6.90	13.21	4.31		
AC-FT	9050	5260	2770	2340	1520	1660	3670	5450	2350	2530	4850	1580		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	19962.0	MEAN	54.7	MAX	1100	MIN	9.2	CFSM	7.95	IN.	107.93	AC-FT	39590
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	21694.4	MEAN	59.4	MAX	1100	MIN	9.6	CFSM	8.63	IN.	117.30	AC-FT	43030

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50065500 RIO MAMEYES NEAR SABANA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS JUNE 1983 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
JUN, 18	0949	32	93	23.0	AUG, 15	1036	70	77	23.5
JUL, 17	0952	41	90	23.5	SEP, 09	0944	24	108	24.5

RIO SABANA BASIN

50067000 RIO SABANA AT SABANA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'52", Long 65°43'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank along Highway 988, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) north of junction of Highways 988 and 983 in Sabana, and 3.3 mi (5.3 km) south of Luquillo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.96 mi² (10.26 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1979 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (80 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Nov. 2-13. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--7 years (1980-86), 18.3 ft³/s (0.518 m³/s), 62.76 in/yr (1,594 mm/yr), 13,260 acre-ft/yr (16.3 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 9,010 ft³/s (255 m³/s), Apr. 21, 1983, gage height, 19.35 ft (5.898 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 0.86 ft³/s (0.024 m³/s), Apr. 17, 1983.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1330	2,200	62.3	13.19	4.020	May 13	0915	*2,260	64.0	*13.27	4.045
Oct. 24	0445	1,760	49.8	12.55	3.825	Aug. 13	1845	2,000	56.6	12.90	3.932
Nov. 15	1515	1,610	45.6	12.30	3.749	Aug. 24	1615	1,710	48.4	12.46	3.798

Minimum discharge, 1.3 ft³/s (0.037 m³/s), Aug. 21, 22.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	16	21	13	6.2	3.3	3.3	10	92	28	4.5	6.7	79		
2	22	82	12	7.7	4.9	2.3	4.2	34	18	5.7	4.6	16		
3	30	33	12	6.6	12	2.1	3.4	45	16	5.4	4.4	9.9		
4	11	28	11	10	30	3.0	3.3	17	14	4.0	4.8	8.1		
5	23	26	20	6.4	15	2.9	96	11	16	10	3.7	20		
6	713	25	13	5.7	6.1	2.5	14	16	12	9.6	3.9	13		
7	169	22	11	5.3	5.3	4.4	5.6	160	11	8.9	4.9	7.9		
8	49	20	10	5.0	4.0	2.3	6.1	21	9.8	5.5	3.5	6.2		
9	33	19	12	29	3.4	3.7	4.5	21	17	3.7	3.4	5.6		
10	27	18	11	10	3.2	2.3	3.2	23	17	3.5	5.0	5.2		
11	25	48	9.9	6.3	3.1	2.7	3.0	25	11	3.3	6.4	4.7		
12	21	130	16	5.3	3.0	2.2	2.8	10	9.9	4.3	9.8	4.6		
13	20	115	10	5.0	2.5	2.7	2.7	190	13	3.1	136	4.3		
14	20	49	8.7	4.5	3.5	2.8	2.6	139	16	3.2	76	3.9		
15	17	353	10	4.6	3.1	2.9	2.7	26	16	5.6	12	3.6		
16	16	56	8.7	5.2	2.5	2.6	5.0	18	24	3.7	5.2	3.5		
17	14	35	8.9	4.4	2.6	2.9	3.5	15	13	5.2	2.6	3.2		
18	29	29	8.4	3.8	2.7	2.6	2.5	75	8.4	3.3	2.0	3.1		
19	32	26	10	3.7	9.2	2.6	2.3	22	19	2.5	1.9	2.9		
20	19	33	15	3.9	4.3	2.5	2.2	16	9.1	2.4	1.7	2.9		
21	19	57	12	5.7	2.5	2.5	3.3	17	7.5	2.9	1.5	3.3		
22	14	22	19	4.6	2.4	2.3	3.1	44	6.7	2.3	1.5	3.4		
23	117	21	16	7.4	2.2	2.3	2.4	13	6.1	2.3	3.1	3.1		
24	350	19	11	8.1	2.1	2.4	2.7	10	6.0	4.8	117	2.5		
25	59	19	8.8	5.0	2.2	3.5	2.1	9.0	5.5	3.4	18	3.1		
26	33	17	9.5	3.6	2.1	3.0	2.0	8.3	6.3	2.1	5.9	3.4		
27	34	16	7.6	3.1	2.4	2.8	36	26	22	2.0	4.0	5.7		
28	25	15	9.0	3.2	3.7	66	76	21	5.9	2.8	156	4.3		
29	48	14	7.3	2.9	---	49	171	91	5.1	11	143	4.3		
30	26	17	6.6	3.7	---	7.2	195	21	4.9	36	19	3.1		
31	26	---	6.2	3.7	---	22	---	143	---	14	13	---		
TOTAL	2057	1395	343.6	189.6	143.3	218.3	673.2	1379.3	374.2	181.0	780.4	243.8		
MEAN	66.4	46.2	11.1	6.12	5.12	7.04	22.4	44.5	12.5	5.84	25.2	8.13		
MAX	713	353	20	29	30	66	195	190	28	36	156	79		
MIN	11	14	6.2	2.9	2.1	2.1	2.0	8.3	4.9	2.0	1.5	2.5		
CFSM	16.8	11.7	2.80	1.55	1.29	1.78	5.66	11.2	3.16	1.47	6.36	2.05		
IN.	19.32	13.01	3.23	1.78	1.35	2.05	6.32	12.96	3.52	1.70	7.33	2.29		
AC-FT	4080	2750	682	376	284	433	1340	2740	742	359	1550	484		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	7466.9	MEAN	20.5	MAX	713	MIN	1.2	CFSM	5.18	IN.	70.14	AC-FT	14810
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	7968.7	MEAN	21.8	MAX	713	MIN	1.5	CFSM	5.51	IN.	74.86	AC-FT	15810

RIO SABANA BASIN

50067000 RIO SABANA AT SABANA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
JUN, 18	1244	8.2	105	26.0	AUG, 15	1312	10	87	26.0
JUL, 17	1247	6.0	118	26.5	SEP, 09	1214	5.4	118	26.5

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'56", long 65°41'42", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank off Highway 976, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Highway 977 bridge, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) downstream from Quebrada Peñón, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) northeast of Colonia Paraiso, and 3.3 mi (5.3 km) southwest of Fajardo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--14.9 mi² (38.6 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1960-61 (occasional low and peak-flow measurements only), March 1961 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 137.60 ft (41.940 m) above mean sea level. Due to flood damage, gage datum has had changes as follows: Mar. 24, 1961 to May 5, 1969, 138.95 ft (42.352 m); May 6, 1969 to Mar. 16, 1972, 135.05 ft (41.163 m); Mar. 17, 1972 to Mar 25, 1975, 138.60 ft (42.245 m).

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: July 23 to Aug. 4. Records fair, except those for estimated daily discharges which are poor. Low flow affected by diversions for water supply about 400 m upstream from gaging station (estimated mean daily discharge is 9.0 ft³/s (0.255 m³/s).

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--25 years (1962-86), 67.7 ft³/s (1.917 m³/s), 61.70 in/yr (1,567 mm/yr), 49,050 acre-ft/yr (60.5 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 68 ft³/s (1.32 m³/s), 49,300 acre-ft/yr (61 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 19,600 ft³/s (555 m³/s), Oct. 24, 1974, gage height, 13.62 ft (4.151 m), datum then in use, from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analyses and slope-area measurements of peak discharges; minimum discharge, 0.86 ft³/s (0.024 m³/s), May 3, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,500 ft³/s (99.1 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1530	6,760	191	10.41	3.173	May 13	0945	*7,900	224	*11.15	3.398
May 7	0330	3,860	109	8.17	2.490						

Minimum discharge, 4.1 ft³/s (0.110 m³/s), Apr. 26, 27.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	57	102	42	34	22	6.6	13	338	64	16	32	188		
2	227	217	42	46	29	5.8	8.7	131	41	15	24	43		
3	146	74	37	41	26	5.6	7.3	84	34	18	23	30		
4	66	61	34	66	292	5.9	22	32	31	17	25	27		
5	76	57	85	32	74	6.5	272	19	31	19	17	48		
6	2120	54	45	27	31	6.2	60	48	26	36	16	97		
7	555	47	37	23	25	11	19	488	25	31	16	30		
8	165	42	35	22	21	6.4	21	69	24	23	16	24		
9	86	39	49	217	18	8.6	15	190	35	16	15	21		
10	57	37	50	48	17	7.4	11	166	47	15	16	19		
11	47	123	42	32	18	7.6	12	162	30	14	47	17		
12	38	354	50	26	14	8.2	7.5	49	45	19	39	16		
13	30	418	38	24	15	25	7.1	575	48	15	184	16		
14	26	292	31	22	13	39	6.2	374	38	16	70	15		
15	23	911	45	21	12	55	5.6	44	65	62	50	15		
16	20	246	37	29	10	17	8.3	29	50	26	25	14		
17	21	171	41	26	13	9.8	9.5	24	49	34	18	13		
18	287	153	35	20	13	7.3	5.6	376	26	21	15	12		
19	58	125	40	19	18	6.6	4.6	70	31	18	14	12		
20	32	124	50	20	20	7.0	4.4	32	25	17	13	11		
21	48	185	49	26	9.7	6.2	8.9	32	23	18	13	11		
22	41	83	74	21	8.5	5.2	11	32	21	15	16	12		
23	428	82	50	36	7.5	4.7	6.7	23	18	15	24	17		
24	945	75	40	56	7.1	4.6	11	21	18	25	241	14		
25	222	62	31	31	7.7	7.9	6.0	19	18	20	62	11		
26	209	55	37	20	7.2	11	4.4	19	17	15	23	13		
27	162	50	27	17	6.6	14	33	24	52	14	17	19		
28	110	47	36	16	7.4	23	156	22	19	17	337	24		
29	192	43	27	16	---	62	504	136	18	47	481	14		
30	97	62	24	21	---	18	360	32	16	136	72	23		
31	106	---	22	28	---	20	---	421	---	58	45	---		
TOTAL	6697	4391	1282	1083	762.7	429.1	1620.8	4081	985	828	2006	826		
MEAN	216	146	41.4	34.9	27.2	13.8	54.0	132	32.8	26.7	64.7	27.5		
MAX	2120	911	85	217	292	62	504	575	65	136	481	188		
MIN	20	37	22	16	6.6	4.6	4.4	19	16	14	13	11		
CFSM	14.5	9.80	2.78	2.34	1.83	.93	3.62	8.86	2.20	1.79	4.34	1.85		
IN.	16.72	10.96	3.20	2.70	1.90	1.07	4.05	10.19	2.46	2.07	5.01	2.06		
AC-FT	13280	8710	2540	2150	1510	851	3210	8090	1950	1640	3980	1640		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	24980.7	MEAN	68.4	MAX	2120	MIN	4.3	CFSM	4.59	IN.	62.37	AC-FT	49550
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	24991.6	MEAN	68.5	MAX	2120	MIN	4.4	CFSM	4.60	IN.	62.40	AC-FT	49570

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1982 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.--USD-49 Sediment sampler since February 1983.

REMARKS.--Sediment samples were collected by a local observer once daily during low flow and more than once daily during high flow events for concentration and particle size analyses. Sediment samples were also collected periodically by survey staff.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 2,210 mg/L October 6, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 2.0 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 22,100 tons (20,000 tonnes) October 6, 1985; minimum daily, 0.02 tons (0.02 tonne) March 24, 1986.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 2,210 mg/L October 6, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 2.0 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 22,100 tons (20,000 tonnes) October 6, 1985; minimum daily, 0.02 tons (0.02 tonne) March 24, 1986.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985										
23...	1215	102	96	7.40	24.5	24	8.8	--	--	2300 4800
DEC										
03...	1310	35	128	8.20	25.5	3.4	--	--	<10	360 160
FEB 1986										
11...	1240	26	133	7.90	24.0	3.0	9.6	--	14	54 K32
APR										
14...	1230	6.7	143	8.20	27.0	2.4	9.7	123	25	K140 K14
JUL										
02...	1100	15	127	8.60	28.0	2.5	9.9	127	15	80 K1400
SEP										
02...	1150	42	94	7.05	25.5	8.9	8.5	105	11	K1000 600

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
23...	20	0	4.4	2.3	7.4	0.7	1.2	21	<.05	7.1	9.0
DEC											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	39	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	34	--	--	--
APR											
14...	36	0	7.7	4.1	12	0.9	1.2	43	<0.5	5.4	15
JUL											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	41	--	--	--
SEP											
02...	24	0	5.1	2.7	8.7	0.8	1.2	25	--	8.6	8.7

K = non-ideal count

RIO FAJARDO BASIN
50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued
WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	ALDRIN, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DDD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DDE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DDT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)
JUL 1986 02...	1100	<0.1	<0.01	<0.1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	ENDRIN, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	ETHION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	LINDANE DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	MALA- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)
JUL 1986 02...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	MIREX, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	PARA- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	PER- THANE DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	TRI- THION DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)
JUL 1986 02...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.1	<0.1	<1	<0.01

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	57	21	5.5	102	58	36	42	20	2.4
2	227	134	170	217	176	353	42	19	2.2
3	146	107	77	74	37	7.6	37	17	1.6
4	66	13	2.4	61	29	4.8	34	16	1.4
5	76	25	5.9	57	27	4.1	85	63	34
6	2120	2210	22100	54	26	4.0	45	23	3.0
7	555	346	857	47	21	2.7	37	17	1.7
8	165	90	42	42	18	2.0	35	18	1.9
9	86	44	11	39	13	1.4	49	24	3.8
10	57	27	4.2	37	10	1.0	50	25	3.8
11	47	22	2.8	123	95	154	42	19	2.6
12	38	17	1.7	354	301	538	50	16	2.5
13	30	14	1.1	418	291	1020	38	6	.63
14	26	12	.84	292	240	409	31	4	.33
15	23	11	.68	911	865	4170	45	22	3.2
16	20	9	.49	246	171	147	37	17	1.8
17	21	9	.51	171	101	51	41	20	2.4
18	287	415	3260	153	102	54	35	17	1.7
19	58	27	6.7	125	72	29	40	19	2.2
20	32	15	1.3	124	71	26	50	25	4.1
21	48	25	4.4	185	143	182	49	26	5.8
22	41	39	53	83	41	9.2	74	33	7.9
23	428	394	1530	82	41	9.4	50	26	4.1
24	945	851	3710	75	37	7.7	40	21	2.5
25	222	155	148	62	30	5.0	31	11	.93
26	209	145	157	55	27	4.0	37	19	2.2
27	162	91	56	50	24	3.2	27	13	.95
28	110	60	20	47	21	2.6	36	17	1.9
29	192	132	115	43	20	2.4	27	14	1.0
30	97	52	15	62	32	6.8	24	12	.79
31	106	64	26	---	---	---	22	11	.73
TOTAL	6697	---	32385.52	4391	---	7246.9	1282	---	106.06

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	34	19	2.7	22	10	.67	6.6	8	.14
2	46	20	3.8	29	15	1.7	5.8	5	.08
3	41	27	7.1	26	15	2.1	5.6	5	.08
4	66	37	10	292	302	794	5.9	8	.14
5	32	15	1.3	74	41	14	6.5	8	.13
6	27	10	.73	31	14	1.1	6.2	7	.17
7	23	10	.62	25	11	.74	11	10	.37
8	22	10	.59	21	10	.57	6.4	5	.09
9	217	180	384	18	8	.39	8.6	12	.41
10	48	33	5.3	17	8	.37	7.4	4	.08
11	32	14	1.2	18	10	.48	7.6	3	.05
12	26	12	.84	14	6	.23	8.2	4	.08
13	24	11	.71	15	9	.52	25	13	1.7
14	22	9	.53	13	5	.18	39	22	4.0
15	21	9	.51	12	7	.23	55	26	8.9
16	29	13	1.2	10	7	.19	17	8	.43
17	26	13	.94	13	7	.25	9.8	5	.14
18	20	9	.49	13	6	.21	7.3	4	.08
19	19	8	.41	18	9	.74	6.6	3	.05
20	20	6	.32	20	13	1.1	7.0	4	.08
21	26	11	.85	9.7	7	.18	6.2	3	.05
22	21	11	.68	8.5	5	.11	5.2	2	.03
23	36	16	1.7	7.5	5	.10	4.7	2	.03
24	56	22	4.3	7.1	5	.10	4.6	2	.02
25	31	14	1.4	7.7	5	.10	7.9	5	.13
26	20	9	.49	7.2	4	.08	11	6	.36
27	17	6	.28	6.6	8	.14	14	10	.56
28	16	6	.26	7.4	9	.22	23	19	4.1
29	16	6	.26	---	---	---	62	35	11
30	21	10	.44	---	---	---	18	7	.46
31	28	13	1.1	---	---	---	20	10	.72
TOTAL	1083	---	435.05	762.7	---	820.80	429.1	---	34.66

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	13	6	.23	338	277	1050	64	26	6.3
2	8.7	5	.17	131	111	130	41	13	1.4
3	7.3	5	.13	84	71	101	34	15	1.3
4	22	15	4.2	32	19	2.2	31	14	1.2
5	272	236	643	19	14	.85	31	10	.84
6	60	43	25	48	36	47	26	10	.70
7	19	7	.36	488	468	1050	25	11	.74
8	21	10	.81	69	36	9.1	24	11	.71
9	15	7	.32	190	197	640	35	31	4.1
10	11	5	.16	166	286	383	47	31	6.5
11	12	5	.16	162	122	105	30	14	1.2
12	7.5	4	.08	49	24	3.4	45	27	4.1
13	7.1	3	.06	575	517	5890	48	28	6.1
14	6.2	3	.05	374	295	1030	38	21	2.7
15	5.6	3	.04	44	21	2.6	65	38	11
16	8.3	5	.14	29	13	1.0	50	29	5.7
17	9.5	8	.22	24	7	.51	49	37	10
18	5.6	5	.08	376	354	1230	26	11	.78
19	4.6	3	.04	70	43	15	31	19	2.0
20	4.4	3	.04	32	15	1.3	25	14	.94
21	8.9	5	.14	32	17	1.9	23	10	.64
22	11	5	.17	32	17	2.0	21	9	.54
23	6.7	3	.06	23	11	.68	18	7	.34
24	11	17	.74	21	10	.57	18	7	.34
25	6.0	5	.08	19	8	.41	18	8	.39
26	4.4	5	.06	19	8	.41	17	9	.52
27	33	19	5.6	24	12	1.1	52	34	19
28	156	128	278	22	12	.76	19	5	.26
29	504	558	2040	136	109	239	18	4	.19
30	360	445	1290	32	21	2.0	16	3	.13
31	---	---	---	421	321	1290	---	---	---
TOTAL	1620.8	---	4290.14	4081	---	13230.79	985	---	90.66

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	16	3	.13	32	20	1.7	188	117	384
2	15	6	.24	24	11	.71	43	12	1.7
3	18	8	.39	23	10	.62	30	9	.73
4	17	10	.46	25	11	.74	27	9	.65
5	19	9	.62	17	8	.37	48	27	6.6
6	36	19	2.5	16	6	.26	97	67	40
7	31	16	1.5	16	3	.13	30	14	1.1
8	23	11	.85	16	2	.09	24	11	.71
9	16	8	.35	15	4	.16	21	14	.79
10	15	6	.24	16	8	.35	19	13	.67
11	14	7	.26	47	31	19	17	11	.50
12	19	11	.67	39	33	12	16	10	.43
13	15	9	.36	184	178	552	16	9	.39
14	16	9	.42	70	43	15	15	7	.28
15	62	32	7.9	50	28	7.0	15	6	.24
16	26	17	1.2	25	9	.58	14	7	.26
17	34	20	1.9	18	6	.29	13	9	.32
18	21	10	.58	15	5	.20	12	9	.29
19	18	8	.39	14	3	.11	12	9	.29
20	17	7	.32	13	2	.07	11	9	.27
21	18	7	.34	13	2	.07	11	8	.24
22	15	7	.28	16	5	.25	12	5	.16
23	15	7	.28	24	13	2.4	17	7	.32
24	25	4	.16	241	179	278	14	6	.23
25	20	10	.54	62	51	27	11	5	.15
26	15	7	.28	23	11	.67	13	5	.18
27	14	6	.23	17	7	.33	19	8	.41
28	17	8	.37	337	268	884	24	13	1.3
29	47	46	67	481	396	1330	14	6	.23
30	136	10	1.4	72	24	7.6	23	12	1.6
31	58	24	3.8	45	13	1.9	---	---	---
TOTAL	828	---	95.96	2006	---	3143.60	826	---	445.04

RIO FAJARDO BASIN
50072500 RIO FAJARDO BELOW FAJARDO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'35", long 65°38'47", 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southwest of Playa de Fajardo, and 0.5 mi (0.8 km) east of Fajardo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--23.4 sq mi (60.6 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
30...	1130	91	150	6.70	26.5	1900	--	--	15	5700	5700
DEC											
03...	1620	45	180	7.80	26.5	4.5	--	--	<10	26000	4500
FEB 1986											
11...	1545	26	184	7.80	26.5	2.3	6.0	--	35	K20000	4200
MAY											
06...	1230	154	155	7.00	26.5	330	6.6	83	50	K80000	80000
JUL											
02...	1425	24	172	7.70	31.0	3.0	8.7	117	<10	K120	K80
SEP											
02...	1410	77	136	7.25	28.0	17	8.0	103	<10	26000	8500

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
30...	38	3	8.5	4.0	10	0.7	1.8	35	<0.5	8.2	16
DEC											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	48	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	44	--	--	--
MAY											
06...	34	0	8.2	3.4	11	0.8	2.3	35	<0.5	9.6	18
JUL											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	39	--	--	--
SEP											
02...	35	2	8.7	3.3	12	0.9	1.6	33	--	10	12

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
30...	0.10	21	91	22	16	0.360	0.040	0.400	0.130	0.57
DEC										
03...	--	--	--	--	1	--	<0.010	0.100	0.140	0.16
FEB 1986										
11...	--	--	--	--	1	--	--	--	--	--
MAY										
06...	<0.10	17	90	38	412	0.440	0.060	0.500	0.130	0.77
JUL										
02...	--	--	--	--	22	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.060	0.24
SEP										
02...	0.10	18	85	18	14	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.150	0.35

K = non-ideal count

RIO BLANCO BASIN

50075000 RIO ICACOS NEAR NAGUABO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°16'38", long 65°47'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, in Caribbean National Forest, off Highway 191, at El Yunque, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream from confluence with Rio Cubuy, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) north of Florida, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) northwest of Naguabo Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.26 mi² (3.26 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1945 to March 1953 (operated by Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority), annual maximum, water years 1953-62, annual low-flow measurements 1962-66, October 1979 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder, crest-stage gage and sharp-crested weir. Elevation of gage is 2,020 ft (616 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--No estimated daily discharges during water year. Records poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--14 years (1946-52, 1980-86), 15.1 ft³/s (0.428 m³/s), 162.74 in/yr (4,134 mm/yr), 10,940 acre-ft/yr (13.5 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 14 ft³/s (0.40 m³/s), 10,100 acre-ft/yr (12 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 2,860 ft³/s (81.0 m³/s), Apr. 21, 1983, gage height, 8.96 ft (2.731 m), from rating curve extended above 30 ft³/s (0.850 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum daily discharge, 1.5 ft³/s (0.042 m³/s), Mar. 22, Apr. 10, 1946.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 650 ft³/s (18.4 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 24	0630	756	21.4	5.60	1.707	May 13	0845	*859	24.3	*5.86	1.786
Apr. 5	1445	827	23.4	5.78	1.762						

Minimum discharge, 3.9 ft³/s (0.110 m³/s), Apr. 27.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	13	16	13	10	6.5	4.8	7.6	31	8.6	6.5	7.9	24
2	37	20	13	10	10	4.8	6.9	11	7.0	6.4	6.6	8.6
3	16	14	12	20	7.5	4.8	5.6	7.4	6.6	6.8	6.9	7.6
4	14	15	11	15	40	5.8	11	7.3	6.3	5.6	6.4	7.1
5	24	14	19	9.6	11	5.0	107	6.9	6.0	9.9	5.8	7.0
6	239	13	12	8.3	8.3	4.9	12	15	5.9	14	5.5	11
7	62	12	11	7.9	7.5	4.9	7.2	34	6.3	8.7	6.2	7.1
8	22	12	16	7.9	6.7	4.6	11	9.0	7.6	6.4	5.7	6.6
9	18	12	13	38	6.4	6.1	7.5	24	9.4	5.8	5.2	6.4
10	16	12	14	10	6.1	4.9	6.2	20	12	5.4	5.2	6.3
11	15	41	15	10	6.0	6.4	5.8	16	7.8	5.7	41	6.1
12	14	47	20	8.5	5.8	4.9	5.6	8.4	10	8.9	9.2	6.0
13	14	68	13	7.9	5.6	14	5.4	76	12	5.5	43	5.9
14	14	52	11	7.5	5.7	17	5.2	26	11	8.1	13	5.7
15	13	100	14	7.5	5.5	18	5.0	9.6	20	14	9.3	5.6
16	12	26	11	10	5.3	12	5.0	8.8	12	8.0	8.6	5.3
17	12	20	11	9.2	6.4	9.1	4.8	9.6	11	9.6	6.9	5.1
18	28	23	11	7.6	5.5	6.4	4.8	22	8.3	6.0	6.0	5.1
19	15	19	10	7.7	18	5.8	4.6	14	10	5.6	5.7	4.9
20	14	29	15	8.3	7.1	5.5	4.5	9.1	8.6	5.4	5.5	4.9
21	14	41	12	9.3	5.8	5.2	4.6	8.9	8.8	5.3	5.4	5.0
22	23	17	17	8.3	5.5	5.2	4.5	8.2	7.6	5.1	7.2	5.3
23	75	20	12	9.8	5.3	4.9	4.5	7.7	7.3	4.9	31	6.3
24	129	17	11	12	5.2	5.0	4.4	7.8	7.0	6.8	64	5.1
25	21	16	11	7.8	5.2	5.2	4.2	7.4	6.8	5.0	11	5.6
26	31	15	11	7.0	5.1	7.5	4.2	8.4	7.9	4.7	7.6	6.9
27	18	14	9.5	6.7	5.0	5.7	6.2	9.9	11	5.0	6.9	6.9
28	16	13	12	6.4	5.0	16	14	8.7	7.2	5.7	69	6.1
29	24	13	9.3	6.4	---	16	50	15	6.8	80	52	5.3
30	15	16	8.5	7.1	---	7.2	56	7.5	6.5	78	9.9	12
31	16	---	8.2	7.7	---	11	---	56	---	11	8.5	---
TOTAL	994	747	386.5	309.4	223.0	238.6	385.3	510.6	263.3	363.8	482.1	210.8
MEAN	32.1	24.9	12.5	9.98	7.96	7.70	12.8	16.5	8.78	11.7	15.6	7.03
MAX	239	100	20	38	40	18	107	76	20	80	69	24
MIN	12	12	8.2	6.4	5.0	4.6	4.2	6.9	5.9	4.7	5.2	4.9
CFSM	25.5	19.8	9.92	7.92	6.32	6.11	10.2	13.1	6.97	9.29	12.4	5.58
IN.	29.35	22.05	11.41	9.13	6.58	7.04	11.38	15.07	7.77	10.74	14.23	6.22
AC-FT	1970	1480	767	614	442	473	764	1010	522	722	956	418

CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	5343.6	MEAN	14.6	MAX	239	MIN	3.7	CFSM	11.6	IN.	157.76	AC-FT	10600
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	5114.4	MEAN	14.0	MAX	239	MIN	4.2	CFSM	11.1	IN.	151.00	AC-FT	10140

RIO BLANCO BASIN
50075000 RIO ICACOS NEAR NAGUABO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
MAY, 15	1034	9.8	56	20.5	AUG, 18	1034	6.2	69	21.0
JUN, 19	0948	8.3	60	20.5	SEP, 10	1006	6.4	69	21.0
JUL, 16	1031	6.5	68	21.0					

Figure 23.--Río Guanajibo basin.

RIO HUMACAO BASIN

50082000 RIO HUMACAO AT HIGHWAY 3 AT HUMACAO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-66, 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECA, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
17...	1645	73	157	7.50	28.0	64	7.6	--	20	43000	25000
DEC 19...	1055	31	264	7.80	27.0	10	8.0	--	20	K110000	39000
FEB 1986											
19...	1320	20	289	7.20	30.5	2.7	6.0	--	34	270000	K200000
APR 22...	0935	8.9	332	7.60	28.0	1.8	7.7	99	29	530000	110000
JUL 16...	1125	23	264	7.50	29.5	15	8.0	106	26	200000	7400
SEP 19...	0950	14	294	7.55	28.0	7.1	7.9	102	40	K11000	2200

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
17...	53	0	14	4.4	16	1	2.5	53	<0.5	11	17
DEC 19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	69	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	76	--	--	--
APR 22...	100	5	28	7.5	30	1	2.5	96	<0.5	14	37
JUL 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	79	--	--	--
SEP 19...	82	0	22	6.5	25	1	2.0	85	--	14	31

DATE	FLUORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
17...	0.10	31	130	25	84	0.760	0.040	0.800	0.250	0.85
DEC 19...	--	--	--	--	3	0.870	0.030	0.900	0.730	0.47
FEB 1986										
19...	--	--	--	--	11	0.930	0.070	1.00	0.620	0.48
APR 22...	0.20	38	210	5.2	1	0.760	0.040	0.800	1.30	0.40
JUL 16...	--	--	--	--	20	0.680	0.020	0.700	0.310	0.29
SEP 19...	0.10	40	190	7.0	7	0.980	0.020	1.00	0.250	0.15

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50083500 RIO GUAYANES AT YABUCA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'33", long 65°54'03", at bridge on Highway 182, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) west-northwest of Yabucoa plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.2 sq mi (44.6 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-62, 1968-70, 1980 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
18...	1145	84	132	7.80	26.0	66	--	--	19	K32000	6700
DEC 18...	1045	37	170	7.50	23.5	--	8.4	--	--	K12000	4600
FEB 1986											
20...	1030	64	110	7.30	21.5	140	10.0	--	57	4800	2500
APR 25...	1050	19	166	7.40	25.0	5.0	8.4	102	20	560	450
JUL 22...	1215	28	155	7.35	28.0	10	8.1	104	13	K1500	680
SEP 22...	1325	34	156	7.50	27.5	10	8.0	102	<10	2000	2700

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
18...	37	0	9.3	3.4	12	0.9	1.3	44	<0.5	8.6	11
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	51	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	27	--	--	--
APR 25...	48	0	12	4.5	15	1	1.3	59	<0.5	5.7	10
JUL 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	57	--	--	--
SEP 22...	44	0	11	4.0	14	0.9	1.4	57	--	6.1	11

DATE	FLUORIDE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
18...	0.10	32	100	24	90	0.380	0.020	0.400	0.070	0.23
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	<0.010	0.500	0.020	0.18
FEB 1986										
20...	--	--	--	--	192	0.460	0.040	0.500	0.070	0.83
APR 25...	0.10	38	120	6.4	2	--	<0.010	0.200	0.030	0.27
JUL 22...	--	--	--	--	14	--	<0.010	0.200	0.050	0.55
SEP 22...	0.20	36	120	11	18	--	<0.010	0.200	0.060	0.24

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50083500 RIO GUAYANES AT YABUCOA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985 18...	0.30	0.70	3.1	0.090	<1	<100	20	1	4	10
DEC 18...	0.20	0.70	3.1	0.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 20...	0.90	1.4	6.2	0.110	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 25...	0.30	0.50	2.2	0.030	<1	100	10	<1	5	<10
JUL 22...	0.60	0.80	3.5	0.050	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 22...	0.30	0.50	2.2	0.060	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1985 18...	5300	2	150	0.10	<1	<1	40	<0.010	2	0.05
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 25...	850	1	100	<0.10	<1	<1	<10	<0.010	<1	0.02
JUL 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	ALDRIN, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DDD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DDE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DDT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)
JUL 1986 22...	1215	<0.1	<0.01	<0.1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	ENDRIN, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	ETHION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	LINDANE DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	MALA- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)
JUL 1986 22...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	MIREX, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	PARA- THION, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	PER- THANE DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L)	DIS- SOLVE TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUL 1986 22...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.1	<0.1	<10	<0.01

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50086500 RIO GUAYANES ABOVE MOUTH AT PLAYA DE GUAYANES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'45", long 65°49'42", at old railroad crossing, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) from mouth, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Playa de Guayanés, and 3.5 mi (5.6 km) northeast of Yabucoa plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--34.0 sq mi (88.1 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
31...	1250	402	132	7.10	28.0	120	8.8	--	33	3400	3900
DEC 18...	1430	88	182	7.70	26.0	13	7.2	--	<10	K460	K430
FEB 1986											
20...	1300	100	285	7.60	27.5	21	10.0	--	49	4400	2800
MAY 08...	1130	77	162	7.60	27.5	18	7.9	101	23	3700	2600
JUL 22...	0955	57	201	7.55	27.5	22	7.4	94	14	K790	530
SEP 22...	1055	46	197	7.65	27.0	11	8.7	110	29	6000	4900

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CaCO3	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CaCO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
31...	56	18	16	4.0	10	0.6	2.4	38	<0.5	9.9	11
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	49	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	79	--	--	--
MAY 08...	37	0	9.5	3.3	13	1	3.1	43	<0.5	9.2	12
JUL 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	66	--	--	--
SEP 22...	49	0	12	4.6	18	1	1.8	66	--	10	15

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
31...	<0.10	25	100	110	276	0.340	0.060	0.400	0.120	0.98
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	14	--	<0.010	0.500	0.020	0.28
FEB 1986										
20...	--	--	--	--	50	0.560	0.040	0.600	0.120	0.58
MAY 08...	<0.10	28	100	22	44	0.290	0.010	0.300	0.070	0.53
JUL 22...	--	--	--	--	26	--	<0.010	0.400	0.030	0.27
SEP 22...	0.20	35	140	17	13	--	<0.010	0.200	0.050	0.15

K = non-ideal count

RIO MAUNABO BASIN
50091000 RIO MAUNABO AT MAUNABO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'24", long 65°54'19", at bridge on Highway 3, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) southwest of Maunabo plaza, and 1.3 mi (2.1 km) upstream from mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.4 sq mi (32.1 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-66, 1975 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
17...	1210	41	216	7.90	28.0	14	7.6	--	19	3500	1900
DEC 17...	1430	19	240	7.80	28.0	3.4	7.6	98	<10	K1200	520
FEB 1986											
19...	1030	17	240	7.40	26.5	3.4	6.8	--	26	2000	1500
MAY 07...	0955	55	156	7.40	23.5	42	7.8	93	31	4300	45000
JUL 23...	1310	19	207	7.50	30.0	4.2	7.6	101	25	21000	470
SEP 23...	1205	16	230	7.65	30.0	16	8.0	107	20	35000	6000

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
17...	63	0	15	6.1	17	1	1.1	67	<0.5	11	16
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	72	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	74	--	--	--
MAY 07...	41	9	9.7	4.1	11	0.8	2.1	32	<0.5	10	25
JUL 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	74	--	--	--
SEP 23...	60	0	14	6.2	18	1	1.5	72	--	8.5	15

DATE	FLUORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TOMS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
17...	0.10	38	140	16	31	0.490	0.010	0.500	0.040	0.36
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	5	--	<0.010	0.400	0.020	0.28
FEB 1986										
19...	--	--	--	--	13	--	<0.010	0.200	0.030	0.17
MAY 07...	<0.10	23	100	16	60	0.780	0.020	0.800	0.150	0.75
JUL 23...	--	--	--	--	34	--	<0.010	0.200	0.020	0.38
SEP 23...	0.20	35	140	6.0	50	--	<0.010	0.100	0.080	0.22

K = non-ideal count

RIO CHICO BASIN
50091800 RIO CHICO AT PROVIDENCIA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'16", long 66°00'18", at flat low bridge 200 ft (61 m) south of Highway 3, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) above mouth, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) southeast of Patillas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.9 sq mi (12.8 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
31...	1700	40	282	6.90	28.0	18	8.0	104	19	K2000	4900
DEC 17...	1230	2.5	624	7.40	27.0	1.5	0.8	--	87	K140000	20000
FEB 1986											
13...	1600	0.66	921	7.40	28.0	15	0	--	220	290000	K100000
MAY 07...	1245	0.38	801	7.40	30.5	26	0	0	240	2000000	K110000
JUL 23...	1055	0.86	540	7.45	30.0	4.0	0	0	110	2500000	K140000
SEP 23...	0910	0.25	744	7.35	28.5	7.5	0.3	4	270	K1200000	150000

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
31...	61	0	14	6.3	21	1	1.3	85	<0.5	17	23
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	156	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	207	--	--	--
MAY 07...	110	0	27	10	70	3	11	238	1.6	43	69
JUL 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	174	--	--	--
SEP 23...	130	0	31	13	63	2	11	215	--	32	70

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
31...	0.10	28	160	17	36	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.270	0.43
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	1	--	0.010	<0.100	5.70	2.9
FEB 1986										
13...	--	--	--	--	2	--	0.020	<0.100	18.0	6.0
MAY 07...	<0.10	29	400	0.41	14	--	0.020	<0.100	0.290	39
JUL 23...	--	--	--	--	16	--	0.010	<0.100	12.0	7.0
SEP 23...	0.20	33	380	0.26	23	--	0.030	<0.100	4.60	31

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'04", long 66°01'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, at foot bridge, off Highway 184, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from Lago Patillas Dam and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest of Patillas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.3 mi² (47.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to October 1965 (annual low-flow and occasional measurements only), January 1966 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 235 ft (72 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 27 to Nov. 18. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--20 years (1967-86), 60.7 ft³/s (1.719 m³/s), 45.04 in/yr (1,144 mm/yr), 43,980 acre-ft/yr (54.2 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 61 ft³/s (1.73 m³/s), 44,200 acre-ft/yr (54 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 14,800 ft³/s (419 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage height, 12.45 ft (3.795 m), from rating curve extended above 250 ft³/s (7.08 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 4.6 ft³/s (0.130 m³/s), May 13-16, 1968.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,500 ft³/s (70.8 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1145	*8,440	239	*12.49	3.807	May 13	0845	3,490	98.8	9.37	2.856
Oct. 26	1715	4,130	117	9.87	3.008	May 18	1200	2,620	74.2	8.59	2.618

Minimum discharge, 6.2 ft³/s (0.176 m³/s), Apr. 26, 27.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	63	120	44	29	24	14	35	41	52	30	18	48		
2	60	80	43	32	23	13	23	18	43	26	16	40		
3	88	200	41	37	33	12	16	12	43	25	15	32		
4	83	135	41	45	43	15	119	9.5	39	23	19	28		
5	179	120	47	34	46	15	55	8.7	40	22	17	29		
6	2570	100	50	28	28	13	49	36	38	30	14	28		
7	1570	90	48	26	23	13	24	42	33	30	25	26		
8	629	80	41	26	21	11	20	19	35	22	44	22		
9	245	75	40	49	21	11	24	25	134	20	18	21		
10	158	70	40	49	20	11	18	251	222	17	16	20		
11	117	65	40	33	20	12	16	217	72	31	55	19		
12	93	85	64	29	20	12	14	75	55	38	34	19		
13	76	165	49	27	20	14	13	455	59	22	57	19		
14	65	170	39	26	18	23	12	257	71	22	46	20		
15	57	900	36	26	18	35	12	102	52	34	22	19		
16	52	230	35	26	17	18	11	65	60	28	17	17		
17	64	170	34	33	24	13	11	60	49	23	16	15		
18	75	100	35	35	26	11	11	443	43	21	15	11		
19	62	81	38	29	43	9.9	11	162	41	17	14	11		
20	46	73	42	27	38	9.3	13	99	41	15	14	11		
21	45	68	35	28	26	8.3	12	81	37	19	13	11		
22	44	59	34	26	21	7.8	9.4	77	33	16	12	17		
23	221	56	32	25	17	7.8	9.0	58	31	14	13	26		
24	262	53	46	93	15	7.8	8.4	48	30	12	15	90		
25	204	50	44	50	15	7.1	8.0	43	30	12	13	111		
26	553	49	41	36	15	9.4	7.0	40	30	11	11	67		
27	280	47	33	30	14	18	7.2	38	36	9.8	11	33		
28	110	46	34	29	14	18	10	37	32	14	111	26		
29	280	44	31	28	---	216	213	44	27	16	573	22		
30	250	47	32	29	---	45	75	39	24	28	101	20		
31	270	---	29	26	---	36	---	161	---	22	58	---		
TOTAL	8871	3628	1238	1046	663	666.4	866.0	3063.2	1532	669.8	1423	878		
MEAN	286	121	39.9	33.7	23.7	21.5	28.9	98.8	51.1	21.6	45.9	29.3		
MAX	2570	900	64	93	46	216	213	455	222	38	573	111		
MIN	44	44	29	25	14	7.1	7.0	8.7	24	9.3	11	11		
CFSM	15.6	6.61	2.18	1.84	1.30	1.17	1.58	5.40	2.79	1.18	2.51	1.60		
IN.	18.03	7.37	2.52	2.13	1.35	1.35	1.76	6.23	3.11	1.36	2.89	1.78		
AC-FT	17600	7200	2460	2070	1320	1320	1720	6080	3040	1330	2820	1740		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	25899.5	MEAN	71.0	MAX	2570	MIN	8.3	CFSM	3.88	IN.	52.65	AC-FT	51370
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	24544.4	MEAN	67.2	MAX	2570	MIN	7.0	CFSM	3.67	IN.	49.89	AC-FT	48680

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED SATUR- ATION	COLI- FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)
OCT 1985 21...	1530	58	173	8.20	27.0	16	8.6	108	K5600	K5500	49
JAN 1986 13...	1500	27	156	8.30	27.0	1.0	7.6	96	>1200	K39	49
APR 07...	1410	24	138	8.10	27.0	--	8.0	102	300	530	--
JUL 01...	1220	33	154	8.00	27.5	1.8	8.3	106	380	300	48

DATE	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED AS SI02)
OCT 1985 21...	1	11	5.1	14	0.9	0.70	48	8.2	12	<0.10	26
JAN 1986 13...	0	11	5.1	13	0.8	0.40	56	11	11	0.10	23
APR 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	--	--
JUL 01...	0	11	4.9	14	0.9	0.60	74	11	9.7	0.20	24

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITU- ENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHORUS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHORUS, ORTHO, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHATE, ORTHO, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS P04)
OCT 1985 21...	101	110	16	0.140	0.120	0.15	0.30	0.020	<0.010	<0.010	--
JAN 1986 13...	103	110	7.5	--	--	--	0.30	0.030	0.010	--	--
APR 07...	--	--	--	0.100	0.030	0.04	0.30	0.020	0.030	0.010	0.03
JUL 01...	105	120	9.3	<0.100	<0.010	--	0.30	0.020	0.020	0.020	0.06

DATE	ALUM- INUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYL- LIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)
OCT 1985 21...	40	1	17	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	<1	41	<1
JAN 1986 13...	10	<1	16	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	1	18	<1
APR 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUL 01...	20	<1	11	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	1	18	<5

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	LITHIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)	MANGA- NESE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRON- TIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
OCT 1985 21...	<4	18	0.2	<10	<1	<1	<1	39	<6	7
JAN 1986 13...	<4	7	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1	39	<6	4
APR 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUL 01...	<4	5	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1	38	<6	7

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1985 21...	1505	88	43	10	79
JAN 1986 13...	1530	24	26	1.7	90
APR 07...	1400	25	21	1.4	95
JUL 01...	1210	29	25	2.0	98

RIO COAMO BASIN
50106500 RIO COAMO NEAR COAMO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1978 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
NOV 1985											
02...	1240	143	677	8.00	28.0	44	8.4	109	10	4800	1700
DEC											
02...	1500	65	682	8.20	28.0	12	9.2	120	10	K13000	870
FEB 1986											
25...	1130	15	715	7.90	26.0	2.4	8.4	104	23	--	--
APR											
29...	1220	15	675	8.20	30.0	2.3	8.0	108	50	K71000	8800
JUL											
07...	1200	21	609	8.15	31.5	2.0	9.1	125	21	370	K140
SEP											
03...	1240	17	571	8.00	33.0	3.0	6.2	88	<10	K6500	520

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
NOV 1985											
02...	240	26	66	19	28	0.8	2.8	217	<0.5	30	38
DEC											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	217	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	236	--	--	--
APR											
29...	240	0	65	20	38	1	3.3	245	<0.5	33	47
JUL											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	232	--	--	--
SEP											
03...	240	22	63	19	35	1	3.3	214	--	34	36

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
NOV 1985										
02...	0.20	31	350	133	87	3.38	0.020	3.40	0.160	0.54
DEC										
02...	--	--	--	--	24	4.06	0.040	4.10	0.330	0.67
FEB 1986										
25...	--	--	--	--	12	3.19	0.210	3.40	0.660	0.74
APR										
29...	0.20	27	380	15	32	1.58	0.120	1.70	1.60	0.80
JUL										
07...	--	--	--	--	5	2.27	0.130	2.40	0.360	0.54
SEP										
03...	0.20	32	350	16	4	2.08	0.120	2.20	0.800	0.60

K = non-ideal count

RIO DESCALABRADO BASIN

50108000 RIO DESCALABRADO NEAR LOS LLANOS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'08", long 66°25'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Highway 14, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) west of Los Llanos, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) east of Juana Diaz.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.9 mi² (33.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1959-65 (annual low-flow measurements only), 1965 (annual maximum discharge), January 1966 to June 1969, July to December 1969 (maximum discharge only), February 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 220 ft (67 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 1-24, Dec. 13 to Jan. 9. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 30,000 ft³/s (850 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 24.37 ft (7.43 m), from rating curve extended above 10,000 ft³/s (283 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; no flow many days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	unknown	*30,000	850	*24.37	7.428	May 13	0645	7,900	224	14.56	4.448

Minimum daily discharge, 0.90 ft³/s (0.025 m³/s), Aug. 21-23.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	5.7	23	7.8	6.2	4.7	2.1	1.8	2.7	13	4.7	2.5	3.5		
2	5.6	21	7.5	6.4	4.6	2.3	1.8	1.8	11	4.6	2.3	2.5		
3	5.4	27	8.8	6.0	5.0	2.3	2.1	2.7	11	4.4	2.1	2.2		
4	5.0	15	9.4	6.2	5.2	2.3	6.3	1.7	11	4.3	1.9	2.1		
5	6.0	13	9.1	6.0	4.7	2.3	3.7	1.4	10	4.3	1.8	1.8		
6	200	64	8.6	6.2	4.2	2.3	2.6	1.4	9.7	4.3	1.7	1.6		
7	2600	32	8.3	6.4	4.0	2.2	2.4	2.3	9.4	4.5	2.0	1.6		
8	300	26	11	6.2	3.6	2.2	2.6	3.0	9.1	4.3	4.5	1.6		
9	30	21	12	7.0	3.4	2.1	3.7	1.9	8.9	4.3	2.2	1.5		
10	22	20	10	6.5	3.2	2.2	2.5	16	9.3	4.0	2.0	1.5		
11	18	19	10	6.1	3.1	2.1	2.2	32	8.1	3.9	1.9	1.4		
12	16	17	10	6.3	3.1	2.1	2.0	2.9	7.7	3.8	1.6	1.6		
13	15	16	9.8	6.2	2.9	1.9	1.9	686	7.6	3.4	1.4	1.7		
14	20	15	9.4	6.0	2.6	2.0	1.9	74	7.3	3.6	1.8	1.6		
15	13	15	9.0	6.2	2.9	1.9	1.9	26	7.0	4.2	1.7	1.6		
16	10	13	8.8	6.2	2.8	1.9	3.2	16	7.0	3.8	1.4	1.5		
17	9.0	13	8.4	6.6	3.0	1.8	5.1	17	6.6	3.2	1.3	1.5		
18	8.4	14	8.2	6.7	3.1	2.0	2.3	14	6.4	3.0	1.3	1.5		
19	8.0	11	8.4	6.2	2.8	2.4	1.9	9.4	6.4	2.8	1.3	1.4		
20	7.4	10	8.6	6.3	3.7	2.2	1.8	7.7	6.0	2.3	1.2	1.5		
21	8.0	10	9.0	6.1	3.3	2.2	1.7	7.0	5.8	2.8	1.1	1.5		
22	7.0	9.2	8.8	5.8	3.0	1.9	1.7	6.1	5.6	2.6	1.1	1.5		
23	10	9.5	8.6	5.7	2.4	1.7	1.7	5.2	5.4	2.5	4.5	1.5		
24	12	9.6	8.6	5.7	2.2	1.6	1.6	4.4	5.2	2.9	1.4	2.1		
25	10	9.2	8.0	7.6	2.0	1.6	1.7	3.8	5.2	3.8	1.1	2.3		
26	12	8.8	7.4	8.0	3.0	1.6	1.7	2.9	5.1	3.0	1.2	2.0		
27	5.6	8.0	6.8	6.2	2.1	1.5	1.7	2.2	5.1	2.8	1.1	2.2		
28	15	7.8	6.3	6.8	2.1	1.6	2.4	1.7	5.0	2.7	1.8	2.7		
29	38	7.9	6.2	5.9	---	1.6	78	19	4.7	2.6	21	2.1		
30	95	8.0	6.0	9.2	---	1.5	5.8	8.3	4.7	2.7	2.0	1.4		
31	25	---	6.0	6.3	---	1.6	---	77	---	2.9	3.1	---		
TOTAL	3542.1	493.0	264.8	199.2	92.7	61.0	151.7	1057.5	224.3	109.5	77.3	54.5		
MEAN	114	16.4	8.54	6.43	3.31	1.97	5.06	34.1	7.48	3.53	2.49	1.82		
MAX	2600	64	12	9.2	5.2	2.4	78	686	13	4.7	21	3.5		
MIN	5.0	7.8	6.0	5.7	2.0	1.5	1.6	1.4	4.7	2.5	1.1	1.4		
CFSM	8.84	1.27	.66	.50	.26	.15	.39	2.64	.58	.27	.19	.14		
IN.	10.21	1.42	.76	.57	.27	.18	.44	3.05	.65	.32	.22	.16		
AC-FT	7030	978	525	395	184	121	301	2100	445	217	153	108		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	7144.43	MEAN	19.6	MAX	2600	MIN	.47	CFSM	1.52	IN.	20.60	AC-FT	14170
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	6327.6	MEAN	17.3	MAX	2600	MIN	1.1	CFSM	1.34	IN.	18.25	AC-FT	12550

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50111500 RIO JACAGUAS AT JUANA DIAZ, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'16", long 66°30'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on Highway 14 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Juana Diaz plaza, and 4.0 mi (6.4 km) downstream from Lago Guayabal.

DRAINAGE AREA.--49.8 mi² (129.0 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 131 ft (40 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 1, 2, Oct. 7-30, Jan. 24 to Feb. 2 and Feb. 9-15. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Flow regulation from Lago Guayabal.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 40,000 ft³/s (1,130 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 29.42 ft (8.967 m) from rating curve extended above 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and logarithmic extension; minimum daily discharge, 1.2 ft³/s (0.034 m³/s), May 18, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum discharge, 40,000 ft³/s (1,130 m³/s), Oct. 7, gage height, 29.42 ft (8.967 m) from rating curve extended above 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and logarithmic extension; minimum daily discharge 1.6 ft³/s (0.045 m³/s), Mar. 21.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	100	259	55	32	8.3	4.6	2.7	8.9	84	7.8	6.2	6.4		
2	90	225	58	36	15	4.4	2.9	8.1	56	7.8	6.3	4.7		
3	43	275	82	34	21	4.5	3.6	11	78	6.9	6.2	4.8		
4	31	181	85	29	18	4.6	4.3	54	99	7.3	6.2	5.4		
5	40	547	80	17	17	4.5	5.3	52	99	7.7	6.4	4.8		
6	3440	215	80	19	16	4.4	5.6	56	91	8.2	6.7	3.9		
7	3000	249	71	33	14	4.3	5.5	65	73	8.3	7.1	3.9		
8	1000	184	48	42	13	4.2	5.7	81	78	8.3	7.2	3.7		
9	500	143	51	53	13	3.7	7.4	104	114	8.6	6.5	4.5		
10	250	107	64	57	12	3.6	7.2	148	97	7.4	6.4	5.0		
11	240	103	60	42	10	3.3	7.0	488	105	7.6	6.6	5.0		
12	210	136	53	19	7.8	2.8	7.5	131	77	7.8	6.6	4.5		
13	200	125	52	18	7.4	2.8	7.8	2150	64	7.3	7.9	4.2		
14	300	118	52	38	7.0	3.0	7.8	796	38	7.7	8.7	4.6		
15	200	128	45	33	6.6	2.9	7.8	280	13	8.2	8.5	4.8		
16	180	149	43	31	6.6	2.7	7.6	185	8.6	7.6	9.0	4.9		
17	150	114	47	25	6.5	2.6	7.3	135	21	7.5	8.1	5.3		
18	140	160	50	22	6.2	2.4	7.9	148	46	7.4	7.6	5.4		
19	130	146	35	16	6.5	2.3	7.5	150	52	6.6	7.6	3.6		
20	120	117	29	12	6.6	1.9	7.3	136	22	6.6	8.0	3.5		
21	140	107	38	20	6.3	1.6	7.1	120	18	6.6	7.9	3.5		
22	110	100	23	22	5.9	4.4	6.7	121	12	6.6	8.0	3.6		
23	300	81	25	13	5.9	5.2	6.2	112	8.1	6.6	7.9	3.7		
24	450	71	39	12	5.9	5.4	6.3	78	6.6	6.7	8.4	4.4		
25	400	73	44	11	5.6	5.4	7.5	46	10	6.9	7.6	4.4		
26	450	90	53	10	4.7	5.0	7.8	56	9.8	6.2	6.5	4.0		
27	250	89	43	10	4.4	5.0	7.4	69	8.9	5.4	6.1	17		
28	200	91	31	9.7	5.0	3.8	8.0	53	8.3	5.2	5.9	11		
29	300	86	19	9.7	---	3.6	12	177	7.7	5.3	31	7.8		
30	500	83	21	9.2	---	3.2	9.9	149	7.6	5.8	12	7.3		
31	319	---	35	8.7	---	2.8	---	131	---	6.5	9.4	---		
TOTAL	13783	4552	1511	743.3	262.2	114.9	204.6	6299.0	1412.6	220.4	254.5	159.6		
MEAN	445	152	48.7	24.0	9.36	3.71	6.82	203	47.1	7.11	8.21	5.32		
MAX	3440	547	85	57	21	5.4	12	2150	114	8.6	31	17		
MIN	31	71	19	8.7	4.4	1.6	2.7	8.1	6.6	5.2	5.9	3.5		
CFSM	8.94	3.05	.98	.48	.19	.07	.14	4.08	.95	.14	.16	.11		
IN.	10.30	3.40	1.13	.56	.20	.09	.15	4.71	1.06	.16	.19	.12		
AC-FT	27340	9030	3000	1470	520	228	406	12490	2800	437	505	317		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	36401.7	MEAN	99.7	MAX	3440	MIN	2.2	CFSM	2.00	IN.	27.19	AC-FT	72200
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	29517.1	MEAN	80.9	MAX	3440	MIN	1.6	CFSM	1.62	IN.	22.05	AC-FT	58550

RIO INABON BASIN

50112500 RIO INABON AT REAL ABAJO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'10", long 66°33'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on private road, off Highway 511 at Hacienda La Concordia, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) upstream from diversion canal, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) north of Real Abajo, and 6.1 mi (9.8 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.70 mi² (25.12 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1962-63 (annual low-flow measurements only), February to June 1964 (monthly measurements only), July 1964 to July 1970, April 1971 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 410 ft (125 m), from topographic map. Prior to April 1971 nonrecording gage and crest-stage gage at different datum.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Nov. 4-25. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--20 years (1965-69, 1972-86), 19.0 ft³/s (0.538 m³/s), 26.60 in/yr (676 mm/yr), 13,760 acre-ft/yr (17.0 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 18 ft³/s (0.51 m³/s), 13,000 acre-ft/yr (16 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 19,000 ft³/s (538 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 25.3 ft (7.71 m), datum then in use, from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 30 ft³/s (0.850 m³/s) on basis of contracted opening and flow-over-road measurements of peak flow; minimum daily discharge, 0.80 ft³/s (0.023 m³/s), July 23, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s), and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 7	0300	*19,000	538	*25.30	7.711	Oct. 26	1745	896	25.4	9.97	3.039
Oct. 14	1615	651	18.4	7.89	2.405	May 13	2215	1,200	34.0	12.26	3.737
Oct. 23	1915	680	19.2	8.15	2.484	July 24	1445	713	20.2	8.43	2.569

Minimum discharge, 1.8 ft³/s (0.051 m³/s), Mar. 17.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	26	61	18	6.8	5.6	4.2	4.2	22	11	6.1	9.1	21		
2	23	52	17	7.3	4.8	4.0	5.5	15	9.7	5.9	7.3	15		
3	21	56	16	7.0	6.1	6.5	14	17	11	5.8	6.2	13		
4	19	48	16	7.2	6.5	4.6	19	23	10	7.6	5.3	13		
5	23	45	15	7.1	7.6	4.0	18	18	9.7	8.0	4.9	10		
6	519	90	16	7.3	5.4	3.4	15	19	9.3	8.6	4.9	9.2		
7	1840	70	15	7.5	4.9	3.5	8.2	24	9.6	7.6	8.2	8.5		
8	343	57	14	7.2	4.6	3.0	12	23	16	7.1	18	7.8		
9	122	52	13	9.6	4.3	2.8	16	21	13	6.4	8.3	7.2		
10	95	44	13	8.9	4.0	2.9	8.3	48	14	5.9	6.6	6.2		
11	85	37	12	6.9	4.2	2.8	6.4	76	16	6.6	5.2	5.8		
12	80	47	12	6.8	4.0	2.8	5.7	32	17	7.6	4.8	5.6		
13	83	37	11	6.8	3.8	2.9	5.1	325	21	7.0	7.6	5.6		
14	102	31	11	6.7	3.5	2.7	4.6	141	26	6.3	7.1	5.6		
15	76	34	10	6.5	3.4	2.4	4.3	38	22	9.0	5.3	5.6		
16	54	50	9.8	6.5	3.3	2.4	5.3	25	8.1	6.3	4.6	5.3		
17	47	49	9.5	6.5	3.5	13	4.5	20	8.0	3.7	4.3	5.1		
18	43	70	9.1	6.5	3.7	14	6.5	18	7.8	4.3	4.1	4.8		
19	39	52	9.2	6.4	11	6.6	6.3	18	7.8	4.3	4.1	4.8		
20	38	38	9.5	6.2	21	4.9	4.4	15	7.7	4.7	3.3	5.3		
21	41	32	9.8	6.2	8.6	4.3	4.4	14	7.5	4.0	2.8	4.8		
22	36	28	9.6	6.2	5.9	3.9	4.1	13	7.3	3.7	2.8	4.7		
23	87	27	9.4	6.2	4.8	3.7	3.8	12	7.0	3.2	12	5.1		
24	107	24	9.1	6.4	4.5	3.7	4.0	12	7.8	39	9.7	6.6		
25	94	22	8.9	7.0	4.4	3.6	3.8	11	8.3	12	7.6	7.1		
26	107	22	8.3	7.0	3.8	3.6	3.8	12	7.6	8.8	8.1	5.6		
27	89	20	7.5	6.1	3.7	3.5	3.8	10	7.7	10	6.2	8.3		
28	79	20	7.3	6.0	3.5	3.3	5.2	11	6.6	10	5.8	11		
29	68	19	6.7	5.9	---	10	34	16	6.5	9.2	35	7.4		
30	109	19	6.7	9.5	---	7.4	26	15	6.5	13	22	6.1		
31	83	---	6.5	7.1	---	4.5	---	14	---	12	26	---		
TOTAL	4578	1253	345.9	215.3	154.4	144.9	266.2	1078	327.5	253.7	267.2	231.1		
MEAN	148	41.8	11.2	6.95	5.51	4.67	8.87	34.8	10.9	8.18	8.62	7.70		
MAX	1840	90	18	9.6	21	14	34	325	26	39	35	21		
MIN	19	19	6.5	5.9	3.3	2.4	3.8	10	6.5	3.2	2.8	4.7		
CFSM	15.3	4.31	1.15	.72	.57	.48	.91	3.59	1.12	.84	.89	.79		
IN.	17.56	4.81	1.33	.83	.59	.56	1.02	4.13	1.26	.97	1.02	.89		
AC-FT	9080	2490	686	427	306	287	528	2140	650	503	530	458		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	11799.9	MEAN	32.3	MAX	1840	MIN	1.7	CFSM	3.33	IN.	45.25	AC-FT	23410
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	9115.2	MEAN	25.0	MAX	1840	MIN	2.4	CFSM	2.58	IN.	34.96	AC-FT	18080

RIO INABON BASIN

50112500 RIO INABON AT REAL ABAJO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 28	1203	82	250	24.5	JUL, 22	1147	4.4	276	28.5
APR, 24	1150	4.0	272	25.5	AUG, 25	1203	7.0	255	29.0
MAY, 28	1041	11	245	25.5	SEP, 26	1204	5.5	265	28.5
JUN, 24	1014	6.8	256	26.0					

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50114000 RIO CERRILLOS NEAR PONCE, PR

Location.--Lat 18°04'15", long 66°34'51", Hydrologic unit 21010004, on right bank off Highway 139, 2.3 mi (3.7 km) upstream from Quebrada Ausubo and 4.6 mi (7.4 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1985											
04...	1655	41	254	8.40	28.0	6.0	8.0	102	28	640	570
DEC											
03...	1300	23	316	8.20	24.5	220	8.0	97	18	K120	550
FEB 1986											
04...	1630	12	313	8.40	24.5	22	4.4	53	40	K120	200
APR											
30...	0955	45	225	8.00	22.5	20	8.5	100	12	K1800	3300
JUL											
08...	1230	11	264	8.25	28.5	1.6	9.0	117	--	K18	66
SEP											
04...	1310	25	240	8.10	27.0	23	8.4	107	31	570	530

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
04...	110	11	35	6.5	9.8	0.4	1.2	103	<0.5	18	8.0
DEC											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	126	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	121	--	--	--
APR											
30...	89	5	28	4.7	7.9	0.4	1.1	84	<0.5	13	7.4
JUL											
08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	111	--	--	--
SEP											
04...	110	8	34	5.5	8.9	0.4	1.2	100	--	15	6.2

DATE	FLUORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
04...	<0.10	23	160	18	5	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.030	0.37
DEC										
03...	--	--	--	--	478	0.650	0.050	0.700	0.120	0.28
FEB 1986										
04...	--	--	--	--	27	--	<0.010	0.600	0.020	0.38
APR										
30...	<0.10	16	130	16	20	1.48	0.020	1.50	0.050	0.45
JUL										
08...	--	--	--	--	5	--	<0.010	0.200	0.020	0.28
SEP										
04...	<0.10	20	150	10	26	--	<0.010	0.500	0.040	0.26

K = non-ideal count

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50115000 RIO PORTUGUES NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'45", long 66°38'01". Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank 30 ft (9 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 504, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from small unnamed tributary, 4.4 mi (7.1 km) upstream from Rio Chiquito, and 4.7 mi (7.6 km) north of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.82 mi² (22.84 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February to June 1964 (monthly measurements only), July 1964 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 470 ft (143 m), from topographic map. Prior to Dec. 4, 1964, non-recording gage at same site and datum.

REMARKS.--No estimated daily discharges during water year. Records fair. Some low-flow regulation due to unknown activity upstream.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--22 years (1965-86), 18.7 ft³/s (0.530 m³/s), 28.79 in/yr (731 mm/yr), 13,550 acre-ft/yr (16.7 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 18 ft³/s (0.51 m³/s), 13,000 acre-ft/yr (16 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 21,000 ft³/s (595 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 20.2 ft (6.16 m), from floodmarks at downstream side of bridge, from rating curve extended above 150 ft³/s (4.25 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 1.0 ft³/s (0.028 m³/s), May 29, 1973.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 800 ft³/s (22.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1530	2,990	84.7	9.78	2.981	Apr. 29	1530	911	25.8	6.01	1.832
Oct. 7	0500	*21,000	595	*20.20	6.157	Apr. 30	1730	1,220	34.6	6.72	2.048
Oct. 26	1815	1,120	31.7	6.50	1.981	May 13	0630	1,940	54.9	8.15	2.484
Oct. 29	2345	805	22.8	5.77	1.759	May 13	2200	2,660	75.3	9.31	2.838
Oct. 30	1400	1,000	28.3	6.20	1.890	July 31	1800	1,230	34.8	6.74	2.054
Nov. 6	1415	1,420	40.2	7.16	2.182						

Minimum discharge, 2.8 ft³/s (0.079 m³/s), Apr. 27.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	18	79	18	11	5.5	4.5	4.3	57	16	8.8	46	65
2	17	60	18	11	5.5	4.2	4.2	23	15	9.0	17	26
3	16	72	18	8.0	5.9	4.4	20	22	19	9.1	15	14
4	15	51	17	7.9	8.3	4.3	26	15	18	8.0	13	12
5	17	40	17	7.7	9.5	4.3	12	13	16	8.1	33	9.8
6	559	187	16	7.2	5.9	4.2	6.8	13	15	6.6	12	9.1
7	1450	91	16	7.1	6.5	4.1	4.7	51	12	6.3	48	8.5
8	257	57	14	6.9	5.6	4.0	27	52	14	6.8	60	8.5
9	95	45	14	7.9	5.4	4.0	19	29	12	11	16	7.8
10	61	38	14	8.4	5.4	3.9	6.4	55	12	18	12	7.5
11	47	32	13	6.9	5.4	4.1	4.8	142	26	36	10	7.1
12	36	41	13	6.7	4.9	4.6	4.2	60	15	63	8.7	7.0
13	29	32	13	6.6	4.9	4.1	4.0	500	12	77	8.7	6.8
14	27	27	13	6.4	5.0	4.5	3.8	250	10	97	8.6	6.8
15	21	30	12	6.3	4.8	4.0	3.8	78	10	69	8.3	6.6
16	17	43	12	6.2	4.7	4.0	3.7	46	11	30	7.4	6.6
17	15	42	12	6.0	4.8	4.0	3.7	50	10	23	7.1	6.4
18	21	71	11	6.0	4.8	5.0	3.5	25	11	25	7.1	6.2
19	13	46	11	5.9	6.9	4.2	3.5	20	13	25	6.9	6.0
20	12	34	13	6.0	11	3.9	3.4	16	13	26	6.9	7.0
21	13	28	12	6.0	5.4	3.8	3.6	13	14	21	6.8	6.8
22	11	25	13	5.6	5.0	3.7	3.5	12	11	19	7.2	6.0
23	88	24	12	5.6	4.5	3.6	3.3	12	11	18	10	5.7
24	89	21	13	5.6	4.7	3.6	3.3	11	11	35	10	6.5
25	64	20	12	6.2	4.8	3.7	3.2	11	11	24	17	6.5
26	136	18	12	7.2	4.4	3.5	3.2	14	9.1	18	14	6.6
27	80	18	11	5.5	4.5	3.4	3.0	13	10	20	11	22
28	65	18	11	5.7	4.5	3.4	8.6	13	11	21	11	12
29	66	18	11	7.8	---	8.4	101	32	11	18	46	6.9
30	270	18	11	8.8	---	5.2	150	21	14	84	21	5.6
31	122	---	11	8.1	---	3.9	---	28	---	144	44	---
TOTAL	3747	1326	414	218.2	158.5	130.5	451.5	1677	393.1	984.7	549.7	319.3
MEAN	121	44.2	13.4	7.04	5.66	4.21	15.1	54.1	13.1	31.8	17.7	10.6
MAX	1450	187	18	11	11	8.4	150	500	26	144	60	65
MIN	11	18	11	5.5	4.4	3.4	3.0	11	9.1	6.3	6.8	5.6
CFSM	13.7	5.01	1.52	.80	.64	.48	1.71	6.13	1.49	3.61	2.01	1.20
IN.	15.80	5.59	1.75	.92	.67	.55	1.90	7.07	1.66	4.15	2.32	1.35
AC-FT	7430	2630	821	433	314	259	896	3330	780	1950	1090	633

CAL YR 1985 TOTAL 10204.1 MEAN 28.0 MAX 1450 MIN 2.4 CFSM 3.17 IN. 43.04 AC-FT 20240
WTR YR 1986 TOTAL 10369.5 MEAN 28.4 MAX 1450 MIN 3.0 CFSM 3.22 IN. 43.74 AC-FT 20570

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN
50115000 RIO PORTUGUES NEAR PONCE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
04...	1000	15	260	8.50	24.0	1.7	8.1	97	<10	K160	140
DEC 03...	0930	18	318	8.50	22.0	0.70	8.6	100	<10	73	69
FEB 1986											
04...	1340	6.3	317	8.60	23.0	0.30	8.4	98	23	60	86
APR 11...	1230	5.1	300	8.40	25.5	1.5	8.4	105	22	350	50
JUL 08...	0930	5.8	297	8.20	24.5	1.2	9.6	117	<10	56	38
SEP 04...	0950	12	260	8.15	24.0	1.5	8.8	107	<10	330	550

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
04...	130	10	40	6.9	9.5	0.4	1.3	118	<0.5	8.3	--
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	128	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	134	--	--	--
APR 11...	130	14	42	7.3	11	0.4	1.4	121	<0.5	10	9.3
JUL 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	136	--	--	--
SEP 04...	120	4	37	6.5	9.0	0.4	1.4	115	--	7.8	7.4

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
04...	--	--	--	--	4	0.990	0.010	1.00	0.020	0.18
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	4	--	<0.010	1.10	<0.010	--
FEB 1986										
04...	--	--	--	--	3	--	<0.010	0.900	0.020	0.38
APR 11...	0.10	20	170	2.4	9	--	<0.010	1.40	0.330	0.27
JUL 08...	--	--	--	--	4	--	<0.010	0.700	0.030	0.27
SEP 04...	0.10	20	160	4.9	1	--	<0.010	1.00	<0.010	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50116200 RIO PORTUGUES AT PONCE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'20", long 66°36'28", 1,300 ft (400 m) south of Las Americas Avenue Bridge, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of CSC 50115900, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) west of Highways 1 and 2 junction, and 0.7 mi (1.1 km) southeast of Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.9 sq mi (49.0 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)		
NOV 1985	02...	1535	45	540	8.10	30.0	220	7.0	94	37	K130000	4100
DEC 02...	1740	65	546	7.90	27.5	3.2	7.8	100	14	K18000	9000	
FEB 1986	25...	1415	4.2	686	7.60	31.0	14	8.6	116	30	--	--
APR 30...	1300	26	336	8.00	30.5	97	7.4	99	61	K170000	K19000	
JUL 07...	1435	4.9	525	7.55	34.0	4.2	8.1	115	24	K6400	K160	
SEP 03...	1555	15	343	8.25	34.0	60	7.6	108	<10	26000	9000	

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
NOV 1985	200	26	59	12	24	0.8	2.2	171	<0.5	32	27
DEC 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	152	--	--	--
FEB 1986	25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	174	--	--	--
APR 30...	120	0	35	7.4	20	0.8	2.1	118	<0.5	20	18
JUL 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	164	--	--	--
SEP 03...	130	0	38	7.6	24	1	2.0	126	--	31	19

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
NOV 1985	0.10	23	280	34	558	2.03	0.070	2.10	0.440	0.96
DEC 02...	--	--	--	--	6	2.16	0.040	2.20	0.190	0.41
FEB 1986	25...	--	--	--	25	1.46	0.040	1.50	0.090	0.41
APR 30...	0.10	17	190	13	194	1.75	0.050	1.80	0.400	0.60
JUL 07...	--	--	--	--	10	1.03	0.070	1.10	0.200	0.80
SEP 03...	0.20	20	220	8.6	39	0.550	0.050	0.600	0.230	0.67

K = non-ideal count

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50116200 RIO PORTUGUES AT PONCE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
NOV 1985 02...	1.4	3.5	15	0.530	1	200	80	<1	27	50
DEC 02...	0.60	2.8	12	0.110	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 25...	0.50	2.0	8.9	0.140	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 30...	1.0	2.8	12	0.330	<1	100	50	1	18	30
JUL 07...	1.0	2.1	9.3	0.190	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 03...	0.90	1.5	6.6	0.260	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
NOV 1985 02...	21000	14	720	0.10	<1	<1	100	<0.010	2	<0.01
DEC 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 30...	8800	14	290	<0.10	<1	<1	70	<0.010	1	0.05
JUL 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 07...	1435	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.03	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 07...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUL 1986 07...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124200 RIO GUAYANILLA NEAR GUAYANILLA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'40", long 66°47'53", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) north of junction of Highways 2 and 132, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) downstream from Quebrada Consejo, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) north-northwest from Plaza de Guayanilla.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.9 mi² (49.0 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1981 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 80 ft (24 m) from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 6, 7 and July 12 to Aug. 13. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--5 years (1982-86), 22.9 ft³/s (0.648 m³/s), 16.45 in/yr (418 mm/yr), 16,590 acre-ft/yr (20.4 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 14,700 ft³/s (416 m³/s), Sept. 12, 1982, gage height, 20.4 ft (6.21 m), from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and indirect measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 1.8 ft³/s (0.051 m³/s), Apr. 17-19, 1981.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 800 ft³/s (22.7 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	0445	*11,900	337	*19.13	5.831	May 13	2145	1,300	36.8	10.35	3.155
Oct. 23	1715	961	27.2	9.66	2.944	May 29	2100	961	27.2	9.66	2.944
Oct. 30	1330	1,000	28.3	9.75	2.972	Sept. 27	1545	918	26.0	9.56	2.914
May 13	0630	1,340	37.9	10.43	3.179						

Minimum discharge, 3.8 ft³/s (0.108 m³/s), Mar. 11, 12.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	19	138	22	10	6.4	4.7	4.3	18	18	6.6	44	16		
2	15	109	21	9.7	6.3	4.5	4.4	7.7	14	6.6	14	10		
3	17	113	20	9.7	6.6	4.5	17	6.9	13	6.3	11	7.7		
4	17	92	20	9.7	7.3	4.5	68	7.3	12	7.4	9.0	6.8		
5	19	82	20	9.3	9.1	4.5	18	7.6	11	7.1	32	6.6		
6	600	89	20	8.9	6.8	4.3	9.2	5.6	9.7	7.4	10	6.0		
7	1500	129	19	9.0	6.8	4.1	6.8	10	9.7	6.6	46	5.6		
8	401	115	18	9.1	6.6	4.3	6.1	16	9.5	6.3	56	5.4		
9	156	83	17	8.6	6.3	4.3	5.9	7.9	9.0	6.0	16	5.1		
10	89	71	17	9.8	6.3	4.1	5.6	30	9.5	6.0	10	4.9		
11	65	65	17	8.6	6.1	4.0	5.6	100	12	6.0	8.0	6.6		
12	51	84	17	8.9	6.0	4.1	5.2	19	11	6.6	6.6	5.6		
13	64	60	15	9.3	5.8	4.5	5.0	468	8.6	70	5.9	5.4		
14	54	48	16	9.3	5.6	5.5	4.9	274	8.6	90	30	5.1		
15	40	35	15	9.0	5.6	4.3	4.9	51	8.2	65	10	4.9		
16	35	53	15	9.0	5.6	4.1	4.9	26	8.2	25	6.6	4.7		
17	34	81	14	9.0	5.6	4.1	5.0	20	7.9	20	6.3	4.5		
18	70	57	14	9.0	5.6	4.1	5.1	18	7.4	25	6.0	4.5		
19	33	39	14	8.8	5.6	4.2	4.9	17	7.4	27	5.8	4.3		
20	29	34	13	8.9	7.4	4.3	4.6	15	7.3	30	5.6	7.2		
21	27	31	13	9.0	5.8	4.2	4.7	14	7.0	18	5.1	50		
22	27	29	13	8.7	5.1	4.1	4.7	13	7.2	16	10	7.4		
23	210	29	13	8.4	4.8	4.1	4.6	13	7.9	15	23	5.6		
24	184	28	12	8.3	4.7	4.2	4.3	12	8.3	35	9.0	4.9		
25	154	26	12	9.0	4.7	4.5	4.3	13	7.7	18	5.1	4.9		
26	144	24	12	9.3	4.7	4.3	4.3	16	7.7	13	4.7	116		
27	183	24	11	8.2	4.7	4.1	4.3	15	8.0	16	4.1	221		
28	266	23	11	7.8	4.7	4.0	5.2	16	7.7	21	4.0	86		
29	142	23	11	18	---	4.8	7.9	135	7.1	13	8.6	26		
30	355	23	10	7.6	---	4.9	39	38	6.3	76	5.4	52		
31	244	---	10	6.8	---	4.2	---	42	---	130	87	---		
TOTAL	5244	1837	473	284.7	166.6	134.4	278.7	1452.0	276.9	801.9	504.8	700.7		
MEAN	169	61.2	15.3	9.18	5.95	4.34	9.29	46.8	9.23	25.9	16.3	23.4		
MAX	1500	138	22	18	9.1	5.5	68	468	18	130	87	221		
MIN	15	23	10	6.8	4.7	4.0	4.3	5.6	6.3	6.0	4.0	4.3		
CFSM	8.94	3.24	.81	.49	.31	.23	.49	2.48	.49	1.37	.86	1.24		
IN.	10.32	3.62	.93	.56	.33	.26	.55	2.86	.55	1.58	.99	1.38		
AC-FT	10400	3640	938	565	330	267	553	2880	549	1590	1000	1390		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	12871.1	MEAN	35.3	MAX	1500	MIN	2.9	CFSM	1.87	IN.	25.33	AC-FT	25530
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	12154.7	MEAN	33.3	MAX	1500	MIN	4.0	CFSM	1.76	IN.	23.92	AC-FT	24110

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124700 RIO GUAYANILLA AT CENTRAL RUFINA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'40", long 66°46'49", at dirt road bridge, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) from mouth, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) east of Central Rufina and 0.9 mi (1.4 km) southeast of Guayanilla.

DRAINAGE AREA.--22.8 sq mi (59.1 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960-65, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, (PERCENT (HIGH LEVEL)) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1985											
03...	1650	9.0	423	8.30	30.0	7.0	6.4	--	16	520000	35000
DEC											
06...	1150	13	523	8.40	27.5	2.4	7.8	99	13	K65000	K11000
FEB 1986											
07...	1030	2.8	873	7.50	26.5	2.7	0	--	79	23000	K120000
MAY											
01...	0925	27	318	7.80	23.5	23	8.2	97	17	K5000	4000
JUL											
09...	0905	1.7	808	7.50	27.5	2.8	1.2	15	39	35000	K5500
SEP											
05...	0915	2.0	705	7.65	28.0	1.7	4.0	51	12	K9900	K1000

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
03...	170	33	44	14	22	0.8	2.6	135	<0.5	46	22
DEC											
06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	266	--	--	--
MAY											
01...	120	12	32	9.4	11	0.5	1.8	107	<0.5	25	13
JUL											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	267	--	--	--
SEP											
05...	280	32	76	21	43	1	4.1	244	--	73	44

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
03...	0.10	19	250	6.1	1	0.070	0.030	0.100	1.60	0.70
DEC										
06...	--	--	--	--	5	0.740	0.060	0.800	1.70	0.30
FEB 1986										
07...	--	--	--	--	11	0.380	0.120	0.500	13.0	--
MAY										
01...	<0.10	14	170	13	37	1.17	0.030	1.20	0.760	0.44
JUL										
09...	--	--	--	--	6	0.160	0.040	0.200	5.50	3.6
SEP										
05...	0.10	23	430	2.3	1	0.350	0.050	0.400	5.40	2.4

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124700 RIO GUAYANILLA AT CENTRAL RUFINA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985 03...	2.3	2.4	11	0.640	1	<100	30	<1	5	10
DEC 06...	2.0	2.8	12	0.410	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 07...	--	--	--	2.20	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 01...	1.2	2.4	11	0.250	2	100	40	<1	12	10
JUL 09...	9.1	9.3	41	1.80	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 05...	7.8	8.2	36	1.70	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1985 03...	--	4	80	0.20	<1	<1	20	<0.010	2	0.35
DEC 06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 01...	2200	1	100	<0.10	<1	<1	30	<0.010	<1	0.07
JUL 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	0905	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.07	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.02	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01

RIO LOCO BASIN

50129700 RIO LOCO AT GUANICA. PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'33", long 66°54'52", 0.6 mi (1.0 km) northwest of Guánica and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northeast of Ensenada.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1975 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
03...	1215	370	284	8.10	26.0	53	--	--	<10	K14000	600
DEC											
06...	0920	--	663	8.20	24.0	17	7.2	--	15	K450	K910
FEB 1986											
07...	1230	--	21100	7.40	27.0	0.50	0	--	190	2000	2000
MAY											
01...	1235	--	9100	7.60	26.0	19	3.2	41	120	K9500	6500
JUL											
09...	1120	--	7200	7.85	30.0	7.8	5.4	73	79	370	270
SEP											
05...	1120	--	6750	7.55	30.0	4.6	4.0	54	--	310	600

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT. FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
03...	110	6	26	10	11	0.5	2.1	100	<0.5	12	9.6
DEC											
06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	192	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	233	--	--	7500
MAY											
01...	1000	850	80	200	1500	21	52	178	<0.5	410	2700
JUL											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	288	--	--	2300
SEP											
05...	840	580	90	150	1200	18	41	267	--	340	2100

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
03...	<0.10	17	150	148	15	0.790	0.010	0.800	0.040	0.46
DEC										
06...	--	--	--	--	26	1.28	0.020	1.30	0.040	0.46
FEB 1986										
07...	--	--	--	--	30	0.480	0.020	0.500	0.180	0.62
MAY										
01...	0.30	17	5100	--	25	0.380	0.020	0.400	0.060	0.54
JUL										
09...	--	--	--	--	7	0.380	0.020	0.400	0.130	0.47
SEP										
05...	0.30	27	4100	--	13	0.290	0.010	0.300	0.080	0.52

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO LOCO BASIN

50129700 RIO LOCO AT GUANICA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985 03...	0.50	1.3	5.8	0.080	<1	<100	20	<1	30	30
DEC 06...	0.50	1.8	8.0	0.090	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 07...	0.80	1.3	5.8	0.130	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 01...	0.60	1.0	4.4	0.170	1	100	660	1	19	20
JUL 09...	0.60	1.0	4.4	0.140	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 05...	0.60	0.90	4.0	0.090	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1985 03...	4900	12	170	0.90	<1	<1	20	<0.010	--	0.04
DEC 06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 01...	890	1	90	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	<1	0.31
JUL 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	1120	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.01	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01

Figure 20.--Southeastern river basins--Río Humacao to Río Seco basins.

LAGUNA CARTAGENA BASIN

50129899 LAGUNA CARTAGENA NEAR BOQUERON, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'52", Long 67°06'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) south of Hacienda Desengaño, and 4.3 mi (6.9 km) southeast of Boquerón.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

LAKE LEVEL RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 36 ft (11 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 15.39 ft (4.691 m), Nov. 3, 1985; minimum elevation, 7.43 ft (2.265 m), July 29, 1985.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 14.17 ft (4.319 m), Oct. 7; minimum elevation, 7.54 ft (2.298 m), May 4-6.

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS AT 2400

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	8.50	9.56	8.55	8.23	8.23	7.86	7.59	7.56	8.38	7.67	8.02	8.16
2	8.45	9.28	8.52	8.21	8.23	7.82	7.60	7.56	8.37	7.65	8.02	8.19
3	8.40	9.11	8.48	8.21	8.28	7.75	7.60	7.55	8.33	7.62	8.02	8.20
4	8.35	8.98	8.45	8.20	8.28	7.73	7.61	7.54	8.25	7.62	7.99	8.19
5	8.32	8.87	8.43	8.20	8.27	7.70	7.61	7.54	8.19	7.62	7.97	8.17
6	9.33	9.19	8.41	8.20	8.26	7.67	7.62	7.62	8.13	7.62	7.95	8.17
7	13.95	10.70	8.39	8.20	8.24	7.66	7.62	7.59	8.08	7.62	7.95	8.19
8	13.38	10.68	8.38	8.18	8.22	7.65	7.63	7.58	8.03	7.62	7.93	8.18
9	12.33	10.10	8.36	8.18	8.21	7.63	7.63	7.58	7.98	7.61	7.92	8.15
10	11.59	9.61	8.35	8.17	8.19	7.57	7.63	9.46	7.96	7.60	7.92	8.13
11	10.99	9.38	8.34	8.17	8.17	7.56	7.62	10.64	8.03	7.61	7.85	8.11
12	10.35	9.52	8.34	8.16	8.15	7.60	7.62	10.09	7.99	7.62	7.71	8.09
13	9.85	10.56	8.33	8.16	8.12	7.89	7.62	13.64	7.97	7.58	7.63	8.09
14	9.79	10.32	8.31	8.16	8.11	7.87	7.62	12.68	7.94	7.64	7.70	8.09
15	9.42	9.73	8.30	8.19	8.09	7.88	7.62	11.60	7.94	7.69	7.60	8.09
16	9.12	9.36	8.29	8.19	8.08	7.89	7.62	10.77	7.93	7.71	7.60	8.07
17	9.03	9.20	8.29	8.18	8.07	7.91	7.62	10.05	7.91	7.80	7.61	8.05
18	9.76	9.19	8.29	8.18	8.05	7.98	7.61	9.57	7.89	7.83	7.62	8.03
19	9.51	9.15	8.28	8.17	8.04	7.99	7.62	9.29	7.90	7.84	7.62	8.02
20	9.21	9.07	8.28	8.17	8.03	8.00	7.61	9.10	7.88	7.34	7.62	8.02
21	9.02	8.99	8.28	8.17	8.02	8.00	7.61	8.96	7.87	7.84	7.63	8.15
22	8.90	8.92	8.29	8.17	8.01	8.00	7.61	8.84	7.84	7.83	7.65	8.19
23	9.68	8.87	8.28	8.17	8.01	8.00	7.60	8.75	7.83	7.89	7.85	8.14
24	9.96	8.85	8.26	8.17	7.98	8.00	7.59	8.67	7.82	7.94	7.91	8.15
25	9.64	8.83	8.25	8.21	7.97	7.99	7.59	8.63	7.82	7.91	7.95	8.15
26	9.34	8.79	8.23	8.22	7.95	7.99	7.59	8.60	7.82	7.91	7.95	8.35
27	9.17	8.73	8.22	8.23	7.93	7.96	7.60	8.54	7.81	7.95	7.96	8.84
28	9.10	8.68	8.21	8.21	7.91	7.97	7.60	8.40	7.78	8.01	7.98	9.06
29	9.06	8.63	8.22	8.22	---	7.95	7.57	8.42	7.76	8.03	8.06	9.03
30	10.09	8.59	8.24	8.23	---	7.59	7.57	8.39	7.73	8.02	8.09	8.99
31	9.97	---	8.24	8.23	---	7.60	---	8.38	---	8.02	8.13	---
MEAN	9.79	9.31	8.33	8.19	8.11	7.83	7.61	9.02	7.97	7.77	7.85	8.25
MAX	13.95	10.70	8.55	8.23	8.28	8.00	7.63	13.64	8.38	8.03	8.13	9.06
MIN	8.32	8.59	8.21	8.16	7.91	7.56	7.57	7.54	7.73	7.58	7.60	8.02

LAGUNA CARTAGENA BASIN

50129900 LAGUNA CARTAGENA OUTFLOW NEAR BOQUERON, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'52", long 67°06'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) south of Hacienda Desengaño, and 4.3 mi (6.9 km) southeast of Boquerón.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 36 ft (11 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--No estimated daily discharges during water year. Records fair.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 1,290 ft³/s (36.5 m³/s), Nov. 3, 1984, gage height, 15.39 ft (4.691 m), from rating curve extended above 50 ft³/s (1.42 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; no flow part or all of each day Mar 8-12, Mar. 31 to May 9, July 2-16, Aug. 14-22, 1986.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 60 ft³/s (1.70 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 7	1400	*751	21.3	*14.17	4.319	May 11	1100	74	2.10	10.75	3.277
Nov. 8	0545	87	2.46	10.95	3.338	May 14	0200	594	16.8	13.71	4.179
Nov. 14	0315	69	1.95	10.65	3.246						

No flow part or all of each day Mar. 8-12, Mar. 31 to May 9, July 2-16, Aug. 14-22.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	3.6	32	3.8	.93	.93	.09	.00	.00	2.4	.01	.19	.60		
2	3.1	21	3.4	.87	.93	.07	.00	.00	2.4	.00	.19	.80		
3	2.7	15	3.0	.78	1.1	.04	.00	.00	2.1	.00	.19	.95		
4	2.2	12	2.7	.76	1.2	.03	.00	.00	1.6	.00	.15	.94		
5	1.8	9.7	2.4	.78	1.2	.02	.00	.00	1.1	.00	.14	.85		
6	3.3	9.4	2.1	.78	1.1	.01	.00	.00	.75	.00	.12	.76		
7	516	28	1.9	.78	1.0	.01	.00	.00	.44	.00	.11	.83		
8	650	81	1.8	.71	.91	.00	.00	.00	.26	.00	.11	.89		
9	371	56	1.7	.67	.82	.00	.00	.00	.17	.00	.10	.80		
10	200	34	1.5	.64	.70	.00	.00	3.6	.13	.00	.09	.64		
11	119	22	1.5	.62	.60	.00	.00	67	.17	.00	.08	.53		
12	70	20	1.5	.57	.55	.00	.00	55	.17	.00	.03	.44		
13	44	32	1.5	.56	.42	.04	.00	344	.14	.00	.01	.36		
14	31	63	1.3	.54	.31	.09	.00	485	.12	.00	.00	.41		
15	27	41	1.2	.64	.31	.09	.00	229	.11	.00	.00	.39		
16	17	24	1.2	.73	.27	.10	.00	109	.11	.00	.00	.36		
17	13	17	1.1	.71	.26	.10	.00	57	.10	.02	.00	.28		
18	15	15	1.1	.67	.24	.16	.00	33	.09	.05	.00	.23		
19	29	14	1.1	.65	.21	.21	.00	22	.08	.05	.00	.21		
20	20	14	1.1	.62	.21	.23	.00	16	.08	.05	.00	.19		
21	14	11	1.1	.62	.18	.23	.00	13	.07	.05	.00	.54		
22	11	10	1.1	.62	.19	.23	.00	10	.06	.05	.00	.42		
23	12	8.6	1.1	.62	.18	.23	.00	8.2	.05	.07	.00	.24		
24	41	8.2	1.1	.62	.16	.23	.00	6.7	.05	.08	.07	.12		
25	32	7.9	.99	.65	.15	.23	.00	5.6	.05	.09	.10	.08		
26	24	7.4	.91	.81	.13	.21	.00	5.2	.04	.09	.11	.11		
27	16	6.5	.81	.88	.12	.19	.00	4.6	.04	.10	.12	1.1		
28	15	5.6	.73	.86	.11	.17	.00	3.4	.04	.14	.13	5.2		
29	12	4.9	.80	.84	---	.17	.00	2.4	.03	.21	.23	5.2		
30	19	4.3	.86	.86	---	.12	.00	2.6	.02	.20	.31	4.6		
31	44	---	.99	.96	---	.00	---	2.5	---	.19	.52	---		
TOTAL	2378.7	634.5	47.39	22.35	14.49	3.30	.00	1484.80	12.97	1.45	3.11	29.07		
MEAN	76.7	21.1	1.53	.72	.52	.11	.00	47.9	.43	.05	.10	.97		
MAX	650	81	3.8	.96	1.2	.23	.00	485	2.4	.21	.52	5.2		
MIN	1.8	4.3	.73	.54	.11	.00	.00	.00	.02	.00	.00	.08		
CFSM	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00		
IN.	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00		
AC-FT	4720	1260	94	44	29	6.5	.00	2950	26	2.9	6.2	58		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	3882.72	MEAN	10.6	MAX	650	MIN	.00	CFSM	.00	IN.	.00	AC-FT	7700
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	4632.13	MEAN	12.7	MAX	650	MIN	.00	CFSM	.00	IN.	.00	AC-FT	9190

LAGUNA CARTAGENA BASIN

50129900 LAGUNA CARTAGENA OUTFLOW NEAR BOQUERON, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
NOV, 12	1320	21.4	414	25.0	MAR, 05	1203	0.02	1100	25.0
DEC, 12	1207	1.4	504	21.5					

LAGUNA JOYUDA BASIN

50130320 QUEBRADA NAMEY AT JOYUDA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'51", long 67°10'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) northeast of Joyuda and 0.3 mi (0.5 km) upstream from Laguna Joyuda.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.38 mi² (0.98 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to September 1986.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 5.77 ft (1.75 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--No estimated daily discharges during the period of record. Records fair.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT PERIOD.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 12 ft³/s (.340 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Apr. 29	1545	13	.368	14.99	4.569	May 29	2100	13	.368	14.97	4.563
May 3	1630	22	.623	15.27	4.654	July 15	1430	17	.481	15.13	4.612
May 6	2130	40	1.13	15.71	4.788	July 23	1700	16	.453	15.11	4.605
May 13	0430	64	1.81	16.14	4.919	July 30	1545	17	.481	15.13	4.612
May 13	2015	*119	3.37	*16.85	5.136						

No flow many days.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1		---	.06	.04	.02	.01	.00	.08	.32	.08	.20	.26
2		---	.06	.04	.02	.01	.00	.08	.28	.07	.13	.20
3		---	.06	.04	.02	.01	.00	2.6	.25	.07	.17	.20
4		---	.06	.04	.04	.01	.01	.48	.21	.07	.20	.18
5		---	.06	.04	.02	.01	.01	.46	.19	.62	.21	.15
6		---	.06	.04	.02	.01	.00	3.0	.17	.17	.20	.14
7		---	.06	.04	.02	.01	.00	2.3	.16	1.1	2.5	.12
8		---	.07	.04	.02	.02	.00	.21	.17	.17	.71	.13
9		---	.13	.04	.02	.02	.00	.13	.15	.11	.40	.12
10		---	.07	.04	.02	.02	.00	.64	.16	.09	.36	1.1
11		---	.07	.03	.02	.02	.00	.39	.42	.09	.29	.22
12		---	.06	.03	.01	.03	.00	.24	.20	.08	.27	.15
13		---	.06	.03	.01	.19	.00	16	.15	.07	.30	.16
14		---	.06	.03	.01	.07	.00	4.7	.15	.31	.27	.17
15		---	.06	.03	.02	.03	.00	1.3	.54	1.6	.24	.13
16		---	.07	.03	.01	.03	.00	.87	.17	.14	.21	.11
17		---	.07	.03	.01	.05	.00	.75	.14	.45	.20	.10
18		---	.07	.03	.02	.05	.02	.65	.12	.17	.19	.09
19		---	.06	.02	.05	.04	.01	.58	.11	.08	.17	.08
20		---	.06	.02	.02	.03	.01	.52	.10	.71	.16	1.2
21		---	.06	.02	.02	.03	.01	.47	.09	.14	.16	.30
22		---	.06	.02	.02	.03	.01	.42	.08	.08	.18	.14
23		---	.06	.02	.01	.02	.01	.38	.08	1.5	.30	.11
24		---	.06	.02	.01	.02	.01	.36	.08	.17	.79	.11
25		---	.06	.42	.01	.02	.01	.34	.08	.13	.22	.12
26		.05	.05	.04	.01	.02	.01	.33	.08	.11	.17	.15
27		.06	.05	.02	.01	.02	.01	.30	.09	.22	.14	.16
28		.06	.05	.02	.01	.02	.01	.37	.08	.14	.13	.16
29		.06	.05	.03	---	.01	1.7	1.6	.08	.10	.32	.15
30		.06	.05	.02	---	.01	.12	.66	.08	1.7	.17	.15
31		---	.04	.02	---	.00	---	.37	---	.82	1.3	---
TOTAL		---	1.92	1.33	.50	.87	1.96	41.58	4.98	11.36	11.26	6.56
MEAN		---	.06	.04	.02	.03	.06	1.34	.17	.37	.36	.22
MAX		---	.13	.42	.05	.19	1.7	16	.54	1.7	2.5	1.2
MIN		---	.04	.02	.01	.00	.00	.08	.08	.07	.13	.08
CFSM		---	.16	.11	.05	.07	.17	3.53	.45	.97	.95	.58
IN.		---	.19	.13	.05	.09	.19	4.07	.49	1.11	1.10	.64
AC-FT		---	3.8	2.6	.0	1.7	3.9	82	9.9	23	22	13

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50133600 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR SAN GERMAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'18", Long 67°03'56", at bridge on Highway 347, 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest of San Germán.

DRAINAGE AREA.--45.5 sq mi (117.8 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEARS OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985										
02...	0815	44	426	8.00	25.5	12	--	--	12	5200
DEC										
05...	0745	28	574	7.90	23.0	5.2	4.4	52	12	K15000
FEB 1986										
06...	0900	18	709	7.70	21.5	1.5	2.0	--	36	20000
MAY										
02...	1150	55	369	7.60	26.5	24	5.8	73	23	K18000
JUL										
10...	1205	8.2	632	7.75	28.5	3.0	4.3	56	<10	K550
SEP										
17...	1100	5.7	665	7.85	27.5	2.2	4.0	51	30	<1000

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
02...	200	19	22	35	12	0.4	1.6	180	<0.5	20	14
DEC											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	216	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	241	--	--	--
MAY											
02...	160	7	18	28	12	0.4	2.0	153	<0.5	15	15
JUL											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	249	--	--	32
SEP											
17...	250	0	27	45	42	1	3.5	253	--	51	37

DATE	FLUORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
02...	0.20	33	250	29	77	0.650	0.050	0.700	0.140	0.36
DEC										
05...	--	--	--	--	7	0.510	0.090	0.600	0.390	0.51
FEB 1986										
06...	--	--	--	--	9	0.400	0.100	0.500	1.20	0.40
MAY										
02...	0.10	29	210	31	36	0.630	0.170	0.700	0.570	0.43
JUL										
10...	--	--	--	--	6	0.470	0.130	0.600	1.60	0.40
SEP										
17...	0.90	36	390	6.1	2	0.500	0.100	0.600	2.40	0.80

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136000 RIO ROSARIO AT ROSARIO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'22", long 67°04'31", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, on left bank above low dam, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) below Quebrada Figueroa, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) northeast of Rosario, and 1.6 mi (8.6 km) below Quebrada Palma.

DRAINAGE AREA.--16.4 mi² (42.5 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1960 to June 1966 (gage-height records only) in files of Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority. June 1975 to September 1986 (discontinued).

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete control. Elevation of gage is 230 ft (70 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 1-6, Nov. 13 to Dec. 12, May 16-27, June 1-9, June 17 to July 10. Records poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--11 years (1976-86), 46.4 ft³/s (1.314 m³/s), 38.42 in/yr (976 mm/yr), 33,620 acre-ft/yr (41.4 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 46 ft³/s (1.30 m³/s), 33,300 acre-ft/yr (41 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 33,800 ft³/s (957 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage height, 19.6 ft (5.97 m), from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 60 ft³/s (1.70 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum daily discharge, 2.4 ft³/s (0.068 m³/s), June 18, 21, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	0715	*5,590	158	*9.26	2.822	May 13	2145	1,710	48.4	5.86	1.786
Oct. 19	1630	1,500	42.5	5.58	1.701	June 12	1845	2,780	78.7	7.05	2.149
Oct. 28	1445	1,570	44.5	5.68	1.731	June 15	1645	4,180	118	8.22	2.505

Minimum discharge, 8.2 ft³/s (0.232 m³/s), Apr. 13-15.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	78	134	32	22	17	12	10	16	54	32	100	30		
2	66	118	31	22	17	11	10	19	47	30	52	27		
3	78	115	30	22	19	12	14	124	44	29	42	54		
4	62	134	30	22	22	12	26	167	41	28	42	33		
5	54	206	30	21	18	11	15	142	38	29	37	26		
6	1200	135	30	20	17	12	11	65	35	31	34	23		
7	1350	103	28	20	17	12	10	124	36	28	46	21		
8	272	92	28	20	16	14	10	73	43	28	39	26		
9	203	83	27	19	15	13	11	59	38	26	34	23		
10	164	71	28	20	15	12	9.6	147	65	24	32	21		
11	120	84	26	19	15	12	11	140	177	23	32	20		
12	100	70	27	19	14	12	9.0	65	353	22	30	20		
13	87	56	28	19	15	12	8.5	527	192	21	44	20		
14	96	50	27	18	14	12	8.2	309	112	21	81	20		
15	125	56	27	18	14	13	8.5	121	506	26	70	19		
16	88	62	26	17	14	11	9.7	110	223	32	39	19		
17	74	76	26	18	14	12	9.0	84	100	47	35	19		
18	68	62	25	18	14	15	81	72	80	29	32	20		
19	237	50	25	17	20	13	53	64	62	25	30	25		
20	235	45	24	17	24	12	35	56	56	89	29	39		
21	275	43	24	18	15	11	21	52	50	76	27	31		
22	164	41	23	21	14	11	25	48	46	32	26	65		
23	166	40	23	17	13	11	22	46	42	26	50	36		
24	163	38	23	17	13	12	17	43	40	148	38	31		
25	119	36	23	26	13	16	16	42	39	73	47	30		
26	167	35	23	28	13	12	19	45	37	43	39	32		
27	342	34	23	17	12	12	16	42	37	42	31	44		
28	326	32	22	17	12	11	16	100	35	47	27	43		
29	191	31	22	18	---	11	23	13	33	38	27	87		
30	194	31	22	22	---	11	18	10	32	130	28	64		
31	164	---	22	22	---	11	---	65	---	135	41	---		
TOTAL	7028	2163	805	611	436	374	552.5	3208	2693	1410	1261	968		
MEAN	227	72.1	26.0	19.7	15.6	12.1	18.4	103	89.8	45.5	40.7	32.3		
MAX	1350	206	32	28	24	16	81	527	506	148	100	87		
MIN	54	31	22	17	12	11	8.2	16	32	21	26	19		
CFSM	13.8	4.40	1.59	1.20	.95	.74	1.12	6.28	5.48	2.77	2.48	1.97		
IN.	15.94	4.91	1.83	1.39	.99	.85	1.25	7.28	6.11	3.20	2.86	2.20		
AC-FT	13940	4290	1600	1210	865	742	1100	6360	5340	2800	2500	1920		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	20693	MEAN	56.7	MAX	1350	MIN	11	CFSM	3.46	IN.	46.94	AC-FT	41040
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	21509.5	MEAN	58.9	MAX	1350	MIN	8.2	CFSM	3.59	IN.	48.79	AC-FT	42660

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'36", long 67°05'08", at bridge on Highway 348, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) southwest of Rosario plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.3 mi² (47.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 50.0 ft (15.2 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 7-9 and April 27 to May 8. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	0715	*5,880	166	*12.67	3.862	June 15	1715	1,920	54.4	8.41	2.563
Oct. 19	1645	1,630	46.2	7.94	2.420						

Minimum discharge, 8.7 ft³/s (0.246 m³/s), Apr. 15.DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	77	118	32	21	18	12	11	17	49	31	110	33		
2	64	102	31	22	16	11	10	19	43	29	59	29		
3	76	96	30	22	19	11	13	130	39	28	45	62		
4	60	135	30	21	23	12	32	160	37	28	49	34		
5	53	206	30	20	18	11	18	100	35	29	39	27		
6	208	126	30	20	16	11	12	66	33	30	35	23		
7	1550	99	28	19	17	12	11	120	33	27	60	23		
8	331	88	28	18	16	13	11	105	40	27	43	28		
9	182	80	27	18	15	12	12	50	36	25	35	24		
10	147	72	28	18	15	11	9.8	137	34	24	32	22		
11	129	86	27	19	15	11	12	143	141	24	33	21		
12	105	66	26	18	14	11	9.6	61	268	25	29	20		
13	94	57	27	18	14	11	9.6	500	214	24	47	20		
14	103	52	26	18	14	11	9.4	338	100	23	87	19		
15	139	55	26	17	13	13	10	135	363	29	83	18		
16	96	60	25	17	13	11	11	91	207	35	42	19		
17	76	75	24	18	13	12	44	72	104	56	35	18		
18	67	64	23	19	13	16	66	62	78	34	34	20		
19	248	51	23	17	22	14	34	54	64	29	31	26		
20	258	46	23	16	27	12	21	48	55	82	29	52		
21	324	44	23	16	14	12	25	44	49	95	27	34		
22	159	41	23	25	13	12	17	41	45	38	26	81		
23	168	40	23	18	12	12	16	38	42	30	52	30		
24	162	38	23	18	12	13	18	36	39	135	40	22		
25	112	37	23	30	13	18	15	36	38	81	48	22		
26	175	35	23	35	13	13	26	39	36	41	44	27		
27	362	34	22	19	12	14	17	36	36	41	33	37		
28	335	33	22	18	12	12	17	80	34	49	28	41		
29	186	32	22	18	---	12	23	132	32	37	29	80		
30	189	31	23	23	---	12	18	118	31	137	29	68		
31	157	---	22	24	---	11	---	63	---	142	47	---		
TOTAL	6392	2099	793	620	432	379	558.4	3071	2355	1465	1360	980		
MEAN	206	70.0	25.6	20.0	15.4	12.2	18.6	99.1	78.5	47.3	43.9	32.7		
MAX	1550	206	32	35	27	18	66	500	363	142	110	81		
MIN	53	31	22	16	12	11	9.4	17	31	23	26	18		
CFSM	11.3	3.83	1.40	1.09	.84	.67	1.02	5.42	4.29	2.58	2.40	1.79		
IN.	12.99	4.27	1.61	1.26	.88	.77	1.14	6.24	4.79	2.98	2.76	1.99		
AC-FT	12680	4160	1570	1230	857	752	1110	6090	4670	2910	2700	1940		
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	20504.4	MEAN	56.2	MAX	1550	MIN	9.4	CFSM	3.07	IN.	41.68	AC-FT	40670

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN
50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS 1979 TO CURRENT YEAR.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

INSTRUMENTATION.--USD-49 SEDIMENT SAMPLER SINCE OCTOBER 1985.

REMARKS.--sediment samples were collected by a local observer once daily during low flow and more than once daily during high flow events for concentration and particle size analyses. Sediment samples are collected periodically by survey staff.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 8,150 mg/L October 7, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 74,700 tons (67,800 tonnes) October 7, 1985; Minimum daily, 0.05 ton (0.04 tonne) several days.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECA, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1985											
02...	1815	51	245	8.00	25.0	10	--	--	<10	K1500	600
DEC											
04...	1020	30	270	8.50	22.0	1.6	8.4	99	<10	K22	88
FEB 1986											
05...	1145	18	281	8.40	22.5	2.0	--	--	16	K81	75
APR											
08...	1400	10	278	8.80	26.0	1.5	11.0	137	17	68	430
JUL											
09...	1435	26	260	8.10	28.5	1.2	8.8	114	<10	110	550
SEP											
16...	1140	19	266	8.35	28.5	2.0	9.8	128	11	K150	90

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
02...	110	7	20	15	6.5	0.3	1.5	105	<0.5	8.5	7.1
DEC											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	111	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR											
08...	120	4	24	15	9.4	0.4	1.1	118	<0.5	7.7	9.3
JUL											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	121	--	--	--
SEP											
16...	120	0	23	16	8.3	0.3	1.5	130	--	6.9	7.7

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
OCT 1985							
06...	1830	689	2600	4840	24	34	53
20...	1710	958	2610	6750	19	32	43
21...	1620	1390	3320	12500	15	22	31
NOV							
05...	1755	663	3940	7050	25	38	53
MAY 1986							
13...	0728	1030	2720	7530	13	20	28

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
OCT 1985							
06...	68	80	86	95	98	99	100
20...	62	75	85	95	98	99	100
21...	44	58	67	84	94	99	99
NOV							
05...	69	87	91	96	99	100	100
MAY 1986							
13...	41	56	63	78	87	92	96

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN
50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued
SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	78	61	14	119	15	4.8	32	9	.78
2	66	40	6.9	102	13	3.6	31	9	.75
3	78	72	30	96	12	3.1	30	8	.65
4	62	35	7.2	135	193	178	30	9	.73
5	54	10	1.4	206	572	1290	30	9	.73
6	209	608	1440	126	70	27	30	9	.73
7	1550	8150	74700	99	15	4.0	28	7	.53
8	330	270	300	88	10	2.4	28	7	.53
9	185	30	15	80	10	2.2	27	6	.44
10	148	39	20	72	10	1.9	28	6	.45
11	131	65	29	86	75	43	27	6	.44
12	107	15	4.3	66	12	2.1	26	5	.35
13	97	54	46	57	10	1.5	27	5	.36
14	103	90	36	51	10	1.4	26	5	.35
15	140	241	226	55	10	1.5	26	5	.35
16	98	63	18	60	12	1.9	25	5	.34
17	78	18	3.8	75	41	11	24	4	.26
18	69	15	2.7	64	17	2.9	23	4	.25
19	247	1030	4100	51	10	1.4	23	4	.25
20	258	553	995	46	10	1.2	23	4	.25
21	324	949	2380	43	10	1.2	22	4	.25
22	160	110	59	41	10	1.1	22	5	.31
23	170	247	234	40	10	1.1	22	5	.31
24	162	89	48	38	10	1.0	22	5	.30
25	113	30	9.1	37	10	1.0	22	5	.31
26	176	330	521	35	9	.85	22	5	.31
27	362	933	2230	34	9	.83	22	5	.30
28	334	766	1610	33	9	.80	21	5	.30
29	186	42	24	32	9	.78	22	4	.24
30	190	68	71	31	9	.75	22	4	.24
31	157	30	13	---	---	---	22	4	.24
TOTAL	6422	---	89194.4	2098	---	1594.31	785	---	12.63

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN
50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued
SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	21	4	.23	17	3	.15	11	2	.06
2	22	4	.24	16	3	.13	11	2	.06
3	21	4	.24	19	3	.15	11	2	.06
4	21	4	.23	23	5	.31	12	2	.06
5	20	3	.16	17	3	.15	11	2	.06
6	19	3	.16	16	3	.13	11	2	.06
7	19	3	.15	17	3	.14	12	2	.06
8	18	3	.15	16	3	.13	13	2	.07
9	18	3	.15	15	2	.08	12	2	.06
10	18	3	.15	15	2	.08	11	2	.06
11	18	3	.15	15	2	.08	11	2	.06
12	17	3	.15	14	2	.08	11	2	.06
13	18	3	.15	14	2	.08	11	2	.06
14	17	3	.15	14	2	.08	11	2	.06
15	17	3	.14	13	2	.07	13	3	.11
16	17	3	.14	13	2	.07	11	2	.06
17	18	3	.15	13	2	.07	12	3	.10
18	18	3	.15	13	2	.07	16	4	.17
19	17	3	.14	22	13	2.3	14	3	.11
20	16	3	.13	27	11	.98	12	3	.10
21	16	3	.13	14	3	.11	12	3	.10
22	24	10	.83	13	3	.11	12	3	.10
23	17	3	.15	12	3	.10	11	3	.10
24	17	3	.15	12	3	.10	12	4	.14
25	30	17	3.5	13	3	.11	18	6	.29
26	35	16	2.9	13	3	.11	13	3	.11
27	18	4	.21	12	2	.06	14	4	.15
28	18	3	.15	12	2	.06	12	2	.06
29	18	3	.15	---	---	---	11	2	.06
30	23	5	.31	---	---	---	11	2	.06
31	23	5	.32	---	---	---	11	2	.06
TOTAL	609	---	12.11	430	---	6.09	374	---	2.73

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	32	7	.59	110	116	43	33	18	1.6
2	30	5	.39	59	32	5.1	29	10	.78
3	29	7	.53	45	12	1.5	62	51	18
4	28	7	.53	49	41	9.6	35	22	2.0
5	29	8	.63	39	17	1.8	28	7	.51
6	31	10	.81	35	12	1.1	24	7	.43
7	28	6	.44	60	55	15	23	7	.43
8	28	6	.44	43	15	1.7	29	9	1.0
9	26	5	.34	35	10	.95	24	10	.65
10	24	5	.32	32	10	.86	22	10	.59
11	24	5	.32	33	10	.89	21	9	.51
12	24	5	.32	29	9	.70	20	8	.43
13	24	5	.32	47	33	7.7	20	8	.43
14	23	5	.31	87	151	128	19	7	.36
15	29	9	.83	82	88	35	19	6	.29
16	36	22	4.0	42	20	2.3	19	6	.29
17	56	44	9.9	35	12	1.1	18	6	.31
18	34	15	1.4	34	10	.92	21	6	.29
19	29	10	.78	31	10	.84	26	9	1.0
20	90	122	100	30	9	.70	53	44	12
21	95	93	35	27	8	.58	35	10	.92
22	38	20	2.1	26	8	.56	82	104	76
23	30	15	1.2	50	46	20	31	15	1.2
24	135	279	464	40	30	3.2	22	10	.59
25	82	46	15	48	42	13	22	10	.59
26	41	10	1.1	44	35	4.2	27	9	.85
27	41	10	1.1	33	12	1.1	37	23	5.1
28	49	10	1.3	28	10	.76	41	27	4.1
29	37	10	1.0	29	10	.78	80	126	112
30	137	241	300	29	10	.78	68	45	8.0
31	143	197	94	47	40	10	---	---	---
TOTAL	1482	---	1039.00	1358	---	313.72	990	---	251.25

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	11	2	.06	17	10	.54	54	10	1.3
2	10	2	.05	19	482	755	47	8	.93
3	13	3	.14	130	609	1030	44	8	.84
4	32	25	2.7	160	514	1170	41	8	.80
5	17	9	.44	100	184	95	38	7	.66
6	12	5	.16	66	475	938	35	7	.62
7	11	4	.12	120	688	1790	36	7	.62
8	11	3	.09	105	128	52	43	10	1.1
9	12	4	.13	50	40	5.4	38	9	.87
10	9.8	2	.05	136	190	130	36	8	.73
11	11	3	.10	142	174	86	141	215	213
12	9.5	2	.05	60	40	6.6	271	900	2170
13	9.5	2	.05	499	1440	3620	215	338	304
14	9.3	2	.05	342	711	1080	102	98	31
15	9.9	2	.05	150	28	10	362	1100	3570
16	11	3	.09	104	18	4.4	208	320	224
17	44	57	45	84	16	3.1	105	50	14
18	66	90	30	73	11	1.8	79	23	4.8
19	34	35	3.2	65	10	1.5	65	12	2.1
20	21	30	1.7	57	10	1.3	56	10	1.5
21	24	30	2.0	52	10	1.2	50	9	1.2
22	17	25	1.1	49	10	1.1	46	8	.97
23	16	22	.95	46	9	.92	43	8	.91
24	18	25	1.2	43	8	.78	40	7	.74
25	15	22	.89	42	8	.78	39	7	.72
26	25	20	1.4	45	9	.95	37	7	.68
27	17	15	.69	42	8	.78	37	7	.68
28	17	10	.54	87	95	59	35	5	.46
29	23	10	.54	139	175	105	33	5	.43
30	18	10	.54	127	99	37	32	5	.42
31	---	---	---	70	15	2.6	---	---	---
TOTAL	554.0	---	94.08	3221	---	10990.75	2408	---	6550.08

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°08'36", Long 67°08'57", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at bridge on Highway 100, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) west of Hormigueros, and 2.0 mi (3.2 km) downstream from Rio Rosario.

DRAINAGE AREA.--120 mi² (311 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Annual low-flow measurements 1959, monthly measurements April 1959 to November 1967, January 1973 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is at mean sea level. Previous to Nov. 7, 1980, at site 0.3 mi (0.5 km) upstream at datum 7.36 ft (2.243 m) higher.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 7-22, Nov. 29 to Dec. 9, Dec. 22 to Jan. 7, Feb. 1, 2, Aug. 13, 14 and June 17 to July 14. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--13 years (1974-86), 218 ft³/s (6.174 m³/s), 24.67 in/yr (627 mm/yr), 157,900 acre-ft/yr (195 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 210 ft³/s (5.95 m³/s), 152,000 acre-ft/yr (187 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 128,000 ft³/s (3,620 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage height, 28.50 ft (8.687 m), site and datum then in use, from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on the basis of contracted-opening measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 4.6 ft³/s (0.130 m³/s), June 22, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,000 ft³/s (56.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	unknown	*40,000	1,133	*28.00	8.534	May 14	0630	7,680	217	22.89	6.977

Minimum discharge, 5.0 ft³/s (0.142 m³/s), Apr. 3, 15-17.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	167	643	110	47	60	18	9.8	345	186	66	391	182		
2	134	498	105	49	55	16	8.7	254	155	60	180	177		
3	119	421	100	48	47	17	30	400	143	60	144	140		
4	159	672	98	45	52	24	91	324	130	62	207	140		
5	152	716	96	43	47	20	63	279	117	85	201	101		
6	624	507	94	41	38	17	45	299	105	66	117	86		
7	5000	464	92	41	35	17	34	490	96	59	129	77		
8	10000	377	90	40	32	21	28	312	90	55	163	68		
9	2000	310	90	39	31	22	29	188	89	52	118	68		
10	1150	281	87	39	29	18	22	548	76	50	103	74		
11	800	324	83	38	28	17	18	968	286	48	90	83		
12	630	287	81	36	27	16	15	351	375	43	80	59		
13	530	326	79	36	26	22	12	2720	640	43	74	55		
14	600	253	79	36	26	38	8.7	4890	208	42	86	49		
15	840	214	81	35	26	27	8.2	1490	466	54	301	48		
16	540	216	79	35	25	22	10	622	679	65	123	47		
17	420	244	79	36	27	19	8.3	412	197	71	94	47		
18	390	266	77	35	27	30	93	297	149	88	82	47		
19	1750	217	75	32	24	27	59	229	127	50	73	53		
20	1700	189	74	30	51	28	24	196	115	60	71	196		
21	2050	172	72	30	30	23	26	164	100	237	65	169		
22	800	159	70	38	27	18	19	156	91	80	64	138		
23	578	151	65	32	24	17	10	151	86	57	162	97		
24	1090	169	66	32	22	17	12	143	81	383	196	71		
25	571	144	62	33	23	26	11	134	78	310	134	60		
26	501	137	58	66	21	21	28	133	74	125	154	171		
27	1140	131	54	45	22	19	22	143	71	93	96	196		
28	1380	125	54	39	19	15	19	173	67	95	77	218		
29	874	120	52	42	---	12	268	391	66	80	110	160		
30	1000	115	52	47	---	12	392	722	62	182	87	186		
31	1170	---	47	67	---	9.9	---	250	---	385	106	---		
TOTAL	38859	8848	2401	1252	901	625.9	1423.7	18174	5205	3206	4078	3263		
MEAN	1254	295	77.5	40.4	32.2	20.2	47.5	586	174	103	132	109		
MAX	10000	716	110	67	60	38	392	4890	679	385	391	218		
MIN	119	115	47	30	19	9.9	8.2	133	62	42	64	47		
CFSM	10.4	2.46	.65	.34	.27	.17	.40	4.88	1.45	.86	1.10	.91		
IN.	12.05	2.74	.74	.39	.28	.19	.44	5.63	1.61	.99	1.26	1.01		
AC-FT	77080	17550	4760	2480	1790	1240	2820	36050	10320	6360	8090	6470		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	87887	MEAN	241	MAX	10000	MIN	20	CFSM	2.01	IN.	27.24	AC-FT	174300
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	88236.6	MEAN	242	MAX	10000	MIN	8.2	CFSM	2.02	IN.	27.35	AC-FT	175000

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
02...	1315	133	368	8.10	26.0	15	--	--	<10	K7000	K1100
DEC											
05...	1230	94	484	7.80	24.0	11	6.8	--	<10	31000	4700
FEB 1986											
06...	1445	39	564	7.80	26.0	10	6.2	--	36	35000	4000
APR											
09...	1300	31	521	8.00	27.0	16	5.9	75	18	28000	K800
JUL											
10...	0915	51	424	7.85	27.0	1.7	6.5	82	<10	K61000	3500
SEP											
16...	1615	46	440	7.90	29.0	8.5	5.4	71	20	57000	8200

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
02...	180	24	27	28	12	0.4	1.8	159	<0.5	17	13
DEC											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	189	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	197	--	--	--
APR											
09...	230	32	31	36	20	0.6	2.3	194	<0.5	40	22
JUL											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--
SEP											
16...	200	4	31	30	16	0.5	2.1	197	--	18	17

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
02...	0.20	32	230	81	11	0.760	0.040	0.800	0.230	0.37
DEC										
05...	--	--	--	--	34	0.770	0.030	0.800	0.140	0.36
FEB 1986										
06...	--	--	--	--	12	0.860	0.040	0.900	0.320	0.58
APR										
09...	0.40	34	300	25	23	0.750	0.050	0.800	0.290	0.51
JUL										
10...	--	--	--	--	11	--	<0.010	0.500	0.010	0.19
SEP										
16...	0.20	33	270	33	12	0.630	0.070	0.700	0.410	0.09

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985										
02...	0.60	1.4	6.2	0.340	<1	<100	20	1	22	10
DEC										
05...	0.50	1.3	5.8	0.360	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986										
06...	0.90	1.8	8.0	0.490	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
09...	0.80	1.6	7.1	0.550	2	<100	140	<1	21	<10
JUL										
10...	0.20	0.70	3.1	0.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP										
16...	0.50	1.2	5.3	0.460	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1985										
02...	1600	2	120	<0.10	<1	<1	10	<0.010	<1	0.04
DEC										
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986										
06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
09...	1100	3	140	<0.10	<1	<1	10	<0.010	<1	0.07
JUL										
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP										
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986									
10...	0915	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.07	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986								
10...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUL 1986								
10...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01

Figure 24.--Río Yagüez and Río Grande de Añasco basins.

RIO YAGÜEZ BASIN

50138800 RIO YAGÜEZ NEAR MAYAGÜEZ, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'31", long 67°07'07", at steel-truss bridge on unnumbered paved road about 800 ft (244 m) south of Highway 106, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) west of Highways 106 and 352 junction, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) east-northeast from Mayagüez plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.7 sq mi (17.3 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
01...	1225	10	263	8.20	24.5	6.0	8.5	--	19	K700	810
DEC 06...	0730	8.8	297	8.20	21.0	0.80	8.6	--	<10	K36	440
FEB 1986											
05...	1420	5.3	282	8.40	24.5	14	10.0	--	46	59000	87000
MAY 02...	0810	11	162	7.80	22.5	670	8.5	99	28	59000	87000
JUL 11...	0815	5.3	303	8.00	24.5	1.5	8.4	101	13	K620	620
SEP 17...	0755	6.1	306	7.95	23.0	1.5	8.6	101	17	290	2900

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
01...	120	5	30	10	9.7	0.4	2.3	111	<0.5	7.7	7.3
DEC 06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
MAY 02...	63	0	16	5.6	6.9	0.4	2.0	67	<0.5	9.1	8.6
JUL 11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	138	--	--	--
SEP 17...	130	0	37	10	11	0.4	2.1	139	--	7.8	9.4

DATE	FLUORIDE, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
01...	<0.10	29	160	4.4	2	0.790	0.010	0.800	0.020	0.18
DEC 06...	--	--	--	--	4	--	<0.010	0.900	0.010	--
FEB 1986										
05...	--	--	--	--	10	--	<0.010	0.800	0.010	0.39
MAY 02...	<0.10	19	110	3.1	672	0.730	0.070	0.800	0.160	0.44
JUL 11...	--	--	--	--	3	0.620	0.080	0.700	0.390	0.41
SEP 17...	<0.10	30	190	3.1	3	--	<0.010	0.600	0.040	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50143000 RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO NEAR LARES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'26", long 66°55'00", at bridge on Highway 124, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) downstream from confluence of Rio Blanco and Rio Prieto, and 3.7 mi (6.0 km) southwest of Lares plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--26.3 sq mi (68.1 sq km) this does not include 36.2 sq mi (93.8 sq km) which contributes only during high floods, and 3.5 sq mi (9.1 sq km) which contributes only part of its storm runoff.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959-68, 1970 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
31...	1030	890	175	7.80	23.5	61	8.2	--	25	K1700	4900
DEC 11...	1225	50	291	8.20	24.5	1.7	9.4	--	11	270	56
FEB 1986											
11...	1215	28	312	8.45	23.0	71	8.7	103	21	120	500
MAY 01...	1430	212	224	7.81	25.0	33	8.2	100	63	4800	20000
JUL 10...	1200	34	268	7.90	29.0	750	7.3	95	61	1200	2000
SEP 11...	1200	35	293	7.51	29.0	630	7.4	98	25	K2700	1800

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
31...	70	6	18	6.0	8.0	0.4	1.8	64	<0.5	10	7.3
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	114	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	121	--	--	--
MAY 01...	82	7	23	5.9	9.1	0.5	2.4	75	<0.5	14	8.2
JUL 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	105	--	--	--
SEP 11...	100	8	27	8.2	13	0.6	2.5	93	--	18	12

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
31...	<0.10	20	110	263	51	1.18	0.020	1.20	0.050	0.55
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	1	1.29	0.010	1.30	0.030	0.27
FEB 1986										
11...	--	--	--	--	126	1.13	0.070	1.20	0.030	0.37
MAY 01...	<0.10	22	130	74	504	1.65	0.050	1.70	0.260	0.44
JUL 10...	--	--	--	--	824	1.12	0.380	1.50	1.10	1.0
SEP 11...	0.20	28	160	16	1130	2.34	0.360	2.70	0.180	1.0

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50144000 RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'05", long 67°03'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, on right bank, at downstream side of bridge on Highway 108, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) downstream from Quebrada La Zumbadora, 4.4 mi (7.1 km) northwest of Las Marias, 5.4 mi (8.7 km) southwest of San Sebastián.

DRAINAGE AREA.--94.3 mi² (244.2 km²), does not include 36.2 mi² (93.8 km²) which contributes only during high floods, and 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) which contributes only part of its storm runoff.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1963 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 103.72 ft (31.614 m) above mean sea level (Puerto Rico Department of Public Works bench mark). Previous to Oct. 30, 1975, a site 600 ft (180 m) upstream at same datum.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Oct. 7, 8. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Transbasin diversion (except during floods) to Rio Yauco basin for hydroelectric power and irrigation above Lago Guayo, Yahuecas, and Prieto, combined usable storage 17,300 acre-ft (21.3 hm³). Limited storm runoff is contributed to basin by 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) above Rio Toro Diversion dam.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--23 years (1964-86), 313 ft³/s (8.864 m³/s), 45.08 in/yr (1,145 mm/yr), 226,800 acre-ft/yr (280 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 303 ft³/s (8.581 m³/s), 220,000 acre-ft/yr (271 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 140,000 ft³/s (3,960 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage height, 33.9 ft (10.33 m), from rating curve extended above 4,000 ft³/s (113 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 31 ft³/s (0.878 m³/s), Apr. 19, 20, 1965.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 6,000 ft³/s (170 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 6	2115	8,630	244	8.68	2.646	Nov. 4	1800	10,400	294	9.50	2.896
Oct. 7	0500	*53,600	1,518	*21.94	6.687	Apr. 30	2015	9,090	257	8.90	2.713
Oct. 26	2230	6,590	187	7.60	2.316	May 1	1915	10,800	306	9.71	2.960
Oct. 28	1715	7,880	223	8.30	2.530	May 13	2330	11,400	323	9.96	3.036

Minimum discharge, 42 ft³/s (1.189 m³/s), Apr. 15, 16.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN VALUES													
	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	599	851	227	147	116	73	56	2680	259	208	473	398		
2	328	743	221	153	107	66	56	1410	229	204	370	554		
3	230	952	215	140	151	74	106	1180	217	200	260	497		
4	210	1570	211	139	237	115	331	1210	201	203	324	315		
5	180	759	206	135	154	79	171	1160	192	167	427	226		
6	1300	520	205	128	123	72	132	1480	182	177	558	196		
7	4400	446	197	127	114	69	87	1770	382	243	836	175		
8	2500	394	189	127	119	81	90	1220	359	291	727	198		
9	1650	359	187	150	109	72	103	1010	285	252	567	195		
10	967	335	188	158	107	63	82	1310	680	179	406	176		
11	1170	317	183	130	103	89	74	1350	442	199	341	169		
12	840	299	179	123	95	71	62	784	443	175	376	173		
13	1050	286	180	122	97	70	56	4170	600	147	475	154		
14	769	284	173	117	97	68	50	3920	329	240	408	138		
15	1520	317	171	114	96	70	45	1360	726	235	450	153		
16	733	440	172	111	86	59	58	974	550	573	319	172		
17	424	587	172	107	84	59	153	759	326	570	390	278		
18	336	658	169	111	95	172	314	652	476	476	305	325		
19	506	372	164	104	106	148	269	578	427	342	281	156		
20	727	309	161	100	104	93	116	496	278	459	270	140		
21	703	287	158	96	120	74	304	396	267	516	243	144		
22	516	272	156	113	91	65	115	339	244	264	233	195		
23	619	266	157	100	79	56	91	286	234	214	250	180		
24	1260	262	154	139	80	56	175	261	224	335	312	145		
25	919	260	148	112	99	101	112	283	215	297	362	153		
26	1300	252	148	160	85	90	238	315	229	472	418	140		
27	2370	248	147	127	84	73	120	625	563	331	257	132		
28	2290	244	146	112	80	68	102	445	254	299	233	420		
29	1270	237	146	108	---	64	791	464	224	343	235	129		
30	998	232	147	197	---	72	1780	438	215	605	340	99		
31	1160	---	144	207	---	59	---	293	---	584	256	---		
TOTAL	33844	13358	5421	4014	3018	2441	6239	33618	10252	9800	11702	6525		
MEAN	1092	445	175	129	108	78.7	208	1084	342	316	377	218		
MAX	4400	1570	227	207	237	172	1780	4170	726	605	836	554		
MIN	180	232	144	96	79	56	45	261	182	147	233	99		
CFSM	11.6	4.72	1.86	1.37	1.15	.83	2.21	11.5	3.63	3.35	4.00	2.31		
IN.	13.35	5.27	2.14	1.58	1.19	.96	2.46	13.26	4.04	3.87	4.62	2.57		
AC-FT	67130	26500	10750	7960	5990	4840	12380	66680	20330	19440	23210	12940		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	131791	MEAN	361	MAX	19100	MIN	65	CFSM	3.83	IN.	51.99	AC-FT	261400
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	140232	MEAN	384	MAX	4400	MIN	45	CFSM	4.07	IN.	55.32	AC-FT	278200

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50144000 RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR--Continued

(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1963 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3
OCT 1985 02...	1040	270	209	8.00	24.0	57	8.9	K15000	6000	93	6
JAN 1986 09...	1140	124	250	8.20	22.0	1.3	9.7	--	--	110	3
APR 11...	1300	84	273	7.56	28.0	20	8.5	140	--	110	17
JUL 02...	1115	206	235	7.91	27.0	130	8.1	260	220	100	2

DATE	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)
OCT 1985 02...	24	8.0	7.7	0.4	3.8	87	9.5	5.9	<0.10	26	128
JAN 1986 09...	28	9.6	10	0.4	1.4	107	10	8.5	0.10	30	154
APR 11...	29	9.4	10	0.4	1.8	94	13	7.9	0.10	29	162
JUL 02...	26	9.0	11	0.5	1.6	100	10	7.9	0.10	31	156

DATE	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITU- ENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOS- PHORUS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHORUS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHORUS, ORTHO, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS- PHATE, ORTHO, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS PO4)
OCT 1985 02...	140	93	0.800	0.040	0.05	0.60	0.100	0.050	0.030	0.09
JAN 1986 09...	160	52	0.730	0.030	0.04	0.30	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.12
APR 11...	160	37	0.670	0.100	0.13	0.30	0.060	0.040	0.030	0.09
JUL 02...	160	87	0.860	0.210	0.27	0.50	0.100	0.040	0.040	0.12

DATE	ALUM- INUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYL- LIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)
OCT 1985 02...	40	<1	42	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	2	33	<1
JAN 1986 09...	<10	<1	39	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	1	6	<1
APR 11...	40	<1	37	<0.5	1	<1	<3	8	50	2
JUL 02...	40	<1	36	0.7	<1	<1	<3	3	20	<5

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN
50144000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)
WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	LITHIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)	MANGA- NESE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRON- TIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
OCT 1985 02...	<4	33	<0.1	<10	2	<1	<1	120	<6	9
JAN 1986 09...	<4	12	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1	150	<6	<3
APR 11...	7	18	0.1	<10	1	<1	<1	140	9	31
JUL 02...	<4	10	0.2	<10	2	<1	<1	140	9	6

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. é FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1985 02...	1022	266	114	82	97
JAN 1986 09...	1140	124	36	12	88
APR 11...	1300	85	70	16	99

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN

50146000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR AÑASCO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°16'00", long 67°08'05", at bridge on Highway 430, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) south of Highway 109 at El Espino and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) east-southeast from Añasco plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--139 sq mi (360 sq km) this does not include 39.7 sq mi (102.8 sq km), flow is diverted to south coast.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED SATUR- ATION	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
03...	1000	333	196	7.60	25.0	58	8.6	--	<10	2500	4300
DEC											
10...	1610	235	246	7.80	26.5	3.0	9.0	--	<10	220	K100
FEB 1986											
10...	1800	114	254	8.00	25.5	30	8.1	100	37	K110	340
APR											
30...	1530	--	170	7.08	24.5	740	8.0	--	94	26000	62000
JUL											
09...	1430	291	291	7.40	28.5	300	7.3	93	29	15700	28000
SEP											
10...	1425	243	259	7.68	30.0	46	7.8	104	<10	340	K130

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
03...	80	0	19	7.8	7.6	0.4	1.7	81	<0.5	9.3	6.0
DEC											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	105	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	103	--	--	--
APR											
30...	68	15	19	5.1	6.5	0.4	2.2	53	<0.5	15	6.7
JUL											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	72	--	--	--
SEP											
10...	98	0	25	8.6	10	0.5	2.0	98	--	8.2	7.0

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TOMS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
03...	<0.10	27	130	114	69	0.680	0.020	0.700	0.070	0.43
DEC										
10...	--	--	--	--	10	0.790	0.010	0.800	0.040	0.36
FEB 1986										
10...	--	--	--	--	32	0.780	0.020	0.800	0.030	0.27
APR										
30...	<0.10	17	100	0.0	1160	1.12	0.080	1.20	0.230	2.5
JUL										
09...	--	--	--	--	487	0.920	0.080	1.00	0.140	0.46
SEP										
10...	0.10	32	150	100	1	0.890	0.010	0.900	0.060	0.14

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50146000 RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO NEAR ANASCO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985 03...	0.50	1.2	5.3	0.100	<1	<100	40	<1	12	20
DEC 10...	0.40	1.2	5.3	0.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 10...	0.30	1.1	4.9	0.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 30...	2.7	3.9	17	0.450	1	300	40	1	21	120
JUL 09...	0.60	1.6	7.1	0.070	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 10...	0.20	1.1	4.9	0.070	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1985 03...	4100	5	170	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	4	0.03
DEC 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 30...	50000	11	1700	0.20	1	<1	190	<0.010	<1	0.09
JUL 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	1430	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.01	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01

Figure 25.--Río Culebrinas basin.

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50147600 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'51", long 67°02'40", at bridge on Highway 423, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) south of Quebrada El Salto Bridge on Highway 111, and 2.1 mi (3.4 km) west of Central La Plata.

DRAINAGE AREA.--58.2 sq mi (150.7 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
02...	1815	--	316	7.60	25.0	150	8.1	--	31	23000	28000
DEC 11...	0925	76	281	7.80	23.0	4.7	8.1	--	<10	4800	650
FEB 1986											
11...	0925	28	342	8.05	21.5	4.9	7.8	89	35	K1100	20000
MAY 01...	0955	334	416	7.97	23.5	56	9.7	--	--	6300	7500
JUL 10...	0905	77	267	7.73	25.5	20	7.5	--	11	K12000	860
SEP 11...	0825	72	309	7.65	25.5	4.7	7.5	92	12	5900	770

DATE	HARDNESS (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WATER TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1985											
02...	120	0	42	3.8	6.6	0.3	2.0	121	<0.5	14	8.0
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	127	--	--	--
MAY 01...	160	8	57	5.4	11	0.4	4.8	157	<0.5	15	10
JUL 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	106	--	--	--
SEP 11...	110	3	36	5.4	12	0.5	2.3	109	--	10	9.7

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
02...	<0.10	14	160	0.0	262	0.760	0.040	0.800	0.120	0.78
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	5	1.32	0.080	1.40	0.080	0.42
FEB 1986										
11...	--	--	--	--	10	0.950	0.050	1.00	0.480	0.82
MAY 01...	<0.10	17	210	193	80	1.04	0.060	1.10	0.150	0.65
JUL 10...	--	--	--	--	17	1.02	0.080	1.10	0.120	0.38
SEP 11...	0.10	34	170	34	7	1.12	0.080	1.20	0.110	0.39

E = estimate
K = non-ideal count

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50147800 RIO CULEBRINAS AT HIGHWAY 404 NEAR MOCA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'42", long 67°05'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, on right bank, at bridge on Highway 404, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) downstream from Quebrada Yagruma, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) southeast of Moca.

DRAINAGE AREA.--71.2 mi² (184.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1967 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 45 ft (14 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Nov. 5-20. Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--19 years (1968-86), 310 ft³/s (8.779 m³/s), 59.13 in/yr (1,502 mm/yr), 224,600 acre-ft/yr (277 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 290 ft³/s (8.21 m³/s), 210,000 acre-ft/yr (260 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 69,000 ft³/s (1,950 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage height, 36.6 ft (11.16 m) from slope-area measurement, but may have been exceeded by flood of Oct. 23, 1974, from rating curve extended above 2,600 ft³/s (73.6 m³/s) on basis of slope-area and contracted-opening measurements of peak flow; minimum discharge, 16 ft³/s (0.453 m³/s), Apr. 17-19, 1979.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 11,300 ft³/s (320 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 1	2030	20,400	578	26.11	7.958	May 3	2145	23,500	666	27.11	8.263
Oct. 7	1145	23,200	657	26.99	8.226	May 5	2030	*34,700	983	*30.12	9.181
Nov. 3	2030	25,400	719	27.65	8.428	May 6	1900	24,200	685	27.32	8.327
Apr. 27	0015	27,300	773	28.20	8.595	May 13	1015	29,800	844	28.88	8.803
Apr. 28	2230	11,300	320	22.43	6.837	May 26	2100	12,600	357	23.08	7.035
Apr. 29	2000	11,900	337	22.72	6.925	May 27	1830	15,400	436	24.28	7.400

Minimum discharge, 33 ft³/s (0.934 m³/s), Mar. 15, 24, 27.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	4300	241	122	67	77	46	61	833	249	151	184	202		
2	1280	204	119	66	70	48	51	862	222	146	315	940		
3	362	5030	117	62	97	72	100	4370	207	141	201	313		
4	275	1290	115	61	133	129	121	1660	190	137	143	212		
5	238	1520	112	60	96	61	128	8440	178	132	431	144		
6	460	1020	128	59	78	49	83	8440	168	149	307	123		
7	10700	800	123	58	75	42	132	6790	311	239	272	103		
8	900	660	108	58	66	39	312	962	420	165	299	94		
9	439	500	103	70	63	39	226	571	235	138	1170	88		
10	327	450	101	91	61	36	124	1710	1640	127	294	87		
11	1470	400	99	63	63	75	85	580	375	147	196	81		
12	587	380	96	60	60	53	72	1350	212	128	163	78		
13	406	360	92	57	61	39	63	11700	246	115	148	83		
14	275	370	88	54	56	37	56	4530	217	110	148	85		
15	241	980	88	52	58	34	52	680	185	204	156	91		
16	222	1100	87	50	53	45	53	482	175	222	226	75		
17	203	700	84	49	55	58	109	368	154	161	155	70		
18	187	390	83	50	54	172	96	316	166	129	128	70		
19	177	260	83	48	63	60	77	287	601	136	139	67		
20	169	206	82	48	80	46	120	263	685	705	115	64		
21	166	195	79	45	92	39	163	382	479	193	106	63		
22	158	178	77	47	63	38	194	287	477	133	103	103		
23	170	169	78	45	53	35	1010	523	291	119	98	77		
24	242	159	75	43	50	35	1910	379	207	119	104	63		
25	162	152	71	45	53	34	354	269	184	171	112	94		
26	1860	146	70	44	50	41	3040	2100	238	887	171	88		
27	1740	139	69	45	50	109	3350	2500	317	258	97	62		
28	1700	135	68	42	49	200	2260	470	190	164	184	486		
29	455	131	68	50	---	305	3130	843	167	420	111	139		
30	327	128	68	104	---	164	1100	426	158	243	134	98		
31	280	---	66	127	---	90	---	292	---	270	103	---		
TOTAL	30478	18393	2819	1820	1879	2270	18632	63665	9544	6559	6513	4343		
MEAN	983	613	90.9	58.7	67.1	73.2	621	2054	318	212	210	145		
MAX	10700	5030	128	127	133	305	3350	11700	1640	887	1170	940		
MIN	158	128	66	42	49	34	51	263	154	110	97	62		
CFSM	13.8	8.61	1.28	.82	.94	1.03	8.72	28.8	4.47	2.98	2.95	2.04		
IN.	15.92	9.61	1.47	.95	.98	1.19	9.73	33.26	4.99	3.43	3.40	2.27		
AC-FT	60450	36480	5590	3610	3730	4500	36960	126300	18930	13010	12920	8610		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	136055	MEAN	373	MAX	10700	MIN	33	CFSM	5.24	IN.	71.08	AC-FT	269900
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	166915	MEAN	457	MAX	11700	MIN	34	CFSM	6.42	IN.	87.21	AC-FT	331100

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50147800 RIO CULEBRINAS AT HIGHWAY 404 NEAR MOCA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
NOV, 20	1151	212	325	25.0	JUL, 09	0942	141	250	25.5
DEC, 11	0930	100	266	23.0	AUG, 11	1202	197	229	27.0
MAY, 06	1203	759	291	25.0	SEP, 04	1057	170	231	25.0
JUN, 11	1253	206	242	25.0					

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50149100 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR AGUADA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'03", long 67°09'40", at bridge on Highway 2, and 2.3 mi (3.7 km) northeast of Aguada plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--97.0 Sq mi (251.2 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1970 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED SATUR- ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1985											
03...	1400	--	269	7.40	26.0	140	5.2	--	30	50000	8000
DEC											
10...	1250	167	310	7.80	24.5	2.9	8.1	--	<10	520	K11000
FEB 1986											
10...	1500	70	312	7.95	23.5	13	7.5	89	14	K1000	2500
APR											
30...	1200	1710	312	7.60	25.5	190	5.5	--	36	K15000	36000
JUL											
09...	1035	211	281	7.53	26.5	60	7.0	--	19	3100	2200
SEP											
10...	1030	183	336	7.70	27.0	17	7.4	93	25	980	500

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1985											
03...	120	0	41	3.9	6.6	0.3	1.8	121	<0.5	14	8.8
DEC											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	131	--	--	--
FEB 1986											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	125	--	--	--
APR											
30...	130	16	46	3.9	7.9	0.3	3.6	115	<0.5	15	9.0
JUL											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	117	--	--	--
SEP											
10...	130	0	42	5.7	12	0.5	2.3	130	--	9.6	9.9

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS- SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1985										
03...	0.10	16	160	--	254	0.360	0.040	0.400	0.100	0.90
DEC										
10...	--	--	--	--	3	0.870	0.030	0.900	0.100	0.40
FEB 1986										
10...	--	--	--	--	26	0.570	0.030	0.600	0.130	0.27
APR										
30...	<0.10	14	170	776	320	0.750	0.050	0.800	0.170	0.73
JUL										
09...	--	--	--	--	220	0.670	0.030	0.700	0.100	0.80
SEP										
10...	0.10	33	190	95	31	0.870	0.030	0.900	0.110	0.19

E = estimate
K = non-ideal count

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50149100 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR AGUADA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1985 03...	1.0	1.4	6.2	0.200	1	100	30	<1	22	20
DEC 10...	0.50	1.4	6.2	0.090	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 10...	0.40	1.0	4.4	0.070	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 30...	0.90	1.7	7.5	0.200	1	100	30	3	20	30
JUL 09...	0.90	1.6	7.1	0.200	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 10...	0.30	1.2	5.3	0.070	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1985 03...	11000	29	360	0.10	<1	<1	40	<0.010	3	0.05
DEC 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1986 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 30...	14000	10	350	0.20	<1	<1	40	<0.010	2	0.09
JUL 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	1035	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.01	<0.010

DATE	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.02	<0.01

DATE	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)
JUL 1986 09...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01

Discharge

at

Partial-Record

Stations in Puerto Rico

DISCHARGE AT CREST-STAGE PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

The following table contains annual maximum discharge for crest-stage stations. A crest-stage gage is a device which will register the peak stage occurring between inspections of the gage. A stage-discharge relation for each gage is developed from discharge measurements made by indirect measurements of peak flow or by current meter. The date of the maximum discharge is not always certain but is usually determined by comparison with nearby continuous-record stations, weather record, or local inquiry. Only the maximum discharge for each water year is given. Information on some lower floods may have been obtained, and discharge measurements may have been made for purposes of establishing the stage-discharge relation, but these are not published herein. The years given in the period of record represent years for which the annual maximum has been determined.

Annual maximum discharge at crest-stage partial-record stations during water year 1986

Station number	Station name	Location	Drainage area mi ² (km ²)	Period of record	Date	Annual maximum	
						Gage height ft (m)	Discharge ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río Bucaná basin							
50114390	Río Bucaná Floodway Channel at Highway 14 bridge near Ponce, PR	Lat 18°02'29", long 66°34'58", on left upstream side of Highway 14 bridge, .2 mi (.3 km) southeast of Escuela Cerrillos, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) northeast of Degetau Plaza in Ponce.	24.9 (64.5)	1985-86	10/07/85	129.88 (39.59)	17,400 (493)
Río Portugués basin							
50115900	Río Portugués at Highway 14 at Ponce, PR	Lat 18°01'09", long 66°36'26", on left downstream side of Highway 14 bridge, 1.7 mi (2.7 km) downstream from Río Chiquito, and 0.6 mi (0.97 km) northeast of Degetau Plaza in Ponce.	18.6 (48.2)	1963-86	10/07/85	17.67 (5.386)	12,000 (340)

Water-Quality at
Partial-Record
Stations in
Puerto
Rico

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Water-quality partial-record stations are particular sites where chemical-quality, biological and or sediment data are collected systematically over a period of years for use in hydrological analysis. The data are collected usually less than quarterly.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	DEPTH AT SAMPLE LOCATION, TOTAL (FEET)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANSPARANCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, (PER-CENT SATURATION)	COLIFORM, FE CAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN									
50010720	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°22'05"N LONG 066°54'36"W)								
NOV 1985									
20...	1015	1.00	267	8.05	26.0	52.0	--	--	K8
MAR 1986									
06...	1125	1.00	285	8.35	26.5	77.0	7.2	92	68
AUG									
22...	0905	1.00	254	8.05	29.0	90.0	7.8	104	K9
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN									
50025110	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°19'15"N LONG 066°40'11"W)								
NOV 1985									
19...	1010	1.00	198	7.50	25.5	10.0	--	--	K1300
MAR 1986									
07...	1050	1.00	191	8.70	26.0	56.0	7.0	87	K9
AUG									
21...	0905	1.00	212	7.95	30.0	44.0	8.7	117	31
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN									
50039900	LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°05'04"N LONG 066°06'03"W)								
NOV 1985									
14...	1245	1.00	77	6.80	23.5	27.0	8.2	100	--
MAR 1986									
12...	1205	1.00	87	8.60	24.5	63.0	6.6	84	--
AUG									
18...	1205	1.00	--	7.65	27.5	83.0	7.6	--	--
50044400	LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°19'33"N LONG 066°12'28"W)								
NOV 1985									
13...	1505	1.00	333	8.00	25.0	11.0	--	--	K8500
MAR 1986									
11...	1300	1.00	390	8.50	27.0	39.0	6.9	87	42
AUG									
15...	1200	1.00	368	7.90	29.5	54.0	8.2	109	31
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN									
50057500	LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18°16'51"N LONG 066°00'35"W)								
NOV 1985									
15...	1130	--	214	7.55	24.0	4.00	--	--	20000
MAR 1986									
04...	1425	1.00	382	7.40	26.0	30.0	5.0	62	>10
AUG									
19...	1040	1.00	266	6.95	30.0	23.0	2.7	37	K1500

K = non-ideal count

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CAC03	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDEE (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50010720	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°22'05"N LONG 066°54'36"W)							
NOV 1985 20...	50	118	1	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.010	0.69
MAR 1986 06...	37	123	2	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.030	0.47
AUG 22...	28	116	2	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.020	0.48
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED								
50025110	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°19'15"N LONG 066°40'11"W)							
NOV 1985 19...	650	59	18	0.760	0.040	0.800	0.020	0.58
MAR 1986 07...	45	66	4	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.020	0.38
AUG 21...	100	82	1	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.010	0.39
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50039900	LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°05'04"N LONG 066°06'03"W)							
NOV 1985 14...	--	27	5	0.090	0.010	0.100	0.020	0.28
MAR 1986 12...	--	31	6	--	<0.010	<0.100	<0.010	--
AUG 18...	--	32	4	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.020	0.18
50044400	LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°19'33"N LONG 066°12'28"W)							
NOV 1985 13...	4200	116	33	0.880	0.020	0.900	0.030	0.47
MAR 1986 11...	K5	144	4	0.070	0.030	0.100	0.020	0.48
AUG 15...	K15	142	<1	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.020	0.28
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50057500	LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18°16'51"N LONG 066°00'35"W)							
NOV 1985 15...	32000	69	204	0.520	0.080	0.600	0.320	1.1
MAR 1986 04...	69	105	1	0.350	0.050	0.400	1.30	0.80
AUG 19...	K250	81	18	0.410	0.090	0.500	0.880	0.52

K = non-ideal count

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	CHLOR-A PHYTO- PLANK- TON CHROMO FLUOROM (UG/L)	CHLOR-B PHYTO- PLANK- TON CHROMO FLUOROM (UG/L)	PLANK- TON BIOMASS ASH WT (MG/L)	PLANK- TON BIOMASS DRY WT (MG/L)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50010720	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°22'05"N LONG 066°54'36"W)							
NOV 1985 20...	0.70	--	--	0.030	30.0	4.20	--	--
MAR 1986 06...	0.50	--	--	0.020	17.0	2.40	--	--
AUG 22...	0.50	--	--	0.020	9.30	0.800	3.5	220
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED								
50025110	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°19'15"N LONG 066°40'11"W)							
NOV 1985 19...	0.60	1.4	6.2	0.070	16.0	0.400	--	--
MAR 1986 07...	0.40	0.60	2.7	0.030	14.0	3.90	3.0	230
AUG 21...	0.40	--	--	0.030	17.0	1.40	7.0	6280
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50039900	LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°05'04"N LONG 066°06'03"W)							
NOV 1985 14...	0.30	0.40	1.8	0.010	11.0	0.700	--	--
MAR 1986 12...	<0.20	--	--	0.010	17.0	5.80	75	330
AUG 18...	0.20	--	--	0.020	10.0	2.70	9.8	240
50044400	LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°19'33"N LONG 066°12'28"W)							
NOV 1985 13...	0.50	1.4	6.2	0.170	18.0	4.10	--	--
MAR 1986 11...	0.50	0.60	2.7	0.160	30.0	3.80	3.2	250
AUG 15...	0.30	--	--	0.090	72.0	14.0	13	180
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50057500	LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18°16'51"N LONG 066°00'35"W)							
NOV 1985 15...	1.4	2.0	8.9	0.350	1.60	0.300	--	--
MAR 1986 04...	2.1	2.5	11	0.660	76.0	2.20	--	--
AUG 19...	1.4	1.9	8.4	0.470	3.40	0.300	3.9	260

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	TIME	DEPTH AT SAMPLE LOCATION, TOTAL (FEET)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANS-PAR-ENCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50010790		LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)								
NOV 1985										
20...	0930	1.00	264	7.95	26.0	52.0	--	--	K3	<1
20...	0935	74.0	321	7.85	24.0	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986										
06...	1030	1.00	280	8.30	26.0	78.0	6.8	86	K7	K13
06...	1040	78.0	309	7.45	24.0	--	0.4	5	--	--
AUG										
22...	0930	1.00	259	7.95	28.5	140	7.4	98	K7	24
22...	0935	44.0	303	7.15	24.5	--	0.2	2	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED										
50020050		LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)								
NOV 1985										
18...	1415	1.00	109	7.00	21.5	18.0	--	--	340	360
18...	1430	76.0	94	6.60	20.5	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986										
05...	1450	1.00	137	8.75	24.5	58.0	--	--	K47	K8
05...	1440	100.0	155	7.25	21.5	--	--	--	--	--
AUG										
20...	1230	1.00	141	8.05	26.5	29.0	--	--	K7	<1
20...	1220	86.0	155	7.00	22.0	--	--	--	--	--
50027090		LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)								
NOV 1985										
19...	1110	1.00	172	7.85	26.5	13.0	--	--	80	K8
19...	1120	82.0	156	7.15	23.0	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986										
07...	0955	1.00	195	8.75	26.0	56.0	7.2	90	27	K15
07...	0950	86.0	206	7.20	23.5	--	0.4	5	--	--
AUG										
21...	1050	1.00	212	8.00	30.0	56.0	7.2	97	K7	K4
21...	1045	78.0	227	6.80	28.0	--	0.6	8	--	--
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50039950		LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)								
NOV 1985										
14...	1200	1.00	67	6.75	--	25.0	--	--	22	K8
14...	1205	67.0	78	6.55	22.0	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986										
12...	1120	1.00	88	--	24.0	55.0	--	--	50	K12
12...	1125	63.0	90	7.05	22.0	--	--	--	--	--
AUG										
18...	1115	1.00	100	7.45	27.5	111	--	--	K1	K14
18...	1125	69.0	92	6.10	23.0	--	--	--	--	--
50044950		LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)								
NOV 1985										
13...	1250	1.00	285	7.65	26.5	18.0	--	--	340	300
13...	1405	66.0	128	6.70	23.0	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986										
11...	1145	1.00	369	8.20	26.5	51.0	5.8	73	K4	21
11...	1150	59.0	309	7.20	23.5	--	0	0	--	--
AUG										
15...	1300	1.00	621	7.65	30.0	73.0	7.3	98	--	--
15...	1250	57.0	158	6.80	22.5	--	0	0	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50058800		LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)								
NOV 1985										
15...	1040	1.00	261	7.20	26.0	20.0	--	--	2300	400
15...	1035	24.0	251	7.20	25.5	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986										
04...	1530	1.00	338	8.05	26.0	40.0	7.8	97	30	22
04...	1525	27.0	343	7.20	24.5	--	0.2	2	--	--
AUG										
19...	1000	1.00	265	7.55	30.0	32.0	--	--	K12	K120
19...	0950	33.0	304	6.85	29.0	--	--	--	--	--

K = non-ideal court

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	HARD- NESS (MG/L CAC03)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WATER TOT FLD MG/L AS CAC03	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WATER TOTAL FIELD MG/L AS CAC03	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50010790 LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS,PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)										
NOV 1985										
20...	120	10	43	3.1	5.0	0.2	1.5	110	9.6	7.1
20...	150	35	55	3.0	4.5	0.2	1.5	115	10	6.5
MAR 1986										
06...	130	14	48	3.5	5.4	0.2	1.6	120	8.4	7.3
06...	150	28	54	3.5	5.6	0.2	1.9	121	9.5	8.0
AUG										
22...	120	1	41	3.1	4.9	0.2	1.6	114	9.0	6.9
22...	130	0	49	2.8	4.2	0.2	1.5	143	8.4	5.4
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED										
50020050 LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS,PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)										
NOV 1985										
18...	40	0	11	3.1	5.0	0.4	0.90	41	5.2	4.6
18...	37	0	10	3.0	4.4	0.3	1.0	38	5.0	4.5
MAR 1986										
05...	58	0	16	4.4	6.1	0.4	1.0	59	3.3	5.5
05...	61	0	17	4.6	6.2	0.4	1.0	62	3.3	5.3
AUG										
20...	62	0	17	4.8	6.6	0.4	1.1	66	3.9	5.8
20...	61	0	17	4.5	5.4	0.3	1.5	72	4.9	5.1
50027090 LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO,PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)										
NOV 1985										
19...	61	6	16	5.0	8.1	0.5	1.7	55	11	7.8
19...	59	4	17	4.1	7.2	0.4	1.6	55	8.3	10
MAR 1986										
07...	76	8	20	6.4	11	0.6	1.8	68	13	9.6
07...	80	6	21	6.6	10	0.5	2.1	74	12	9.4
AUG										
21...	79	2	21	6.4	10	0.5	2.0	77	14	10
21...	90	0	24	7.2	11	0.5	2.3	94	14	10
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50039950 LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY,PR (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)										
NOV 1985										
14...	23	1	4.1	3.0	6.5	0.6	0.70	22	1.9	7.2
14...	25	0	5.0	3.1	7.2	0.6	0.70	27	4.7	7.6
MAR 1986										
12...	28	0	5.6	3.4	7.7	0.6	0.70	30	3.8	8.8
12...	29	0	6.0	3.4	7.4	0.6	0.70	30	3.8	8.5
AUG										
18...	28	0	5.8	3.2	12	1	0.90	32	5.7	8.8
18...	28	0	5.9	3.3	6.2	0.5	1.4	36	8.7	10
50044950 LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)										
NOV 1985										
13...	100	7	25	10	15	0.7	1.9	97	15	18
13...	45	1	11	4.2	6.9	0.5	2.1	44	8.9	7.1
MAR 1986										
11...	140	10	34	14	22	0.8	2.2	133	13	23
11...	120	9	29	12	16	0.7	2.3	113	11	17
AUG										
15...	130	5	29	13	20	0.8	1.3	121	16	24
15...	52	0	13	4.7	6.8	0.4	2.2	56	8.8	11
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50058800 LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)										
NOV 1985										
15...	87	5	20	9.0	19	0.9	2.3	82	14	18
15...	81	2	19	8.2	18	0.9	2.7	79	16	16
MAR 1986										
04...	99	10	23	10	26	1	2.3	89	16	24
04...	99	4	23	10	25	1	2.3	95	16	25
AUG										
19...	78	0	18	8.0	22	1	2.8	85	18	20
19...	82	0	19	8.3	22	1	3.0	93	16	21

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50010790	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)							
NOV 1985								
20...	<0.10	2.0	140	2	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.010
20...	<0.10	5.0	150	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986								
06...	0.20	4.8	150	2	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.020
06...	0.20	6.3	160	--	--	--	--	--
AUG								
22...	0.10	6.4	140	1	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.020
22...	0.10	6.9	160	--	--	--	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED								
50020050	LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)							
NOV 1985								
18...	<0.10	15	69	7	--	<0.010	0.300	0.020
18...	<0.10	14	65	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986								
05...	0.20	19	91	4	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.020
05...	0.20	19	94	--	--	--	--	--
AUG								
20...	<0.10	17	96	6	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.030
20...	<0.10	17	99	--	--	--	--	--
50027090	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)							
NOV 1985								
19...	<0.10	20	100	4	0.670	0.030	0.700	0.030
19...	<0.10	21	100	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986								
07...	0.20	18	120	5	0.090	0.010	0.100	0.020
07...	0.10	22	130	--	--	--	--	--
AUG								
21...	0.10	22	130	3	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.020
21...	0.10	24	150	--	--	--	--	--
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50039950	LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)							
NOV 1985								
14...	<0.10	14	51	5	--	0.010	<0.100	0.020
14...	<0.10	17	61	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986								
12...	0.20	16	64	4	--	<0.010	<0.100	<0.010
12...	0.20	17	65	--	--	--	--	--
AUG								
18...	<0.10	19	75	3	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.020
18...	<0.10	13	70	--	--	--	--	--
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)							
NOV 1985								
13...	0.10	22	170	12	0.790	0.010	0.800	0.020
13...	0.10	14	81	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986								
11...	0.10	20	210	4	--	<0.010	<0.100	<0.010
11...	0.10	22	180	--	--	--	--	--
AUG								
15...	0.20	18	190	1	--	<0.010	<0.100	0.020
15...	0.20	13	93	--	--	--	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)							
NOV 1985								
15...	0.10	29	160	14	0.730	0.070	0.800	0.090
15...	0.10	27	150	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986								
04...	0.20	23	180	5	0.260	0.040	0.300	0.020
04...	0.20	24	180	--	--	--	--	--
AUG								
19...	0.20	20	160	5	0.030	0.070	0.100	0.020
19...	0.20	23	170	--	--	--	--	--

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DATE	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	CHLOR-A PHYTO- PLANK- TON CHROMO FLUOROM (UG/L)	CHLOR-B PHYTO- PLANK- TON CHROMO FLUOROM (UG/L)	PLANK- TON BIOMASS ASH WT (MG/L)	PLANK- TON BIOMASS DRY WT (MG/L)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED									
50010790	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS,PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)								
NOV 1985									
20...	0.59	0.60	--	--	0.020	24.0	2.10	--	--
20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986									
06...	0.28	0.30	--	--	0.020	9.20	0.400	--	--
06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG									
22...	0.38	0.40	--	--	0.010	2.40	0.200	4.7	270
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED									
50020050	LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS,PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)								
NOV 1985									
18...	0.48	0.50	0.80	3.5	0.030	15.0	0.500	--	--
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986									
05...	0.38	0.40	--	--	0.020	27.0	2.40	5.0	270
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG									
20...	0.37	0.40	--	--	0.020	19.0	0.300	8.2	280
20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
50027090	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO,PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)								
NOV 1985									
19...	0.67	0.70	1.4	6.2	0.080	36.0	1.30	--	--
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986									
07...	0.38	0.40	0.50	2.2	0.020	11.0	0.300	4.2	270
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG									
21...	0.28	0.30	--	--	0.020	15.0	1.30	6.4	280
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED									
50039950	LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY,PR (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)								
NOV 1985									
14...	0.38	0.40	--	--	0.010	9.40	0.700	--	--
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986									
12...	--	<0.20	--	--	0.020	14.0	4.90	3.2	260
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG									
18...	0.38	0.40	--	--	0.030	3.10	0.700	8.4	250
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)								
NOV 1985									
13...	0.68	0.70	1.5	6.6	0.140	43.0	9.10	--	--
13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986									
11...	--	0.50	--	--	0.060	32.0	4.40	4.6	260
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG									
15...	0.38	0.40	--	--	0.030	32.0	2.30	12	280
15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED									
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)								
NOV 1985									
15...	0.61	0.70	1.5	6.6	0.170	33.0	1.40	--	--
15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1986									
04...	0.88	0.90	1.2	5.3	0.190	58.0	3.50	--	--
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG									
19...	0.68	0.70	0.80	3.5	0.181	42.0	3.30	13	550
19...	--	--	--	--	0.430	--	--	--	--

Ground-Water Records
for
Puerto Rico

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

182422067015100. Local number, 165.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'22", long 67°01'51".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Saltos # 1 (Mateo Perez).

AQUIFER.--Cibao Formation, Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.40 m), cased 16 in (0.40 m) 0-40 ft (0-12.2 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 40-200 ft (12.2-61.0 m). Depth 200 ft (61.0 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 689 ft (210 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Hole on pump base, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum. Prior November 1985, hole on top of pump base, 1.00 ft (0.30 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Pumping discontinued. Observation well. Automatic recorder installed on November 14, 1985. Formerly published as 182421067015000.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1982 to March 1985. November 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 53.39 ft (16.27 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 23, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 70.60 ft (21.52 m) below land-surface datum, June 18, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	59.85	59.23	58.76	57.91	57.29	56.70	55.82	55.20	54.48	53.83
2	---	---	59.85	59.19	58.66	57.87	57.25	56.69	55.81	55.21	54.50	53.90
3	---	---	59.84	59.07	58.67	57.91	57.27	56.65	55.79	55.17	54.50	53.93
4	---	---	59.82	59.11	58.65	57.91	57.28	56.63	55.74	55.16	54.46	53.91
5	---	---	59.78	59.13	58.59	57.89	57.25	56.60	55.75	55.11	54.46	53.85
6	---	---	59.59	59.11	58.59	57.85	57.24	56.55	55.76	55.09	54.42	53.84
7	---	---	59.61	59.08	58.60	57.84	57.19	56.47	55.72	55.08	54.37	53.85
8	---	---	59.61	59.09	58.64	57.88	57.18	56.31	55.71	55.09	54.35	53.82
9	---	---	59.60	59.10	58.56	57.91	57.15	56.30	55.70	55.07	54.34	53.82
10	---	---	59.61	59.06	58.54	57.89	57.11	56.31	55.70	55.06	54.33	53.81
11	---	---	59.57	59.03	58.59	57.79	57.11	56.30	55.65	54.99	54.32	53.70
12	---	---	59.59	59.07	58.50	57.76	57.08	56.31	55.64	54.96	54.33	53.63
13	---	---	59.57	59.06	58.43	57.78	57.02	56.23	55.59	54.96	54.29	53.70
14	---	---	59.51	58.98	58.44	57.74	56.98	56.26	55.54	54.92	54.26	53.72
15	---	60.15	59.50	59.05	58.45	57.70	57.00	56.28	55.53	54.83	54.18	53.71
16	---	60.05	59.50	59.03	58.40	57.65	57.04	56.25	55.51	54.81	54.15	53.68
17	---	60.00	59.49	58.99	58.36	57.66	57.05	56.20	55.47	54.79	54.16	53.64
18	---	60.16	59.44	58.87	58.40	57.66	57.04	56.18	55.41	54.79	54.17	53.66
19	---	60.21	59.44	58.89	58.48	57.68	56.97	56.19	55.43	54.72	54.18	53.65
20	---	60.16	59.41	59.05	57.80	57.68	56.97	56.19	55.42	54.68	54.19	53.64
21	---	60.11	59.39	58.89	57.94	57.60	56.98	56.14	55.36	54.70	54.17	53.58
22	---	60.12	59.30	58.81	57.95	57.57	56.96	56.09	55.33	54.81	54.09	53.49
23	---	60.06	59.23	58.82	57.95	57.58	56.94	56.09	55.34	54.79	53.99	53.45
24	---	60.04	59.24	58.82	57.94	57.61	56.88	56.07	55.32	54.66	53.98	53.50
25	---	60.00	59.28	58.72	57.85	57.60	56.86	56.01	55.30	54.69	54.05	53.58
26	---	59.98	59.23	58.71	57.83	57.54	56.82	55.94	55.29	54.71	54.10	53.58
27	---	59.96	59.23	58.74	57.88	57.48	56.79	55.95	55.27	54.67	54.04	53.46
28	---	59.96	59.24	58.78	57.94	57.45	56.75	55.93	55.23	54.63	53.97	53.46
29	---	59.96	59.30	58.74	---	57.41	56.74	55.90	55.24	54.58	53.98	53.52
30	---	59.87	59.22	58.77	---	57.37	56.70	55.87	55.20	54.55	54.00	53.57
31	---	---	59.23	58.83	---	57.35	---	55.87	---	54.51	53.92	---
LOW	---	---	59.85	59.23	58.76	57.91	57.29	56.70	55.82	55.21	54.50	53.93
HIGH	---	---	59.22	58.71	57.80	57.35	56.70	55.87	55.20	54.51	53.92	53.45

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW
LAND-SURFACE DATUM

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

18264706652400. Local number, 202.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'47", long 66°55'24".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Carmelo Barreto Garcia well.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-296 ft (0-90.2 m), diameter 13 in (0.33 m), cased 13 in (0.33 m) 0-550 ft (0-167.6 m), perforated 270-529 ft (82.3-161.2 m). Depth 550 ft (167.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 475 ft (145 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.50 ft (0.46 m) above land-surface datum. Prior July 25, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.30 ft (1.00 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on November 13, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 409.17 ft (127.76 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 25, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 452.80 ft (138.01 m) below land-surface datum, June 26, 1986.

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	432.09	433.34	434.55	435.83	434.36	---	451.94	451.18	---
2	---	---	433.90	432.10	433.35	434.58	435.85	434.04	---	451.81	451.27	---
3	---	---	433.70	432.13	433.37	434.68	435.88	433.70	---	451.67	451.34	---
4	---	---	433.55	432.16	433.45	434.71	435.92	433.15	---	451.59	451.36	---
5	---	---	433.39	432.20	433.51	434.76	435.92	432.23	---	451.48	451.41	---
6	---	---	433.24	432.24	433.58	434.78	435.92	431.32	---	451.40	451.47	---
7	---	---	433.08	432.26	433.60	434.84	435.91	430.56	---	451.35	451.50	---
8	---	---	432.96	432.29	433.63	434.92	435.90	429.84	---	451.29	451.55	---
9	---	---	432.82	432.36	433.67	434.98	435.88	429.17	---	451.20	451.63	---
10	---	---	432.69	432.36	433.72	435.02	435.81	428.59	---	451.13	451.68	---
11	---	---	432.57	432.36	433.77	435.03	435.77	428.05	---	451.07	451.75	---
12	---	---	432.43	432.41	433.81	435.08	435.69	427.53	---	451.03	451.83	---
13	---	---	432.33	432.43	433.83	435.14	435.60	426.93	---	451.01	451.87	---
14	---	435.31	432.23	432.49	433.89	435.17	435.56	426.24	---	450.98	451.90	---
15	---	435.18	432.14	432.55	433.93	435.20	435.51	425.25	---	450.90	451.94	---
16	---	435.02	432.06	432.61	433.99	435.24	435.45	423.99	---	450.90	451.98	---
17	---	434.83	431.97	432.63	434.03	435.30	435.41	422.77	---	450.86	452.08	---
18	---	434.71	---	432.64	434.03	435.36	435.39	421.84	---	450.86	452.19	---
19	---	---	431.96	432.69	434.05	435.42	435.34	420.95	---	450.84	---	---
20	---	---	431.93	432.72	434.12	435.47	435.34	---	---	450.84	---	---
21	---	---	431.91	432.78	434.16	435.48	435.33	---	---	450.88	---	---
22	---	---	431.92	432.83	434.22	435.54	435.30	---	---	450.98	---	---
23	---	---	431.91	432.85	434.26	435.58	435.27	---	---	450.99	---	---
24	---	---	431.96	432.90	434.32	435.63	435.21	---	---	450.96	---	---
25	---	---	431.96	432.93	434.31	435.67	435.17	---	---	450.99	---	---
26	---	---	431.99	432.97	434.37	435.69	435.11	---	---	451.03	---	409.29
27	---	---	432.01	433.00	434.46	435.71	435.05	---	452.60	451.05	---	409.33
28	---	---	431.99	433.09	434.53	435.76	434.98	---	452.38	451.06	---	409.41
29	---	---	431.99	433.15	---	435.81	434.90	---	452.24	451.08	---	409.53
30	---	---	432.03	433.20	---	435.82	434.71	---	452.06	451.12	---	409.64
31	---	---	432.08	433.28	---	435.84	---	---	---	451.15	---	---
LOW	---	---	---	433.28	434.53	435.84	435.92	---	---	451.94	---	---
HIGH	---	---	---	432.09	433.34	434.55	434.71	---	---	450.84	---	---

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CAMUY BASIN

182856066510900. Local number, 203.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°28'56", Long 66°51'09".

Owner: P.R. Industrial Development Corporation.

Name: Vicente Amador Well.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m) 0-130 ft (0-39.6 m), perforated 110-130 (33.5-39.6 m); open hole 130-140 ft (39.6-42.7 m). Depth 140 ft (42.7 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 116 ft (35.4 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.97 ft (0.90 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on November 14, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorder, 97.99 ft (29.87 m) below land-surface datum, June 27, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 99.70 ft (30.38 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 6, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	98.85	99.24	99.36	99.49	99.48	98.92	98.24	98.56	98.76	98.69
2	---	---	98.86	99.26	99.36	99.51	99.47	98.84	98.25	98.58	98.77	98.69
3	---	---	98.87	99.25	99.39	99.53	99.45	98.74	98.26	98.59	98.79	98.68
4	---	---	98.88	99.27	99.38	99.56	99.45	98.64	98.28	98.60	98.80	98.70
5	---	---	98.87	99.27	99.37	99.60	99.45	98.59	98.31	98.60	98.81	98.69
6	---	---	98.87	99.27	99.39	99.61	99.44	98.56	98.34	98.61	98.80	98.69
7	---	---	98.86	99.26	99.36	99.62	99.44	98.50	98.37	98.62	98.80	98.68
8	---	---	98.87	99.27	99.38	99.61	99.41	98.44	98.39	98.65	98.80	98.71
9	---	---	98.87	99.29	99.35	99.62	99.35	98.40	98.44	98.67	98.80	98.73
10	---	---	98.88	99.27	99.36	99.62	99.27	98.37	98.46	98.69	98.80	98.75
11	---	---	98.93	99.30	99.37	99.62	99.21	98.34	98.47	98.70	98.79	98.76
12	---	---	98.97	99.28	99.35	99.61	99.20	98.31	98.50	98.70	98.79	98.76
13	---	---	99.03	99.29	99.37	99.61	99.18	98.26	98.52	98.70	98.78	98.77
14	---	98.76	99.07	99.30	99.37	99.63	99.16	98.10	98.53	98.70	98.76	98.77
15	---	98.73	99.08	99.30	99.37	99.63	99.16	98.03	98.55	98.70	98.73	98.78
16	---	98.67	99.10	99.30	99.38	99.65	99.18	97.99	98.56	98.69	98.73	98.79
17	---	98.61	99.11	99.30	99.38	99.65	99.20	98.00	98.56	98.69	98.72	98.77
18	---	98.62	99.11	99.30	99.38	99.66	99.21	98.02	98.56	98.70	98.72	98.76
19	---	98.65	99.10	99.30	99.39	99.67	99.20	98.03	98.57	98.70	98.73	98.78
20	---	98.66	99.12	99.29	99.61	99.68	99.21	98.05	98.57	98.71	98.73	98.79
21	---	98.66	99.15	99.30	99.59	99.67	99.20	98.08	98.58	98.70	98.73	98.79
22	---	98.67	99.16	99.30	99.58	99.64	99.14	98.10	98.59	98.69	98.72	98.79
23	---	98.67	99.16	99.33	99.57	99.60	99.12	98.11	98.60	98.70	98.71	98.81
24	---	98.66	99.18	99.32	99.53	99.58	99.11	98.14	98.63	98.70	98.69	98.82
25	---	98.67	99.17	99.33	99.52	99.53	99.10	98.17	98.65	98.70	98.66	98.81
26	---	98.71	99.20	99.34	99.50	99.53	99.10	98.18	98.65	98.71	98.64	98.83
27	---	98.76	99.19	99.34	99.49	99.53	99.10	98.21	98.54	98.72	98.69	98.84
28	---	98.80	99.19	99.36	99.49	99.52	99.09	98.23	98.55	98.73	98.68	98.86
29	---	98.82	99.21	99.36	---	99.51	99.01	98.23	98.56	98.72	98.71	98.86
30	---	98.83	99.20	99.35	---	99.50	98.95	98.23	98.56	98.72	98.70	98.86
31	---	---	99.24	99.38	---	99.49	---	98.23	---	98.74	98.69	---
LOW	---	---	99.24	99.38	99.61	99.68	99.48	98.92	98.65	98.74	98.81	98.86
HIGH	---	---	98.85	99.24	99.35	99.49	98.95	97.99	98.24	98.56	98.64	98.68

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

182737066370900. Local number, 204.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'37", long 66°37'09".

Owner: Sucesión Marquez.

Name: Gilberto Rivera well.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Abandoned unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 48.0 ft (14.63 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Air hole on pump base, 0.50 ft (0.15 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Automatic recorder installed on October 16, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 50.00 ft (15.24 m) below land-surface datum, May 14, 1986; lowest water level recorded., 52.28 ft (15.93 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 5-6, 19-20, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	51.34	51.62	51.94	52.08	52.05	52.05	51.76	51.34	51.96	52.08	52.02
2	---	51.39	51.65	51.95	52.13	52.08	52.03	51.74	51.39	51.98	52.11	51.98
3	---	51.45	51.69	51.95	52.13	52.10	52.01	51.35	51.39	51.99	52.13	51.99
4	---	51.48	51.73	51.91	52.11	52.16	52.02	51.10	51.43	51.99	52.15	52.01
5	---	51.43	51.68	51.91	52.14	52.20	52.01	50.96	51.45	51.98	52.11	51.99
6	---	51.42	51.66	51.92	52.13	52.19	52.03	50.93	51.52	51.97	52.08	51.98
7	---	51.43	51.65	51.91	52.13	52.15	52.04	50.95	51.56	51.98	52.05	51.98
8	---	51.41	51.63	51.90	52.12	52.11	52.02	50.97	51.58	51.98	52.03	52.03
9	---	51.39	51.63	51.90	52.13	52.14	51.94	51.00	51.60	51.99	52.02	52.08
10	---	51.38	51.63	51.89	52.13	52.13	51.91	51.03	51.61	52.00	52.02	52.18
11	---	51.36	51.65	51.88	52.11	52.13	51.92	51.04	51.61	51.99	52.04	52.22
12	---	51.39	51.67	51.87	52.12	52.11	51.94	51.06	51.64	51.99	52.07	52.21
13	---	51.31	51.75	51.87	52.13	52.14	51.95	51.10	51.62	51.99	52.14	52.21
14	---	51.32	51.81	51.88	52.13	52.14	51.95	50.94	51.65	52.00	52.14	52.18
15	---	51.25	51.83	51.91	52.15	52.16	51.95	50.87	51.65	51.99	52.10	52.16
16	51.29	51.10	51.86	51.94	52.11	52.18	51.97	50.84	51.66	52.00	52.12	52.10
17	51.40	50.98	51.86	51.96	52.12	52.15	51.98	50.88	51.69	52.01	52.11	52.03
18	51.44	51.01	51.87	51.96	52.15	52.18	51.97	50.92	51.69	52.01	52.10	52.01
19	51.49	51.07	51.85	51.97	52.14	52.20	51.96	50.98	51.69	52.01	52.07	52.02
20	51.53	51.14	51.88	51.96	52.08	52.22	51.94	51.04	51.70	52.00	52.04	52.02
21	51.53	51.16	51.89	51.97	52.05	52.21	51.90	51.08	51.70	51.93	52.02	52.04
22	51.52	51.18	51.87	51.99	52.04	52.16	51.87	51.13	51.66	51.92	51.99	52.06
23	51.49	51.19	51.86	51.99	52.05	52.09	51.83	51.18	51.63	51.93	51.96	52.10
24	51.47	51.21	51.86	51.97	52.03	52.07	51.78	51.23	51.95	51.97	51.96	52.14
25	51.44	51.25	51.85	51.95	52.02	52.05	51.76	51.25	51.95	51.98	51.95	52.12
26	51.34	51.43	51.87	51.95	51.98	52.07	51.79	51.26	51.93	51.99	51.99	52.19
27	51.29	51.49	51.90	51.94	51.98	52.07	51.83	51.30	51.93	52.02	52.05	52.24
28	51.27	51.56	51.91	51.96	52.00	52.04	51.89	51.32	51.94	52.03	52.09	52.25
29	51.29	51.59	51.95	51.99	---	52.05	51.77	51.33	51.96	52.04	52.09	52.22
30	51.31	51.61	51.93	52.00	---	52.05	51.74	51.33	51.96	52.03	52.05	52.23
31	51.32	---	51.92	52.04	---	52.05	---	51.34	---	52.05	52.04	---
LOW	---	51.61	51.95	52.04	52.15	52.22	52.05	51.76	51.96	52.05	52.15	52.25
HIGH	---	50.98	51.62	51.87	51.98	52.04	51.74	50.84	51.34	51.92	51.95	51.98

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW
LAND-SURFACE DATUM

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182621066343300. Local number, 135
LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'21", long 66°34'33".

Owner: Puerto Rico Land Authority.
Name: Lederle.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled agricultural water-table well, diameter 24 in (0.61 m), cased 0-30 ft (0-9.1 m), diameter 16.62 in (0.42 m), cased to 0-450 ft (0-137.2 m). Depth 550 ft (167.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 287 ft (87.48 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.80 ft (0.85 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1979 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 276.8 ft (84.38 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 16, 1981; lowest water level recorded, 283.9 ft (86.55 m) below land-surface datum, May 3, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	283.46	282.93	282.97	283.31	283.41	283.40	283.42	283.11	282.40	282.84	283.11	283.09
2	283.49	282.94	282.99	283.30	283.46	283.44	283.41	283.08	282.42	282.87	283.13	283.08
3	283.52	282.98	283.01	283.29	283.48	283.46	283.40	282.77	282.45	282.89	283.14	283.09
4	283.54	283.00	283.03	283.26	283.48	283.52	283.39	281.20	282.48	282.90	283.15	283.11
5	283.55	282.95	283.01	283.25	283.52	283.54	283.39	280.62	282.53	282.90	283.15	283.12
6	283.53	282.92	282.99	283.27	283.53	283.56	283.40	280.90	282.57	282.90	283.15	283.12
7	283.38	282.91	282.96	283.29	283.55	283.55	283.42	281.20	282.61	282.91	283.14	283.12
8	283.03	282.90	282.96	283.32	283.55	283.53	283.40	281.42	282.67	282.93	283.14	283.14
9	282.88	282.88	282.97	283.33	283.56	283.53	283.32	281.60	282.70	282.95	283.14	283.15
10	282.84	282.89	283.01	283.34	283.55	283.54	283.24	281.74	282.74	282.98	283.14	283.22
11	282.84	282.91	283.07	283.33	283.54	283.53	283.23	281.81	282.75	282.98	283.14	283.23
12	282.83	282.94	283.10	283.30	283.53	283.53	283.23	281.94	282.77	282.98	283.15	283.21
13	282.81	282.93	283.15	283.28	283.53	283.53	283.25	281.99	282.78	282.96	283.16	283.19
14	282.81	282.92	283.19	283.26	283.53	283.54	283.24	281.93	282.79	282.96	283.15	283.16
15	282.85	282.83	283.19	283.27	283.52	283.53	283.26	281.71	282.79	282.94	283.17	283.16
16	282.89	282.71	283.20	283.28	283.52	283.55	283.28	281.53	282.78	282.93	283.13	283.16
17	282.96	282.47	283.19	283.30	283.49	283.54	283.30	281.53	282.78	282.93	283.12	283.15
18	283.00	282.40	283.19	283.31	283.52	283.54	283.30	281.59	282.79	282.92	283.13	283.14
19	283.01	282.40	283.17	283.32	283.52	283.56	283.28	281.64	282.79	282.96	283.13	283.15
20	283.03	282.43	283.18	283.32	283.52	283.59	283.25	281.78	282.80	283.01	283.14	283.16
21	283.03	282.48	283.20	283.34	283.48	283.60	283.22	281.82	282.82	283.04	283.14	283.18
22	283.02	282.53	283.20	283.37	283.46	283.57	283.18	281.95	282.82	283.07	283.13	283.20
23	283.01	282.56	283.20	283.38	283.46	283.53	283.15	282.00	282.81	283.11	283.12	283.23
24	283.00	282.61	283.22	283.38	283.45	283.51	283.13	282.11	282.85	283.11	283.11	283.24
25	282.99	282.68	283.23	283.37	283.44	283.47	283.12	282.16	282.87	283.11	283.09	283.22
26	282.95	282.73	283.26	283.36	283.38	283.47	283.13	282.21	282.86	283.10	283.09	283.23
27	282.92	282.80	283.30	283.36	283.36	283.48	283.15	282.29	282.85	283.13	283.12	283.25
28	282.87	282.87	283.33	283.36	283.37	283.45	283.17	282.34	282.86	283.12	283.13	283.26
29	282.88	282.92	283.35	283.38	---	283.44	283.15	282.37	282.86	283.11	283.13	283.24
30	282.90	282.95	283.34	283.38	---	283.44	283.13	282.38	282.85	283.11	283.12	283.25
31	282.91	---	283.31	283.39	---	283.43	---	282.39	---	283.10	283.10	---
LOW	283.55	283.00	283.35	283.39	283.56	283.60	283.42	283.11	282.87	283.13	283.17	283.26
HIGH	282.81	282.40	282.96	283.25	283.36	283.40	283.12	280.62	282.40	282.84	283.09	283.08
WTR YR 1986	MEAN 283		LOW 283.60		HIGH 280.62							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182757066325600. Local number, 206.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'57", long 66°32'56".

Owner: P.R. Department of Agriculture.

Name: Plazuela No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-85 ft (0-25.9 m), open hole 85-101 ft (25.9-30.8 m). Depth 101 ft (30.8 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 7.0 ft (2.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on August 15, 1985. Estimated noon values: Jan. 5-8, Feb. 16-19.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.86 ft (1.18 m) below land-surface datum, May 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 5.47 ft (1.67 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 12, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.20	4.68	4.80	5.08	5.20	5.15	5.24	4.92	4.58	4.92	4.99	---
2	5.23	4.68	4.83	5.08	5.20	5.17	5.23	4.89	4.60	4.94	5.02	---
3	5.27	4.68	4.84	5.10	5.20	5.24	5.22	4.39	4.61	4.96	5.05	---
4	5.31	4.68	4.82	5.11	5.20	5.25	5.22	4.07	4.64	4.97	5.07	---
5	5.31	4.68	4.80	5.11	5.20	5.25	5.21	4.01	4.68	4.96	5.09	---
6	5.27	4.68	4.77	5.11	5.20	5.25	5.22	4.02	4.71	4.95	---	---
7	4.77	4.68	4.77	5.10	5.20	5.29	5.24	4.06	4.75	4.97	---	---
8	4.55	4.68	4.78	5.10	5.20	5.28	5.22	4.09	4.78	4.97	---	---
9	4.56	4.68	4.80	5.10	5.20	5.30	5.08	4.13	4.80	4.99	---	---
10	4.61	4.68	4.83	5.10	5.20	5.37	5.05	4.15	4.82	5.01	---	---
11	4.64	4.68	4.89	5.09	5.20	5.37	5.06	4.17	4.82	5.00	---	---
12	4.61	4.68	4.95	5.08	5.20	5.37	5.08	4.25	4.85	4.99	---	---
13	4.58	4.68	4.98	5.06	5.20	5.39	5.10	4.21	4.84	4.99	---	---
14	4.57	4.68	4.99	5.08	5.20	5.34	5.10	3.94	4.86	4.99	---	---
15	4.60	4.68	5.01	5.11	5.20	5.34	5.12	3.88	4.85	4.98	---	---
16	4.65	4.68	4.99	5.13	5.21	5.31	5.14	3.89	4.86	4.98	---	---
17	4.72	4.68	4.98	5.13	5.23	5.32	5.15	3.94	4.87	4.99	---	---
18	4.76	4.67	5.00	5.15	5.25	5.38	5.14	4.02	4.87	4.99	---	---
19	4.81	4.67	5.02	5.14	5.27	5.36	5.12	4.09	4.88	4.99	---	---
20	4.84	4.67	5.01	5.16	5.28	5.35	5.10	4.16	4.89	4.99	---	---
21	4.84	4.67	5.01	5.20	5.24	5.34	4.98	4.23	4.91	4.94	---	---
22	4.83	4.67	5.01	5.20	5.24	5.33	4.96	4.29	4.89	4.93	---	---
23	4.81	4.67	5.03	5.20	5.23	5.33	4.96	4.33	4.87	4.92	---	---
24	4.78	4.67	5.07	5.20	5.21	5.34	4.95	4.40	4.90	4.92	---	---
25	4.74	4.67	5.12	5.20	5.28	5.36	4.93	4.45	4.92	4.92	---	---
26	4.65	4.59	5.13	5.20	5.22	5.34	4.96	4.49	4.89	4.93	---	---
27	4.61	4.66	5.13	5.20	5.19	5.42	4.99	4.53	4.90	4.93	---	---
28	4.60	4.72	5.10	5.20	5.20	5.42	5.02	4.56	4.91	4.97	---	---
29	4.62	4.75	5.10	5.20	---	5.38	4.94	4.57	4.92	4.98	---	---
30	4.64	4.78	5.10	5.20	---	5.35	4.91	4.57	4.93	4.99	---	---
31	4.68	---	5.10	5.20	---	5.39	---	4.58	---	4.97	---	---
LOW	5.31	4.78	5.13	5.20	5.28	5.42	5.24	4.92	4.93	4.92	---	---
HIGH	4.55	4.59	4.77	5.06	5.19	5.15	4.91	3.88	4.58	5.01	---	---

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW
LAND-SURFACE DATUM

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182710066303700. Local number, 207.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'10", long 66°30'37".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Cantito La Luisa.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-30 ft (0-9.14 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 0-126 ft (0-38.4 m), perforated 80-126 ft (24.4-38.4 m). Depth 126 ft (38.4 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 59.0 ft (18.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on September 17, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 36.38 ft (11.09 m) below land-surface datum, May 15, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 89.83 ft (27.38 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 5, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	88.83	38.29	38.04	38.69	38.85	38.92	39.09	38.71	37.84	38.62	38.80	38.77
2	89.13	38.29	---	38.71	38.86	38.96	39.09	38.71	37.89	38.63	38.83	38.76
3	89.43	38.29	---	38.73	38.87	39.00	39.09	37.95	37.91	38.65	38.85	38.77
4	89.63	38.29	---	38.74	38.87	39.01	39.10	37.78	37.95	38.66	38.86	38.80
5	89.83	37.85	---	38.74	38.89	39.04	39.08	37.87	37.99	38.67	38.87	38.81
6	89.43	37.92	---	38.75	38.92	39.06	39.08	37.92	38.03	38.69	38.87	38.82
7	80.93	37.97	---	38.78	38.95	39.08	39.09	37.94	38.08	38.69	38.87	38.84
8	76.33	38.00	---	38.86	38.97	39.08	39.09	37.93	38.11	38.72	38.87	38.85
9	77.03	38.01	---	38.88	38.99	39.09	38.94	37.93	38.15	38.75	38.87	38.87
10	79.43	38.05	---	38.84	39.00	39.09	38.91	37.95	38.19	38.78	38.87	38.90
11	80.03	38.08	---	38.83	39.00	39.08	38.90	37.95	38.23	38.79	38.88	38.90
12	80.43	38.12	38.28	38.82	39.01	39.08	38.90	38.00	38.26	38.79	38.89	38.90
13	80.73	38.02	38.33	38.77	39.02	39.10	38.90	37.81	38.28	38.79	38.89	38.90
14	81.13	38.00	38.37	38.77	39.03	39.11	38.90	36.61	38.32	38.79	38.88	38.90
15	81.43	37.79	38.40	38.77	39.04	39.12	38.92	36.41	38.34	38.78	38.87	38.90
16	81.73	37.43	38.43	38.78	39.03	39.13	38.94	36.55	38.37	38.78	38.87	38.90
17	38.21	37.23	38.45	38.82	39.01	39.14	38.96	36.68	38.39	38.78	38.87	38.90
18	38.26	37.24	38.46	38.82	39.02	39.16	38.95	36.82	38.40	38.78	38.87	38.90
19	38.30	37.29	38.47	38.82	39.03	39.18	38.96	36.96	38.42	38.79	38.88	38.91
20	38.33	37.35	38.50	38.83	39.01	39.20	38.92	37.08	38.45	38.80	38.88	38.91
21	38.35	37.42	38.54	38.86	39.00	39.21	38.49	37.21	38.48	38.79	38.89	38.92
22	38.37	37.49	38.56	38.81	39.01	39.20	38.41	37.29	38.50	38.80	38.89	38.92
23	38.38	37.55	38.58	38.83	38.99	39.17	38.50	37.38	38.52	38.76	38.88	38.93
24	38.39	37.61	38.60	38.83	38.97	39.14	38.54	37.47	38.54	38.76	38.86	38.95
25	38.36	37.68	38.61	38.83	38.96	39.12	38.57	37.55	38.56	38.76	38.80	38.94
26	38.33	37.80	38.62	38.84	38.94	39.11	38.61	37.63	38.57	38.71	38.77	38.95
27	38.31	37.85	38.65	38.83	38.93	39.11	38.65	37.70	38.58	38.74	38.81	38.95
28	38.28	37.91	38.66	38.81	38.92	39.10	38.68	37.75	38.59	38.75	38.82	38.97
29	38.28	37.96	38.67	38.82	---	39.07	38.68	37.81	38.60	38.76	38.81	38.96
30	38.27	38.00	38.68	38.82	---	39.07	38.69	37.84	38.61	38.76	38.80	38.96
31	38.28	---	38.68	38.83	---	39.08	---	37.87	---	38.77	38.77	---
LOW	89.83	38.29	---	38.88	39.04	39.21	39.10	38.71	38.61	38.80	38.89	38.97
HIGH	38.21	37.23	---	38.69	38.85	38.92	38.41	36.41	37.84	38.62	38.77	38.76

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182534066283000. Local number, 208.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'34", long 66°28'30".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Acropolis Manati.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 14 in (0.36 m), cased 14 in (0.36 m). Depth 235 ft (71.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 254 ft (77.4 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.70 ft (0.21 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on January 8, 1986.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1986 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 228.21 ft (69.56 m) below land-surface datum, May 18, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 238.14 ft (72.58 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 8, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	236.02	236.04	236.15	236.15	228.99	235.48	237.90	238.14
2	---	---	---	---	236.02	236.04	236.15	236.15	229.03	235.61	237.97	238.14
3	---	---	---	---	236.02	236.04	236.15	235.67	229.10	235.70	238.08	238.14
4	---	---	---	---	236.02	236.04	236.15	234.89	229.23	235.84	238.10	238.14
5	---	---	---	---	236.02	236.04	236.15	234.45	229.36	235.94	238.13	238.14
6	---	---	---	---	236.02	236.04	236.15	234.21	229.55	236.05	238.13	238.14
7	---	---	---	---	236.02	236.04	236.15	234.18	229.68	236.11	238.13	238.14
8	---	---	---	---	236.02	236.04	236.15	234.18	229.89	236.24	238.14	238.14
9	---	---	---	235.33	236.02	236.04	236.15	234.20	230.03	236.29	238.14	238.14
10	---	---	---	235.30	236.02	236.04	236.15	234.23	230.18	236.40	238.14	238.14
11	---	---	---	235.30	236.02	236.04	236.15	234.16	230.30	236.45	238.14	238.14
12	---	---	---	235.33	236.02	236.04	236.15	234.13	230.48	236.49	238.14	238.14
13	---	---	---	235.41	236.02	236.04	236.15	233.79	230.66	236.62	238.14	238.14
14	---	---	---	235.44	236.02	236.04	236.15	230.91	230.83	236.69	238.14	238.14
15	---	---	---	235.57	236.02	236.04	236.15	229.82	230.99	236.80	238.14	238.14
16	---	---	---	235.64	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.86	231.14	236.83	238.14	238.14
17	---	---	---	235.67	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.33	231.26	236.85	238.14	238.14
18	---	---	---	235.71	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.23	231.41	236.95	238.14	238.14
19	---	---	---	235.82	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.24	231.57	237.02	238.14	238.14
20	---	---	---	235.86	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.35	231.75	237.08	238.14	238.14
21	---	---	---	235.89	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.46	231.89	237.15	238.14	238.14
22	---	---	---	235.91	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.61	232.05	237.26	238.14	238.14
23	---	---	---	235.91	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.69	232.20	237.34	238.14	238.14
24	---	---	---	235.91	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.84	232.34	237.47	238.14	238.14
25	---	---	---	235.91	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.90	234.69	237.53	238.14	238.14
26	---	---	---	235.91	236.02	236.04	236.15	229.04	234.86	237.57	238.14	238.14
27	---	---	---	235.91	236.04	236.04	236.15	229.16	235.00	237.65	238.14	238.14
28	---	---	---	235.91	236.04	236.04	236.15	229.25	235.11	237.68	238.14	238.14
29	---	---	---	236.02	---	236.04	236.15	229.29	235.24	237.74	238.14	238.14
30	---	---	---	236.02	---	236.04	236.15	229.02	235.35	237.81	238.14	238.14
31	---	---	---	236.02	---	236.04	---	228.98	---	237.87	238.14	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	236.04	236.04	236.15	236.15	235.35	237.87	238.14	238.14
HIGH	---	---	---	---	236.02	236.04	236.15	228.23	228.98	235.48	237.90	238.14

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182634066262500. Local number, 209.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'34", long 66°26'25".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Coto Norte No. 3.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon-Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-495 ft (0-150.9 m), perforated 255-455 ft (77.7-138.7 m). Depth 495 FT (150.9 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 99.0 ft (30.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.30 ft (0.70 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on September 11, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 71.50 ft (21.79 m) below land-surface datum, July 23, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 81.96 ft (24.98 m) below land-surface datum, June 24, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	81.81	80.20	78.88	81.14	81.57	81.48	81.83	81.56	78.59	80.99	79.66	79.80
2	81.82	80.34	79.05	81.17	81.57	81.50	81.83	81.02	78.83	---	79.71	79.83
3	81.84	80.46	79.21	81.19	81.57	81.54	81.82	79.69	78.99	---	79.77	79.74
4	81.86	80.54	79.34	81.21	81.57	81.56	81.81	78.50	79.16	---	79.79	79.78
5	81.86	80.18	79.48	81.24	81.57	81.57	81.63	78.09	79.37	---	79.83	79.81
6	81.68	80.18	79.58	81.26	81.58	81.59	81.71	78.62	79.56	---	79.85	79.85
7	77.93	80.24	79.71	81.29	81.58	81.62	81.71	78.89	79.69	---	79.86	79.86
8	78.05	80.36	79.83	81.33	81.58	81.62	81.72	78.99	79.82	---	79.88	79.89
9	78.47	80.46	79.93	81.34	81.58	81.64	81.18	79.21	79.95	---	79.90	79.93
10	78.83	80.54	80.03	81.32	81.57	81.64	81.38	79.37	80.07	---	79.91	79.95
11	79.12	80.64	80.11	81.32	81.56	81.64	81.46	79.22	80.17	---	79.92	79.96
12	79.35	80.71	80.19	81.33	81.55	81.64	81.52	79.11	80.29	---	79.94	79.98
13	79.58	79.44	80.29	81.33	81.55	81.65	81.59	77.17	80.38	---	79.95	80.01
14	79.77	79.25	80.38	81.35	81.55	81.66	81.62	73.93	80.40	---	79.94	80.03
15	79.96	77.62	80.44	81.37	81.56	81.65	81.66	72.79	80.48	---	79.93	80.05
16	80.12	75.83	80.51	81.39	81.53	81.65	81.65	72.64	80.54	---	79.94	80.08
17	80.29	75.29	80.57	81.41	81.52	81.68	81.55	72.80	80.59	---	79.96	80.09
18	80.42	75.28	80.63	81.40	81.52	81.70	81.54	73.15	80.65	---	79.98	80.11
19	80.47	75.43	80.69	81.42	81.51	81.73	81.60	73.67	80.71	---	79.99	80.14
20	80.54	75.69	80.73	81.43	81.51	81.75	81.65	74.25	80.75	---	80.02	80.17
21	80.54	75.99	80.78	81.45	81.50	81.77	81.42	74.82	80.80	---	80.03	80.18
22	80.63	76.39	80.83	81.48	81.50	81.79	81.45	75.38	80.85	---	80.03	80.19
23	80.69	76.74	80.86	81.49	81.49	81.78	81.19	75.90	80.89	---	80.03	80.21
24	80.68	77.08	80.88	81.52	81.49	81.77	81.33	76.38	81.14	79.51	80.02	80.24
25	80.42	77.40	80.88	81.53	81.47	81.76	81.41	76.81	81.78	79.53	79.84	80.25
26	79.76	77.72	80.94	81.53	81.46	81.74	81.48	77.20	81.18	79.56	79.91	80.25
27	79.89	77.99	80.99	81.52	81.49	81.74	81.51	77.66	81.20	79.57	79.92	80.26
28	79.41	78.23	81.03	81.54	81.49	81.77	81.50	77.96	81.24	79.60	79.94	80.28
29	79.61	78.49	81.07	81.57	---	81.80	81.51	78.23	81.26	79.60	79.93	80.29
30	79.82	78.73	81.10	81.55	---	81.82	81.53	78.23	81.29	79.60	79.83	80.31
31	80.02	---	81.12	81.56	---	81.83	---	78.48	---	79.64	79.79	---
LOW	81.86	80.71	81.12	81.57	81.58	81.83	81.83	81.56	81.78	---	80.03	80.31
HIGH	77.93	75.28	78.88	81.14	81.46	81.48	81.18	72.64	78.59	---	79.66	79.74

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182308066260400. Local number, 210.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'08", long 66°26'04".
Owner: Gelo Martinez.

Name: Gelo Martinez well.

AQUIFER.--Lares Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 574 ft (174.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on February 27, 1986.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 40.56 ft (12.36 m) below land-surface datum, May 22, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 67.67 ft (20.62 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 6, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 31	49.00	Nov. 26	21.40	Jan. 8	49.03	Jan. 29	49.30

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	62.52	67.11	62.68	44.20	49.06	50.04	54.51
2	---	---	---	---	---	62.52	67.29	62.33	44.95	49.05	50.48	54.73
3	---	---	---	---	---	62.87	67.38	51.86	45.78	49.05	51.36	54.76
4	---	---	---	---	---	63.14	67.55	48.97	46.53	49.05	52.42	53.42
5	---	---	---	---	---	63.83	67.63	48.03	47.26	49.04	53.53	53.21
6	---	---	---	---	---	64.23	67.67	48.14	47.80	49.04	54.77	54.08
7	---	---	---	---	---	64.66	67.61	48.44	48.26	49.04	55.92	55.14
8	---	---	---	---	---	65.01	67.51	48.41	48.65	49.05	57.00	56.32
9	---	---	---	---	---	65.27	67.46	48.26	48.91	49.06	57.99	57.60
10	---	---	---	---	---	65.49	67.43	47.97	49.02	49.05	58.80	58.93
11	---	---	---	---	---	65.66	67.43	47.61	49.04	49.06	59.42	59.70
12	---	---	---	---	---	65.77	66.95	47.51	49.04	49.07	59.80	60.42
13	---	---	---	---	---	65.87	66.79	47.24	49.04	49.07	60.01	60.97
14	---	---	---	---	---	65.93	66.69	46.15	49.04	49.07	59.97	61.67
15	---	---	---	---	---	66.02	66.67	45.13	49.03	49.07	59.49	62.10
16	---	---	---	---	---	53.11	66.04	66.67	43.83	49.04	49.06	58.95
17	---	---	---	---	---	66.09	66.71	42.92	49.04	49.05	58.69	62.41
18	---	---	---	---	---	66.13	66.81	42.17	49.04	49.05	58.76	62.51
19	---	---	---	---	---	66.17	66.75	41.49	49.04	49.06	59.21	62.59
20	---	---	---	---	---	66.23	66.68	41.03	49.04	49.04	59.78	62.66
21	---	---	---	---	---	66.28	66.58	40.75	49.04	49.06	60.33	62.74
22	---	---	---	---	---	66.35	66.31	40.60	49.03	49.07	60.97	62.81
23	---	---	---	---	---	66.42	65.96	40.59	49.03	49.10	61.58	62.87
24	---	---	---	---	---	66.46	63.05	40.69	49.04	49.13	62.06	62.97
25	---	---	---	---	---	66.53	62.58	40.86	49.04	49.15	62.09	63.14
26	---	---	---	---	---	66.61	62.48	41.13	49.04	49.20	61.25	63.45
27	---	---	---	---	---	62.23	66.67	62.53	41.49	49.04	49.20	60.45
28	---	---	---	---	62.38	66.77	62.62	41.92	49.04	49.20	60.08	63.90
29	---	---	---	---	---	66.86	62.66	42.39	49.05	49.19	59.91	64.08
30	---	---	---	---	---	66.91	62.71	42.91	49.05	49.25	58.67	64.21
31	---	---	---	---	---	66.91	---	43.53	---	49.63	55.87	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	66.91	67.67	62.68	49.05	49.63	62.09	64.21
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	62.52	62.48	40.59	44.20	49.04	50.04	53.21

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW
LAND-SURFACE DATUM

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182615066235300. Local number, 211.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'15", long 66°23'53".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Rosario No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 14 in (0.36 m) 0-200 ft (0-61.0 m), diameter 12 in (0.30 m) 200-250 ft (61.0-76.2 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-250 ft (0-76.2 m), perforated 210-250 ft (64.0-76.2 m), diameter 10 in (0.25 m) 250-270 ft (76.2-82.3 m), open hole; concrete sealed 0-200 ft (0-61.0 m). Depth 270 ft (82.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 215 ft (65.5 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.15 ft (0.35 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on September 17, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 191.29 ft (58.30 m) below land-surface datum, May 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 193.10 ft (58.86 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 21, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	193.05	192.23	191.85	192.42	192.82	192.85	193.06	192.90	191.86	192.57	192.69	192.69
2	193.05	192.24	191.88	192.42	192.84	192.89	193.04	192.88	191.86	192.57	192.69	192.69
3	193.06	192.27	191.92	192.42	192.85	192.91	193.05	192.80	191.87	192.57	192.69	192.69
4	193.09	192.30	191.94	192.43	192.86	192.94	193.05	192.67	191.87	192.58	192.69	192.69
5	193.09	192.30	191.95	192.43	192.89	192.96	193.03	192.52	191.91	192.58	192.69	192.69
6	193.09	192.30	191.96	192.45	192.91	192.98	193.02	192.49	191.97	192.60	192.69	192.69
7	192.52	192.30	191.97	192.45	192.93	192.98	193.02	192.49	192.00	192.60	192.72	192.69
8	192.13	192.30	191.98	192.68	192.93	192.98	193.02	192.49	192.08	192.60	192.73	192.69
9	192.02	192.30	192.01	192.69	192.94	192.98	192.97	192.45	192.10	192.60	192.73	192.69
10	192.02	192.31	192.06	192.69	192.96	192.98	192.93	192.41	192.12	192.60	192.73	192.69
11	192.07	192.32	192.07	192.68	192.96	192.98	192.93	192.40	192.16	192.60	192.73	192.69
12	192.10	192.33	192.08	192.67	192.96	192.98	192.93	192.40	192.18	192.60	192.74	192.69
13	192.13	192.33	192.12	192.67	192.99	192.98	192.93	192.24	192.18	192.60	192.74	192.69
14	192.19	192.19	192.16	192.67	192.99	192.99	192.93	192.21	192.19	192.60	192.74	192.69
15	192.24	192.08	192.17	192.67	192.99	192.99	192.93	191.34	192.19	192.60	192.74	192.69
16	192.29	191.70	192.19	192.67	192.99	193.03	192.93	191.30	192.19	192.60	192.74	192.69
17	192.40	191.39	192.21	192.68	192.99	193.04	192.99	191.29	192.19	192.60	192.74	192.69
18	192.41	191.31	192.22	192.68	192.99	193.05	192.99	191.29	192.19	192.60	192.74	192.69
19	192.41	191.31	192.23	192.69	193.00	193.05	192.99	191.29	192.29	192.60	192.74	192.69
20	192.41	191.31	192.24	192.69	193.01	193.08	192.98	191.29	192.34	192.60	192.74	192.69
21	192.41	191.36	192.25	192.71	193.01	193.10	192.96	191.31	192.37	192.60	192.74	192.69
22	192.41	191.43	192.26	192.73	193.01	193.10	192.92	191.36	192.38	192.60	192.74	192.69
23	192.42	191.51	192.32	192.75	193.01	193.10	192.90	191.45	192.38	192.69	192.74	192.70
24	192.42	191.57	192.32	192.75	193.00	193.09	192.89	191.55	192.53	192.69	192.74	192.70
25	192.42	191.65	192.33	192.75	192.99	193.09	192.89	191.59	192.56	192.69	192.74	192.71
26	192.36	191.66	192.34	192.75	192.98	193.09	192.89	191.71	192.57	192.69	192.70	192.71
27	192.31	191.70	192.37	192.75	192.85	193.09	192.90	191.75	192.57	192.69	192.70	192.71
28	192.26	191.74	192.38	192.76	192.85	193.09	192.90	191.78	192.57	192.69	192.70	192.71
29	192.22	191.79	192.40	192.77	---	193.07	192.91	191.84	192.57	192.69	192.70	192.71
30	192.19	191.82	192.41	192.79	---	193.07	192.90	191.86	192.57	192.69	192.70	192.71
31	192.23	---	192.41	192.80	---	193.06	---	191.86	---	192.69	192.69	---
LOW	193.09	192.33	192.41	192.80	193.01	193.10	193.06	192.90	192.57	192.69	192.74	192.71
HIGH	192.02	191.31	191.85	192.42	192.82	192.85	192.89	191.29	191.86	192.57	192.69	192.69
WTR YR 1986	MEAN 193		LOW 193.10		HIGH 191.29							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182515066194000. Local number, 212.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'15", long 66°19'40".

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey.

Name: Ponderosa TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone-Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-136 ft (0-41.1 m), perforated 121-131 ft (36.9-39.9 m); bentonite packed 0.5-121 ft (0.15-36.9 m).
Depth 136 ft (39.9 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 98.0 ft (29.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Automatic recorder installed on October 17, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 64.00 ft (19.51 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 1, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 73.79 ft (22.49 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 29, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	66.17	64.19	65.37	66.74	68.18	70.31	72.37	68.56	67.99	68.42	69.30
2	---	66.17	64.22	65.39	66.78	67.08	71.09	71.06	68.73	68.05	68.49	69.22
3	---	66.17	64.27	65.42	66.82	68.53	71.06	70.48	68.84	68.09	68.53	69.16
4	---	66.14	64.25	65.46	66.86	68.97	70.84	70.18	68.91	68.12	68.57	69.11
5	---	66.09	64.29	65.49	66.90	69.37	70.66	69.90	68.19	68.16	68.60	69.07
6	---	66.03	64.32	65.51	66.94	69.71	70.53	69.73	68.91	68.20	68.67	69.05
7	---	66.02	64.38	65.53	66.98	69.95	70.42	69.63	67.28	68.21	68.70	69.03
8	---	66.02	64.38	65.86	67.02	70.20	70.34	69.49	67.20	68.25	68.74	69.02
9	---	66.03	64.40	65.90	67.06	70.27	70.27	69.35	67.17	68.28	68.78	69.01
10	---	66.03	64.50	65.95	67.11	70.51	70.21	69.24	67.08	68.32	68.81	68.95
11	---	66.03	64.50	65.95	67.14	70.73	70.15	69.05	66.96	68.35	68.79	68.95
12	---	66.03	64.50	65.96	67.18	70.90	70.09	68.88	66.91	68.35	68.82	68.99
13	---	65.99	64.50	65.99	67.23	71.05	70.06	68.69	66.98	68.22	68.84	71.05
14	---	65.94	64.50	66.02	67.28	71.19	70.03	68.20	67.05	68.22	68.84	71.29
15	---	65.94	64.50	66.07	67.28	71.32	69.93	67.79	67.10	68.24	68.84	71.44
16	---	65.29	64.50	66.10	67.29	71.46	69.89	67.50	67.17	68.25	68.84	71.84
17	---	64.95	64.87	66.14	67.35	71.57	69.90	67.29	67.00	68.25	68.86	72.13
18	66.76	64.76	64.85	66.17	67.40	71.72	70.04	67.11	67.24	68.25	68.89	72.38
19	66.72	64.59	64.87	66.18	67.44	71.83	71.75	66.97	67.29	68.25	68.91	72.59
20	66.72	64.48	64.94	66.21	67.49	71.87	71.93	66.86	67.32	68.12	68.93	72.77
21	66.64	64.37	64.99	66.25	67.55	71.87	72.10	66.78	67.38	68.02	68.97	72.92
22	66.64	64.31	65.05	66.29	67.56	71.97	72.10	66.71	67.42	68.06	68.99	73.05
23	66.65	64.24	65.11	66.33	67.57	72.08	72.21	66.54	67.48	68.12	69.68	73.19
24	66.65	64.18	65.11	66.37	67.57	72.17	72.31	66.46	67.52	68.17	71.19	73.46
25	66.65	64.10	65.14	66.41	67.60	72.18	72.39	66.46	67.70	68.22	71.32	73.39
26	66.65	64.11	65.18	66.45	68.30	72.26	72.47	66.46	67.76	68.28	71.31	73.47
27	66.64	64.11	65.22	66.48	68.13	72.35	72.51	68.02	67.82	68.31	71.58	73.55
28	66.60	64.16	65.22	66.54	67.57	72.42	72.53	68.19	67.86	68.35	71.67	73.42
29	66.49	64.16	65.28	66.59	---	72.49	70.82	68.40	67.90	68.40	70.23	73.65
30	66.22	64.16	65.30	66.63	---	71.03	72.21	68.42	67.94	68.36	69.61	73.74
31	66.17	---	65.33	66.68	---	70.48	---	68.63	---	68.37	69.42	---
LOW	---	66.17	65.33	66.68	68.30	72.49	72.53	72.37	68.91	68.40	71.67	73.74
HIGH	---	64.10	64.19	65.37	66.74	67.08	69.89	66.46	66.91	67.99	68.42	68.95

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182330066185700. Local number, 213.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'30", long 66°18'57".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Pampano No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Rio Indio Limestone-Lares Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-130 ft (0-39.6 m), diameter 14 in (0.36 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-220 ft (0-67.1 m); open hole 220-330 ft (67.6-100.6 m). Depth 330 ft (100.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 394 ft (120 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.95 ft (0.90 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on September 16, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 34.40 ft (10.50 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 6, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 49.55 ft (15.10 m) below land-surface datum, May 1, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	47.17	40.55	34.62	37.26	40.39	45.09	47.96	49.54	43.13	43.03	44.69	46.42
2	47.21	40.48	34.62	37.36	40.44	45.19	47.05	49.49	43.01	43.08	44.78	46.09
3	47.30	40.48	34.61	37.50	40.49	45.35	47.17	49.38	42.90	43.12	44.87	46.19
4	47.33	40.47	34.59	37.60	40.65	45.47	47.29	49.32	42.75	43.19	44.92	46.19
5	47.32	40.48	34.57	37.76	40.79	45.58	47.33	49.11	42.80	43.24	44.97	46.25
6	47.18	40.50	34.55	37.88	40.88	45.64	47.37	49.00	42.82	43.33	45.03	46.25
7	46.21	40.51	34.60	37.96	40.97	45.79	47.34	48.84	42.76	43.38	45.05	46.31
8	45.08	40.55	34.67	38.07	41.03	45.96	47.34	48.50	42.76	43.44	45.08	46.34
9	44.47	40.56	34.72	38.19	41.12	46.10	47.57	48.32	42.82	43.53	45.16	46.39
10	44.00	40.56	34.79	38.28	41.19	46.17	47.71	48.13	42.88	43.55	45.21	46.08
11	43.63	40.51	34.84	38.33	41.30	46.18	47.80	47.81	42.93	43.57	45.30	46.19
12	43.33	40.51	34.91	38.42	41.40	46.29	47.87	47.40	42.95	43.61	44.93	46.27
13	43.12	40.39	34.97	38.51	41.46	46.39	47.94	47.10	42.91	43.72	45.31	46.40
14	42.97	40.18	35.03	38.61	41.52	46.46	48.03	46.26	42.92	43.76	45.39	46.45
15	42.90	39.68	35.12	38.76	42.37	46.53	48.14	45.41	43.01	43.75	45.43	46.53
16	42.90	38.75	35.22	38.82	42.66	46.61	48.25	44.83	43.00	43.81	45.50	46.55
17	42.78	37.93	35.32	38.91	42.91	46.72	48.36	44.15	42.88	43.87	45.61	46.56
18	42.74	37.43	35.42	38.98	42.91	46.82	48.48	44.09	42.81	43.94	45.70	46.62
19	42.64	36.93	35.53	39.09	43.05	46.94	48.53	43.89	42.80	43.98	45.77	46.68
20	42.55	36.43	35.72	39.17	43.19	46.90	48.68	43.84	42.79	44.02	45.85	46.72
21	42.37	36.03	35.86	39.30	43.30	46.95	48.77	43.78	42.75	44.11	45.89	46.73
22	42.25	35.72	35.99	39.40	43.42	47.08	48.84	43.73	42.73	44.21	45.89	46.74
23	42.06	35.42	36.11	39.49	43.62	47.22	48.93	43.68	42.76	44.27	45.89	46.76
24	41.92	35.18	36.29	39.57	43.59	47.32	49.01	43.69	42.69	44.25	46.01	46.74
25	41.68	35.20	36.40	39.65	43.63	47.41	49.09	43.63	42.72	44.31	46.14	46.88
26	41.54	35.07	36.59	39.75	43.77	47.51	49.16	43.62	42.78	44.41	46.25	46.91
27	41.38	34.94	36.69	39.84	44.00	47.58	49.22	43.68	42.81	44.41	46.31	46.91
28	41.17	34.86	36.80	39.98	45.01	47.68	49.32	43.63	42.84	44.45	46.33	46.98
29	40.91	34.81	36.88	40.07	---	47.80	49.35	43.57	42.90	44.53	46.41	47.05
30	40.75	34.69	37.00	40.14	---	47.85	49.45	43.43	42.95	44.59	46.46	47.11
31	40.64	---	37.15	40.26	---	47.94	---	43.29	---	44.64	46.43	---
LOW	47.33	40.56	37.15	40.26	45.01	47.94	49.45	49.54	43.13	44.64	46.46	47.11
HIGH	40.64	34.69	34.55	37.26	40.39	45.09	47.05	43.29	42.69	43.03	44.69	46.08

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182746066170800. Local number, 214.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'46", long 66°17'08".
Owner: Dorado Beach Hotel.
Name: Dorado Beach No. 7.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 18 in (0.46 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 39.0 ft (11.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.10 ft (0.34 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on November 7, 1985. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- November 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 18.23 ft (5.56 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 16, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 20.12 ft (6.13 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 19, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	19.00	19.45	19.62	19.70	19.83	19.77	19.38	19.78	19.97	19.71
2	---	---	19.07	19.47	19.64	19.76	19.84	19.69	19.42	19.82	20.00	19.65
3	---	---	19.14	19.47	19.61	19.77	19.83	19.67	19.43	19.82	20.02	19.69
4	---	---	19.18	19.46	19.60	19.80	19.85	19.70	19.49	19.83	20.01	19.68
5	---	---	19.14	19.47	19.62	19.85	19.84	19.64	19.54	19.81	19.97	19.62
6	---	---	19.15	19.47	19.61	19.82	19.84	19.68	19.58	19.79	19.89	19.62
7	---	19.10	19.12	19.45	19.64	19.79	19.85	19.64	19.62	19.81	19.83	19.64
8	---	19.10	19.12	19.36	19.61	19.77	19.84	19.55	19.65	19.80	19.85	19.70
9	---	19.10	19.08	19.35	19.64	19.79	19.78	19.53	19.62	19.79	19.85	19.79
10	---	19.07	19.08	19.28	19.65	19.79	19.76	19.54	19.62	19.80	19.88	19.86
11	---	19.01	19.04	19.26	19.66	19.80	19.76	19.46	19.62	19.78	19.92	19.87
12	---	18.99	19.06	19.29	19.68	19.79	19.78	19.45	19.64	19.74	19.94	19.87
13	---	18.80	19.13	19.34	19.71	19.84	19.77	19.40	19.60	19.78	19.97	19.91
14	---	18.76	19.17	19.37	19.72	19.84	19.78	18.74	19.62	19.79	19.96	19.94
15	---	18.54	19.22	19.44	19.75	19.85	19.79	19.02	19.63	19.81	19.96	19.92
16	---	18.29	19.29	19.46	19.70	19.88	19.82	19.05	19.66	19.84	19.99	19.85
17	---	18.46	19.30	19.45	19.72	19.87	19.83	19.08	19.68	19.84	19.98	19.75
18	---	18.61	19.32	19.45	19.73	19.91	19.87	19.12	19.69	19.84	19.96	19.73
19	---	18.71	19.32	19.44	19.69	19.95	19.85	19.11	19.72	19.85	19.92	19.76
20	---	18.75	19.39	19.40	19.63	19.99	19.87	19.16	19.76	19.83	19.89	19.75
21	---	18.78	19.36	19.44	19.59	19.94	19.84	19.20	19.75	19.71	19.88	19.77
22	---	18.81	19.31	19.45	19.58	19.89	19.83	19.22	19.69	19.72	19.77	19.82
23	---	18.80	19.31	19.43	19.60	19.84	19.85	19.23	19.68	19.69	19.73	19.85
24	---	18.79	19.31	19.40	19.59	19.83	19.86	19.26	19.70	19.66	19.75	19.89
25	---	18.82	19.29	19.37	19.59	19.79	19.84	19.27	19.70	19.67	19.72	19.90
26	---	18.84	19.34	19.39	19.55	19.84	19.85	19.27	19.71	19.73	19.79	19.94
27	---	18.90	19.37	19.40	19.57	19.84	19.85	19.31	19.71	19.80	19.86	19.98
28	---	18.93	19.37	19.47	19.62	19.79	19.85	19.31	19.73	19.82	19.92	19.99
29	---	18.97	19.41	19.52	---	19.83	19.83	19.33	19.77	19.86	19.91	19.95
30	---	18.97	19.40	19.52	---	19.85	19.79	19.32	19.79	19.89	19.79	19.90
31	---	---	19.42	19.58	---	19.86	---	19.36	---	19.94	19.73	---
LOW	---	---	19.42	19.58	19.75	19.99	19.87	19.77	19.79	19.94	20.02	19.99
HIGH	---	---	19.00	19.26	19.55	19.70	19.76	18.74	19.38	19.66	19.72	19.62

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182548066171200. Local number, 215.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'48", long 66°17'12".
 Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.
 Name: Maguayo No. 5.
 AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone-Cibao Formation.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m) 0-95 ft (0-29.0 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-60 ft (0-18.3 m), diameter 16 in (0.41 m) 95-145 ft (29.0-44.2 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-145 ft (0-44.2 m), perforated 65-145 ft (19.8-44.2 m). Depth 145 ft (44.2 m).
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 66 ft (20.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.60 ft (0.49 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on August 13, 1985.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 40.89 ft (12.46 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 20, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 44.25 ft (13.49 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 1, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	44.25	41.91	41.58	42.51	42.97	43.49	44.07	44.03	42.14	43.27	43.62	43.47
2	44.22	41.95	41.64	42.53	42.99	43.50	44.00	43.97	42.20	43.29	43.63	43.44
3	44.22	42.00	41.69	42.55	43.01	43.53	44.02	43.93	42.24	43.32	43.65	43.42
4	44.22	42.02	41.73	42.56	43.03	43.56	44.02	43.92	42.29	43.35	43.67	43.42
5	44.20	42.03	41.77	42.58	43.04	43.58	44.02	43.88	42.36	43.37	43.68	43.44
6	44.13	42.05	41.79	42.60	43.05	43.61	43.98	43.83	42.43	43.39	43.69	43.46
7	43.62	42.06	41.83	42.62	43.07	43.63	43.98	43.79	42.47	43.40	43.71	43.46
8	43.62	42.09	41.88	42.64	43.09	43.66	43.99	43.72	42.53	43.42	43.72	43.48
9	42.07	42.14	41.91	42.66	43.10	43.69	43.97	43.67	42.57	43.44	43.74	43.49
10	41.58	42.17	41.94	42.63	43.12	43.71	43.95	43.60	42.62	43.47	43.74	43.51
11	41.29	42.20	41.95	42.62	43.14	43.72	43.95	43.51	42.67	43.48	43.75	43.54
12	41.12	42.22	41.99	42.62	43.17	43.74	43.95	43.40	42.72	43.44	43.75	43.56
13	41.07	42.13	42.01	42.63	43.19	43.76	43.96	43.27	42.75	43.43	43.73	43.59
14	41.09	42.04	42.03	42.64	43.21	43.77	43.98	42.70	42.77	43.44	43.71	43.63
15	41.15	41.86	42.06	42.67	43.23	43.78	44.00	42.29	42.80	43.44	43.71	43.66
16	41.26	41.49	42.09	42.68	43.25	43.79	44.01	41.89	42.83	43.43	43.71	43.68
17	41.36	41.24	42.11	42.69	43.28	43.81	44.02	41.55	42.85	43.42	43.72	43.70
18	41.46	41.02	42.13	42.70	43.30	43.84	44.03	41.38	42.88	43.43	43.74	43.72
19	41.53	40.92	42.14	42.71	43.32	43.86	44.04	41.30	42.90	43.44	43.75	43.75
20	41.61	40.90	42.18	42.72	43.33	43.88	44.06	41.29	42.94	43.45	43.77	43.77
21	41.68	40.92	42.22	42.74	43.35	43.90	44.06	41.33	42.98	43.47	43.78	43.79
22	41.74	40.96	42.24	42.77	43.36	43.92	44.06	41.39	43.01	43.48	43.79	43.82
23	41.83	41.02	42.27	42.79	43.40	43.94	44.07	41.49	43.04	43.49	43.80	43.83
24	41.87	41.07	42.29	42.80	43.41	43.97	44.07	41.59	43.08	43.51	43.81	43.86
25	41.90	41.22	42.31	42.81	43.43	43.98	44.08	41.66	43.11	43.51	43.80	43.89
26	41.88	41.29	42.33	42.84	43.44	43.99	44.08	41.73	43.15	43.53	43.79	43.90
27	41.86	41.35	42.37	42.85	43.46	44.00	44.09	41.82	43.17	43.54	43.78	43.91
28	41.85	41.42	42.41	42.87	43.48	44.01	44.10	41.88	43.19	43.56	43.78	43.93
29	41.86	41.48	42.43	42.90	---	44.02	44.11	41.95	43.22	43.57	43.73	43.94
30	41.87	41.53	42.46	42.91	---	44.03	44.08	42.02	43.25	43.59	43.61	43.96
31	41.88	---	42.49	42.94	---	44.05	---	42.07	---	43.60	43.52	---
LOW	44.25	42.22	42.49	42.94	43.48	44.05	44.11	44.03	43.25	43.60	43.81	43.96
HIGH	41.07	40.90	41.58	42.51	42.97	43.49	43.95	41.29	42.14	43.27	43.52	43.42

WTR YR 1986 MEAN 43.0 LOW 44.25 HIGH 40.90

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182530066135400. Local number, 216.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'30", long 66°13'54".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Pozo Navy-Campanillas.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m) 0-106 ft (0-32.3 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-106 ft (0-32.3 m), perforated 20-106 ft (6.10-32.3 m), diameter 10 in (0.25 m) 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m), perforated 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m). Depth 140 ft (42.7 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 13.0 ft (3.96 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on August 13, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 10.17 ft (3.10 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 21, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 14.72 ft (4.49 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 28, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14.35	11.70	11.34	12.42	13.22	13.97	14.54	14.51	11.68	12.93	13.12	13.29
2	13.46	11.79	11.38	12.46	13.24	14.00	14.54	14.11	11.70	12.96	13.15	13.28
3	14.02	11.88	11.43	12.47	13.23	14.02	14.54	13.96	11.72	12.98	13.20	13.32
4	14.13	11.92	11.46	12.47	13.25	14.06	14.51	13.99	11.76	13.02	13.22	13.37
5	14.02	11.54	10.92	12.50	13.26	14.11	14.47	13.95	11.81	13.03	13.25	13.40
6	13.90	11.40	11.43	12.53	13.25	14.13	14.42	13.88	11.86	13.01	13.26	13.42
7	11.28	11.40	11.48	12.55	13.33	14.16	14.42	13.71	11.93	13.03	13.28	13.45
8	11.23	11.41	11.53	12.60	13.37	14.20	14.44	13.53	11.92	13.06	13.30	13.48
9	11.37	11.42	11.55	12.54	13.40	14.24	14.38	13.46	12.07	13.08	13.33	13.54
10	11.48	11.91	11.58	12.53	13.43	14.24	14.34	13.38	12.23	13.10	13.35	13.62
11	11.56	11.96	11.62	12.52	13.46	14.25	14.35	13.21	12.27	13.09	13.36	13.65
12	11.62	11.98	11.67	12.54	13.50	14.27	14.36	13.15	12.34	12.86	13.38	13.65
13	11.65	11.86	11.73	12.57	13.53	14.30	14.38	12.81	12.37	12.85	13.31	13.70
14	11.67	11.77	11.79	12.60	13.57	14.32	14.40	11.97	12.37	12.86	13.25	13.73
15	11.73	11.42	11.84	12.65	13.61	14.36	14.45	11.89	12.40	12.80	13.13	13.73
16	11.80	10.96	11.72	12.67	13.64	14.39	14.48	12.00	12.29	12.76	13.09	13.77
17	11.85	10.82	11.66	12.68	13.66	14.36	14.51	12.05	12.39	12.73	13.25	13.77
18	11.63	10.85	11.84	12.65	13.69	14.40	14.54	12.03	12.46	12.74	13.42	13.85
19	11.78	10.87	11.92	12.72	13.70	14.44	14.57	12.03	12.53	12.76	13.42	13.85
20	11.78	10.89	11.97	12.74	13.72	14.43	14.58	11.93	12.58	12.76	13.44	13.91
21	11.77	10.74	11.97	12.80	13.74	14.48	14.53	11.87	12.64	12.78	13.49	13.90
22	11.83	10.85	11.81	12.85	13.78	14.50	14.53	11.87	12.66	12.84	13.50	13.89
23	11.86	10.92	11.87	12.89	13.81	14.57	14.55	11.92	12.70	12.87	13.49	13.89
24	11.76	10.98	12.05	12.92	13.83	14.55	14.57	11.96	12.75	12.88	13.51	14.00
25	11.75	11.00	12.12	12.93	13.85	14.51	14.65	12.01	12.79	12.92	13.52	13.98
26	11.78	11.09	12.20	12.97	13.87	14.51	14.65	12.04	12.83	12.96	13.47	13.94
27	11.66	11.15	12.27	12.99	13.91	14.52	14.67	12.05	12.88	12.99	13.61	14.02
28	11.67	11.23	12.30	13.04	13.94	14.50	14.67	11.85	12.87	13.04	13.58	14.02
29	11.73	11.27	12.34	13.10	---	14.51	14.69	11.83	12.89	13.08	13.25	13.97
30	11.78	11.30	12.38	13.14	---	14.53	14.61	11.71	12.91	13.11	13.30	14.00
31	11.59	---	12.42	13.17	---	14.54	---	11.70	---	13.12	13.28	---
LOW	14.35	11.98	12.42	13.17	13.94	14.57	14.69	14.51	12.91	13.12	13.61	14.02
HIGH	11.23	10.74	10.92	12.42	13.22	13.97	14.34	11.70	11.68	12.73	13.09	13.28

WTR YR 1986 MEAN 12.9 LOW 14.69 HIGH 10.74

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182655066142400. Local number, 217.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'55", long 66°14'24".

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey.

Name: Monserrate TW-2.

AQUIFER.--Alluvial Deposits.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-80 ft (0-24.4 m), perforated 10-80 ft (3.05-24.4 m). Depth 80 ft (24.4 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 3.30 ft (1.00 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.50 ft (1.07 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Automatic recorder installed on August 20, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 0.02 ft (0.006 m) below land-surface datum, May 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 1.92 ft (0.58 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 12, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	.72	1.11	1.26	1.51	1.75	1.62	.77	1.26	1.42	1.24
2	---	---	.77	1.09	1.28	1.54	1.75	1.32	.77	1.30	1.46	1.23
3	---	---	.82	1.09	1.29	1.57	1.74	1.25	.78	1.29	1.49	1.29
4	---	---	.83	1.04	1.25	1.61	1.73	1.29	.83	1.31	1.49	1.32
5	---	---	.76	1.04	1.27	1.65	1.70	1.32	.84	1.32	1.47	1.33
6	---	---	.72	1.06	1.29	1.68	1.67	1.36	.90	1.31	1.44	1.33
7	---	---	.71	.96	1.33	1.68	1.68	1.30	.96	1.30	1.44	1.34
8	---	---	.73	1.01	1.33	1.66	1.68	1.13	1.01	1.32	1.44	1.39
9	---	---	.73	.95	1.36	1.69	1.66	1.09	1.09	1.32	1.45	1.45
10	---	---	.74	.90	1.37	1.68	1.57	1.07	1.07	1.35	1.46	1.52
11	---	---	.75	.87	1.36	1.68	1.59	.95	.90	1.33	1.49	1.52
12	---	---	.77	.92	1.37	1.67	1.60	.92	.96	1.19	1.49	1.51
13	---	---	.85	.95	1.38	1.70	1.61	---	.95	1.18	1.45	1.52
14	---	---	.91	.96	1.40	1.70	1.62	---	1.01	1.22	1.41	1.53
15	---	---	.93	1.00	1.42	1.68	1.66	---	1.01	1.20	1.37	1.55
16	---	---	.96	1.01	1.42	1.73	1.69	---	1.03	1.21	1.42	1.54
17	---	---	.89	1.01	1.42	1.73	1.72	.15	1.07	1.21	1.44	1.51
18	---	---	.85	1.01	1.45	1.75	1.75	.30	1.04	1.23	1.46	1.53
19	---	---	.85	1.04	1.45	1.78	1.74	.40	1.09	1.26	1.47	1.55
20	---	---	.89	1.06	1.44	1.82	1.74	.47	1.11	1.27	1.50	1.56
21	---	---	.91	1.13	1.43	1.84	1.70	.46	1.13	1.23	1.54	1.58
22	---	---	.89	1.18	1.45	1.83	1.67	.52	1.17	1.25	1.54	1.58
23	---	---	.88	1.17	1.47	1.78	1.69	.56	1.18	1.26	1.47	1.59
24	---	---	.93	1.17	1.47	1.81	1.70	.58	1.16	1.23	1.49	1.70
25	---	---	.95	1.14	1.45	1.74	1.74	.68	1.21	1.25	1.44	1.68
26	---	.53	1.03	1.16	1.43	1.72	1.77	.73	1.19	1.30	1.48	1.70
27	---	.59	1.05	1.16	1.43	1.73	1.78	.77	1.22	1.34	1.50	1.69
28	---	.65	1.05	1.21	1.50	1.68	1.79	.80	1.23	1.36	1.49	1.70
29	---	.69	1.08	1.23	---	1.69	1.80	.81	1.26	1.40	1.40	1.67
30	---	.69	1.08	1.23	---	1.71	1.71	.84	1.28	1.41	1.28	1.67
31	---	---	1.10	1.23	---	1.76	---	.81	---	1.41	1.25	---
LOW	---	---	1.10	1.23	1.50	1.84	1.80	---	1.28	1.41	1.54	1.70
HIGH	---	---	.71	.87	1.25	1.51	1.57	---	.77	1.18	1.25	1.23

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182441066082600. Local number, 219.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 66°08'26".

Owner: Department of Defense.

Name: Ft. Buchanan No. 1, Buchanan Park well.

AQUIFER.--Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 10 in (0.25 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 0-270 ft (0-82.3 m), perforated 46-685 ft (14.0-20.7 m), 88-120 ft (26.8-36.6 m), 160-191 ft (48.8-58.2 m), 240-270 ft (73.2-82.3 m). Depth 270 ft (82.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 66.0 ft (20.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.75 ft (0.23 m) above land-surface datum. Prior June 30, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.59 ft (1.09 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on December 20, 1985. Estimated noon value: June 30.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 38.10 ft (11.61 m) below land-surface datum, June 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 42.95 ft (13.09 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 4, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	40.52	41.13	41.86	42.88	41.97	39.04	38.78	39.07	39.92
2	---	---	---	40.54	41.09	41.87	42.89	41.75	39.02	38.83	39.10	39.97
3	---	---	---	40.57	41.06	41.91	42.94	41.49	39.00	38.87	39.13	40.10
4	---	---	---	40.58	41.07	41.98	42.95	41.31	39.01	38.90	39.15	40.21
5	---	---	---	40.61	41.09	42.00	42.83	41.21	39.03	38.93	39.21	40.28
6	---	---	---	40.65	41.09	42.03	42.82	41.16	39.06	38.93	39.25	40.37
7	---	---	---	40.65	41.11	42.06	42.76	41.01	39.09	38.87	39.28	40.45
8	---	---	---	40.72	41.11	42.12	42.74	40.82	38.82	38.86	39.32	40.52
9	---	---	---	40.71	41.12	42.16	42.60	40.71	38.57	38.87	39.40	40.60
10	---	---	---	40.67	41.13	42.16	42.48	40.59	38.44	38.88	39.45	40.68
11	---	---	---	40.59	41.17	42.15	42.39	40.45	38.30	38.87	39.50	40.70
12	---	---	---	40.57	41.21	42.18	42.35	40.35	38.23	38.80	39.56	40.73
13	---	---	---	40.57	41.24	42.21	42.28	40.16	38.17	38.75	39.55	40.80
14	---	---	---	40.59	41.29	42.25	42.25	39.87	38.14	38.71	39.50	40.89
15	---	---	---	40.66	41.33	42.27	42.28	39.70	38.12	38.66	39.45	40.96
16	---	---	---	40.71	41.36	42.27	42.33	39.52	38.12	38.63	39.42	41.07
17	---	---	---	40.75	41.39	42.30	42.36	39.46	38.14	38.63	39.42	41.13
18	---	---	---	40.76	41.40	42.34	42.38	39.42	38.16	38.67	39.45	41.23
19	---	---	---	40.78	41.40	42.38	42.38	39.41	38.20	38.70	39.49	41.31
20	---	---	---	40.81	41.45	42.40	42.40	39.42	38.25	38.71	39.54	41.41
21	---	---	40.21	40.87	41.49	42.42	42.40	39.42	38.27	38.78	39.59	41.47
22	---	---	40.21	40.90	41.54	42.53	42.37	39.41	38.27	38.88	39.61	41.50
23	---	---	40.22	40.92	41.59	42.65	42.31	39.45	38.32	38.92	39.61	41.51
24	---	---	40.28	40.93	41.64	42.76	42.26	39.48	38.37	38.90	39.65	41.56
25	---	---	40.35	40.97	41.64	42.83	42.25	39.47	38.41	38.94	39.74	41.67
26	---	---	40.39	41.00	41.69	42.86	42.26	39.47	38.45	39.00	39.83	41.78
27	---	---	40.41	41.05	41.78	42.86	42.26	39.48	38.51	39.01	39.93	41.79
28	---	---	40.40	41.11	41.84	42.85	42.28	39.50	38.55	39.03	40.01	41.79
29	---	---	40.41	41.13	---	42.87	42.25	39.41	38.59	39.09	40.06	41.80
30	---	---	40.44	41.16	---	42.86	42.15	39.23	38.68	39.11	40.02	41.81
31	---	---	40.51	41.14	---	42.88	---	39.12	---	39.08	39.94	---
LOW	---	---	---	41.16	41.84	42.88	42.95	41.97	39.09	39.11	40.06	41.81
HIGH	---	---	---	40.52	41.06	41.86	42.15	39.12	38.12	38.63	39.07	39.92

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO AND RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182413066044000. Local number, 220.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'13", long 66°04'40".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Parque San Luis Rey-Americo Miranda

AQUIFER.--Surficial Deposits-Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused artesian well, diameter 10 in (0.25 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m) 0-166 ft (0-50.6 m), perforated 39-166 ft (11.9-50.6 m). Depth 166 ft (50.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 16.4 ft (5.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned observation well. Automatic recorder installed on Feb. 6, 1986.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1986 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +2.99 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum, Feb. 6, May 8-9, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 0.77 ft (0.23 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 20-21, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	+2.59	+2.21	+2.49	+ .49	+ .01	.08	.30
2	---	---	---	---	---	+2.57	+2.19	+2.72	+ .45	.00	.10	.31
3	---	---	---	---	---	+2.57	+2.19	+2.84	+ .42	.01	.12	.36
4	---	---	---	---	---	+2.56	+2.19	+2.92	+ .39	.03	.14	.38
5	---	---	---	---	---	+2.55	+2.44	+2.93	+ .33	.05	.18	.40
6	---	---	---	---	+2.97	+2.53	+2.48	+2.92	+ .19	+ .01	.21	.40
7	---	---	---	---	+2.97	+2.51	+2.54	+2.92	+ .15	.04	.24	.45
8	---	---	---	---	+2.96	+2.49	+2.56	+2.96	+ .38	.05	.26	.47
9	---	---	---	---	+2.92	+2.47	+2.62	+2.97	+ .55	.07	.31	.49
10	---	---	---	---	+2.90	+2.47	+2.75	---	+ .60	.12	.35	.52
11	---	---	---	---	+2.87	+2.49	+2.82	---	+ .68	.12	.36	.53
12	---	---	---	---	+2.84	+2.49	+2.83	---	+ .69	.09	.39	.53
13	---	---	---	---	+2.83	+2.48	+2.83	---	+ .67	.10	.34	.59
14	---	---	---	---	+2.81	+2.49	+2.82	---	+ .64	.11	.28	.63
15	---	---	---	---	+2.80	+2.50	+2.79	---	+ .61	.04	.20	.65
16	---	---	---	---	+2.77	+2.50	+2.76	---	+ .57	.02	.19	.67
17	---	---	---	---	+2.78	+2.50	+2.73	+ .98	+ .52	+ .02	.20	.68
18	---	---	---	---	+2.77	+2.49	+2.71	+ .92	+ .47	+ .03	.23	.70
19	---	---	---	---	+2.77	+2.48	+2.69	+ .88	+ .42	+ .02	.27	.72
20	---	---	---	---	+2.76	+2.43	+2.66	+ .80	+ .37	.00	.32	.75
21	---	---	---	---	+2.76	+2.40	+2.16	+ .73	+ .34	.03	.36	.76
22	---	---	---	---	+2.73	+2.36	+2.30	+ .69	+ .32	.08	.38	.74
23	---	---	---	---	+2.69	+2.33	+2.37	+ .64	+ .29	.12	.40	.63
24	---	---	---	---	+2.68	+2.31	+2.39	+ .59	+ .24	.07	.42	.61
25	---	---	---	---	+2.69	+2.32	+2.39	+ .55	+ .20	.09	.47	.59
26	---	---	---	---	+2.67	+2.29	+2.36	+ .50	+ .15	.12	.51	.60
27	---	---	---	---	+2.64	+2.28	+2.33	+ .48	+ .12	.14	.56	.59
28	---	---	---	---	+2.63	+2.25	+2.34	+ .43	+ .09	.23	.51	.60
29	---	---	---	---	---	+2.25	+2.34	+ .49	+ .05	.25	.41	.57
30	---	---	---	---	---	+2.22	+2.37	+ .50	+ .03	.24	.34	.57
31	---	---	---	---	---	+2.22	---	+ .49	---	.10	.31	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	+2.22	+2.16	---	+ .03	.25	.56	.76
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	+2.59	+2.83	---	+ .69	+ .03	.08	.30

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182436066031200. Local number, 221.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'36", long 66°03'12".

Owner: P.R. Highway Authority

Name: Hyde Park TW-10.

AQUIFER.--Surficial Deposits-Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-107 ft (0-32.36 m), perforated 19-107 ft (5.79-32.6 m), Depth 107 ft (32.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 82.0 ft (25.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.70 ft (0.21 m) above land-surface datum. Prior July 28, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.14 ft (0.96 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Automatic recorder installed on Dec. 17, 1985.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 1.92 ft (0.58 m) below land-surface datum, May 14, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 15.59 ft (4.75 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 5, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	7.53	9.21	11.93	15.26	7.74	6.29	8.40	7.61	8.01
2	---	---	---	7.60	9.31	12.05	15.37	8.05	6.49	8.45	7.77	8.17
3	---	---	---	7.65	9.41	12.17	15.47	5.43	6.69	8.42	7.94	8.33
4	---	---	---	7.56	9.24	12.29	15.53	5.96	6.85	8.53	8.07	8.46
5	---	---	---	7.66	9.11	12.42	14.80	6.50	7.06	8.59	8.14	8.52
6	---	---	---	7.72	9.31	12.55	13.04	5.75	7.19	8.64	8.24	8.48
7	---	---	---	7.76	9.50	12.69	12.89	5.22	7.23	8.09	8.34	8.54
8	---	---	---	7.83	9.63	12.83	12.89	4.36	7.13	8.22	8.42	8.71
9	---	---	---	7.49	9.74	12.95	12.35	4.79	6.80	8.34	8.54	8.82
10	---	---	---	7.16	9.86	13.07	11.26	5.22	6.93	8.49	8.68	8.96
11	---	---	---	7.36	9.97	13.16	11.42	3.58	6.00	8.55	8.78	9.10
12	---	---	---	7.50	10.03	13.28	11.58	4.10	6.25	8.43	8.75	9.29
13	---	---	---	7.71	10.10	13.41	11.71	2.67	6.42	8.51	8.26	9.46
14	---	---	---	7.83	10.24	13.50	11.85	2.32	6.60	8.51	7.98	9.61
15	---	---	---	7.95	10.36	13.50	12.03	3.25	6.76	8.52	7.65	9.72
16	---	---	---	8.02	10.47	13.59	12.17	4.07	6.94	8.50	7.88	9.85
17	---	---	6.73	8.08	10.57	13.70	12.31	4.59	7.11	8.38	8.09	10.00
18	---	---	6.76	7.94	10.66	13.82	12.44	5.05	7.23	8.47	8.25	10.17
19	---	---	6.80	8.07	10.77	13.94	12.57	5.25	7.34	8.62	8.38	10.11
20	---	---	6.78	8.18	10.88	14.04	12.72	5.67	7.41	8.75	8.53	10.23
21	---	---	6.85	8.28	11.00	14.16	11.33	5.89	7.50	8.85	8.67	10.35
22	---	---	6.84	8.39	11.11	14.28	9.68	6.06	7.57	8.96	8.79	10.27
23	---	---	6.91	8.46	11.24	14.39	9.82	6.29	7.68	9.02	8.93	9.88
24	---	---	7.00	8.52	11.36	14.51	10.02	6.45	7.76	9.10	9.03	10.03
25	---	---	7.07	8.57	11.46	14.63	10.25	6.58	7.84	8.62	9.14	10.17
26	---	---	7.13	8.67	11.57	14.70	10.45	6.71	8.00	8.76	9.26	10.32
27	---	---	7.21	8.77	11.70	14.80	10.59	5.42	8.08	8.93	9.39	10.39
28	---	---	7.27	8.89	11.82	14.90	10.64	5.55	8.11	9.22	9.37	10.52
29	---	---	7.26	8.98	---	14.94	10.64	5.85	8.21	9.33	7.90	10.10
30	---	---	7.22	9.08	---	15.04	10.35	6.08	8.33	8.11	8.21	10.19
31	---	---	7.44	9.11	---	15.16	---	6.22	---	7.35	8.34	---
LOW	---	---	---	9.11	11.82	15.16	15.53	8.05	8.33	9.33	9.39	10.52
HIGH	---	---	---	7.16	9.11	11.93	9.68	2.32	6.00	7.35	7.61	8.01

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

182515065594100. Local number, 222.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'15", long 65°59'41".

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey.

Name: Campo Rico TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Surficial Deposits.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10.0 ft (3.05 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum, Prior July 28, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.10 ft (0.94 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Automatic recorder installed on February 5, 1986.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1986 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 4.42 ft (1.35 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 31, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 7.42 ft (2.26 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 9, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	6.19	4.98	4.82	4.92	6.10	6.11	4.73
2	---	---	---	---	---	6.21	4.95	4.82	6.01	6.19	6.09	4.65
3	---	---	---	---	---	6.21	4.92	5.70	4.98	6.18	6.07	4.72
4	---	---	---	---	---	6.18	4.92	5.77	6.10	6.12	6.09	4.70
5	---	---	---	---	---	6.22	5.80	5.78	6.14	6.01	4.92	4.63
6	---	---	---	---	6.30	6.11	4.91	5.79	6.14	4.99	4.84	4.63
7	---	---	---	---	6.29	4.97	4.95	5.80	6.14	6.08	5.80	4.69
8	---	---	---	---	6.16	4.91	4.93	5.78	6.13	6.00	4.81	4.85
9	---	---	---	---	6.14	4.92	4.88	5.78	6.14	6.00	4.82	6.04
10	---	---	---	---	6.14	4.96	5.92	5.77	6.09	6.05	4.85	6.25
11	---	---	---	---	6.17	6.07	4.98	5.77	6.07	4.98	6.04	6.25
12	---	---	---	---	6.29	6.01	6.00	5.82	6.09	4.97	6.15	6.18
13	---	---	---	---	6.33	6.17	4.96	5.74	6.00	6.06	6.25	6.11
14	---	---	---	---	6.31	6.16	4.98	5.70	6.09	6.14	6.21	6.07
15	---	---	---	---	6.33	6.16	4.97	5.82	6.08	6.16	6.10	4.96
16	---	---	---	---	6.24	6.18	4.96	5.78	6.19	6.29	6.07	4.84
17	---	---	---	---	6.30	6.16	4.97	5.81	6.20	6.32	4.94	4.65
18	---	---	---	---	6.42	6.20	6.04	4.85	6.23	6.32	4.90	4.63
19	---	---	---	---	6.31	6.20	4.93	4.90	6.22	6.28	5.81	4.65
20	---	---	---	---	6.12	6.23	5.90	4.99	6.26	6.14	4.79	4.62
21	---	---	---	---	5.93	6.17	5.81	6.06	6.18	4.92	4.78	4.72
22	---	---	---	---	4.97	4.98	5.84	4.99	6.07	4.90	5.70	4.86
23	---	---	---	---	6.04	4.88	4.87	4.94	6.02	4.86	4.69	6.03
24	---	---	---	---	6.06	5.86	4.87	4.91	6.08	5.77	5.71	6.09
25	---	---	---	---	6.12	4.83	4.85	4.89	6.00	4.78	5.80	6.09
26	---	---	---	---	4.97	4.96	4.89	4.89	4.96	4.89	4.96	6.13
27	---	---	---	---	6.10	6.00	4.89	4.90	6.04	4.98	6.10	6.15
28	---	---	---	---	6.11	4.90	4.93	4.92	6.07	6.08	6.09	6.10
29	---	---	---	---	---	6.04	4.89	4.91	6.12	6.13	6.03	6.06
30	---	---	---	---	---	6.08	4.88	4.88	6.14	6.10	4.90	6.04
31	---	---	---	---	---	6.10	---	4.93	---	6.11	4.82	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	6.23	6.04	6.06	6.26	6.32	6.25	6.25
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	4.83	4.85	4.82	4.92	4.78	4.69	4.62

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO RIO SECO BASINS

175858066100200. Local number, 6.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'58", long 66°10'02".

Owner: Doctor Bruno.

Name: Juana 5.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m). Depth 173 ft (52.74 m) reported, 110 ft (33.54 m) measured.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 127 ft (38.7 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum. After Aug. 7, 1981, top of 16 in (0.41 m) casing, 1.55 ft (0.47 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1960 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 26.20 ft (7.99 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 10, 1979; lowest water level recorded, 65.95 ft (20.10 m) below land-surface datum, June 2, 1968.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	52.02	38.96	30.38	30.68	33.82	37.70	41.77	43.59	44.22	44.38	46.59	48.71
2	52.03	38.31	30.32	30.77	33.95	37.84	41.89	43.67	44.29	44.49	46.61	48.71
3	52.05	37.67	30.26	30.85	34.09	37.98	41.99	43.77	44.33	44.59	46.57	48.69
4	52.06	37.06	30.21	30.96	34.23	38.13	42.07	43.87	44.37	44.67	46.61	48.67
5	52.07	36.47	30.16	31.05	34.36	38.10	42.12	43.98	44.43	44.73	46.76	48.67
6	52.04	35.92	30.10	31.11	34.48	38.33	42.19	44.09	44.47	44.79	46.90	48.69
7	51.88	35.39	30.05	31.19	34.63	38.47	42.27	44.23	44.52	44.85	46.97	48.73
8	51.26	34.91	30.02	31.30	34.80	38.61	42.37	44.31	44.57	44.90	47.06	48.76
9	50.68	34.47	30.00	31.41	34.98	38.70	42.46	44.40	44.62	44.96	47.10	48.81
10	49.89	34.03	29.98	31.50	35.15	38.89	42.49	44.50	44.64	45.02	47.12	48.87
11	48.96	33.64	29.95	31.60	35.30	39.05	42.57	44.60	44.59	45.07	47.16	48.94
12	48.13	33.27	29.95	31.71	35.46	39.22	42.62	44.67	44.54	45.12	47.25	49.01
13	47.35	32.98	29.92	31.81	35.62	39.35	42.63	44.74	44.47	45.17	47.36	49.05
14	46.64	32.70	29.90	31.91	35.76	39.55	42.67	44.78	44.43	45.22	47.41	49.10
15	45.98	32.44	29.90	32.00	35.87	39.66	42.73	44.74	44.38	45.28	47.45	49.16
16	45.39	32.22	29.90	32.12	36.00	39.79	42.80	44.66	44.32	45.33	47.47	49.23
17	44.80	32.04	29.93	32.20	36.13	39.90	42.86	44.58	44.24	45.42	47.51	49.28
18	44.27	31.88	29.92	32.30	36.28	40.05	42.92	44.52	44.10	45.52	47.55	49.35
19	43.75	31.71	29.88	32.43	36.43	40.18	42.96	44.45	43.94	45.62	47.60	49.38
20	43.29	31.54	29.84	32.57	36.56	40.29	43.01	44.39	43.85	45.74	47.68	49.39
21	42.84	31.40	29.86	32.68	36.71	40.42	43.09	44.32	43.84	45.87	47.79	49.42
22	42.44	31.28	29.92	32.81	36.84	40.53	43.15	44.27	43.87	46.00	47.89	49.41
23	42.06	31.16	29.98	32.91	36.95	40.65	43.20	44.20	43.91	46.13	47.98	49.31
24	41.70	31.03	30.03	33.03	37.02	40.79	43.24	44.16	43.93	46.22	48.09	49.36
25	41.39	30.91	30.06	33.12	37.12	40.97	43.28	44.09	43.95	46.27	48.22	49.44
26	41.11	30.82	30.15	33.17	37.25	41.10	43.33	44.03	43.98	46.30	48.34	49.49
27	40.85	30.71	30.26	33.24	37.41	41.22	43.39	43.97	44.02	46.33	48.45	49.49
28	40.58	30.63	30.33	33.32	37.56	41.34	43.46	43.94	44.10	46.37	48.56	49.56
29	40.32	30.55	30.40	33.41	---	41.45	43.49	43.98	44.19	46.40	48.64	49.65
30	40.05	30.45	30.50	33.55	---	41.55	43.53	44.06	44.28	46.44	48.67	49.74
31	39.58	---	30.59	33.67	---	41.67	---	44.14	---	46.51	48.69	---
LOW	52.07	38.96	30.59	33.67	37.56	41.67	43.53	44.78	44.64	46.51	48.69	49.74
HIGH	39.58	30.45	29.84	30.68	33.82	37.70	41.77	43.59	43.84	44.38	46.57	48.67

WTR YR 1986 MEAN 40.9 LOW 52.07 HIGH 29.84

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

180415065513900. Local number, 96.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'15", long 65°51'39".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: USGS TW-2 or Yabucoa 7.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 0-10 ft (0-3.05 m), diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased about 0-183 ft (0-55.79 m), perforated 56-81 ft (17.07-24.70 m), 102-123 ft (31.10-37.50 m), 144-181 ft (43.90-55.18 m). Depth 181 ft (55.18 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 25 ft (7.62 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 4.00 ft (1.22 m) above land-surface.

REMARKS.--Observation recording well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 25, 1978 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 13.39 ft (4.08 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 18, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 28.29 ft (8.62 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 20, 1980.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	16.80	---	13.91	16.27	17.98	19.55	19.63	19.10	16.72	17.05	17.80	16.80
2	16.59	---	14.08	16.32	17.90	19.66	19.61	18.97	16.72	17.15	17.75	16.80
3	16.42	---	14.28	16.38	17.85	19.74	19.56	18.88	16.72	17.24	17.71	16.80
4	16.29	---	14.46	16.40	17.82	19.82	19.52	18.77	16.72	17.30	17.72	16.80
5	16.17	---	14.59	16.43	17.79	19.88	19.46	18.65	16.72	17.40	17.76	16.80
6	15.84	---	14.69	16.46	17.78	19.91	19.37	18.57	16.72	17.45	17.85	16.80
7	15.43	---	14.79	16.48	17.78	19.89	19.29	18.48	16.72	17.45	17.93	16.81
8	15.10	---	14.90	16.52	17.79	19.87	19.21	18.42	16.72	17.46	17.96	16.82
9	14.73	---	15.04	16.59	17.84	19.85	19.14	18.36	16.71	17.46	17.97	16.90
10	14.42	---	15.19	16.69	17.92	19.85	19.04	18.30	16.71	17.46	17.86	16.98
11	14.21	---	15.30	16.82	18.05	19.86	18.96	18.18	16.71	17.46	17.71	17.09
12	14.05	---	15.39	16.96	18.14	19.89	18.94	18.00	16.71	17.46	17.46	17.18
13	13.89	---	15.48	17.13	18.23	19.92	18.92	17.81	16.71	17.46	17.25	17.23
14	13.80	---	15.57	17.28	18.33	19.97	18.89	17.61	16.71	17.46	17.05	17.27
15	13.81	---	15.66	17.42	18.43	20.00	18.90	17.44	16.71	17.46	16.84	17.29
16	13.88	---	15.75	17.54	18.52	20.01	18.95	17.30	16.71	17.46	16.80	17.31
17	14.01	---	15.81	17.62	18.63	20.01	19.01	17.22	16.71	17.46	16.80	17.36
18	14.14	---	15.90	17.69	18.69	20.01	19.10	17.21	16.71	17.46	16.80	17.41
19	14.25	13.40	15.98	17.76	18.76	19.97	19.23	17.12	16.71	17.46	16.80	17.47
20	14.37	13.42	16.00	17.87	18.83	19.89	19.22	17.02	16.71	17.95	16.80	17.52
21	14.57	13.43	16.01	17.95	18.89	19.84	19.22	16.93	16.71	18.17	16.80	17.54
22	14.81	13.47	16.02	18.00	18.95	19.84	19.24	16.85	16.71	18.33	16.80	17.54
23	14.95	13.50	16.01	18.09	18.99	19.79	19.29	16.81	16.71	18.45	16.80	17.53
24	14.94	13.50	16.03	18.17	19.05	19.75	19.36	16.72	16.71	18.45	16.80	17.54
25	14.85	13.53	16.08	18.20	19.14	19.71	19.38	16.72	16.71	18.36	16.80	17.55
26	14.70	13.57	16.14	18.22	19.24	19.69	19.40	16.72	16.71	18.22	16.80	17.61
27	14.57	13.61	16.20	18.22	19.33	19.68	19.41	16.72	16.71	18.15	16.80	17.69
28	---	13.62	16.23	18.23	19.43	19.70	19.39	16.72	16.78	18.13	16.80	17.74
29	---	13.68	16.22	18.22	---	19.70	19.34	16.72	16.88	18.06	16.80	17.80
30	---	13.78	16.19	18.14	---	19.64	19.23	16.72	16.96	17.97	16.80	17.86
31	---	---	16.21	18.07	---	19.62	---	16.72	---	17.92	16.80	---
LOW	---	---	16.23	18.23	19.43	20.01	19.63	19.10	16.96	18.45	17.97	17.86
HIGH	---	---	13.91	16.27	17.78	19.55	18.89	16.72	16.71	17.05	16.80	16.80

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW
LAND-SURFACE DATUM

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175829066232200. Local number, 87.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'29", long 66°23'22".

Owner: Francisco Alomar.

Name: Alomar 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), iron cased. Depth 112 ft (34.14 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 35.32 ft (10.77 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Bottom of clean-out shelter door, 2.50 ft (0.76 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to August 1981, top of recorder shelter floor, 4.00 ft (1.22 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS. Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1967 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 8.45 ft (2.58 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 10, 1970; lowest water level recorded, 49.18 ft (14.99 m) below land-surface datum, July 27, 1974.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	24.01	18.60	18.46	19.59	21.28	21.45	22.03	23.74	22.71	23.35	25.07	23.37
2	23.87	18.58	18.47	19.70	20.72	21.43	22.24	23.15	22.70	23.73	25.11	23.41
3	23.75	18.57	18.48	19.89	20.99	21.43	23.05	23.13	22.71	24.01	24.97	23.44
4	23.84	18.57	18.50	19.86	20.30	21.43	22.52	23.54	23.23	24.10	24.87	23.48
5	23.81	18.56	18.50	19.77	21.12	21.74	23.10	23.98	22.79	23.85	25.04	23.53
6	23.76	18.56	18.51	19.78	21.25	21.81	22.71	24.15	22.77	23.44	24.70	24.12
7	20.58	18.53	18.56	19.83	21.33	21.73	23.19	24.14	22.79	23.49	24.52	24.51
8	19.16	18.52	18.56	19.97	21.29	22.15	23.02	24.26	22.77	23.99	24.85	24.14
9	19.06	18.52	18.60	20.09	20.77	22.21	23.28	24.41	22.77	24.12	24.97	24.56
10	19.10	18.49	18.73	20.18	20.77	22.24	23.10	23.95	22.79	24.28	24.86	24.78
11	19.14	18.45	18.69	20.22	20.69	22.45	23.13	23.15	22.78	24.37	24.77	24.83
12	19.23	18.45	18.73	20.18	20.66	22.37	22.86	22.99	22.33	24.43	24.87	25.03
13	19.34	18.44	18.86	20.16	20.70	22.14	22.59	22.81	23.18	24.40	24.94	25.18
14	19.22	18.44	18.90	20.19	20.21	22.08	23.34	22.43	23.69	24.23	25.13	24.27
15	19.25	18.43	18.84	20.25	20.69	22.28	23.13	22.35	23.60	24.32	25.21	24.22
16	19.32	18.41	18.88	20.31	20.66	21.89	23.46	22.31	23.51	24.48	25.02	24.92
17	19.30	18.44	18.92	20.44	20.79	21.94	23.44	22.32	22.62	24.25	24.99	24.73
18	19.31	18.42	19.05	20.45	21.11	22.52	23.30	22.35	23.11	24.53	24.94	24.90
19	19.43	18.40	19.14	20.35	21.13	22.40	23.52	22.35	23.68	24.60	25.16	24.68
20	19.66	18.41	19.18	20.35	21.07	22.89	22.67	22.38	23.32	24.60	25.30	24.88
21	19.61	18.44	19.21	20.41	21.10	23.03	23.41	22.39	22.97	24.36	25.39	24.89
22	19.27	18.49	19.15	20.53	21.19	23.06	23.52	22.42	23.37	24.56	25.48	24.90
23	19.28	18.50	19.18	20.48	21.21	22.19	23.41	22.45	23.77	24.68	25.17	24.95
24	19.26	18.45	19.35	20.57	20.90	23.17	23.47	22.48	23.88	24.76	24.67	25.13
25	19.09	18.45	19.38	20.53	21.20	23.42	23.52	22.49	23.76	24.87	24.97	25.21
26	19.05	18.48	19.40	20.54	21.28	23.50	23.45	22.50	23.81	24.90	25.09	25.27
27	19.07	18.48	19.45	20.65	21.39	22.95	22.70	22.54	23.94	24.36	24.85	25.17
28	19.06	18.47	19.46	21.08	21.50	22.19	23.52	22.60	23.98	23.75	25.12	24.69
29	19.00	18.47	19.40	21.03	---	22.01	23.60	22.79	23.28	24.80	24.04	25.11
30	18.83	18.48	19.56	21.00	---	21.97	23.78	22.82	23.21	24.92	23.50	25.35
31	18.66	---	19.64	20.88	---	21.97	---	22.73	---	24.98	23.37	---
LOW	24.01	18.60	19.64	21.08	21.50	23.50	23.78	24.41	23.98	24.98	25.48	25.35
HIGH	18.66	18.40	18.46	19.59	20.21	21.43	22.03	22.31	22.62	23.35	23.37	23.37
WTR YR 1986	MEAN 22.0		LOW 25.48		HIGH 18.40							

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW
LAND-SURFACE DATUM

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

180133066503300. Local number, 132.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'33", long 66°50'33".

Owner: Pittsburg Plate Glass 4.

Name: Yauco 2.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-20 ft (0-6.1 m), 12 in (0.30 m) perforated pipe 20-84 ft (6.1-25.61 m), 10 in (0.25 m) perforated pipe 84-190 ft (25.61-57.93 m). Depth 190 ft (57.93 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 75 ft (22.87 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.35 ft (0.72 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1972 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +0.12 ft (0.04 m) below land-surface datum, July 19, 1979; lowest water level recorded, 36.91 ft (11.25 m) below land-surface datum, June 27, 1974.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.42	2.45	5.34	6.57	7.26	8.05	9.94	10.04	5.69	7.40	8.98	10.62
2	7.46	2.45	5.34	6.64	7.26	8.08	9.90	9.80	5.75	7.43	9.00	10.40
3	7.51	2.45	5.37	6.68	7.30	8.14	10.02	9.83	5.83	7.61	9.08	10.54
4	7.53	2.45	5.37	6.68	7.31	8.20	10.01	9.91	5.84	7.67	9.11	10.56
5	7.54	2.45	5.37	6.69	7.28	8.25	9.31	9.94	5.94	7.76	9.29	10.56
6	---	2.45	5.37	6.69	7.28	8.28	9.15	10.04	6.04	7.71	9.31	10.63
7	---	2.45	5.37	6.83	7.30	8.32	9.25	10.04	6.14	7.85	9.44	10.68
8	---	2.45	5.37	6.83	7.32	8.39	9.27	9.74	6.22	7.93	9.14	10.78
9	4.22	2.45	6.21	6.85	7.33	8.43	9.23	9.57	6.28	8.02	9.11	10.78
10	4.25	2.45	6.23	6.86	7.34	8.51	9.21	9.50	6.34	8.10	9.13	10.84
11	4.32	2.45	6.24	6.84	7.39	8.56	9.25	8.24	6.41	8.20	9.16	10.90
12	4.32	2.45	6.27	6.85	7.40	8.63	9.31	7.88	6.14	8.25	9.25	11.04
13	4.32	2.45	6.28	6.90	7.40	8.69	9.35	6.26	6.24	8.23	9.32	11.10
14	4.32	2.45	6.28	6.96	7.40	8.73	9.40	4.44	6.32	8.36	9.44	11.13
15	4.33	5.69	6.30	7.00	7.49	8.78	9.47	5.44	6.43	8.41	9.44	11.24
16	4.33	5.70	6.31	6.99	7.50	8.85	9.56	5.82	6.47	8.30	9.52	11.31
17	4.33	5.67	6.33	7.01	7.54	8.93	9.65	5.95	6.54	8.42	9.57	11.35
18	4.33	5.31	6.34	7.02	7.60	8.98	9.71	6.07	6.60	8.44	9.70	11.42
19	4.33	5.33	6.30	7.04	7.63	9.10	9.80	6.11	6.64	8.52	9.70	11.49
20	4.38	5.33	6.34	7.10	7.66	9.16	9.84	6.16	6.69	8.51	9.88	11.55
21	4.38	5.33	6.34	7.10	7.70	9.30	10.03	6.20	6.70	8.69	10.08	11.51
22	4.38	5.33	6.35	7.15	7.70	9.33	10.09	6.24	6.80	8.73	10.19	11.16
23	4.38	5.33	6.37	7.18	7.80	9.36	10.15	6.31	6.84	8.78	10.27	11.24
24	3.35	5.33	6.30	7.24	7.83	9.45	10.21	6.40	6.94	8.86	10.33	11.31
25	3.35	5.33	6.40	7.23	7.84	9.45	10.30	6.50	7.02	8.92	10.45	11.34
26	3.35	5.33	6.40	7.21	7.90	9.57	10.44	6.58	7.08	8.91	10.49	11.45
27	3.35	5.33	6.44	7.24	7.95	9.64	10.45	6.63	7.10	8.84	10.56	11.17
28	3.35	5.33	6.44	7.28	7.99	9.67	10.57	6.68	7.20	8.87	10.68	9.87
29	3.35	5.34	6.50	7.32	---	9.69	10.70	6.76	7.22	8.87	10.76	9.77
30	3.35	5.34	6.54	7.24	---	9.70	10.84	5.68	7.30	8.92	10.68	9.88
31	2.45	---	6.54	7.28	---	9.85	---	5.66	---	8.96	10.60	---
LOW	---	5.70	6.54	7.32	7.99	9.85	10.84	10.04	7.30	8.96	10.76	11.55
HIGH	---	2.45	5.34	6.57	7.26	8.05	9.15	4.44	5.69	7.40	8.98	9.77

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

175950066354200. Local number, 141.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'50", long 66°35'42".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Restaurada 8A.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused public supply well, diameter 16-10 in (0.41-0.25 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 2-20 ft (0.6-6.1 m), perforated 20-130 ft (6.1-39.6 m), 10 in (0.25 m) 128-165 ft (39.0-50.3 m), perforated. Depth 165 ft (50.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 24 ft (7.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Bottom edge of hole on side of casing, 1.9 ft (0.58 m) above land-surface datum, 26.15 ft (7.97 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1981 to March 1, 1986, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 11.19 ft (3.41 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 09, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 28.59 ft (8.714 m) below land-surface datum, July 9, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14.56	12.12	13.25	---	17.07	16.35						
2	14.60	12.06	13.34	---	16.89	---						
3	14.68	11.95	13.57	---	16.79	---						
4	15.47	11.83	13.59	---	16.23	---						
5	15.36	11.82	13.62	---	16.00	---						
6	14.76	11.86	13.66	---	15.98	---						
7	12.78	11.87	13.71	---	16.06	---						
8	11.22	11.94	13.73	---	16.10	---						
9	11.24	11.96	13.77	13.77	16.12	---						
10	11.39	12.00	13.84	14.36	16.14	---						
11	11.47	12.05	13.87	14.51	16.08	---						
12	11.61	12.16	13.97	14.49	16.07	---						
13	11.68	12.24	14.03	14.46	16.08	---						
14	11.79	12.31	14.15	14.48	16.21	---						
15	11.89	12.38	14.80	14.58	16.08	---						
16	12.05	12.41	15.01	14.59	15.99	---						
17	12.19	12.42	15.08	14.55	15.97	---						
18	12.32	12.50	15.14	16.17	16.04	---						
19	12.40	12.60	15.12	16.60	16.08	---						
20	12.45	12.69	15.02	16.72	16.03	---						
21	12.56	12.79	14.89	16.80	15.94	---						
22	12.66	12.86	14.73	16.94	15.87	---						
23	12.71	12.95	14.54	17.08	15.77	---						
24	12.55	12.99	14.22	17.21	15.68	---						
25	12.48	13.06	---	17.24	15.74	---						
26	12.46	13.12	---	17.22	15.67	---						
27	12.41	13.20	---	17.28	15.96	---						
28	12.41	13.23	---	17.42	16.26	---						
29	12.37	13.24	---	17.54	---	---						
30	12.36	13.25	---	17.27	---	---						
31	12.22	---	---	17.23	---	---						
LOW	15.47	13.25	---	---	17.07	---						
HIGH	11.22	11.82	---	---	15.67	---						

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180132067033800. Local number, 143.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'32", long 67°03'38".

Owner: Pedro P. Vivoni.

Name: Vivoni, Hacienda Amistad.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of unknown age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused irrigation well, diameter 12 in (0.30 m). Depth 200 ft (60.98 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 52.5 ft (16.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole side of casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1981 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 37.36 ft (11.39 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 20, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 39.70 ft (12.10 m) below land-surface datum, June, 29, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	39.35	38.72	37.77	38.17	38.51	38.72	38.96	39.09	38.73	38.78	38.80	38.88
2	39.37	38.72	37.80	38.15	38.51	38.71	38.95	39.10	38.73	38.78	38.83	38.92
3	39.40	38.72	37.78	38.14	38.48	38.74	38.98	39.09	38.73	38.78	38.84	38.95
4	39.40	38.10	37.79	38.18	38.49	38.78	38.99	39.12	38.73	38.78	38.84	38.95
5	39.37	38.09	37.74	38.22	38.51	38.79	38.99	39.11	38.74	38.78	38.86	38.94
6	39.30	38.11	37.70	38.25	38.55	38.78	39.00	39.11	38.74	38.79	38.87	38.95
7	38.72	38.07	37.72	38.23	38.58	38.80	39.01	39.05	38.74	38.80	38.85	38.96
8	38.72	38.02	37.77	38.26	38.56	38.84	39.02	39.01	38.74	38.81	38.85	38.95
9	38.72	38.04	37.78	38.29	38.58	38.86	39.02	39.01	38.74	38.75	38.86	38.97
10	38.72	38.01	37.80	38.29	38.59	38.87	39.02	38.99	38.74	38.75	38.87	38.97
11	38.67	37.94	37.80	38.29	38.61	38.84	39.02	38.86	38.74	38.73	38.87	38.88
12	38.74	37.90	37.84	38.29	38.61	38.84	39.02	38.86	38.74	38.72	38.89	38.88
13	38.73	37.83	37.99	38.29	38.61	38.85	39.00	38.74	38.74	38.73	38.88	38.93
14	38.72	37.77	37.99	38.32	38.60	38.85	39.00	38.74	38.74	38.72	38.88	38.96
15	38.72	37.76	38.00	38.34	38.61	38.85	39.01	38.73	38.75	38.68	38.86	38.97
16	38.73	37.73	38.02	38.39	38.63	38.85	39.04	38.73	38.75	38.68	38.87	38.98
17	38.73	37.72	38.04	38.37	38.65	38.86	39.06	38.73	38.75	38.69	38.90	38.97
18	38.73	37.79	38.04	38.34	38.61	38.88	39.07	38.73	38.75	38.71	38.92	38.98
19	38.72	37.81	38.04	38.37	38.59	38.90	39.06	38.73	38.75	38.71	38.94	38.99
20	38.72	37.78	38.07	38.41	38.60	38.91	39.08	38.74	38.75	38.72	38.96	39.00
21	38.72	37.74	38.06	38.42	38.61	38.91	39.10	38.74	38.76	38.76	38.96	38.98
22	38.72	37.76	38.08	38.41	38.63	38.92	39.13	38.74	38.76	38.81	38.92	38.94
23	38.72	37.77	38.05	38.44	38.65	38.95	39.14	38.74	38.76	38.81	38.86	38.93
24	38.72	37.77	38.13	38.43	38.67	38.98	39.12	38.74	38.76	38.78	38.86	38.96
25	38.72	37.76	38.13	38.43	38.64	38.99	39.12	38.74	38.76	38.78	38.92	38.98
26	38.72	37.77	38.13	38.41	38.65	38.98	39.11	38.74	38.76	38.80	38.95	38.99
27	38.72	37.76	38.16	38.42	38.68	38.97	39.11	38.74	38.77	38.79	38.92	38.95
28	38.72	37.79	38.13	38.47	38.72	38.97	39.08	38.74	38.77	38.78	38.89	38.94
29	38.72	37.80	38.13	38.47	---	38.98	39.09	38.74	38.77	38.79	38.90	38.98
30	38.72	37.77	38.13	38.49	---	38.97	39.08	38.73	38.77	38.79	38.92	39.01
31	38.72	---	38.16	38.48	---	38.97	---	38.73	---	38.79	38.89	---
LOW	39.40	38.72	38.16	38.49	38.72	38.99	39.14	39.12	38.77	38.81	38.96	39.01
HIGH	38.67	37.72	37.70	38.14	38.48	38.71	38.95	38.73	38.73	38.68	38.80	38.88

WTR YR 1986 MEAN 38.6 LOW 39.40 HIGH 37.70

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

182018066593200. Local number, 83.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'18", long 66°59'32".

Owner: P.R. Energy and Power Authority.

Name: San Sebastian Well.

AQUIFER.--San Sebastian Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 300 ft (91.4 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 230 ft (70.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.75 ft (0.84 m) above land-surface datum.

Prior November 1985, top of casing, 2.40 ft (0.73 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Automatic recorder installed on November 14, 1985. Formerly published as 182032066591800

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1967 to January 16, 1985. November 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 21.95 ft (6.69 m) below land-surface datum, May 8, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 40.20 ft (12.25 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 29, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	27.86	29.28	29.72	29.56	28.95	26.46	26.50	28.06	28.27	28.53
2	---	---	27.93	29.30	29.71	29.56	29.00	26.08	26.65	28.12	28.33	28.57
3	---	---	28.01	29.33	29.68	29.59	29.02	26.03	26.79	28.19	28.37	28.30
4	---	---	28.08	29.37	29.60	29.36	28.90	25.49	26.91	28.26	28.40	28.23
5	---	---	28.14	29.40	29.61	29.33	28.79	25.40	27.06	28.31	28.46	28.24
6	---	---	28.27	29.43	29.62	29.32	28.76	25.05	27.20	28.37	28.49	28.30
7	---	---	28.35	29.45	29.62	29.32	28.76	24.43	27.30	28.39	28.52	28.36
8	---	---	28.40	29.48	29.62	29.35	28.69	24.36	27.36	28.42	28.51	28.42
9	---	---	28.46	29.53	29.63	29.37	28.41	24.68	27.37	28.46	28.50	28.49
10	---	---	28.52	29.44	29.64	29.37	28.40	24.89	27.46	28.49	28.39	28.54
11	---	---	28.56	29.44	29.66	29.37	28.43	24.81	27.22	28.53	28.38	28.56
12	---	---	28.62	29.45	29.66	29.36	28.47	25.03	27.28	28.58	28.42	28.61
13	---	---	28.66	29.46	29.66	29.38	28.50	24.76	27.34	28.62	28.46	28.69
14	---	---	28.70	29.50	29.69	29.39	28.55	24.46	27.42	28.65	28.49	28.74
15	---	28.25	28.74	29.51	29.70	29.40	28.61	24.57	27.53	28.66	28.51	28.77
16	---	28.01	28.77	29.55	29.72	29.38	28.68	24.87	27.62	28.59	28.44	28.81
17	---	27.89	28.81	29.55	29.73	29.37	28.72	25.20	27.69	28.61	28.45	28.84
18	---	27.81	28.84	29.55	29.71	29.24	28.77	25.54	27.77	28.64	28.47	28.88
19	---	26.77	28.90	29.58	29.69	29.22	28.79	25.83	27.80	28.67	28.50	28.92
20	---	26.82	28.92	29.60	29.64	29.23	28.84	26.04	27.75	28.69	28.56	28.96
21	---	26.91	28.93	29.62	29.50	29.24	28.83	26.24	27.77	28.61	28.62	28.98
22	---	27.02	28.97	29.65	29.51	29.26	28.72	26.19	27.50	28.65	28.64	29.00
23	---	27.13	29.00	29.66	29.52	29.30	28.67	26.34	27.44	28.68	28.66	29.01
24	---	27.22	29.06	29.68	29.53	29.31	28.24	26.47	27.46	28.71	28.71	29.06
25	---	27.33	29.09	29.69	29.50	29.34	27.98	26.60	27.52	28.73	28.73	29.10
26	---	27.43	29.12	29.70	29.51	29.33	27.99	26.74	27.62	28.66	28.77	29.05
27	---	27.53	29.16	29.71	29.53	29.34	27.52	26.60	27.75	28.30	28.77	29.06
28	---	27.61	29.18	29.76	29.56	29.33	27.41	26.45	27.82	28.29	28.68	29.08
29	---	27.72	29.18	29.76	---	29.17	26.96	26.49	27.91	28.33	28.68	28.93
30	---	27.77	29.23	29.77	---	28.95	26.74	26.35	27.98	28.36	28.62	28.95
31	---	---	29.26	29.71	---	28.95	---	26.41	---	28.28	28.51	---
LOW	---	---	29.26	29.77	29.73	29.59	29.02	26.74	27.98	28.73	28.77	29.10
HIGH	---	---	27.86	29.28	29.50	28.95	26.74	24.36	26.50	28.06	28.27	28.23

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW
LAND-SURFACE DATUM

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

182445067091700. Local number, 200.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 67°09'17".

Owner: Carmelo Sanchez

Name: Aguadilla Cement Well.

AQUIFER.--Surficial deposits.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Abandoned water-table industrial well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), perforated 11-20 ft (3.35-6.10 m). Depth 20 ft (6.10 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10 ft (3.05 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.25 ft (0.99 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Automatic recorder installed on November 1985. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well. Estimated noon values: Nov. 19-Dec 5.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.85 ft (0.87 m) below land-surface datum, May 14, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 8.46 ft (2.58 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 17, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION

Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 09	3.27	Nov. 14	4.75

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	6.41	6.66	---	8.21	7.88	5.57	---	5.79	5.52	6.21
2	---	---	6.55	6.66	---	8.23	7.96	5.08	---	5.83	5.70	6.34
3	---	---	6.70	6.66	---	8.26	8.02	5.31	---	6.16	5.78	6.44
4	---	---	6.84	6.66	---	8.26	8.08	3.89	---	5.86	5.91	6.28
5	---	---	7.02	6.66	7.72	8.26	8.00	4.16	---	5.94	5.98	6.35
6	---	---	7.00	6.66	7.78	8.27	8.07	4.25	---	5.97	5.99	6.36
7	---	---	7.07	6.67	7.86	8.29	8.15	3.56	---	5.78	6.08	6.41
8	---	---	7.14	6.75	7.87	8.30	8.20	3.75	---	5.56	6.39	6.47
9	---	---	7.17	6.78	7.91	8.22	8.23	4.02	---	5.95	6.15	6.59
10	---	---	7.20	6.88	7.95	8.23	8.25	4.14	---	6.18	5.66	6.63
11	---	---	7.21	6.90	7.97	8.27	8.29	4.21	---	6.04	5.90	6.64
12	---	---	7.26	---	8.00	8.15	8.32	4.52	---	5.97	5.34	6.67
13	---	---	7.29	---	8.05	8.19	8.34	3.72	---	6.01	5.72	6.70
14	---	---	7.37	---	8.04	8.23	8.38	3.02	---	6.12	5.62	6.72
15	---	4.70	7.40	---	8.07	8.27	8.41	3.28	---	5.97	5.88	6.77
16	---	4.22	7.41	---	8.09	8.27	8.43	3.33	---	6.36	5.86	6.81
17	---	3.91	7.42	---	8.09	8.10	7.35	3.50	---	6.17	5.91	6.83
18	---	4.13	7.43	---	8.11	8.10	6.80	3.57	---	5.98	6.03	6.87
19	---	4.66	7.42	---	8.11	8.18	6.85	4.21	---	6.03	6.46	6.91
20	---	4.80	7.47	---	8.13	8.22	6.91	4.05	---	6.09	6.64	6.94
21	---	4.95	7.49	---	8.15	8.26	7.00	3.93	---	6.02	6.32	6.96
22	---	5.09	7.48	---	8.15	8.28	7.06	4.10	---	6.21	6.17	7.00
23	---	5.24	7.48	---	8.15	8.30	7.10	3.85	---	6.18	6.19	7.05
24	---	5.38	7.50	---	8.17	8.34	7.13	4.02	---	6.32	6.24	7.07
25	---	5.53	7.55	---	8.18	8.36	6.97	4.22	---	6.23	6.30	7.09
26	---	5.68	7.57	---	8.19	8.37	7.03	---	---	6.31	6.37	6.72
27	---	5.82	7.50	---	8.20	8.38	6.70	---	---	6.31	6.53	6.81
28	---	5.97	7.40	---	8.21	8.39	6.24	---	5.55	6.29	6.01	6.89
29	---	6.11	7.40	---	---	8.09	5.92	---	5.62	6.77	6.08	6.94
30	---	6.26	7.43	---	---	7.92	5.45	---	5.75	5.55	6.08	6.99
31	---	---	7.56	---	---	7.88	---	---	---	5.37	6.11	---
LOW	---	---	7.57	---	---	8.39	8.43	---	---	6.77	6.64	7.09
HIGH	---	---	6.41	---	---	7.88	5.45	---	---	5.37	5.34	6.21

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW
LAND-SURFACE DATUM

Surface-

Water

Records

for

U.S. Virgin Islands

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50252000 BONNE RESOLUTION GUT AT BONNE RESOLUTION, ST. THOMAS, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'57", long 64°57'34", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, on right bank near Hull Bay Road, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean, and 2.5 mi (4.02 km) northwest of Fort Christian, Charlotte Amalie.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.49 mi² (1.27 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1962 to February 1967, March 1979 to April 1981, May 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 280 ft (85 m), from topographic map. December 1962 to February 1967 at site about 100 ft (30 m) downstream at different datum. March 1979 to April 1981 at site about 100 ft (30 m) upstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Nov. 26 to Dec. 6 and June 6-30. Records poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--8 years (1964-66, 1980, 1983-86), 0.29 ft³/s (0.008 m³/s), 8.04 in/yr (204 mm/yr), 210 acre-ft/yr (0.259 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 1,650 ft³/s (46.7 m³/s), Apr. 18, 1983, gage height, 7.00 ft (2.134 m), from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 1.0 ft³/s (0.03 m³/s) on basis of critical-depth analysis and slope-area measurement of peak flow; no flow at times in most years.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 50 ft³/s (1.42 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	0230	58	1.64	1.52	0.463	Nov. 17	1600	118	3.34	1.98	0.604
Oct. 29	2300	*559	15.8	*4.02	1.225	Apr. 29	2345	56	1.59	1.50	0.457
Oct. 30	1915	56	1.59	1.50	0.457	May 13	1830	191	5.41	2.42	0.738
Nov. 5	1000	556	15.7	4.01	1.222						

No flow many days.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	.06	.67	.10	.03	.00	.11	.05	1.1	.40	.08	.08	.17		
2	.06	.40	.09	.03	.00	.12	.06	.43	.40	.07	.10	.09		
3	.05	.28	.08	.03	.00	.11	.03	.50	.40	.09	.12	.07		
4	.06	.20	.07	.03	.00	.07	.01	.17	.40	.09	.13	.07		
5	.44	32	.08	.02	.00	.08	.00	.08	.30	.08	.13	.09		
6	20	.94	.07	.02	.00	.09	.00	.06	.30	.08	.11	.07		
7	5.6	.44	.06	.02	.00	.11	.00	.96	.25	.09	.04	.05		
8	1.0	.32	.05	.01	.00	.12	.00	.91	.25	.09	.08	.05		
9	.44	.22	.06	.05	.00	.13	.01	.15	.25	.08	.07	.05		
10	.29	.15	.06	.03	.00	.15	.01	3.2	.30	.08	.02	.04		
11	.15	.13	.06	.02	.00	.13	.02	1.6	.25	.08	.08	.04		
12	.10	.76	.06	.01	.00	.10	.01	.25	.20	.06	.07	.03		
13	.07	.36	.06	.01	.01	.09	.01	13	.25	.19	.10	.03		
14	.05	.25	.05	.01	.01	.08	.02	2.2	.20	.04	.24	.03		
15	.05	1.0	.05	.01	.01	.06	.02	.55	.30	.09	.08	.03		
16	.05	4.4	.05	.01	.01	.05	.01	.40	.25	.07	.11	.03		
17	.05	8.2	.05	.01	.01	.05	.01	.40	.20	.09	.07	.02		
18	.07	.94	.05	.01	.00	.03	.02	.41	.17	.13	.07	.02		
19	.05	.36	.07	.01	.00	.02	.02	.41	.20	.13	.06	.02		
20	.05	.28	.05	.01	.00	.02	.02	.40	.17	.13	.06	.02		
21	.05	.25	.06	.01	.00	.01	.03	.40	.15	.07	.06	.02		
22	.05	.22	.05	.01	.01	.01	.02	.33	.14	.06	.06	.02		
23	.05	.20	.05	.01	.01	.01	.02	.42	.13	.07	.05	.00		
24	3.8	.15	.04	.02	.02	.00	.02	.40	.12	.10	.05	.00		
25	1.4	.12	.04	.01	.03	.00	.01	.33	.11	.09	.06	.00		
26	.43	.14	.04	.01	.04	.00	.02	.30	.10	.06	.05	.04		
27	2.4	.12	.04	.01	.05	.00	.00	.33	.15	.07	.05	.05		
28	3.3	.11	.07	.01	.05	.00	2.9	.41	.11	.07	.07	.05		
29	29	.10	.05	.01	---	.00	3.2	.41	.09	.06	.17	.05		
30	21	.15	.03	.01	---	.00	3.6	.41	.08	.08	.06	.05		
31	5.5	---	.02	.00	---	.00	---	.40	---	.08	.06	---		
TOTAL	95.67	53.86	1.76	.49	.26	1.75	10.15	31.32	6.62	2.65	2.56	1.30		
MEAN	3.09	1.80	.06	.02	.01	.06	.34	1.01	.22	.08	.08	.04		
MAX	29	32	.10	.05	.05	.15	3.6	13	.40	.19	.24	.17		
MIN	.05	.10	.02	.00	.00	.00	.00	.06	.08	.04	.02	.00		
CFSM	6.31	3.67	.12	.03	.02	.11	.69	2.06	.45	.17	.17	.09		
IN.	7.26	4.09	.13	.04	.02	.13	.77	2.38	.50	.20	.19	.10		
AC-FT	190	107	3.5	.0	.5	3.5	20	62	13	5.3	5.1	2.6		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	163.05	MEAN	.45	MAX	32	MIN	.01	CFSM	.92	IN.	12.38	AC-FT	323
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	208.39	MEAN	.57	MAX	32	MIN	.00	CFSM	1.16	IN.	15.82	AC-FT	413

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50276000 TURPENTINE RUN AT MARIENDAL, ST. THOMAS, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'48", long 64°52'58", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, on right bank, at Mariendal, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream from mouth, and 3.3 mi (5.3 km) southeast of Fort Christian, Charlotte Amalie.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.97 mi² (7.69 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to April 1969, October 1978 to September 1980, June 1982 to July 1986, July to Sept. 1986 (high-water discharges only).

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 40 ft (12 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: June 7 to July 2. Records poor. Since about 1975, low flow augmented by discharges from sewage plant.

AVERAGE DISCHARGES.--10 years (1964-68, 1979-80, 1983-85), 1.22 ft³/s (0.034 m³/s), 5.58 in/yr (142 mm/yr), 884 acre-ft/yr (1.09 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 0.54 ft³/s (0.015 m³/s), 390 acre-ft/yr (0.48 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 9,710 ft³/s (275 m³/s), Apr. 18, 1983, gage height, 11.09 ft (3.380 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) on basis of slope area measurement and step-backwater analysis; no flow many days from 1963 to 1969, and in 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT PERIOD.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 6	0300	138	3.91	2.69	0.820	Nov. 16	0715	118	3.34	2.53	0.771
Oct. 24	1800	346	9.80	3.92	1.195	Apr. 28	2100	490	13.9	4.45	1.356
Oct. 25	2300	537	15.2	4.59	1.399	Apr. 29	1315	*2,050	58.1	*6.45	1.966
Oct. 28	1445	168	4.76	2.92	0.890	Apr. 30	0015	1,440	40.8	5.97	1.820
Nov. 5	1000	193	5.47	3.09	0.942	May 3	0545	147	4.16	2.76	0.841
Nov. 12	1215	253	7.16	3.45	1.052	May 7	2045	348	9.86	3.93	1.198
Nov. 14	2115	302	8.55	3.71	1.131	May 18	0730	257	7.28	3.47	1.058

Minimum discharge, 0.09 ft³/s (0.002 m³/s), Mar. 24, Apr. 10, 11.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.67	2.7	1.7	.90	.24	.32	.22	7.8	4.8	.90		
2	.61	1.7	1.6	.97	2.3	.43	.29	5.1	5.4	.85		
3	.65	1.1	1.5	.85	.33	.28	.37	30	3.6	.83		
4	1.1	1.1	1.5	.95	.28	.32	.42	15	2.8	.76		
5	7.8	22	1.6	.90	.22	.34	.62	5.8	2.4	.74		
6	79	5.0	1.5	.76	.18	.44	.57	4.3	2.4	.87		
7	29	2.1	1.4	.59	.30	.30	.36	37	2.3	.75		
8	7.7	1.4	1.6	.62	.29	.37	.47	18	2.2	---		
9	3.3	1.0	1.5	1.4	.26	.45	.40	5.8	3.0	---		
10	1.6	.86	1.3	.89	.28	.33	.11	8.0	4.0	---		
11	.87	.80	2.0	.75	.43	.41	.16	26	2.5	---		
12	.75	38	1.5	.73	.30	.40	.18	8.4	3.5	---		
13	.71	16	1.1	.57	.25	.48	.39	12	4.0	---		
14	.71	40	1.2	.56	.35	.57	.35	13	3.0	---		
15	.53	30	1.2	.52	.35	.60	.23	6.3	5.0	---		
16	.51	39	1.1	.49	.67	.59	.39	4.8	4.0	---		
17	.54	13	.91	.77	.99	.47	.52	4.6	3.5	---		
18	4.8	8.4	.92	.58	.32	.45	.56	29	2.0	---		
19	1.7	4.6	.99	.55	.35	.43	.69	7.7	2.5	---		
20	.95	6.6	1.1	.52	.25	.36	.45	4.8	1.9	---		
21	.75	4.1	1.1	.40	.31	.37	.22	8.0	1.7	---		
22	.63	3.1	1.0	.43	.37	.39	.62	4.8	1.6	---		
23	1.0	2.8	.82	.35	.38	.46	.70	4.0	1.5	---		
24	58	2.4	.77	1.4	.23	.18	.35	3.5	1.5	---		
25	35	2.0	.80	.56	.27	.34	.56	3.3	1.4	---		
26	29	2.1	.79	.58	.27	.34	.71	3.2	1.3	---		
27	17	1.9	.74	.38	.27	.34	.80	3.0	3.5	---		
28	40	1.9	.80	.37	.26	.55	82	4.4	1.5	---		
29	25	1.7	.97	.28	---	.47	183	2.6	1.3	---		
30	25	2.1	.69	.27	---	.34	87	2.4	1.1	---		
31	6.7	---	.74	.24	---	.42	---	12	---	---		
TOTAL	381.58	259.46	36.44	20.13	11.30	12.54	363.71	304.6	81.2	---		
MEAN	12.3	8.65	1.18	.65	.40	.40	12.1	9.83	2.71	---		
MAX	79	40	2.0	1.4	2.3	.60	183	37	5.4	---		
MIN	.51	.80	.69	.24	.18	.18	.11	2.4	1.1	---		
CFSM	4.14	2.91	.40	.22	.13	.13	4.07	3.31	.91	---		
IN.	4.78	3.25	.46	.25	.14	.16	4.56	3.82	1.02	---		
AC-FT	757	515	72	40	22	25	721	604	161	---		

CAL YR 1985 TOTAL 877.82 MEAN 2.40 MAX 79 MIN .17 CFSM .81 IN. 10.99 AC-FT 1740

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50295000 GUINEA GUT AT BETHANY, ST. JOHN, VI

LOCATION.--Lat. 18°19'55", Long 64°46'50", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 600 ft (183 m) southeast of Bethany Church, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) east of Government House at Cruz Bay.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.37 mi² (0.96 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to October 1967, September 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete control. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (79 m), from topographic map. Prior to September 1982, at datum 1.00 ft (0.30 m) higher.

REMARKS.--No estimated daily discharges during water year. Records poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--8 years (1964-67, 1983-86), 0.10 ft³/s (0.003 m³/s), 3.60 in/yr (91 mm/yr), 71.00 acre-ft/yr (0.088 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 946 ft³/s (26.8 m³/s), Apr. 18, 1983, gage height, 5.33 ft (1.625 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 1.0 ft³/s (0.028 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and slope-area measurement of peak flow; no flow many days each year.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 10 ft³/s (0.283 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 30	0115	34	0.96	2.34	0.713	May 13	1430	14	0.40	2.09	0.637
Apr. 30	0015	52	1.47	2.47	0.753	May 17	2030	19	0.54	2.17	0.661
May 3	0730	32	0.91	2.32	0.707	May 18	0630	*206	5.83	*3.29	1.003

No flow many days.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	.01	.07	.04	.01	.01	.00	.00	.04	.02	.02	.02	.02		
2	.01	.06	.03	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.02	.02	.02	.02		
3	.01	.06	.02	.01	.01	.00	.00	2.5	.02	.02	.02	.02		
4	.01	.06	.02	.01	.01	.00	.00	.02	.02	.02	.02	.02		
5	.01	.06	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.02	.02	.02	.03		
6	.43	.06	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.03	.02	.02	.04		
7	.15	.06	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.90	.02	.02	.02	.03		
8	.01	.06	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.38	.02	.02	.02	.03		
9	.01	.06	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.02	.02	.02	.02	.04		
10	.01	.06	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.62	.02	.02	.02	.04		
11	.00	.06	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	3.6	.02	.02	.02	.04		
12	.00	.11	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.53	.02	.02	.02	.04		
13	.00	.16	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	3.0	.02	.02	.02	.05		
14	.00	.23	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	2.7	.02	.02	.02	.05		
15	.00	.27	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.23	.02	.04	.02	.04		
16	.00	.56	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.04	.02	.05	.02	.03		
17	.00	.12	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	1.9	.02	.04	.02	.02		
18	.01	.06	.02	.01	.00	.00	.00	9.3	.02	.04	.02	.03		
19	.01	.06	.02	.01	.00	.00	.00	.79	.02	.03	.02	.03		
20	.01	.10	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.05	.02	.03	.02	.03		
21	.00	.05	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.69	.02	.02	.02	.04		
22	.00	.05	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.05	.02	.02	.02	.04		
23	.00	.05	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.01	.02	.01	.02	.05		
24	.01	.04	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.01	.02	.01	.02	.05		
25	.01	.04	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.01	.02	.01	.02	.05		
26	.02	.04	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.02	.02	.01	.02	.06		
27	.04	.04	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.03	.02	.01	.02	.06		
28	.04	.04	.01	.01	.00	.00	.09	.02	.02	.01	.02	.06		
29	.06	.04	.01	.00	---	.00	.73	.02	.02	.01	.02	.06		
30	5.1	.04	.01	.00	---	.00	4.3	.02	.02	.01	.02	.05		
31	1.1	---	.01	.00	---	.00	---	.03	---	.02	.02	---		
TOTAL	7.07	2.77	.40	.28	.04	.00	5.12	27.53	.61	.65	.62	1.17		
MEAN	.23	.09	.01	.01	.00	.00	.17	.89	.02	.02	.02	.04		
MAX	5.1	.56	.04	.01	.01	.00	4.3	9.3	.03	.05	.02	.06		
MIN	.00	.04	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.02	.01	.02	.02		
CFSM	.62	.25	.04	.02	.00	.00	.46	2.41	.05	.06	.05	.11		
IN.	.71	.28	.04	.03	.00	.00	.51	2.77	.06	.07	.06	.12		
AC-FT	14	5.5	.8	.6	.08	.00	10	55	1.2	1.3	1.2	2.3		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	13.47	MEAN	.04	MAX	5.1	MIN	.00	CFSM	.10	IN.	1.35	AC-FT	27
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	46.26	MEAN	.13	MAX	9.3	MIN	.00	CFSM	.35	IN.	4.65	AC-FT	92

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50345000 JOLLY HILL GUT AT JOLLY HILL, ST. CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°44'00", long 64°51'47", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, on Mahogany Road at Jolly Hill, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northeast of Frederiksted.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.10 mi² (5.44 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to December 1968. Monthly measurements, 1962, 69. October 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder, crest-stage gage and sharp-crested concrete control. Elevation of gage is 140 ft (43 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated daily discharges: Nov. 26 to Dec. 10. Records poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--9 years (1964-68, 1983-86), 0.107 ft³/s (0.003 m³/s), 0.69 in/yr (17.5 mm/yr), 77.5 acre-ft/yr (0.10 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 288 ft³/s (8.156 m³/s), Nov. 7, 1984, gage height, 3.62 ft (1.103 m); no flow many days each year.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 25 ft³/s (0.71 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 6	1730	*118	3.34	*2.81	0.856	Nov. 12	1800	46	1.30	2.26	0.689

No flow many days.

DISCHARGE, IN CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	.00	.99	1.1	.49	.28	.14	.06	.08	.19	.11	.07	.01		
2	.00	1.4	1.1	.47	.26	.14	.06	.08	.20	.11	.05	.01		
3	.00	1.3	1.0	.45	.26	.14	.06	.08	.20	.11	.05	.01		
4	.00	1.5	1.0	.44	.26	.13	.07	.08	.20	.11	.06	.00		
5	.00	1.5	.95	.44	.26	.13	.18	.08	.20	.11	.16	.00		
6	8.2	1.5	.90	.44	.25	.13	.13	.10	.20	.11	.18	.00		
7	3.9	1.3	.90	.43	.23	.13	.09	.09	.20	.11	.15	.00		
8	1.2	1.2	.86	.41	.22	.13	.09	.09	.20	.10	.04	.00		
9	.54	1.2	.86	.67	.22	.13	.09	.08	.20	.10	.02	.00		
10	.51	1.2	.78	.52	.22	.13	.09	.20	.19	.10	.02	.00		
11	.49	1.2	.71	.49	.21	.13	.08	.27	.18	.10	.03	.00		
12	.49	5.6	.76	.46	.20	.13	.08	.16	.48	.10	.03	.00		
13	.41	3.7	.68	.45	.19	.13	.08	.14	1.1	.10	.03	.00		
14	.33	2.7	.64	.43	.18	.13	.08	.14	.98	.10	.06	.00		
15	.33	2.5	.64	.41	.18	.13	.08	.13	.74	.09	.02	.00		
16	.33	2.4	.66	.41	.19	.12	.08	.14	.15	.09	.02	.00		
17	.39	2.6	.61	.41	.19	.10	.08	.15	.18	.09	.02	.00		
18	.40	2.5	.62	.42	.18	.10	.08	.18	.11	.09	.02	.00		
19	.38	2.2	.62	.41	.16	.10	.08	.18	.11	.09	.01	.00		
20	.37	2.4	.62	.40	.16	.10	.08	.18	.11	.09	.01	.00		
21	.37	2.3	.61	.39	.16	.10	.07	.18	.11	.08	.01	.00		
22	.37	1.9	.63	.38	.16	.10	.07	.18	.11	.08	.00	.00		
23	.41	1.8	.61	.37	.14	.09	.06	.18	.11	.07	.00	.00		
24	.42	1.7	.60	.36	.14	.09	.06	.18	.11	.07	.00	.04		
25	.48	1.5	.57	.34	.14	.09	.06	.19	.11	.08	.00	.07		
26	.54	1.5	.57	.32	.14	.09	.06	.20	.11	.08	.00	.03		
27	.52	1.4	.56	.31	.14	.09	.06	.20	.11	.08	.00	.00		
28	.67	1.4	.55	.31	.14	.09	.08	.27	.11	.08	.01	.00		
29	1.7	1.2	.54	.31	---	.07	.07	.20	.11	.07	.02	.00		
30	1.2	1.2	.51	.30	---	.07	.08	.19	.11	.07	.01	.00		
31	1.0	---	.49	.29	---	.06	---	.18	---	.06	.03	---		
TOTAL	25.95	56.79	22.25	12.73	5.46	3.44	2.39	4.78	7.22	2.83	1.13	.17		
MEAN	.84	1.89	.72	.41	.19	.11	.08	.15	.24	.09	.04	.01		
MAX	8.2	5.6	1.1	.67	.28	.14	.18	.27	1.1	.11	.18	.07		
MIN	.00	.99	.49	.29	.14	.06	.06	.08	.11	.06	.00	.00		
CFSM	.40	.90	.34	.20	.09	.05	.04	.07	.11	.04	.02	.00		
IN.	.46	1.01	.39	.23	.10	.06	.04	.08	.13	.05	.02	.00		
AC-FT	51	113	44	25	11	6.8	4.7	9.5	14	5.6	2.2	.3		
CAL YR 1985	TOTAL	132.68	MEAN	.36	MAX	8.2	MIN	.00	CFSM	.17	IN.	2.35	AC-FT	263
WTR YR 1986	TOTAL	145.14	MEAN	.40	MAX	8.2	MIN	.00	CFSM	.19	IN.	2.57	AC-FT	288

Ground-Water Records
for
U.S. Virgin Islands

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174225064471900. Local number, 1.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'25", long 64°47'19".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Fairplains 6 (FP6).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 20 ft (6.10 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of pump concrete base, 2.20 ft (0.67 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 15.64 ft (4.77 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 25, 1982; lowest water level measured, a58.57 ft (17.9 m) below land-surface datum, June 20, 1983.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level						
Dec. 10	a58.03	Feb. 24	17.38	Apr. 29	17.37	June 30	16.10

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174225064472000. Local number, 2.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'25", long 64°47'20".

Owner: U.S. Government, Virgin Islands Government.

Name: USGS-10, Fairplains 2 (FP2).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 20 ft (6.10 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at concrete base wall, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1983 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 20.91 ft (6.37 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 27, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 25.02 ft (7.63 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 22, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	23.31	21.87	21.45	21.70	21.95	22.43	22.10	22.14	21.81	21.77	22.08	22.33
2	23.30	21.85	21.54	21.74	21.96	22.46	22.11	22.20	21.79	21.75	22.06	22.29
3	23.26	21.81	21.61	21.77	21.98	22.40	22.10	22.23	21.82	21.81	22.05	22.36
4	23.24	21.72	21.65	21.81	21.94	22.37	22.07	22.21	21.81	21.81	22.09	22.64
5	23.16	21.65	21.69	21.85	21.91	22.42	22.07	22.22	21.84	21.73	22.09	22.83
6	23.01	21.61	21.72	21.87	21.90	22.44	22.02	22.23	21.84	21.69	22.18	22.96
7	22.92	21.54	21.76	21.81	21.90	22.48	22.03	22.22	21.84	21.68	22.12	23.02
8	22.78	21.49	21.75	21.88	21.89	22.51	22.01	22.23	21.84	21.71	22.10	23.10
9	22.72	21.52	21.76	21.94	21.88	22.51	21.94	22.20	21.85	21.68	22.17	23.20
10	22.74	21.52	21.88	21.83	21.89	22.41	21.91	22.17	21.83	21.70	22.19	23.28
11	22.72	21.51	22.04	21.76	21.93	22.37	21.90	22.13	21.80	21.75	22.14	23.34
12	22.69	21.51	22.10	21.79	21.93	22.42	21.91	22.07	21.78	21.81	22.07	23.43
13	22.58	21.41	21.96	21.75	21.90	22.45	21.90	22.00	21.77	21.85	22.10	23.50
14	22.49	21.30	21.60	21.74	21.91	22.47	21.95	22.00	21.77	21.86	22.11	23.35
15	22.39	21.23	21.50	21.76	21.90	22.53	21.92	21.95	21.77	21.79	22.09	23.41
16	22.43	21.17	21.44	21.73	22.00	22.49	21.92	21.94	21.79	21.77	22.08	23.47
17	22.45	21.15	21.42	21.71	22.05	22.40	21.93	21.93	21.79	21.83	22.02	23.58
18	22.44	21.12	21.39	21.70	21.96	22.35	21.90	21.92	21.80	21.88	21.97	23.64
19	22.43	21.11	21.47	21.69	21.93	22.32	21.90	21.92	21.85	21.91	21.98	23.63
20	22.42	21.07	21.55	21.68	21.93	22.33	21.90	21.95	21.89	21.89	22.06	23.67
21	22.42	21.05	21.58	21.65	21.96	22.29	21.91	21.97	21.86	21.93	22.18	23.69
22	22.41	21.03	21.62	21.64	21.96	22.27	21.94	21.97	21.88	21.93	22.15	23.70
23	22.40	21.01	21.65	21.75	22.07	22.23	21.92	21.91	21.91	21.91	22.17	23.73
24	22.38	20.95	21.69	21.83	22.11	22.21	21.95	21.87	21.88	22.01	22.23	23.74
25	22.35	20.94	21.71	21.88	22.11	22.18	22.11	21.84	21.87	22.05	22.23	23.68
26	22.34	20.94	21.74	21.88	22.19	22.10	22.16	21.81	21.85	22.04	22.25	23.82
27	22.32	20.93	21.73	21.82	22.27	22.12	22.23	21.79	21.86	22.00	22.40	23.80
28	22.30	21.10	21.69	21.79	22.36	22.11	22.15	21.78	21.88	21.98	22.35	23.82
29	22.16	21.12	21.61	21.87	---	22.11	22.10	21.77	21.81	21.98	22.30	23.85
30	22.08	21.28	21.55	21.90	---	22.11	22.14	21.81	21.80	22.06	22.31	23.87
31	21.96	---	21.64	21.92	---	22.11	---	21.82	---	22.11	22.30	---
LOW	23.31	21.87	22.10	21.94	22.36	22.53	22.23	22.23	21.91	22.11	22.40	23.87
HIGH	21.96	20.93	21.39	21.64	21.88	22.10	21.90	21.77	21.77	21.68	21.97	22.29
WTR YR 1986	MEAN 22.1	LOW 23.87	HIGH 20.93									

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174243064475100. Local number, 3.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'43", long 64°47'51".

Owner: U.S. Government, Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Golden Grove-6 (PW6).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Upper edge of hole at 8 in (0.20 m) casing, 4.20 ft (1.28 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 14.76 ft (4.50 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 25, 1982; lowest water level recorded, 28.67 ft (8.74 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 6, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	28.62	22.44	21.03	23.37	24.65	25.39	26.11	26.75	25.91	26.68	27.27	27.79
2	28.63	22.15	21.18	23.42	24.66	25.41	26.15	26.77	25.93	26.71	27.29	27.80
3	28.64	21.98	21.29	23.47	24.67	25.45	26.18	26.79	25.95	26.74	27.30	27.81
4	28.65	21.90	21.40	23.54	24.72	25.47	26.20	26.81	25.96	26.76	27.30	27.82
5	28.66	21.90	21.48	23.60	24.76	25.50	26.21	26.83	25.99	26.78	27.33	27.83
6	28.67	21.92	21.56	23.64	24.79	25.52	26.22	26.85	26.02	26.80	27.35	27.84
7	28.52	21.95	21.67	23.69	24.81	25.55	26.23	26.86	26.04	26.82	27.36	27.86
8	27.96	22.03	21.79	23.74	24.84	25.58	26.25	26.87	26.05	26.84	27.38	27.87
9	27.34	22.12	21.86	23.81	24.87	25.61	26.27	26.89	26.09	26.86	27.39	27.88
10	26.96	22.18	21.95	23.84	24.91	25.63	26.29	26.92	26.13	26.87	27.42	27.89
11	26.71	22.25	22.02	23.87	24.94	25.64	26.31	26.93	26.16	26.89	27.44	27.90
12	26.54	22.36	22.14	23.90	24.96	25.66	26.32	26.81	26.19	26.91	27.46	27.91
13	26.39	21.98	22.22	23.93	24.98	25.67	26.33	26.39	26.21	26.93	27.47	27.93
14	26.30	20.90	22.28	23.99	25.01	25.68	26.37	26.08	26.22	26.95	27.49	27.94
15	26.25	20.32	22.34	24.07	25.03	25.69	26.40	25.89	26.25	26.96	27.50	27.95
16	26.20	20.10	22.43	24.07	25.06	25.70	26.43	25.73	26.28	26.97	27.52	27.96
17	26.16	20.05	22.50	24.10	25.09	25.72	26.47	25.67	26.30	26.98	27.54	27.97
18	26.12	19.85	22.56	24.14	25.11	25.74	26.49	25.61	26.32	27.00	27.56	27.99
19	26.10	19.68	22.63	24.19	25.14	25.76	26.50	25.56	26.35	27.01	27.57	28.01
20	26.10	19.65	22.69	24.22	25.16	25.80	26.52	25.55	26.40	27.04	27.58	28.03
21	26.09	19.73	22.73	24.24	25.18	25.82	26.55	25.55	26.43	27.06	27.58	28.05
22	26.12	19.83	22.80	24.27	25.20	25.87	26.56	25.57	26.47	27.06	27.59	28.07
23	26.15	19.93	22.87	24.31	25.25	25.91	26.58	25.60	26.49	27.11	27.61	28.08
24	26.18	20.05	22.94	24.35	25.29	25.93	26.59	25.64	26.51	27.13	27.62	28.09
25	26.20	20.18	22.99	24.39	25.30	25.95	26.60	25.67	26.54	27.15	27.65	28.11
26	26.09	20.35	23.05	24.43	25.32	25.96	26.62	25.69	26.56	27.17	27.67	28.12
27	25.86	20.51	23.11	24.48	25.34	25.98	26.65	25.73	26.58	27.19	27.69	28.14
28	25.69	20.66	23.15	24.52	25.38	26.01	26.68	25.77	26.59	27.20	27.71	28.16
29	25.20	20.78	23.20	24.54	---	26.04	26.70	25.80	26.61	27.22	27.74	28.17
30	24.12	20.90	23.26	24.59	---	26.06	26.73	25.84	26.65	27.24	27.76	28.19
31	23.14	---	23.30	24.61	---	26.09	---	25.88	---	27.25	27.77	---
LOW	28.67	22.44	23.30	24.61	25.38	26.09	26.73	26.93	26.65	27.25	27.77	28.19
HIGH	23.14	19.65	21.03	23.37	24.65	25.39	26.11	25.55	25.91	26.68	27.27	27.79
WTR YR 1986	MEAN 25.5	LOW 28.67	HIGH 19.65									

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174245064475800. Local number, 4.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'45", long 64°47'58".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Golden Grove - 1 (PW1).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m),

0-104 ft (0-31.70 m), perforated 64-104 ft (19.51-31.70 m). Depth 104 ft (31.70 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Lower edge of 1 in. (0.02 m) pipe at pump base, 3.40 ft (1.04 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1983 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD: Highest water level measured, 23.09 ft (7.04 m) below land-surface datum, May 18, 1983; lowest water level measured, a58.30 ft (17.77 m) below land-surface datum, September 27, 1983.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level						
Dec. 10	a45.05	Feb. 25	27.12	Apr. 29	a 48.03	June 30	a56.03

174336064523200. Local number, 5.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'36", long 64°52'32".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Mahogany Road 3.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary age and volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m),

0-104 ft (0-31.70 m), perforated 64-104 ft (19.51-31.70 m). Depth 104 ft (31.70 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 70 ft (21.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Lower edge of 2 in. (0.05 m) pipe at pump base, 3.70 ft (1.13 m) above land-surface datum.

Prior to December 1969, top of instrument platform, 2.57 ft (0.78 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumpage.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1964 to December 1969, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 26.24 ft (8.00 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 16, 1969; lowest water level measured, 74.31 ft (22.6 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 29, 1965.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 10	38.16	Feb. 25	42.79

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174303064484400. Local number, 6.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'03", long 64°48'44".

Owner: U.S. Government, Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Adventure 28.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Pleistocene age and marl of Oligocene age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m). Depth 97 ft (29.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 80 ft (24.39 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Upper edge of hole at 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum. Prior June 20, 1983, top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 0.90 ft (0.27 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1973 to March 1974, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 24.90 ft (7.59 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 25, 1982; lowest water level recorded, 40.18 ft (12.25 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 5, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	39.95	35.83	33.55	34.66	34.98	35.44	35.74	35.82	34.70	35.65	36.55	37.11
2	39.95	35.50	33.59	34.66	34.99	35.45	35.74	35.83	34.73	35.68	36.58	37.09
3	39.95	35.24	33.66	34.69	34.98	35.47	35.75	35.86	34.73	35.72	36.61	37.08
4	39.95	35.00	33.69	34.71	34.99	35.49	35.75	35.88	34.75	35.75	36.63	37.08
5	39.95	34.81	33.72	34.75	35.01	35.52	35.76	35.91	34.79	35.78	36.66	37.08
6	39.95	34.65	33.75	34.79	35.03	35.52	35.76	35.93	34.83	35.81	36.69	37.08
7	39.95	34.54	33.81	34.80	35.05	35.53	35.74	35.95	34.86	35.83	36.70	37.12
8	39.96	34.47	33.85	34.83	35.07	35.55	35.71	35.95	34.89	35.86	36.72	37.15
9	39.31	34.45	33.91	34.36	35.09	35.57	35.69	35.95	34.93	35.89	36.75	37.18
10	38.95	34.47	33.95	34.82	35.11	35.58	35.67	35.96	34.98	35.93	36.78	37.20
11	38.70	34.50	33.99	34.80	35.14	35.58	35.65	35.96	35.01	35.95	36.80	37.23
12	38.50	34.53	34.05	34.79	35.16	35.59	35.64	35.95	35.02	35.98	36.82	37.25
13	38.37	34.43	34.09	34.78	35.17	35.59	35.63	35.51	35.04	36.01	36.84	37.29
14	38.29	34.20	34.14	34.78	35.19	35.59	35.60	35.22	35.07	36.03	36.85	37.33
15	38.25	33.87	34.18	34.79	35.21	35.60	35.60	35.01	35.10	36.06	36.87	37.36
16	38.23	33.62	34.22	34.79	35.23	35.60	35.60	34.88	35.13	36.09	36.89	37.40
17	38.23	33.52	34.26	34.80	35.25	35.62	35.60	34.80	35.17	36.12	36.92	37.42
18	38.23	33.44	34.28	34.81	35.25	35.63	35.60	34.75	35.21	36.15	36.96	37.45
19	38.23	33.38	34.30	34.82	35.27	35.64	35.60	34.71	35.24	36.18	36.99	37.47
20	38.23	33.29	34.32	34.85	35.28	35.65	35.60	34.70	35.29	36.20	37.02	37.50
21	38.23	33.26	34.35	34.86	35.29	35.66	35.62	34.69	35.32	36.23	37.05	37.52
22	38.24	33.25	34.35	34.88	35.31	35.67	35.65	34.68	35.34	36.27	37.06	37.54
23	38.24	33.25	34.32	34.88	35.33	35.68	35.67	34.68	35.38	36.30	37.07	37.55
24	38.24	33.26	34.44	34.88	35.35	35.70	35.69	34.70	35.42	36.33	37.08	37.57
25	38.10	33.30	34.48	34.89	35.35	35.71	35.72	34.71	35.46	36.36	37.09	37.57
26	37.78	33.33	34.51	34.88	35.36	35.71	35.74	34.71	35.50	36.39	37.14	37.57
27	37.50	33.38	34.54	34.89	35.39	35.71	35.77	34.72	35.53	36.42	37.15	37.55
28	37.24	33.45	34.56	34.91	35.42	35.72	35.77	34.73	35.55	36.43	37.16	37.54
29	37.04	33.49	34.57	34.93	---	35.72	35.78	34.70	35.59	36.46	37.16	37.54
30	36.61	33.52	34.60	34.93	---	35.73	35.80	34.70	35.63	36.49	37.16	37.54
31	36.26	---	34.63	34.96	---	35.73	---	34.71	---	36.52	37.15	---
LOW	39.96	35.83	34.63	34.96	35.42	35.73	35.80	35.96	35.63	36.52	37.16	37.57
HIGH	36.26	33.25	33.55	34.66	34.98	35.44	35.60	34.68	34.70	35.65	36.55	37.08

WTR YR 1986 MEAN 35.7 LOW 39.96 HIGH 33.25

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174525064460600. Local number, 7.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°45'25", long 64°46'06".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Concordia 14.

AQUIFER.--Sand and gravel.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Depth 85 ft (25.91 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 0.50 in (0.01 m) pipe on top of pump concrete base, 2.30 ft (0.70 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumpage.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 15.56 ft (4.74 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 13, 1984; lowest water level measured, 41.75 ft (12.73 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 24, 1983.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level						
Dec. 10	18.05	Feb. 24	21.05	Apr. 29	23.15	June 30	22.01

174527064460100. Local number, 8.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°45'27", long 64°46'01".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Concordia 1 (Main pump house).

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Depth 82 ft (25.0 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.20 ft (0.67 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumpage.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 16.68 ft (5.08 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 13, 1984; lowest water level measured, 28.39 ft (8.66 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 8, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level						
Dec. 10	19.17	Feb. 24	21.60	Apr. 29	23.17	June 30	22.30

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174532064460300. Local number, 9.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°45'32", long 64°46'03".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Concordia 7.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-81 ft (0-24.7 m).
Depth 81 ft (24.7 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 35 ft (10.7 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole in pump base, 2.20 ft (0.67 m) above land-surface datum. Previous to Mar. 25, 1982,
hole in pump base 2.50 ft (0.76 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1962 to October 1968, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 1.75 ft (0.53 m) below land-surface datum, May 11,
1966; lowest water level measured, 57.40 ft (17.5 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 5, 1964.WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level						
Dec. 10	a21.59	Feb. 24	8.01	Apr. 29	9.43	June 30	8.70

174329064454700. Local number, 10.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'29", long 64°45'47".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Barren Spot 5 (PWD-5).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-130 ft (0-39.63 m),
perforated 71-130 ft (21.64-39.53 m). Depth 130 ft (39.63 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 75 ft (22.86 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on top of pump base, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 61.86 ft (18.86 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 26,
1982; lowest water level measured, a75.52 ft (a23.02 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 8, 1982.WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level						
Dec. 10	a69.46	Feb. 24	65.13	Apr. 29	64.86	June 30	64.14

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182050064580400. Local number, 1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'50", long 64°58'04".

Owner: U.S. Government, Virgin Islands Government.

Name: USGS-8 (Family well - Thatch Farm).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table production well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m) 0-25 ft (0-7.62 m), open hole 25-80 ft (7.62-24.4 m). Depth 80 ft (24.4 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 80 ft (24.4 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.50 ft (0.76 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to Mar. 23, 1982, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Non-potable public-water supply and observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1963 to August 1969, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 2.33 ft (0.71 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 20, 1984; lowest water level measured, 56.44 ft (17.21 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 24, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 11	a7.52	Feb. 26	a24.72	Apr. 30	a38.10	July 1	a30.79

182138064543100. Local number, 2.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'38", long 64°54'31".

Owner: Mahogany Run Resort.

Name: Mahogany 15.

AQUIFER.--Fractured rocks.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 145 ft (44.21 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 120 ft (36.6 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.20 ft (0.36 m) below land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 12.45 ft (3.79 m) below land-surface datum, July 1, 1986; lowest water level measured, 88.62 ft (27.01 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 4, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 11	a14.64	Feb. 26	26.52	Apr. 30	35.50	July 1	12.45

182138064542500. Local number, 3.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'38", long 64°54'25".

Owner: Mahogany Run Resort.

Name: Mahogany 16.

AQUIFER.--Fractured rocks.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table production well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 145 ft (44.21 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 130 ft (39.6 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) below land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 17.52 ft (5.34 m) below land-surface datum, July 1, 1986; lowest water level measured, a103.85 ft (31.65 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 4, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 11	17.74	Feb. 26	47.02	Apr. 30	39.62	July 1	17.52

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182136064541900. Local number, 4.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'36", long 64°54'19".
Owner: Mahogany Run Resort
Name: Mahogany 17.

AQUIFER.--Fractured rock.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table production well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).
Depth 145 ft (44.21 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 140 ft (42.7 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing at land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Public water supply. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 17.49 ft (5.33 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 11 1985; lowest water level measured, 60.40 ft (18.41 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 10, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 11	17.49	Feb. 26	33.38	Apr. 30	37.55	July 1	18.62

182029064535200. Local number, 5.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'29", long 64°53'52".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government, V.I. Housing Authority.
Name: Donoe 3.

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rock undifferentiated. Fracture at 165 ft (50.3 m), from drilling log.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), open hole 20-400 ft (6.10-122 m). Depth 400 ft (122 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 235 ft (71.6 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.30 ft (0.70 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 54.24 ft (16.53 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 20, 1984; lowest water level measured, 90.98ft (27.73m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 30, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 11	64.69	Feb. 26	76.36	Apr. 30	90.98	July 1	66.18

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182038064550300. Local number, 6.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'38", long 64°55'03".

Owner: U.S. Government, Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Grade School 3.

AQUIFER.--Volcanic breccia.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 70 ft (21.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to June 27, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.90 ft (0.88 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.72 ft (1.13 m) below land-surface datum, May 22, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 35.38 ft (10.79 m) below land-surface datum, July 21, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	22.55	13.65	13.81	19.95	22.42	23.87	24.65	17.05	4.65	9.41	13.95	17.15
2	22.61	13.27	14.10	20.01	22.48	23.90	24.67	15.79	4.79	9.62	13.96	17.27
3	22.56	13.24	14.39	20.08	22.54	23.93	24.70	14.59	4.87	9.82	14.01	17.28
4	22.53	13.42	14.70	20.16	22.60	23.97	24.73	13.08	5.00	10.02	14.08	17.29
5	22.53	13.68	15.01	20.22	22.68	24.02	24.72	12.23	5.15	10.16	14.15	17.33
6	21.16	13.58	15.28	20.27	22.77	24.07	24.60	11.87	5.32	10.37	14.23	17.37
7	17.33	13.32	15.57	20.33	22.87	24.13	24.46	11.84	5.45	10.54	14.33	17.40
8	15.42	13.23	15.84	20.47	22.99	24.16	24.35	10.92	5.58	10.74	14.51	17.44
9	14.53	13.39	16.12	20.69	23.10	24.19	24.30	10.11	5.71	10.94	14.69	17.53
10	14.15	13.67	16.36	20.77	23.20	24.20	24.28	9.97	5.84	11.14	14.87	17.62
11	14.25	13.99	16.58	20.82	23.24	24.23	24.29	9.31	5.96	11.33	15.04	17.72
12	14.81	14.33	16.78	20.90	23.29	24.25	24.31	8.16	6.09	11.53	15.21	17.84
13	15.51	14.35	16.95	20.97	23.32	24.28	24.32	7.91	6.20	11.73	15.38	17.97
14	16.16	14.03	17.12	21.04	23.35	24.34	24.35	7.10	6.29	11.93	15.44	18.08
15	16.82	13.78	17.29	21.12	23.38	24.39	24.39	6.30	6.42	12.15	15.50	18.18
16	17.43	13.20	17.44	21.21	23.41	24.39	24.44	6.11	6.52	12.36	15.58	18.43
17	18.00	12.26	17.61	21.28	23.44	24.39	24.48	6.12	6.64	12.56	15.70	18.67
18	18.52	11.49	17.77	21.37	23.44	24.40	24.51	5.94	6.73	12.75	15.82	18.96
19	19.00	11.12	17.97	21.43	23.44	24.41	24.54	4.46	6.82	12.92	15.96	19.23
20	19.33	11.04	18.24	21.49	23.44	24.45	24.64	4.20	6.90	13.12	16.12	19.49
21	19.60	11.15	18.47	21.55	23.46	24.50	24.82	4.11	7.14	13.32	16.25	19.73
22	19.86	11.34	18.61	21.60	23.47	24.52	24.93	3.84	7.43	13.54	16.39	19.94
23	20.10	11.58	18.78	21.66	23.52	24.55	25.06	3.78	7.67	13.75	16.51	20.12
24	20.32	11.85	18.93	21.71	23.59	24.57	25.19	3.86	7.89	13.92	16.63	20.31
25	19.86	12.16	19.10	21.75	23.68	24.59	25.26	3.94	8.08	14.08	16.74	20.48
26	18.97	12.47	19.25	21.79	23.76	24.61	25.28	4.05	8.28	14.23	16.81	20.64
27	18.41	12.73	19.40	21.82	23.81	24.62	25.29	4.20	8.52	14.30	16.86	20.77
28	17.84	13.00	19.52	21.85	23.84	24.64	25.30	4.34	8.75	14.28	16.93	20.89
29	17.01	13.25	19.64	21.93	---	24.64	22.93	4.43	8.98	14.21	16.99	21.00
30	15.84	13.52	19.74	22.17	---	24.64	18.42	4.57	9.17	14.12	16.93	21.10
31	14.49	---	19.85	22.32	---	24.65	---	4.69	---	14.01	17.00	---
LOW	22.61	14.35	19.85	22.32	23.84	24.65	25.30	17.05	9.17	14.30	17.00	21.10
HIGH	14.15	11.04	13.81	19.95	22.42	23.87	18.42	3.78	4.65	9.41	13.95	17.15

WTR YR 1986 MEAN 16.8 LOW 25.30 HIGH 3.78

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182010064472600. Local number, 1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'10", long 64°47'26".

Owner: U.S. Government, National Park Services.

Name: NPS-2 (Cruz Bay).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), 4 in (0.10 m) cased, 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), open hole 20-99 ft (6.10-30.2 m). Depth 99 ft (30.2 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 4.10 ft (1.25 m) above old land-surface datum after 1.40 ft (0.43 m) land fill and 2.70 ft (0.82 m) casing extension occurred. Prior to June 29, 1983, top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 1.40 ft (0.43 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping nearby well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1964, discontinued. June 30, 1983 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, +1.41 ft (0.43 m) below land-surface datum, May 1, 1986; lowest water level measured, 42.56 ft (12.98 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 30, 1967.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 12	22.93	Feb. 27	33.17	May 1	+1.41	July 2	8.46

182109064460300. Local number, 2.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'09", long 64°46'03".

Owner: U.S. Government, National Park Service.

Name: NPS-5 (Trunk Bay).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table production well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-12 ft (0-3.66 m), open hole 12-60 ft (3.66-18.3 m). Depth 60 ft (18.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 0.70 ft (0.21 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to Mar. 24, 1982 top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.00 ft (0.30 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Active water supply well for recreation facilities at Trunk Bay.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1964 to December 1969, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 12.83 ft (3.91 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 24, 1985; lowest water level measured, a57.29 ft (17.47 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 27, 1968.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 12	25.39	Feb. 27	a47.44	May 1	35.50	July 2	14.80

a Pumping.

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182116064451000. Local number, 3.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'16", long 64°45'10".

Owner: U.S. Government, National Park Service.

Name: NPS-6 (Cinnamon Bay).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table production well, diameter 6-in (0.15 m), cased 0-51 ft (0-15.55 m), open hole 51-70 ft (15.55-21.34 m). Depth 70 ft (21.34 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to June 29,

1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing at land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Abandoned as production well. Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1964 to December 1969, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 41.12 ft (12.54 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 15, 1969; lowest water level recorded, 63.15 ft (19.25 m) below land-surface datum, July 1, 1968.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	57.40	56.55	54.33	56.48	---	57.21	57.34	56.68	49.54	55.14	56.26	56.10
2	57.41	56.42	54.45	56.50	---	57.21	57.36	56.45	49.80	55.23	56.30	56.08
3	57.43	56.32	54.61	56.52	---	57.21	57.39	56.27	49.99	55.29	56.34	56.08
4	57.45	56.25	54.75	56.54	---	57.24	57.40	56.06	50.10	55.35	56.37	56.08
5	57.47	56.15	54.88	56.56	---	57.24	57.40	55.83	50.27	55.42	56.40	56.08
6	57.47	56.11	54.99	56.60	---	57.23	57.40	55.64	50.53	55.50	56.42	56.08
7	57.34	56.07	55.08	56.63	---	57.24	57.39	55.47	50.79	55.55	56.43	56.08
8	57.26	56.05	55.17	56.67	---	57.26	57.38	55.25	51.06	55.60	56.43	56.10
9	57.19	56.03	55.24	56.69	---	57.27	57.35	54.97	51.32	55.65	56.45	56.13
10	57.15	56.03	55.30	56.70	---	57.27	57.32	54.67	51.58	55.72	56.46	56.17
11	57.14	56.02	55.34	56.69	---	57.28	57.31	54.42	51.85	55.78	56.46	56.21
12	57.13	56.05	55.41	56.67	---	57.28	57.31	53.93	52.11	55.84	56.43	56.24
13	57.10	56.06	55.48	56.66	---	57.29	57.31	53.41	52.37	55.87	56.42	56.25
14	57.07	55.89	55.56	56.66	---	57.31	57.30	52.81	52.64	55.91	56.39	56.25
15	57.06	55.57	55.61	56.67	---	57.33	57.30	52.09	52.90	55.93	56.35	56.25
16	57.06	55.03	55.66	56.68	---	57.39	57.31	51.56	53.15	55.95	56.32	56.28
17	57.06	54.36	55.73	56.69	---	57.42	57.33	51.29	53.37	55.97	56.31	56.30
18	57.05	53.72	55.80	56.71	---	57.47	57.33	51.19	53.55	56.00	56.31	56.32
19	57.04	53.25	55.86	56.71	---	57.51	57.33	50.00	53.73	56.03	56.31	56.35
20	57.04	53.04	55.92	56.71	---	57.55	57.33	48.90	53.89	56.06	56.33	56.36
21	57.03	52.99	56.00	56.75	---	57.57	57.32	48.30	54.04	56.08	56.36	56.36
22	57.03	53.03	56.05	56.80	---	57.58	57.29	47.60	54.21	56.11	56.38	56.36
23	57.03	53.11	56.09	56.83	---	57.56	57.24	46.49	54.34	56.13	56.35	56.35
24	57.03	53.22	56.13	56.86	---	57.53	57.21	45.76	54.46	56.14	56.31	56.37
25	57.03	53.37	56.19	56.86	---	57.48	57.19	45.66	54.59	56.14	56.26	56.40
26	57.01	53.52	56.26	56.89	---	57.40	57.19	46.12	54.69	56.14	56.21	56.41
27	57.00	53.71	56.31	56.91	---	57.35	57.22	46.83	54.79	56.15	56.18	56.41
28	56.98	53.84	56.38	---	57.22	57.33	57.21	47.49	54.89	56.17	56.18	56.42
29	56.96	54.01	56.42	---	---	57.31	57.14	48.05	54.98	56.20	56.17	56.43
30	56.93	54.16	56.44	---	---	57.31	57.01	48.70	55.05	56.23	56.15	56.44
31	56.74	---	56.45	---	---	57.33	---	49.13	---	56.24	56.12	---
LOW	57.47	56.55	56.45	---	---	57.58	57.40	56.68	55.05	56.24	56.46	56.44
HIGH	56.74	52.99	54.33	---	---	57.21	57.01	45.66	49.54	55.14	56.12	56.08

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182042066454500. Local number, 5.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'42", long 66°45'45".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: DPW-6. (Sussanaberg)

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Sounded depth 70 ft (21.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.60 ft (0.49 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to June 28, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 1.33 ft (0.40 m) below land-surface datum, May 18, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 22.78 ft (6.94 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 5, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	22.72	8.83	6.42	10.42	13.70	16.63	18.54	15.82	2.38	5.22	9.09	11.79
2	22.73	8.83	6.54	10.53	13.81	16.69	18.60	15.89	2.73	5.29	9.17	11.87
3	22.75	8.83	6.68	10.63	13.91	16.77	18.64	11.93	2.79	5.33	9.30	11.98
4	22.77	11.72	6.85	10.74	14.02	16.84	18.69	12.58	2.88	5.51	9.42	12.06
5	22.78	11.89	7.01	10.85	14.13	16.92	18.72	13.08	2.97	5.60	9.56	12.15
6	18.80	11.96	7.17	10.95	14.23	16.99	18.76	13.18	3.05	5.71	9.71	12.25
7	17.39	12.03	7.40	11.06	14.34	17.05	18.82	10.48	3.14	5.83	9.79	12.34
8	20.63	12.10	7.60	11.16	14.44	17.14	18.87	7.49	3.23	5.99	9.96	12.44
9	21.06	12.21	7.76	11.27	14.55	17.23	18.91	6.02	3.31	6.15	10.09	12.55
10	20.96	12.28	7.89	11.37	14.66	17.29	18.95	8.55	3.40	6.29	10.23	12.65
11	20.78	12.41	8.05	11.48	14.76	17.36	19.00	3.85	3.49	6.37	10.25	12.73
12	20.59	12.60	8.20	11.59	14.87	17.42	19.05	3.68	3.58	6.53	10.37	12.82
13	20.39	7.41	8.29	11.69	14.97	17.47	19.08	3.28	3.66	6.70	10.42	12.96
14	20.19	5.38	8.45	11.80	15.08	17.54	19.11	2.78	3.75	6.83	10.45	13.06
15	20.05	3.88	8.57	11.90	15.18	17.60	19.14	2.93	3.84	6.92	10.51	13.17
16	19.94	3.05	8.76	12.01	15.29	17.66	19.19	4.14	3.92	7.03	10.60	13.29
17	19.85	3.17	8.82	12.12	15.40	17.71	19.21	5.02	4.01	7.18	10.70	13.38
18	19.76	4.31	8.93	12.22	15.50	17.77	19.27	1.89	4.10	7.36	10.81	13.52
19	19.50	5.41	9.05	12.33	15.61	17.84	19.31	2.10	4.18	7.47	10.92	13.64
20	19.16	5.77	9.15	12.43	15.71	17.90	19.35	2.69	4.27	7.61	11.03	13.76
21	18.99	4.07	9.26	12.54	15.82	17.94	19.38	2.03	4.36	7.78	11.13	13.86
22	18.97	5.18	9.36	12.64	15.93	18.02	19.46	2.15	4.44	8.00	11.24	13.94
23	19.02	5.56	9.47	12.75	16.03	18.09	19.51	2.69	4.53	8.05	11.32	14.07
24	19.08	5.73	9.58	12.86	16.14	18.14	19.55	2.77	4.62	8.10	11.41	14.15
25	19.10	5.88	9.68	12.96	16.24	18.20	19.60	2.78	4.71	8.22	11.55	14.26
26	18.93	5.98	9.79	13.07	16.35	18.24	19.65	2.78	4.79	8.38	11.66	14.29
27	14.09	6.10	9.89	13.17	16.46	18.29	19.69	2.78	4.88	8.51	11.77	14.35
28	15.28	6.22	10.0	13.28	16.56	18.34	19.71	2.78	4.97	8.67	11.83	14.43
29	14.04	6.32	10.10	13.39	---	18.39	19.36	2.76	5.05	8.78	11.85	14.54
30	7.38	6.39	10.21	13.49	---	18.45	13.69	2.69	5.14	8.80	11.79	14.63
31	7.43	---	10.32	13.60	---	18.50	---	2.78	---	8.95	11.77	---
LOW	22.78	12.60	10.32	13.60	16.56	18.50	19.71	15.89	5.14	8.95	11.85	14.63
HIGH	7.38	3.05	6.42	10.42	13.70	16.63	13.69	1.89	2.38	5.22	9.09	11.79

WTR YR 1986 MEAN 11.6 LOW 22.78 HIGH 1.89

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182044064454600. Local number, 6.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'46".
 Owner: Virgin Islands Government.
 Name: DPW-5

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).
 Sounded depth 145 ft (44.2 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.40 ft (0.43 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 18.85ft (5.74m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, a107.4 ft (32.7 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 19, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 12	71.20	Feb. 27	44.26	May 1	48.98	July 2	18.85

182044064454800. Local number, 7.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'48".
 Owner: Virgin Islands Government.
 Name: DPW-4

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).
 Sounded depth 60 ft (18.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 0.60 ft (0.18 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 14.48 ft (4.41 m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, 49.10 ft (14.97 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 26, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 12	48.33	Feb. 27	46.19	May 1	38.23	July 2	14.48

182044064454900. Local number, 8.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'49".
 Owner: Virgin Islands Government.
 Name: DPW-3.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).
 Sounded depth 110 ft (33.5 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 12.17ft (3.71 m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, 69.58 ft (21.21 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 27, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 12	66.74	Feb. 27	69.58	May 1	33.22	July 2	12.17

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182044064455000. Local number, 9.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'50".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: DPW-2.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Sounded depth 65 ft (19.8 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 17.10 ft (5.21 m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, 52.44 ft (15.99 m) below land-surface datum, May 19, 1983.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 12	51.25	Feb. 27	51.49	May 1	43.09	July 2	17.10

182044064455200. Local number, 10.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'52".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: DPW-1.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Sounded depth 60 ft (18.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 16.60 ft (5.06 m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, 38.92 ft (11.86 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 27, 1986

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 12	a38.54	Feb. 27	38.92	May 1	38.65	July 1	16.60

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

181956064464500. Local number, 11.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'56", long 64°46'45".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Guinea Gut Well.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation (Donnelly, 1959).

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 85 ft (25.9 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 280 ft (85.36 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Bottom of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.50 ft (0.46 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to June 28, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.05 ft (0.93 m) below land-surface datum, June 13, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 25.25 ft (7.70 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 2, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	25.21	8.00	8.35	11.48	15.67	19.43	22.20	14.32	3.28	3.83	5.19	7.40
2	25.24	7.56	8.45	11.57	15.81	19.54	22.28	12.94	3.22	3.88	5.36	7.46
3	25.24	7.65	8.54	11.65	15.92	19.66	22.35	11.19	3.22	3.86	5.53	7.58
4	25.24	7.74	8.64	11.75	16.09	19.77	22.42	9.69	3.21	3.95	5.70	7.72
5	25.24	7.84	8.73	11.87	16.23	19.87	22.47	9.00	3.21	3.97	5.90	7.83
6	25.07	7.93	8.85	11.99	16.41	19.97	22.52	8.48	3.19	4.00	6.15	7.99
7	19.65	8.02	8.98	12.14	16.57	20.07	22.59	7.51	3.17	4.02	6.34	8.09
8	16.84	8.10	9.08	12.27	16.73	20.18	22.66	6.94	3.15	4.11	6.55	8.22
9	15.98	8.08	9.17	12.41	16.87	20.28	22.70	6.61	3.14	4.17	6.74	8.38
10	16.52	8.17	9.26	12.41	17.04	20.38	22.74	6.43	3.12	4.24	6.84	8.53
11	16.91	8.26	9.35	12.48	17.20	20.47	22.80	5.43	3.11	4.28	6.83	8.61
12	17.27	8.32	9.40	12.62	17.36	20.58	22.87	5.31	3.12	4.33	6.73	8.69
13	17.61	8.41	9.56	12.75	17.50	20.68	22.93	5.01	3.10	4.42	6.77	8.80
14	17.88	8.50	9.73	12.90	17.65	20.76	22.99	4.50	3.11	4.48	6.65	8.91
15	18.20	8.59	9.83	13.07	17.78	20.84	23.06	4.64	3.11	4.44	6.65	9.02
16	18.53	8.65	9.93	13.19	17.93	20.92	23.14	4.59	3.13	4.37	6.74	9.16
17	18.81	7.77	10.05	13.34	18.06	21.01	23.20	4.53	3.15	4.44	6.90	9.26
18	19.03	7.64	10.16	13.48	18.16	21.09	23.26	3.65	3.17	4.54	7.09	9.41
19	18.28	7.74	10.27	13.66	18.26	21.18	23.31	3.90	3.23	4.60	7.26	9.53
20	17.77	7.77	10.36	13.83	18.37	21.27	23.39	3.97	3.27	4.66	7.46	9.64
21	17.56	7.41	10.43	14.00	18.49	21.35	23.46	3.69	3.25	4.73	7.64	9.75
22	17.55	7.53	10.47	14.15	18.61	21.44	23.53	3.76	3.32	4.84	7.81	9.85
23	17.59	7.62	10.57	14.29	18.74	21.54	23.59	3.72	3.42	4.84	7.96	9.94
24	17.66	7.71	10.66	14.42	18.87	21.62	23.65	3.66	3.47	4.86	8.06	10.03
25	17.41	7.81	10.76	14.57	18.97	21.70	23.71	3.60	3.55	4.97	8.08	10.14
26	17.11	7.90	10.87	14.71	19.07	21.76	23.78	3.54	3.62	5.04	8.20	10.18
27	16.96	7.99	10.99	14.88	19.19	21.83	23.84	3.44	3.62	5.09	8.33	10.25
28	16.78	8.08	11.05	15.05	19.31	21.89	23.64	3.43	3.72	5.20	8.42	10.30
29	16.38	8.17	11.14	15.19	---	21.98	22.69	3.39	3.79	5.36	7.86	10.44
30	11.92	8.26	11.24	15.33	---	22.05	17.21	3.34	3.84	5.34	7.40	10.59
31	8.93	---	11.38	15.49	---	22.14	---	3.31	---	5.10	7.39	---
LOW	25.24	8.65	11.38	15.49	19.31	22.14	23.84	14.32	3.84	5.36	8.42	10.59
HIGH	8.93	7.41	8.35	11.48	15.67	19.43	17.21	3.31	3.10	3.83	5.19	7.40

WTR YR 1986 MEAN 11.7 LOW 25.24 HIGH 3.10

	Page		Page
Access to WATSTORE data.....	31	Cialitos at Highway 649 at Ciales, Río	103-104
Acre-foot, definition of.....	32	Cibuco at Vega Baja, Río.....	115-117
Adenosine triphosphate, definition of.....	32	below Central San Vicente.....	122-123
Adjuntas, Lago Garzas No. 1 near dam near.....	296-299	below Corozal.....	112-114
Adjuntas, Río Grande de Arecibo near.....	70-71	Cibuco basin, gaging-station records in.....	112-115
Aguada, Río Culebrinas near.....	284-285	ground-water records in.....	313-316
Aguas Buenas, Río de Bayamón near.....	140-141	water-quality records in.....	113-123
Algae growth potential, definition of.....	32	Coamo basin, Río, ground-water records in	328
Analyses of samples collected at water-quality		water-quality records in.....	228-229
partial-record stations in Puerto Rico.....	293-299	Coamo near Coamo, Río.....	228-229
Añasco, Río Grande de Añasco near.....	277-278	Color unit, definition of.....	34
Aquifer, definition of.....	32	Comerio, Río de la Plata near.....	129-130
Arecibo, Río Grande de Arecibo above.....	78-79	Contents, definition of.....	34
Artesian, definition of.....	32	Control, definition of.....	34
Artificial substrate, definition of.....	42	Control structure, definition of.....	34
Ash mass, definition of.....	33	Cooperation	2
Bairoa near Caguas, Río.....	171-172	Corozal, Río Cibuco below.....	112-114
Bacteria, definition of	32	Crest-stage station, definition of.....	34
Bahía de San Juan No. 5 at San Juan.....	151	Crest-stage partial-record stations, discharge at....	289
Bayamón, at Flood Channel at Bayamón, Río de.....	144-145	Cubic foot per second, definition of.....	34
near Aguas Buenas.....	140-141	Cubic foot per second-day, definition of.....	34
Bayamón basin, Río de, ground-water records in.....	322	Cubic feet per second per square mile, definition of.....	34
water-quality records in.....	140-145	Culebrinas, at Highway 404 near Moca, Río.....	282-283
Bayamón, Río Guaynabo near.....	142-143	near Aguada.....	284-285
Bayaney, Río Camuy near.....	64-65	near San Sebastián.....	280-281
Bed material, definition of.....	33	Culebrinas basin, Río, gaging station records in....	282
Bed load, definition of.....	41	ground-water records in.....	332-333
Bed load discharge, definition of.....	41	water-quality records in.....	280-285
Biochemical oxygen demand, definition of.....	33	Damsite, Lago Loiza at.....	183
Biomass, definition of.....	33	Definition of terms.....	32-45
Blanca at El Jagual, Quebrada.....	158-159	Descalabrado basin, Río, gaging stations records in..	230
Blanco basin, Río, gaging station records in.....	211-212	Descalabrado near Los Llanos, Río	230
Blasina near Carolina, Quebrada.....	154-155	Diatoms, definition of.....	39
Blue-green algae, definition of	39	Discharge at crest-stage partial-record stations....	289
Bonne Resolution Gut at Bonne Resolution,		Discharge at partial-record stations in Puerto Rico..	289
St. Thomas, VI.....	337	Discharge, definition of.....	34
Boquerón, Laguna Cartagena near.....	250	Dissolved, definition of.....	35
Boquerón, Laguna Cartagena outflow near.....	251-252	Dissolved-solids concentrations.....	35
Borinquen, Río Turabo at.....	164-165	Diversity index, definition of.....	35
Bottom material, definition of	33	Drainage area, definition of.....	35
Bucaná basin, Río, crest-stage partial records in....	289	Drainage basin, definition of.....	35
ground-water records in.....	330	Drainage ditch at Río Cibuco below Central San	
water-quality records in.....	236-237	Vicente.....	120-121
Bucaná Floodway Channel at Highway 14 bridge near		below Warner Lambert Lab. near Sabana.....	118-119
Ponce, Río.....	289	Dry mass, definition of.....	33
Caguas, Lago Loiza No. 4 near mouth near.....	293-295	El Verde, Quebrada Sonadora near.....	190-191
Caguas, Río Bairoa near.....	171-172	El Verde, Quebrada Toronja at.....	192-193
Caguas, Río Caguaitas at Highway 30 at.....	169-172	Espiritu Santo basin, Río, gaging station records in..	190-194
Caguas, Río Grande de Loiza at.....	166-168	water-quality records in.....	195-196
Caguaitas at Highway 30 at Caguas, Río.....	169-170	Espiritu Santo near Río Grande, Río.....	194-196
Caimito near Juncos, Quebrada.....	173-174	Explanation of records.....	9-31
Campo Rico, Río Canóvanas near.....	186-187	Fajardo basin, Río, gaging station records in.....	201
Camuy basin, Río, gaging station records in.....	64-67	water-quality records in.....	202-210
ground-water records in.....	305	Fajardo below Fajardo, Río.....	209-210
Camuy near Bayaney, Río.....	64-65	near Fajardo.....	201-208
near Hatillo.....	66-67	Fecal coliform bacteria, definition of.....	33
Canal Principal de Diversiones at Lago de Guajataca..	56-57	Fecal streptococcal bacteria, definition of.....	33
Canóvanas near Campo Rico, Río.....	186-187	Florida, Río Grande de Arecibo below Lago Dos	
Caonillas above Lago Caonillas near Jayuya, Río.....	74-75	Bocas near	76-77
Carolina, Quebrada Blasina near.....	154-155	Gage-height, definition of.....	35
Cataño, Río Hondo at Flood Channel near.....	138-139	Gaging station, definition of.....	35
Cayaguas at Cerro Gordo, Río	162-163	Grande de Añasco basin, Río, gaging station	
Cayey, Lago Carite No. 1 near dam	296-299	records in.....	274
Cayey, Lago Carite No. 3 on Río de la Plata near....	293-295	water-quality records in.....	272-278
Cells/volume, definition of.....	33	Grande de Añasco near Añasco, Río.....	277-278
Central Cambalache, Río Grande de Arecibo at.....	90-91	near Lares.....	272-273
Central Rufina, Río Guayanilla at.....	244-245	near San Sebastián.....	274-276
Central San Vicente, Drainage Ditch at Río Cibuco		Grande de Arecibo at Central Cambalache, Río.....	90-91
below.....	120-121	above Arecibo.....	78-79
Central San Vicente, Río Cibuco below.....	122-123	below Lago Dos Bocas near Florida.....	76-77
Cerrillos near Ponce, Río.....	236-237	near Adjuntas.....	70-71
Cerro Gordo, Río Cayaguas at	162-163	near Utuado	72-73
Charco Hondo, Río Tanamá at.....	88-89	Grande de Arecibo basin, Río, gaging station records	
Chemical oxygen demand, definition of.....	34	in.....	78-80
Chico at Providencia, Río.....	222-223	ground-water records in.....	306
Chico basin, Río, water-quality records in.....	222-223	water-quality partial-record stations, analyses of	
Chlorophyll, definition of.....	34	samples collected in.....	293-299
Ciales, Río Cialitos at Highway 649 at.....	103-104	water-quality records in.....	70-91
Ciales, Río Grande de Manatí at.....	99-100		
Ciales, Río Grande de Manatí at Highway 149 at.....	101-102		

	Page		Page
Grande de Loiza at Caguas, Río.....	166-168	Icacos near Naguabo, Río.....	211-212
at Quebrada Arenas.....	156-157	Identification numbers, stations.....	12-18
below Trujillo Alto.....	184-185	Inabón at Real Abajo, Río.....	234-235
Grande de Loiza basin, Río, gaging station records		Inabón basin, Río, gaging station records in.....	234-235
in.....	156-187	Instantaneous discharge, definition of.....	34
ground-water records in.....	325	Introduction.....	1
water-quality partial-record stations, analyses		Jacaguas at Juana Díaz, Río.....	231
of samples collected in.....	293-299	Jacaguas basin, Río, gaging station records in.....	231
water-quality records in.....	154-185	Jagual, Quebrada Blanca at El.....	158-159
Grande de Manatí at Ciales, Río.....	99-100	Jayuya, Río Caonillas above Lago Caonillas near.....	74-75
at Highway 2 near Manatí.....	105-109	Jolly Hill Gut at Jolly Hill, St. Croix, VI.....	340
at Highway 149 at Ciales.....	101-102	Joyuda, Quebrada Mamey at.....	253
near Morovis.....	96-98	Juana Díaz, Río Jacaguas at.....	231
Grande de Manatí basin, Río, gaging station records		Juncos, Quebrada Caimito near.....	173-174
in.....	96-105	Juncos, Río Valenciano near.....	175-176
ground-water records in.....	307-312	Lago Carite No.1 near dam near Cayey.....	296-299
water-quality records in.....	94-110	No. 3 on Río de la Plata near Cayey.....	293-295
Grande de Patillas near Patillas, Río.....	224-226	Lago de Guajataca, Canal Principal de Diversiones at.....	56-57
Grande de Patillas basin, Río, gaging station		No. 1 near dam near Quebradillas.....	296-299
records in.....	224	No. 3 near mouth near Quebradillas.....	293-295
water-quality records in.....	225-226	Río Guajataca above.....	54-55
Graphs:		Río Guajataca below.....	58-59
Ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto		Lago Dos Bocas No. 1 near dam near	
Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	6	Utua.....	296-299
Monthly-mean discharge of selected streams in		No. 3 at west branch near Utua.....	293-295
Puerto Rico.....	4	Lago Garzas No. 1 near dam near	
Green algae, definition of.....	39	Adjuntas.....	296-299
Grid showing system for numbering wells and		Lago La Plata No. 3 near dam near	
miscellaneous sites (latitude and longitude)..	18	Naranjito.....	296-299
Ground-water level, records of.....	28-30	No. 5 near mouth near Naranjito.....	293-295
Ground-water quality, records of.....	30-31	Lago Loiza at damsite.....	183
Ground-water records for Puerto Rico.....	303-333	No. 4 near mouth near Caguas.....	293-295
Ground-water records for U.S. Virgin Islands.....	343-358	No. 7 near dam near Trujillo Alto.....	296-299
Ground-water station, definition of.....	35	Laguna Cartagena basin, gaging station records in...	250-252
Ground-water stations in Puerto Rico, map showing		Laguna Cartagena near Boquerón.....	250
location of.....	15	Laguna Cartagena outflow near Boquerón.....	251-252
Ground-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands,		Laguna Joyuda basin, gaging station records in.....	253
map showing location of.....	17	Laguna San José No. 2 at San Juan.....	150
Ground-water wells in U.S. Virgin Islands, map		Laguna Tortuguero basin, water-quality records in...	110
showing location of.....	17	Laguna Tortuguero outlet near Vega Baja.....	110
Guadiana near Naranjito, Río.....	131-132	Land-surface datum, definition of.....	36
Guajataca above Lago de Guajataca, Río.....	54-55	La Plata at Proyecto La Plata, Río de.....	126-128
above mouth near Quebradillas.....	60-62	at Highway 2 near Toa Alta.....	136
at Lares.....	52-53	at Toa Alta.....	133-135
below Lago de Guajataca.....	58-59	near Comerío.....	129-130
Guajataca basin, Río, gaging station records in.....	54-60	La Plata basin, Río de, gaging station records in...	126-136
ground-water records in.....	303-304	ground-water records in.....	317-320
water-quality partial-record stations, analyses of		water-quality partial-record stations, analyses of	
samples collected in.....	293-299	samples collected in.....	293-299
water-quality records in.....	52-62	water-quality records in.....	127-135
Guajatabo near Hormigueros, Río.....	265-267	Lares, Río Grande de Añasco near.....	272-273
near San Germán.....	254-255	Lares, Río Guajataca at.....	52-53
Guajatabo basin, Río, gaging station records in.....	256-265	Levels for Puerto Rico, ground-water.....	303-333
ground-water records in.....	331	Levels for U.S. Virgin Islands, ground water.....	343-358
water-quality records in.....	254-267	Loco at Guánica, Río.....	246-247
Guánica, Río Loco at.....	246-247	Loco basin, Río, water-quality records in.....	246-247
Guayanés above mouth at Playa de Guayanés, Río.....	218-219	Los Llanos, Río Descalabrado near.....	230
at Yabucoa.....	216-217	Mamey at Joyuda, Quebrada.....	253
Guayanés basin, Río, ground-water records in.....	327	Mamey near Gurabo, Quebrada.....	177-178
water-quality records in.....	216-219	Mameyes near Sabana, Río.....	197-198
Guayanilla at Central Rufina, Río.....	244-245	Mameyes basin, Río, gaging station records in.....	197-198
near Guayanilla.....	243	Manatí, Río Grande de Manatí at Highway 2 near.....	105-109
Guayanilla basin, Río, gaging station records in.....	243	Maps:	
water-quality records in.....	244-245	Location of continuous surface-water stations and	
Guaynabo near Bayamón, Río.....	142-143	crest-stage gage stations in Puerto Rico.....	13
Guinea Gut at Bethany, St. John, VI.....	339	Location of ground-water stations in Puerto Rico...	15
Gurabo at Gurabo, Río.....	179-180	Location of ground-water stations in the U.S. Virgin	
near Gurabo.....	181-182	Islands.....	17
Gurabo, Quebrada Mamey near.....	177-178	Location of maximum concentration of fecal coliform	
Hardness, definition of.....	36	bacteria at sample sites.....	10
Hatillo, Río Camuy near.....	66-67	Location of maximum concentration of fecal	
Hato Rey, Río Piedras at.....	148-149	streptococci bacteria at sample sites.....	11
Hondo at Flood Channel near Cataño, Río.....	138-139	Location of surface-water stations in the U.S.	
Hondo basin, Río, ground-water records in.....	321	Virgin Islands.....	16
water-quality records in.....	138-139	Location of water-quality stations in Puerto Rico..	14
Hormigueros, Río Guajatabo near.....	265-267	Río Camuy basin.....	63
Hormigueros, Río Rosario near.....	257-264	Río Cibuco basin.....	111
Humacao at Highway 3 at Humacao, Río.....	214-215	Río Culebrinas basin.....	279
Humacao basin, Río, water-quality records in.....	214-215	Río Grande de Arecibo basin.....	69
Hydrologic Bench-Mark Network, definition of.....	36	Río Grande de Loiza basin.....	153
Hydrologic conditions, summary of.....	2-9		
Hydrologic unit, definition of.....	36		

	Page		Page
Maps:		Providencia, Río Chico at.....	222-223
Río Grande de Manatí basin.....	93	Proyecto La Plata, Río de La Plata at.....	126-128
Río Guajataca basin.....	51	Publications on techniques of water-resources investigations.....	47-48
Río Guanajibo basin.....	249	Puerto Nuevo basin, Río, ground-water records in.....	323-324
Río Herrera to the Río Antón Ruiz basins.....	189	water-quality records in.....	146-151
Río Hondo to the Río Puerto Nuevo basins.....	137	Quality of water records of Puerto Rico, surface- and.....	51-285
Río Humacao to the Río Seco basins.....	213	Quebrada Arenas, Río Grande de Loiza at.....	156-157
Río Inabón to the Río Loco basins.....	233	Quebradillas, Lago Guajataca No. 1 near dam near.....	296-299
Río de la Plata basin.....	125	Quebradillas, Lago Guajataca No. 3 near mouth near.....	293-295
Río Salinas to the Río Jacaguas basins.....	227	Quebradillas, Río Guajataca above mouth near.....	60-62
Río Yagüez and the Río Grande de Añasco basins.....	269	Radiochemical program, definition of.....	40
Maunabo at Maunabo, Río.....	220-221	Real Abajo, Río Inabón at	234-235
Maunabo basin, Río, water-quality records in.....	220-221	Records, explanation of.....	9-31
Maximum concentrations of fecal coliform bacteria at sampled sites, map showing location of.....	10	Records of ground-water levels.....	28-30
Maximum concentrations of fecal streptococci bacteria at sampled sites, map showing location of.....	11	Records of ground-water quality.....	30-31
Mayagüez, Río Yagüez near.....	270-271	Records of stage and water discharge.....	18-23
Mean concentration, definition of	41	Records of surface-water quality.....	23-28
Mean discharge, definition of.....	34	Recoverable from bottom material, definition of.....	40
Measuring point, definition of.....	36	Return period, definition of.....	40
Metamorphic stage, definition of.....	36	Río Grande, Río Espíritu Santo near.....	194-196
Methylene blue active substances, definition of.....	36	Río Piedras, Río Piedras near.....	146-147
Micrograms per gram, definition of	36	Rosario at Rosario, Río.....	256
Micrograms per liter, definition of.....	36	near Hormigueros.....	257-264
Milligrams of carbon per area or volume per unit time for periphyton and macrophytes and for phytoplankton, definition of.....	40	Runoff, in inches, definition of.....	40
Milligrams of oxygen per area or volume per unit time for periphyton and macrophytes and for phytoplankton, definition of.....	40	Sabana at Sabana, Río.....	199-200
Milligrams per liter, definition of.....	36	Sabana basin, Río, gaging station records in.....	199-200
Moca, Río Culebrinas at Highway 404 near.....	282-283	Sabana, Drainage ditch below Warner Lambert Lab. near.....	118-119
Morovis, Río Grande de Manatí near.....	96-98	Sabana, Río Mameyes near.....	197-198
Naguabo, Río Icacos near.....	211-212	Salvatierra near San Lorenzo, Quebrada.....	160-161
Naranjito, Lago La Plata No. 3 near dam near.....	296-299	San Germán, Río Guanajibo near.....	254-255
Naranjito, Lago La Plata No. 5 near mouth near.....	293-295	San Juan, Bahía de San Juan no. 5 at.....	151
Naranjito, Río Guadiana near.....	131-132	San Juan, Laguna San José No. 2 at	150
National Stream-Quality Accounting Network, definition of.....	37	San Lorenzo, Quebrada Salvatierra near.....	160-161
National Trends Network, definition of.....	38	San Sebastián, Río Culebrinas near.....	280-281
Natural substrate, definition of.....	42	San Sebastián, Río Grande de Añasco near.....	274-276
Networks and programs, special.....	9	Seco basin, Río, ground-water records in	326
Organic mass, definition of.....	33	Sediment, definition of.....	41
Organism, definition of.....	38	Sodium-adsorption-ratio, definition of.....	42
Organism count/area, definition of.....	38	Sonadora near El Verde, Quebrada.....	190-191
Organism count/volume, definition of.....	38	Solute, definition of.....	42
Orocovis near Orocovis, Río.....	94-95	Special network and programs.....	9
Parameter code, definition of.....	38	Specific conductance, definition of.....	42
Partial record station, definition of.....	38	Stage-discharge relation, definition of.....	42
Partial-record stations, Discharge at.....	289	Station identification numbers.....	12-18
Particle size, definition of.....	38	St. Croix, VI, Jolly Hill Gut at Jolly Hill.....	340
Particle-size classification, definition of.....	38	St. John, VI, Guinea Gut at Bethany.....	339
Patillas, Río Grande de Patillas near.....	224-226	Streamflow, definition of.....	42
Percent composition, definition of.....	39	St. Thomas, VI, Bonne Resolution Gut at Bonne Resolution.....	337
Periphyton, definition of.....	39	St. Thomas, VI, Turpentine Run at Mariendal.....	338
Pesticides, definition of.....	39	Substrate, definition of.....	42
Phytoplankton, definition of.....	39	Summary of hydrologic conditions.....	2-9
Picourie, definition of.....	39	Surface and quality-of-water records for Puerto Rico.....	51-285
Piedras, at Hato Rey, Río.....	148-149	Surface area, definition of.....	42
near Río Piedras.....	146-147	Surface-water quality, records of.....	23-28
Plankton, definition of.....	39	Surface-water records for U.S. Virgin Islands.....	337-340
Playa de Guayanés, Río Guayanés above mouth at.....	218-219	Surface-water and crest-stage gage stations in Puerto Rico, map showing location of.....	13
Polychlorinated biphenyls, definition of.....	40	Surface-water stations in U.S. Virgin Islands, map showing location of.....	16
Ponce, Río Bucaná floodway channel at Highway 14 bridge near.....	289	Surficial bed material, definition of.....	42
Ponce, Río Cerrillos near.....	236-237	Suspended, definition of.....	42
Ponce, Río Portugués at.....	241-242	Suspended-recoverable, definition of.....	43
Ponce, Río Portugués at Highway 14 at.....	289	Suspended sediment, definition of.....	41
Ponce, Río Portugués near.....	238-240	Suspended-sediment concentration, definition of.....	41
Portugués at Highway 14 at Ponce, Río.....	289	Suspended-sediment discharge, definition of.....	41
at Ponce.....	241-242	Suspended-sediment load, definition of.....	41
near Ponce.....	238-240	Suspended-total, definition of.....	43
Portugués basin, Río, crest-stage partial-record station in	289	Tanamá at Charco Hondo, Río.....	88-89
gaging station records in.....	238	near Utuado.....	80-87
water-quality records in.....	239-242	Taxonomy, definition of.....	43
Primary productivity, definition of.....	40	Techniques of water-resources investigations, publications on.....	46-47
Programs, special networks and.....	9	Terms, definition of.....	32-45
		Thermograph, definition of.....	43

	Page		Page
Time-weighted average, definition of.....	43	Well 207 - Cantito La Luisa.....	309
Toa Alta, Río de La Plata at	133-135	Well 208 - Acrópolis - Manatí.....	310
Toa Alta, Río de La Plata at Highway 2 near.....	136	Well 209 - Coto Norte No. 3.....	311
Tons per acre-foot, definition of.....	44	Well 210 - Gelo Martínez.....	312
Tons per day, definition of.....	44	Guajataca basin, Río	
Toronja at El Verde, Quebrada.....	192-193	Well 165 - Mateo Pérez, Bo. Salto.....	303
Total, definition of.....	44	Well 202 - Carmelo Barreto-García.....	304
Total coliform bacteria, definition of.....	32	Guanajibo basin, Río	
Total discharge, definition of.....	44	Well 143 - Vivoni, Hacienda Amistad.....	331
Total organism count, definition of.....	38	Guayanés basin, Río	
Total-recoverable, definition of.....	44	Well 96 - USGS TW-2 or Yabucoa 7	327
Total sediment discharge, definition of.....	41	Hondo basin, Río	
Total-sediment load, definition of.....	41	Well 218 - Levittown No. 7.....	321
Tritium network, definition of.....	44	La Plata basin, Río de	
Trujillo Alto, Lago Loiza No. 7 near		Well 214 - Dorado Beach No. 7.....	317
dam near.....	296-299	Well 215 - Maguayo No. 5.....	318
Trujillo Alto, Río Grande de Loiza below.....	184-185	Well 216 - Pozo Navy - Campanillas.....	319
Turabo at Borinquen, Río.....	164-165	Well 217 - Monserrate TW-2.....	320
Turpentine Run at Mariendal, St. Thomas, VI.....	338	Puerto Nuevo basin, Río	
		Well 220 - Parque San Luis Rey.....	323
Utuaado, Lago Dos Bocas No. 1 near dam		Well 221 - Hyde Park TW-10.....	324
near.....	296-299	Seco basin, Río	
Utuaado, Lago Dos Bocas No. 3 at west branch near.....	293-295	Well 6 - Juana 5.....	326
Utuaado, Río Grande de Arecibo near.....	72-73	Wells - U.S. Virgin Islands:	
Utuaado, Río Tanamá near.....	80-87	St. Croix	
Valenciano near Juncos, Río.....	175-176	Well 1 - Fairplains 6 (FP6).....	343
Vega Baja, Laguna Tortuguero outlet near.....	110	Well 2 - USGS-10, Fairplains 2 (FP2).....	344
Vega Baja, Río Cibuco at.....	115-117	Well 3 - Golden Grove 6 (PW6).....	345
		Well 4 - Golden Grove 1 (PW1).....	346
Water-discharge, records of stage and.....	18-23	Well 5 - Mahogany Road 3.....	346
Water-quality partial-record stations in Puerto Rico,		Well 6 - Adventure 28.....	347
analyses of samples collected at.....	293-299	Well 7 - Concordia 14.....	348
Water-quality stations in Puerto Rico, map		Well 8 - Concordia 1 (main pump house).....	348
showing location of.....	14	Well 9 - Concordia 7.....	349
Water-resources investigations, publications on		Well 10 - Barren Spot 5 (PWD-5).....	349
techniques of	46-47	St. John	
Water year, definition of.....	44	Well 1 - NPS-2 (Cruz Bay).....	353
WATSTORE data, Access to.....	31	Well 2 - NPS-5 (Trunk Bay).....	353
WDR, definition of.....	44	Well 3 - NPS-6 (Cinnamon Bay).....	354
Weighted average, definition of.....	45	Well 5 - DPW-6.....	355
Wells - Puerto Rico:		Well 6 - DPW-5.....	356
Bayamón basin, Río de		Well 7 - DPW-4.....	356
Well 219 - Fort Buchanan No. 1.....	322	Well 8 - DPW-3.....	356
Bucaná basin, Río		Well 9 - DPW-2.....	357
Well 141 - Restaurada 8A.....	330	Well 10 - DPW-1.....	357
Cibuco basin, Río		Well 11 - Guinea Gut Well.....	358
Well 70 - Sabana Hoyos.....	313	St. Thomas	
Well 211 - Rosario No. 2.....	314	Well 1 - USGS-8 (Family well-Thatch Farm).....	350
Well 212 - Ponderosa TW-1.....	315	Well 2 - Mahogany 15.....	350
Well 213 - Pampano No. 2.....	316	Well 3 - Mahogany 16.....	350
Camuy basin, Río		Well 4 - Mahogany 17.....	351
Well 203 - Vicente Amador.....	305	Well 5 - Donoe 3.....	351
Coamo basin, Río		Well 6 - Grade School 3.....	352
Well 87 - Alomar 1.....	328	Yauco basin, Río	
Culebrinas basin, Río		Well 132 - Yauco 2.....	329
Well 83 - San Sebastián.....	332	Wet mass, definition of.....	33
Well 200 - Aguadilla Cement north.....	333	WSP, definition of.....	45
Grande de Arecibo basin, Río		Yabucoa, Río Guayanés at.....	216-217
Well 204 - Gilberto Rivera.....	306	Yagüez near Mayagüez, Río.....	270-271
Grande de Loiza basin, Río		Yagüez basin, Río, water-quality records in.....	270-271
Well 222 - Campo Rico TW-1.....	325	Yauco basin, Río, ground-water records in.....	329
Grande de Manatí basin, Río		Zooplankton, definition of.....	39
Well 135 - Lederle.....	307		
Well 206 - Plazuela No. 2.....	308		

FACTORS FOR CONVERTING INCH-POUND UNITS TO INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM UNITS (SI)

The following factors may be used to convert the inch-pound units published herein to the International System of Units (SI). This report contains both the inch-pound and SI unit equivalents in the station manuscript descriptions.

Multiply inch-pound units	By	To obtain SI units
<i>Length</i>		
inches (in)	2.54×10^1 2.54×10^{-2}	millimeters (mm) meters (m)
feet (ft)	3.048×10^{-1}	meters (m)
miles (mi)	1.609×10^0	kilometers (km)
<i>Area</i>		
acres	4.047×10^3 4.047×10^{-1}	square meters (m ²) square hectometers (hm ²)
square miles (mi ²)	4.047×10^{-3} 2.590×10^0	square kilometers (km ²) square kilometers (km ²)
<i>Volume</i>		
gallons (gal)	3.785×10^0 3.785×10^0	liters (L) cubic decimeters (dm ³)
million gallons	3.785×10^{-3} 3.785×10^3	cubic meters (m ³) cubic meters (m ³)
cubic feet (ft ³)	3.785×10^{-3} 2.832×10^1	cubic hectometers (hm ³) cubic decimeters (dm ³)
cfs-days	2.832×10^{-2} 2.447×10^3	cubic meters (m ³) cubic meters (m ³)
acre-feet (acre-ft)	2.447×10^{-3} 1.233×10^3 1.233×10^{-3} 1.233×10^{-6}	cubic hectometers (hm ³) cubic meters (m ³) cubic hectometers (hm ³) cubic kilometers (km ³)
<i>Flow</i>		
cubic feet per second (ft ³ /s)	2.832×10^1 2.832×10^1 2.832×10^{-2}	liters per second (L/s) cubic decimeters per second (dm ³ /s) cubic meters per second (m ³ /s)
gallons per minute (gal/min)	6.309×10^{-2} 6.309×10^{-2}	liters per second (L/s) cubic decimeters per second (dm ³ /s)
million gallons per day	6.309×10^{-5} 4.381×10^1 4.381×10^{-2}	cubic meters per second (m ³ /s) cubic decimeters per second (dm ³ /s) cubic meters per second (m ³ /s)
<i>Mass</i>		
tons (short)	9.072×10^{-1}	megagrams (Mg) or metric tons

3 1818 00455272 3
USGS LIBRARY - RESTON

U.S. DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR
INT 413

U.S. DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR
Geological Survey
GPO Box 4424
San Juan, PR 00936

OFFICIAL BUSINESS
PENALTY FOR PRIVATE USE \$300
SPECIAL 4TH CLASS BOOK RATE